

INTEGRATED NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN

Fort Riley, Kansas

July 5, 2016

Ft Riley Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

July 2016

I. In accordance with Title 10, U.S. Code Section 2671; Title 16, U.S. Code, Section 670; and in Public Law 86-797, as amended, the Department of Defense, Department of Interior, and the State of Kansas, through their duly designated representatives whose signatures appear below, approved the following Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) for the protection, development and management of natural resources on the Fort Riley Military Reservation, Kansas.

II. This INRMP will be in full force and effect upon its adoption. Adoption will be indicated by signatures below of duly authorized representatives of the three agencies first above named; will remain in full force and effect as long as permitted by the cited authorities under which it is entered.

III. This INRMP updates the previous *INRMP 2010*, signed in 2010 by duly authorized representatives of Fort Riley, the Kansas Department of Wildlife and Parks and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. This INRMP may be amended or revised by agreement among all parties hereto. Any proposed amendment of this Plan may originate with any of the participating agencies.

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11/20/2016
Date

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7/5/2016
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Fort Riley Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan

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1.0 DEPARTMENT OF THE ARMY VISION, POLICIES AND GOALS

Vision

Achieve an enduring Army enabled by sustainable operations, installations, systems, and communities (Army, 2004).

Policies

The Army's strategy for natural resources management is based on the principle of sustainability. It reflects the Army's appreciation of the interdependence between the mission, the community, and the environment. This strategy applies a community, regional, and ecosystem approach to managing natural resources on the installation. This is a strategy for a homeland that is protected, an environment that is sustained, and waterways and ecological resources that are preserved as natural and economic assets.

- The Army will sustain its testing and training lands' natural resource base in quantity, quality, and configuration to meet current and future requirements.
- The Army will manage range activities to maintain the resiliency and buffering needed to protect the environment and the surrounding communities from impacts of training and testing.
- The Army will apply an ecosystem-based approach to manage natural resources and will collaborate with stakeholders to protect ecosystems. It will be a leader in sustainability; this is crucial to the success of the mission as the Army meets current and future challenges.
- The Army will strengthen and build community partnerships to achieve sustained and sound environmental stewardship and a ready military force through communication, coordination, consultation, and collaboration. It will foster open relationships to increase understanding by all. It will communicate the Army's readiness requirements and environmental initiatives, while at the same time, listening to its neighbors' needs and concerns to build win-win situations together (Army 2004).

Goals

The following goals have been adopted to achieve an enduring Army enabled by sustainable operations, installations, systems, and communities (Army 2004):

- Foster an ethic within the Army that goes beyond environmental compliance to sustainability.
- Strengthen Army operational capability by reducing its environmental footprint through more sustainable practices.
- Meet current and future training, testing, and other mission requirements by sustaining land, air, and water resources.
- Enhance the well-being of Soldiers, Civilians, Families, Neighbors and Communities through leadership in sustainability.

2.0 FORT RILEY INRMP VISION, POLICIES AND GOALS

Vision

Achieve a management strategy that dually supports Fort Riley's current and projected missions and complies with environmental regulations while sustaining the natural resources for future use.

Policies

Fort Riley's Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) will reflect and implement the Army strategy for natural resources management.

- Fort Riley will sustain its testing and training lands' natural resource base in quantity, quality, and configuration to meet current and future requirements.
- Fort Riley will manage range activities to maintain the resiliency and buffering needed to protect the environment and the surrounding communities from impacts of training.
- Fort Riley will apply an ecosystem-based approach to manage natural resources and will collaborate with stakeholders to protect ecosystems.
- Fort Riley will strengthen and build community partnerships to achieve sustained and sound environmental stewardship and a ready military force through communication, coordination, consultation, and collaboration. It will foster open relationships to increase understanding by all. It will communicate the Army's readiness requirements and environmental initiatives, while at the same time, listening to our neighbors' needs and concerns to build win-win situations together.
- Fort Riley will apply adaptive ecosystem management strategies when making natural resources management decisions. The ecosystem management strategy will strive to achieve the potential natural vegetation of the region. Adaptive ecosystem management on Fort Riley will take into account changes in military mission and associated training requirements, and the nature and extent of managed natural resources. Adaptive management will adjust management practices to enable accomplishment of military training requirements and to provide for ancillary uses of the installation's natural resources where and when such uses are compatible with the military training requirements.

Goals

Fort Riley embraces Army and IMCOM (Installation Management Command) policy of sustainability regarding its natural resources management. A critical responsibility of the installation is to provide training lands upon which its Soldiers can develop their war-fighting skills. The following INRMP goals will be adapted to natural resources management in an effort to ensure the long-term sustainability of Fort Riley's training lands.

2.1.1. Strengthen mission sustainability.

- Apply an adaptive ecosystem management approach to integrate planning of natural resources programs.
- Practice adaptive ecosystem management to review and revise management practices.
- Practice sustained yield in consumption of natural resources.

- Coordinate natural resources management actions with other installation activities and resource management agencies.
- Strive for no net loss in the capability of installation lands to support current and future military training at Fort Riley.
- Monitor quality and status of training lands.
- Mitigate effects of training on natural resources.
- Rehabilitate training lands.

2.1.2. Support, maintain, and increase Soldier safety.

- Minimize impediments and safety hazards to training.

2.1.3. Reduce and manage effects of encroachment on the mission.

- Collaborate and partner with stakeholders to protect relevant ecosystems off of the installation.
- Manage the Army Compatible Use Buffer (ACUB) Program.

2.1.4. Enhance the well-being and quality of life of our Soldiers, Civilians, Families, Neighbors and Communities.

- Involve community stakeholders in management planning and decision-making.
- Provide opportunity for natural resource-based recreational activities.
- Provide sustainable forest product use opportunities.
- Provide sustainable agricultural production opportunities.
- Provide professional conservation law enforcement.

2.1.5. Maintain compliance with laws and regulations.

- Maintain compliance with Federal and state laws and regulations.
- Maintain compliance with Executive Orders (EO's).
- Maintain compliance with and Department of Defense (DoD) and Army regulations. (A list of the Federal laws and EO's governing natural resources management on military lands is in Appendix A).

2.1.6. Annually assess this INRMP.

- Assess this INRMP at least annually to determine its effectiveness in sustaining land, air, and water resources, and thereby strengthening mission capabilities.
- Modify this INRMP, as required.

3.0 LOCATION AND ACREAGE

Location

Fort Riley is located in the central portion of northeastern Kansas and occupies portions of Geary, Riley, and Clay counties. The installation's southern boundary is at the confluence of the Smoky Hill and Republican rivers, which combine to form the Kansas River. Milford Lake, a 15,000 acre impoundment of the Republican River, is located at the installation's western boundary. Tuttle Creek Lake is approximately eight miles northeast of the installation. Portions of the installation are bounded by the city limits of Riley, Milford, Junction City, Keats and Ogden (Exhibit 3.1). The City of Manhattan is located approximately two miles east of the installation, although the Manhattan Regional Airport and Manhattan Corporate Technical Park are located adjacent to the installation boundary. Fort Riley is approximately 95 miles west of Kansas City and 90 miles northeast of Wichita.

Installation History

Fort Riley was established in 1853 to protect westward moving pioneers on the Santa Fe Trail. Soldiers rode to famous campaigns such as Beecher's Island, Washita River Fight, and the Battle of Little Big Horn. At the end of the Indian Wars, this frontier post became the home of the Army's Cavalry and Light Artillery Schools in 1893. The Cavalry School was deactivated in 1946 when all horse units in the Army were replaced by mechanized Cavalry and Armor units. Fort Riley has served as a major training and mobilization site, deploying units to fight in the Spanish American War, both World Wars, the Korean Conflict, Vietnam, Desert Storm, and the Global War on Terrorism.

The headquarters of the 1st Infantry Division was transferred from Fort Riley to Germany in 1995. The 1st Brigade of the 1st Infantry Division, along with the 3rd Brigade of the 1st Armored Division and the 937th Engineer Group remained at Fort Riley. Fort Riley once again became a Division Headquarters in 1999 when the 24th Infantry Division was reactivated at the installation, to consolidate Active components and Reserve components into one Division. The 24th Infantry Division served as the Headquarters element for three Enhanced Separate Brigades of the Army National Guard.

A result of the 2005 Base Realignment and Closure (BRAC) decisions and additional mission requirements resulting from the Integrated Global Presence and Basing Strategy was the return of the 1st Infantry Division Headquarters to Fort Riley, as well as the stationing of a third brigade (4th Brigade of the 1st Infantry), a Combat Aviation Brigade, and various additional units to the installation. In March, 2008, the 3rd Brigade of the 1st Armored Division was reflagged as the 2nd Brigade of the 1st Infantry.

In 2015, the 4th Infantry Brigade Combat Team was inactivated as part of the Army's restructuring process. Also announced in 2015 was the Army plan to cut approximately 615 Soldiers from Fort Riley as to reduce overall troop numbers. Fort Riley is reduced to a four brigade installation with a mix of heavy, aviation and sustainment brigades.

Exhibit 3.1. General location of the Fort Riley Military Installation and its surrounding communities.

Acreage and Acquisition

Over the years, Fort Riley has expanded in size. Originally a 23,871 acre post, the first major expansion occurred in 1942 when 31,720 acres, located to the north and east of the installation, were purchased as part of the pre-World War II mobilization effort. The second major expansion occurred in 1965 when 46,065 acres were purchased to accommodate the installation's mission as being the home base for an infantry division. After acquisition of small parcels of excess Corps of Engineers property adjacent to the installation through the General Service Administration office, the installation's present size is 100,775 acres.

Neighbors

Manhattan is the largest city near Fort Riley (population 56,078), followed by Junction City, Ogden, Riley, Wakefield, and Milford (populations 24,665, 2,138, 994, 967, and 594, respectively; U.S. Census Bureau 2014 population estimates). Most land surrounding Fort Riley has traditionally been used for agricultural production, a use generally compatible with the installation's training mission. Recently, this agricultural land has increasingly been parceled, sold, and developed for residential use. Development of residences and residential areas near Fort Riley's boundaries create conditions for potential conflicts between landowners and the installation due to noise and smoke issues, and the potential for grassland fires leaving the installation and burning private property.

4.0 MILITARY MISSION

Overview

Fort Riley is classified as a Tier 1 installation (installation with significant training value to the Major Commands and having high range and land capability) that has an Army-wide strategic and enduring training capability. The principal, currently-stationed units at Fort Riley are 1st Infantry Division Headquarters, 1st and 2nd Armored Brigade Combat Teams, Division Artillery, a Sustainment Brigade, and a Combat Aviation Brigade. Due to reassignment and attrition, Soldier strength at Fort Riley is projected to decrease from approximately 18,000 Soldiers to approximately 16,000 Soldiers by the end of 2017. Fort Riley supports National Guard and Reserve components.

Fort Riley facilities provide year-round support for live-fire exercises, maneuver training for mechanized/armored vehicles, attack helicopter gunnery, operation of rotary-winged aircraft, drone aircraft, small arms firing, mortar, artillery and tank firing exercises, engineer obstacle and demolition training and maneuver training. These training activities are expected to remain stable. Current Fort Riley military assets include approximately 180 tanks, 110 Bradley Fighting Vehicles, 640 other tracked vehicles, 3,985 wheeled vehicles, and 115 Rotary Wing Aircraft.¹

Fort Riley encompasses 100,775 acres. Of this, approximately 70,000 acres separated into 103 training areas are available for maneuver training (Exhibit 4.1). Every unit assigned to Fort Riley conducts rotational training. The most heavily used Maneuver Areas are occupied between 160-210 days per year. Fort Riley aircraft have access to 432 square miles of airspace. Flight operations occur daily, with approximately 21,000 helicopter flight hours annually logged.

The Artillery and Mortar Impact Area and its associated training live-fire ranges consist of 16,200 acres. Cantonment areas total approximately 11,000 acres, including Marshall Army Airfield (MAAF). The Douthit Gunnery Complex, an approximately 2,000-acre site, houses the Digital Multi-Purpose Range Complex (DMPRC) and Digital Multipurpose Training Range (DMPTR). The Gunnery Complex has averaged as high as 230 days of use per year (Range and Training Land Program Development Plan, 2000). Live-fire exercises involving mortars, artillery, and tanks occur throughout the year. These firing ranges for large caliber weapons are used extensively by units assigned to Fort Riley, active Army units assigned to other installations, Army Reserve units, National Guard units, and U.S. Air Force units.

Use of the DMPTR and DMPRC has increased the number of training exercises that can be supported at any one time and throughout a typical training year by approximately one-third. This has allowed more personnel and units to train simultaneously at the installation. Munitions fired at these facilities do not generate any louder noises. However, the additional range capacity allows for a higher throughput of training units, increasing the intensity of the noises that are generated when both ranges are active.

¹ The exact number of Soldiers and military vehicles present at any one time on Fort Riley is variable due to overseas deployments.

Mission and Vision Statements

The 1st Infantry Division and Fort Riley build and maintain combat ready forces; on order deploys these forces to conduct Decisive Action to fight and win in complex environments as members of a Joint Inter-organizational, and Multi-national (JIM) team.

Ongoing Mission Activities

Wide ranges of activities occur on a regular basis at Fort Riley to conduct and support the installation's assigned training mission. These activities are listed in Appendix B.

Effects of Natural Resources Management on the Mission

Fort Riley's ecosystem is dominated by grassland interspersed with wooded areas of varying sizes and densities, which provides a variety of terrain types that are useful for both mounted and dismounted training activities. This ecosystem generally facilitates Fort Riley's mission now and as it is projected to beyond the life of this plan. However, as woody vegetation invades into grasslands, the continued capability of the land to support that training is diminished. Therefore, the objective of this plan is to sustain a grassland-dominated ecosystem interspersed with woodlands in a pattern similar to what currently exists, but with the spatial extent of many of the individual woodlands and the number of isolated trees in grasslands reduced.

4.1.1. Grassland Management

Fort Riley's gently-rolling, open topography lends itself to force-on-force maneuver training, an important component of the installation's mission. Maintaining open grassland to support maneuver or artillery firing training is an important management objective, particularly in Maneuver Areas A, D, E, H, K, L, O, and P, the Douthit Gunnery Complex box, and the Impact Area. Poor grassland management promotes woody plant invasion. As woody vegetation increases in grasslands, weapon firing lines become obscured by tree growth, the ability of commanders to view troop field maneuvers and firing exercises is compromised, and areas with dense shrub are no longer used for dismounted training. Management actions that remove trees from grasslands, suppress and reverse woody encroachment, and maintain a grassy cover all work together to maintain open vistas that support the military mission.

4.1.2. Woodland Management

Woodlands associated with stream drainages and deep ravines provide ideal locations for dismounted military training that occurs on Fort Riley. The woodlands serve as visual barrier for dismounted units in the field, allowing for more efficient use of training lands, particularly in Training Areas 1-24, and Maneuver Areas C, F and I. The presence of large trees on slopes of ravines with steep rock outcrops enhances Soldier safety by serving as a visual deterrent to keep vehicles from falling or rolling down these embankments. Tree lines may be useful for tactical concealment during military training exercises. Around the installation's perimeter, tree lines serve as a visual barrier to on-post activities, can serve as a barrier to unauthorized access, and can reduce the amount of dust moving beyond installation boundaries.

Woodland management further sustains training lands through soil and water conservation. For example, trees have been planted to restore cover after soil mining projects were performed in support of the military and related construction projects. Timber harvest and timber stand

improvement are used to expand and enhance access for military equipment. Areas for thinning and harvest also have been provided to Engineering units for chainsaw training. Trees have been provided at times for the construction of defensive positions.

4.1.3. Agricultural Lease Management

The installation's perimeter lands are leased to farmers for crop production. These leased croplands provide a system of firebreaks, with the primary function of impeding fires that start on the installation from moving off of the installation. This protects private property adjacent to the installation from wildfire, and protects the installation from the liability that would result from destroying private property by fire. A secondary function of the firebreak fields is to provide a distinct demarcation between Fort Riley and privately owned lands so that troops do not stray onto private property. Both functions contribute to the capability of Soldiers to train on the installation up to its boundaries, without land being lost to no-training buffers.

Soldiers and equipment are often stationed in grasslands in such a manner as to be susceptible to wildfire. Reducing the accumulation of standing, dead vegetation through hay harvest lessens the potential danger of wildfires to Soldiers and equipment in the field. Hay harvest also provides, seasonally, areas of short vegetation, which are desired for establishing bivouac sites during training exercises.

4.1.4. T&E Species, Migratory Bird and Wetland Management

Maintaining compliance with endangered species, migratory bird, eagle and wetlands laws, regulations and EO's is of paramount importance in sustaining the military mission on Fort Riley and protecting Army personnel from civil and criminal prosecution. The overall strategies are to prevent conflicts between mission requirements and mandated protection through coordinated, long-term planning with the Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism (KDWPT) and the U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service (USFWS), and to develop partnerships that manage and maintain sensitive habitats off of the installation to preclude future listings of additional species as threatened or endangered and thereby abate encroachment².

Fort Riley has prepared management plans that describe necessary actions to conserve and protect each federally-listed candidate, threatened or endangered species known to occur on the installation, as well as bald eagles and Army Species at Risk (Appendix C). These management plans were prepared with and approved by the USFWS and the KDWPT. They represent Fort Riley's means to minimize or prevent conflicts between listed species and the military mission.

One of the objectives of Fort Riley's Army Compatible Use Buffer (ACUB) program is to ease environmental encroachment issues that might otherwise arise due to loss of tallgrass prairie tracts off of the installation. Similarly, Fort Riley participates in regional conservation planning and partners with private landowners and organizations that manage habitats off of the installation in an effort to retain a functional and regionally significant tallgrass prairie ecosystem around the installation.

² Encroachment refers to external factors that impact military training operations and training lands, with the potential to limit the installation's capability to accomplish its training mission and maintain ready forces

Mission restrictions due to federally-listed threatened and endangered species are minimal due to the limited interface between the species and the mission. Two of the three listed species on the installation are birds that use riverine habitat along the Kansas and Republican rivers. The third listed species is a minnow occurring in a limited number of streams. Stream and riverine habitats do not lend themselves well to mechanized training; thus impact by, and to, military training is limited. Threatened and endangered species are more thoroughly addressed in Section 7.10 and Appendix C.

The DoD and the USFWS signed a memorandum of understanding (MOU) in 2006, pursuant to EO 13186, Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds. This INRMP addresses the key installation responsibilities identified in Section D of the migratory bird MOU (Appendix D).

Wetlands are a minor landform of Fort Riley, generally small and dispersed. Except for crossing streams, Soldiers generally avoid wetlands during maneuver activities because wetlands don't lend themselves to vehicle movements.

4.1.5. ITAM (Integrated Training Area Management)

ITAM is a core component of the Sustainable Range Program (SRP) and is responsible for maintaining training land to help the Army meet its training requirements. To accomplish this mission, ITAM relies on its five components: Land Rehabilitation & Maintenance (LRAM), Range & Training Land Assessment (RTLTA), Sustainable Range Awareness (SRA), Training Requirements & Integration (TRI), and SRP Geographic Information System (GIS). The purposes of the ITAM program components are to integrate mission requirements with environmental management practices and establish the policies and procedures to achieve sustainable use of training and testing lands.

4.1.5.1. LRAM (Land Rehabilitation and Maintenance)

LRAM is the primary program for repair and rehabilitation of training lands within ITAM. LRAM uses land management practices and support from RTLTA to enhance safety and training value of the land by minimizing adverse impacts through rehabilitation and maintenance of training lands. LRAM averages 10 projects a year that improve training land sustainability. Over the past 5 years, treated sites ranged from 0.25-15 acres that enhanced on average 400-500 acres of training land per year.

4.1.5.2. RTLTA (Range and Training Land Assessment)

RTLTA acquires data and assesses information to track the capability and sustainability of the land to support mission activities. RTLTA data is used to identify LRAM projects, ensure that biological considerations are part of the LRAM project prioritization process, determine the effectiveness of LRAM projects, and recommend training load distribution for land so that the sustainability of the training land can be maintained.

4.1.5.3. **SRA (Sustainable Range Awareness)**

SRA provides a proactive means to develop and distribute educational materials that relate procedures to reduce the potential for inflicting avoidable impacts on range and training land during military training.

4.1.5.4. **TRI (Training Requirements Integration)**

TRI facilitates achieving mission goals through decision support and coordinating training needs with other installation plans to provide information and analysis that assist with range and training land planning, scheduling, maintenance and modernization. Information is obtained from SRP GIS, RTLA, LRAM, and appropriate installation offices, and the analysis considers environmental compliance requirements, range facilities requirements, and landscape condition requirements in the development of range and training land management decisions. This includes the integration of RCMP mission goals and objectives into the INRMP and its subordinate plans. TRI is a continual collaboration with the installation range office, natural resources and environmental staff, and state and federal agencies.

4.1.5.5. **SRP Geographical Information System (SRP GIS)**

The SRP GIS Mission is to *create, analyze, manage, and distribute* authoritative standardized spatial information, products, and services for the execution of training strategies and missions on U.S. Army ranges and training lands. Through information excellence, one of the three tenets upon which the SRP was founded, the SRP GIS Program strives to provide the SRP Community, Trainers, and Soldiers with the ability to leverage the most accurate and complete datasets through easily accessible and user-friendly products and applications. SRP GIS provides geospatial data and analysis to support land management decisions and Training Mission geospatial products.

4.1.6. **Quality of Life Management**

The opportunities to harvest fish and wildlife game species are important recreational and morale-building activities for Soldiers and their Families. Thus, every effort is made to allow hunting and fishing to safely coexist with military training exercises. Hunter munition restrictions and minimum distance buffers from Soldiers are established and enforced in the installation's hunting, fishing and trapping regulation, FR 210-15. However, the military mission requirements take precedence over all announced seasons. Hunting and fishing are prohibited in areas when those activities will not safely coexist with planned military training events.

Effects of the Military Mission on Natural Resources

Military training involves three major activities: construction of facilities, maneuver activities, and ordnance explosions. Construction actions generally occur within Cantonment Areas and seldom impact native, high quality habitats. However, construction actions to update ranges or provide improved training realism do occur outside of cantonment areas. Potential effects of such construction actions are evaluated on a case by case basis during the NEPA process, and will not be addressed further in this document.

Maneuver activities' impacts primarily occur on, and parallel to tank trails (CERL 1991). The highest frequency of such disturbance occurs along trails leading to the Douthit Gunnery Complex. Based on data collected throughout the installation, low to moderate levels of disturbance may increase the amount of indiangrass in tallgrass communities. Other grasses, such as tall dropseed, tall witchgrass, and foxtail, also increase as a result of disturbance (CERL 1991) as do forbs, particularly annual forbs, and in some instances woody vegetation. Those changes are most pronounced at the highest levels of disturbance. Ordnance explosions are generally restricted to the Impact Area, which is a minimally managed parcel of land due to the presence of unexploded ordnance.

4.1.7. Soil

Soil impacts primarily result from tactical digging, off-road vehicle movements (both cross-country and minimally maintained trails), explosive ordnance detonations, and borrow actions. These impacts include soil disturbance, erosion and compaction. The areas affected by soil erosion and compaction occur throughout the Maneuver and Training Areas, as well as the Impact Area.

Tactical digging refers to any process or activity involving the disturbance of soil, regardless of size, depth or nature of excavation. This includes creating individual fighting positions, trenches, bunkers, berms, defilades, tank traps, or mine plowing.

The off-road movements of both tracked and wheeled vehicles can compact lower soil horizons, loosen upper soil layers, disrupt root mats, create ruts, and remove vegetative cover. These impacts intensify as the soil's moisture levels and the numbers of vehicles increase. As vehicles repeatedly pass on non-hardened trails, the original corridors become less passable, and the damage can be spread laterally as vehicles attempt to by-pass the disturbed sites. To combat this trail widening, frequently driven trails are hardened with gravel or recycled asphalt pavement, or leveled by road graders.

The repeated crossing of drainage channels at the same non-hardened location creates areas with gully erosion along sloped approaches, destabilized streambanks, and deeply cut stream channels. As the original crossing becomes less passable, the damage can be spread laterally as vehicles attempt to by-pass the disturbed sites. To combat channel damage, crossings are hardened in strategic locations, and unauthorized crossing sites are closed by placement of obstructions across access points.

Loss of vegetative cover following fires exposes the soil surface to wind and direct precipitation impacts. The effect of this exposure on soil varies depending upon the soil type, depth to bedrock, degree of disturbance to vegetative cover, rainfall, and season of occurrence.

Soils are affected in the Impact Area's detonation zone by both non-explosive and explosive rounds. Erosion may be high at the locations of ordnance impact because fires are frequently generated by the impact. Further, the explosive force of live ordnance disturbs and exposes the soil surface as well as destroys protective vegetation cover and root mats. However, the danger posed by unexploded ordnance in the Impact Area prevents actions from being taken to monitor or control soil erosion there.

4.1.8. Water

The primary effects to water from military training result from soil erosion entering surface water in runoff from Training Areas and the Impact Area. Sources of erosion are described in Section 4.5.1. Increased rates of soil erosion at disturbed sites may increase turbidity and sedimentation of some surface waters on the installation. Portions of streams, rivers, and lakes located off-post also may be affected by increased turbidity.

4.1.9. Vegetation

Off-road vehicle maneuvering causes the most notable training impact to vegetation within the Training Areas of Fort Riley. In grasslands, these impacts include: the crushing and shearing of individual plants; the replacement of perennial grasses (such as big bluestem, indianguass, little bluestem, and grama grasses) by early successional grasses and forbs such as curly dock, common mullein, tansy mustard, black medic, field bindweed, and various species of goldenrods and sunflowers; the mechanical disruption and breaking of root mats which allow the invasion of woody plants such as eastern redcedar, buckbrush, dogwood, American elm, and hackberry; and the compaction of soil which hinders seed germination (Goran et al., 1983). Established trees and shrubs are damaged by physical contact or through root damage. Soil compaction can also increase seedling mortality (Goran et al., 1983). Noxious weed seed is spread when transported in wheels and tracks of vehicles, particularly during muddy conditions.

Other activities affecting vegetation on Firing Ranges are wildfires, herbicide application and the periodic mowing and cutting of areas of vegetation to maintain lines-of-sight to targets. Soil sterilant is used on specific small spots around the perimeter of each target mechanism on most Firing Ranges. The average area of soil sterilized around target mechanisms is 0.01 acres. The aggregate area of soil sterilant application is 16.4 acres. Broad-leafed plant herbicides are applied aerially to approximately 780 acres at Ranges 17, 18, and 19 within the Impact Area.

4.1.10. Fish and Wildlife

The military mission affects fish and wildlife on Fort Riley primarily through changes to habitat. Documented effects on habitats are vegetation disturbance and sedimentation into headwaters of streams.

Off-road maneuver training may remove vegetation and change the composition and structure of the floral community. Research has shown faunal communities on Fort Riley change as a result of changes in structure or composition of floral communities. For example, as disturbance by tracked vehicles increased at Fort Riley, the number of deer mice increased, while prairie voles, western harvest mice, and hispid cotton rats decreased (Keating et al. 1994).

Wildfires are occasionally started by military activities such as live fire gunnery, use of flares and smoke grenades, and vehicle exhaust mechanisms in grasslands. Wildfires in grasslands frequently cause almost complete removal of vegetation in relatively large expanses. For example, in 2004, winter and fall wildfires burned over 4,700 acres, one block of which exceeded 2,300 acres.

Quist (1999) attributed siltation in headwater reaches to disturbance within the watershed from military training activities. Fish species diversity increased when stream habitat was disturbed, and the fish community shifted from an assemblage of small, omnivorous species to large, piscivorous species. In particular, increased soil erosion and stream turbidity could adversely impact habitat for the Topeka shiner, a Federally-listed endangered minnow.

Notably, impacts tend to create a spatial and temporal mosaic of habitat conditions rather than installation-wide, permanent change. Habitat integrity on a landscape scale is maintained, but conditions and effects vary. Schaeffer et al. (1990) reported that soil microarthropods, some species of macroarthropods, small mammals, and native earthworm species were negatively affected by military stresses, while plant species diversity, plant foliage biomass, soil mycorrhizae, and many soil characteristics were within the boundaries of nominal variations observed on nearby Konza Prairie. Research conducted on mammalian predators (Kamler 1999) and nocturnal avian predators (Japuntich unpubl. data) have shown that Fort Riley supports some of the highest populations reported in the scientific literature.

Surveys of Henslow's sparrow populations by the Conservation Branch, Directorate of Public Works, Fort Riley, found populations were comparable or higher than Konza Prairie populations. Research conducted on the Henslow's sparrow and the loggerhead shrike (Michaels 1997) found that habitat use by these two species was not related to grassland disturbance from military training. Also, greater prairie-chicken lek surveys show stable populations, which apparently contract population trends in other Flint Hills pasture land.

Direct effects on fish and wildlife can also occur. These include nest disturbance, nest destruction, and direct mortality. For example, occasional collisions between military vehicles and wildlife occur, primarily on installation roads. The potential for bird strikes with rotary-winged aircraft will increase with the stationing of the Combat Aviation Brigade. Wildlife may be killed when training-related wildfires occur, especially during the breeding season when young animals are unable to escape the flames and smoke.

Future Military Mission Impacts on Natural Resources

The future vision for Fort Riley includes housing 2 Heavy Brigades, 1 Artillery Brigade, one Aviation Brigade, one Support Brigade and various partner and tenant organizations. The future mission impacts on natural resources are expected to remain similar to those of today. Most impacts are anticipated to be the result of off-road vehicle (wheeled and tracked) maneuvering. It is expected that land use patterns on Fort Riley will remain stable. It is not known if additional mission changes may occur at Fort Riley during the next five years. It is expected that any future missions will be compatible with land forms currently existing at Fort Riley, and that any additional impacts on natural resources would remain similar to those already occurring.

Any significant change in mission, including fielding of new equipment, will be analyzed under the NEPA process, where applicable, and will be communicated during the INRMP annual reviews. Army guidance is for installations to annually review activities conducted under its INRMP to determine that the plan has been effectively implemented while maintaining the installation's mission.

5.0 FACILITIES

Transportation System

5.1.1. Roadways

Fort Riley has approximately 241 miles of paved roads and 124 miles of graveled tank trails. In addition, the installation's training areas are threaded with a vast network of dirt roads and trails. Fort Riley is served by an extensive, well-maintained, off-post, roadway system. Seven principal roadways access the installation: Grant Avenue (from Junction City, at West Huebner); K18 Highway (at 12th Street, Camp Funston and via Riley Avenue, Ogden, at East Huebner); I-70, Exit 301 (Henry Drive at Marshall Army Airfield); Washington Street (from Junction City at Trooper Drive); US77 Highway (Range Road, into Camp Forsyth); and old US77 Highway (Estes Road, into Custer Hill).

5.1.2. Railways

Fort Riley has 12 miles of track located in three areas: Camp Funston, Camp Whitside, and Main Post. The Army owns the track on the installation, with the exception of the main line, which is owned by the Union Pacific Railroad. Camp Funston is the primary location for rail loading activities. This area contains adequate open land for staging, new dock facilities, good rail access, and night lighting for 24-hour operations. The Camp Funston area has a capacity of 340 rail cars.

5.1.3. Airfields

Marshall Army Airfield (MAAF) is Fort Riley's on-post airfield. It consists of a 4,503-foot long runway (100 feet wide with 25 feet paved shoulders), 50-foot wide taxiways (with 25 feet paved shoulders), and 148,000 square yards of parking aprons. It is primarily designed to accommodate rotary-winged aircraft.

Water Supply

Groundwater is the water source for domestic and industrial use at Fort Riley. The groundwater for most of Fort Riley is withdrawn from aquifers recharged by the Republican and Kansas rivers. Individual well capacities range from 400 to 1,000 gallons per minute (gpm). The total pumping capacity from these wells is 1,400 gpm or 10.8 million gallons per day (mgd). The water used at the Douthit Gunnery Complex is withdrawn from an upland aquifer with well capacity of 80 gpm.

Wastewater

Ft. Riley is served by an advanced wastewater treatment plant (AWWTP) constructed in 2011. The AWWTP influent is primarily domestic wastewater with a design flow of 3 million gallons a day. The treatment process units consist of pumping and preliminary, biological processes, post treatment processes and solids treatment and handling.

Domestic wastewater is collected and conveyed through the gravity collection system (consisting of approximately 85 miles of pipeline) to a series of pump stations that pump the wastewater to the AWWTP. AWWTP biosolids are held in three storage bays prior to being taken to a field storage area where they may be stored up to two years. The dried biosolids are then land applied. Effluent from the AWWTP discharges into Threemile Creek, which empties into the Kansas River.

Effluents are sampled and discharged in accordance with National Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Permit # F-KS51-OO01.

Industrial wastewater is generated in the tactical equipment shops and vehicle washracks on Custer Hill. Wastewater from these operations undergoes oil/water separation and sediment settling in sedimentation basins on Custer Hill. After passing through the sedimentation basins, the water drains into the Central Vehicle Wash Facility lagoon system for further treatment, where it is eventually recycled for exterior vehicle cleaning at the facility.

6.0 RESPONSIBLE AND INTERESTED PARTIES

Full implementation of this INRMP requires collaboration and coordination with many internal and external parties. The list of stakeholders is below. See Appendix E for the duties, responsibilities, and/or coordination for these entities.

- Primary Installation Personnel and Organizations
 - Commanding General
 - Garrison Commander
 - Directorate of Public Works
 - Directorate of Emergency Services
 - Directorate of Family, Morale, Welfare and Recreation
 - Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobilization & Security
 - Staff Judge Advocate
 - Public Affairs Office
 - Medical Department Activity
 - Military Units
 - Environmental Quality Control Council
- Higher Headquarters
 - Headquarters, Installation Management Command (IMCOM)
 - U. S. Army FORSCOM
 - Army Environmental Command
- Other Army Agencies
 - Corps of Engineers, Kansas City District
 - Corps of Engineers, Waterways Experiment Station
 - Corps of Engineers, Construction Engineering Research Laboratories
 - Central Region Environmental Office
- United States Department of Agriculture
 - U.S. Forest Service
 - Natural Resource Conservation Service
 - Animal-Plant Health Inspection Service
- U.S. Department of the Interior
 - U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
 - U.S. Geological Survey, Kansas State University Cooperative Research Unit
- State Agencies
 - Kansas Forest Service
 - Kansas Department of Agriculture
 - Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism
 - Kansas State Historical Society
- Other Interested Parties
 - County Governments
 - Contractors
 - Partners in Flight
 - Kansas Land Trust
 - The Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation
 - Ducks Unlimited

- Pheasants Forever/Quail Forever
- Riley County Conservation District
- Fort Riley Outdoorsmen Group
- National Wild Turkey Federation
- Customers

7.0 NATURAL RESOURCES AND CLIMATE

Setting

Fort Riley lies in the Flint Hills ecoregion (CEC 1997; see Appendix F). This is a region of limestone and shale open hills with relatively narrow, steep valleys. Most of the Flint Hills is pastureland grazed by beef cattle, in contrast to surrounding ecological regions that are mostly in cropland. Potential natural vegetation in the region is tallgrass prairie. The Nature Conservancy lists the tallgrass prairie as the most altered ecological community in North America. Of the 142 million acres of tallgrass prairie that once covered the American heartland, less than 4% remains. The Flint Hills area of Kansas and Oklahoma is by far the largest tallgrass prairie landscape on the continent, with more acres remaining there than in all the other prairie states and provinces combined. However, invasive plants, urban sprawl, urban-to-rural migration, woody encroachment, and continued prairie and ranch fragmentation have degraded a sizable portion of the Flint Hills.

Cultural Resources

A range of cultural resources are present within the boundaries of Fort Riley. These include a National Register of Historic Places listed district and two that are eligible for listing; historic landscapes, structures and objects; prehistoric and historic (including military) archaeological sites; and Native American sacred sites. Fort Riley's mission and mission support activities, including natural resources management activities, have varying degrees of impact on these cultural resources.

Cultural Resources Management occurs in compliance with all pertinent Federal laws, regulations, and executive orders, and in accordance with Army regulations and policy. Cultural Resource Program staff perform reviews of Fort Riley's activities to determine the level of impact to cultural resources and resolve effects, in accordance with the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966, as amended. The review process and resolution of effects has been streamlined via alternative procedures as outlined in an operations and maintenance Programmatic Agreement with the Kansas State Historic Preservation Officer (SHPO) and Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (see Appendix G). Integration and implementation of these procedures is addressed in detail within the Fort Riley Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP). Additional agreements that may impact natural resources or be impacted by Natural Resources Management activities include two Programmatic Agreements addressing privatized Army lodging and housing, in addition to two Comprehensive Agreements with the Kaw Nation of Oklahoma and the Pawnee Tribe of Oklahoma addressing obligations in accordance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act. Lastly, the Cultural Resources Program staff have been delegated the responsibility to act as liaisons with the ACHP, Kansas SHPO and all 12 federally-recognized tribes with interest in prehistoric cultural resources at Fort Riley.

Topography

Elevations on Fort Riley vary from 1,025 to 1,365 feet above mean sea level. Terrain varies from alluvial bottomlands along the Republican and Kansas rivers on the southern portion of the

installation, through the hilly to steep lands in the central and east portions, to the high uplands in the north and west portions.

Geology

Fort Riley is composed of three types of geological-physiographic areas: 1) high upland prairies; 2) alluvial bottomland flood plains; and 3) broken and hilly transition zones. The high upland prairies consist of layers of nearly level to gently dipping limestone and shale of the Permian, with the various shale layers covering the escarpment-forming limestones. The cutting action of the streams on the thick shale units has sculpted much of the area into a rolling plateau. Two types of alluvial bottomlands exist at Fort Riley: wide meandering floodplains of major rivers, with associated terraces; and areas created by smaller creeks and streams that cut the uplands. The transitional areas, extending from the uplands down to the valley floors are broken, sloping to steep country composed of alternating limestones and shales.

Fort Riley is located within a Zone II seismic area, which includes the entire Flint Hills area from Oklahoma to Nebraska. A small fault located northeast of Fort Riley near Tuttle Creek Lake appears to be inactive. Nevertheless, earthquakes producing moderate structural damage are possible within the Fort Riley area. No other identified geologic hazards exist in the Fort Riley area.

Climate

Fort Riley has a temperate continental climate characterized by hot summers, cold, dry winters, moderate winds, low to moderate humidity, and a pronounced peak in rainfall late in the spring and in the first half of summer. Prevailing winds are from the south to southwest during most of the year, except during February and March when the prevailing winds are from the north. Average yearly precipitation is 31.64 inches and most of the precipitation (75%) falls within the six month period from April through September. The three highest rainfall months (May, June, and July) each average more than 4 inches per month. Much of this precipitation occurs during thunderstorms, when 2 inches or more of rain may fall in one storm. December, January, and February are the driest months with each averaging less than 1.56 inches of liquid-equivalent precipitation. An average of about 22 inches of snowfall occurs annually (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 1975).

Insufficient precipitation is the major limiting factor to plant growth at Fort Riley. Normally, spring rains are adequate to recharge soil moisture before the summer months when evapotranspiration rates normally exceed precipitation rates, especially in the latter half of the summer. In years of below average rainfall, soil moisture in the upper soil levels is depleted, which stresses shallow rooted plants.

Soils

The primary soil association encountered on Fort Riley is the Wymore-Irwin. It is a deep, nearly level group of silty, clay loams found in the upland. The Smolan-Geary and the Clime-Sogn are also prevalent (Jantz et. al, 1975). Smolan soils are composed of deep, gently sloping to sloping materials and are typically formed in loess. These tend to be moderately well to well-drained soils with slow permeability. Geary soils consist of deep, gently sloping and sloping deposits that are well drained and have moderate permeability. Clime soils consist of moderately deep, sloping to moderately steep deposits that are calcareous in nature as a result of being formed from the

weathered residuum of calcareous clayey shales. These soils have moderately well to well-drained characteristics with moderately slow permeability. Sogn soils are shallow, sloping underlain by limestone and were formed in residual material weathered from shale and limestone. They have moderate permeability and can be excessively drained. The Eudora-Haynie-Sarpy Eudora association is found on floodplains & terraces. The soils tend to be deep, nearly level silt loams, very fine sandy loams, and loamy fine sands with well-drained characteristics and are moderately permeable.

Water Resources

7.1.1. Wetlands

Wetland areas on Fort Riley include springs, seeps, streams, rivers, ponds, lakes, vernal pools and emergent marshes (Exhibit 7.1). Approximately 1,536 acres of wetlands are present on the installation according to a National Wetlands Inventory completed in 1991 by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. Of this total, 972 acres are considered permanently inundated. The majority of all wetlands are riverine; riverine habitat comprises 144.8 miles and encompasses 748 acres. Lacustrine and palustrine wetlands cover 431 and 270 acres of the installation, respectively.

7.1.1.1. Rivers and Streams

Three rivers are on Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.1), flowing for a combined 13.6 miles. All rivers have surface flow throughout the year. The Republican River and the Smoky Hill River come together at the southern boundary of Fort Riley to form the Kansas River.

Fifteen other streams are present, flowing for a combined 131.2 miles. Onemile, Dry, Dry Branch, Farnum and Rush creeks generally have surface flow only during runoff from storm events. Surface flow in Forsyth Creek is maintained by effluent from the WWTP. The flow in the other streams results from runoff, seeps and springs. Honey, Little Arkansas, Wind, and Fourmile creeks are intermittent. Wildcat, Sevenmile, Timber, Threemile and Madison creeks generally have surface flow year round, although during droughts these will become intermittent as well.

Streams in the southern and central portions of Fort Riley drain to the south into the Republican or Kansas rivers. Streams in the western portion of Fort Riley drain toward the southwest into Milford Lake. Streams in the northeastern portion of Fort Riley drain to the northeast into Wildcat Creek, a tributary of the Kansas River.

Wildcat Creek has been designated a significant fisheries resource (Kansas Fish and Game Commission, 1981). The KDWPT also has rated the Republican, Smoky Hill, and Kansas rivers as high priority fishery resources.

Exhibit 7.1. Wetland areas (springs, seeps, streams, rivers, ponds, lakes, vernal pools, and emergent marshes) on Fort Riley.

7.1.1.2. Ponds and Lakes

Milford Lake is formed by the damming of the Republican River to the northwest of the installation. Presently, 29 other ponds and lakes on Fort Riley are actively managed for sport fishing and game fish (Exhibit 7.2).

Exhibit 7.2. Locations of 29 ponds and lakes actively managed for sport fishing on Fort Riley.

7.1.1.3. Vernal Pools and Emergent Marshes

Vernal pools occur mostly in low areas behind terraces of abandoned crop-fields, and have been constructed in other locations that receive light military use. Emergent marshes exist as man-made wetlands, pools behind beaver dams, or occur along the periphery of water bodies, such as those within the Madison Creek outlet into Milford Lake (Exhibit 7.3).

7.1.2. Surface Water Quality

The Kansas Department of Health and the Environment (KDHE) has designated surface water use categories for the Republican, Smoky Hill, and Kansas rivers; FourMile, Rush, Timber, Little Arkansas, Sevenmile, Threemile and Wildcat creeks; and Milford Lake (KDHE 2004). Designated uses are defined in Kansas Water Quality Standards. The KDHE has determined these surface water bodies are suitable for, and should be protected for, contact recreation, expected or special aquatic life, food procurement, domestic water supply, irrigation, livestock watering, industrial water supply, and groundwater recharge (Exhibit 7.4).

WATER BODY	CLASS	AL	CR	DS	FP	GR	IW	IR	LW
Fourmile Ck	GP	E	C						
Republican R	GP	S	C	X	X	X	X	X	X
Rush Ck	GP	E	b						
Timber Ck	GP	E	C	X					
Kansas R	GP	S	B	X	X	X	X	X	X
Little Arkansas Ck	GP	E							
Sevenmile Ck	GP	E	b						
Threemile Ck	GP	E	C	X	X	X	X	X	X
Wildcat Ck	GP	S	C	X	X	X	X	X	X
Smoky Hill R	GP	E	C	X	X	X	X	X	X
Milford Lake	GP	E	A	X	X		X		

Abbreviations:

CLASS = antidegradation category

GP = general purpose waters

AL = designated for aquatic life use

S = special aquatic life use water

E = expected aquatic life use water

CR = designated for contact recreational use

A = Primary contact recreation stream segment is a designated public swimming area

B = Primary contact recreation stream segment is by law or written permission of the landowner open to and accessible by the public

C = Primary contact recreation stream segment is not open to and accessible by the public under Kansas law.

b = Secondary contact recreation stream segment is not open to and accessible by the public under Kansas law

DS = designated for domestic water supply use

FP = designated for food procurement use

GR = designated for ground water recharge

IW = designated for industrial water supply use

IR = designated for irrigation use

LW = designated for livestock watering use

Exhibit 7.4. Designated surface water use categories determined by the KDHE for waters on Fort Riley.

The KDHE listed Wildcat Creek as an impaired stream due to high fecal coliform bacteria count and low dissolved oxygen under Section 303d of the Clean Water Act. However, anecdotal information provided by Riley County indicated the quality of water in Wildcat Creek passing through Ft. Riley was good. The problems likely are occurring in the lower end of stream, below the confluence of Little Kitten Creek, from poorly functioning on-site waste systems in the vicinity of Manhattan (KDHE 2004). Urban development occurring on the west side of Manhattan, downstream from Fort Riley, is increasing sediment and contaminant loads in Wildcat Creek, and altering hydrogeomorphology.

The ITAM program conducted a water quality study comparing hardened stream crossing sites to unimproved earthen fords at six streams on Fort Riley (Sample 1996). Data was collected on turbidity, total solids, total dissolved solids, total suspended solids, settleable solids, pH, total hardness, calcium hardness, and total alkalinity at stream crossings prior to and after traffic. Water quality associated with hardened stream crossings was determined to be better than that associated with earthen fords.

Flora

Under natural conditions, this region consisted of tall- and mixed-grass prairies dominated by big bluestem, indiangrass, and switchgrass (Kuchler, 1974). The pre-settlement prairie was maintained through frequent wildfires and grazing by herbivores. Fort Riley's current prairie is manipulated primarily by man-made influences and, secondarily, by natural factors. Fort Riley grasslands are interspersed by linear communities of woodlands, highly variable in width, that are associated with streams, other woodland plantings, and man-made water impoundments. Woodlands tend to increase in width the closer the tributary streams are to the river. The flora and fauna in some locations are further influenced by their proximity to Milford Lake. Past and current land management practices, such as the suppression of fire, the introduction of agriculture, and the expansion of urban facilities have degraded the grasslands, allowed for invasive woody vegetation, and resulted in the establishment of several non-native vegetation classes.

In 2003, the Kansas Biological Survey (KBS) completed a project examining the vegetation of Fort Riley that assessed the current condition of vegetation on the installation, located tracts of native prairie, and determined the locations and severity of noxious weed species infestations. In 2011/2012, these surveys were repeated. The KBS developed a new vegetation classification for the installation, identifying eight primary habitat types; floodplain forest, ravine woodland, Flint Hills tallgrass prairie, sand prairie, limestone butte vegetation, altered grassland vegetation, woodland-brushy, and planted/cultivated vegetation (Exhibit 7.5; see Appendix H for detailed descriptions of classification). During their surveys, KBS recorded nearly 520 species of vascular plants (Freeman and Delisle 2004; Appendix I, Table 1).

7.1.3. Grasslands

Freeman and Delisle (2004) considered grasslands to be vegetative communities with grass and forb coverage greater than 25% canopy cover and woody cover less than 25%. Grasslands on Fort Riley consist of two basic types: native grasslands and "go-back" areas. Grasslands comprise approximately 67% of the installation, as shown on Exhibit 7.5. Hay leases were let on 38,000 acres of warm and cool season grasslands during the most recent contracting period in 2015.

7.1.3.1. Native Grasslands

The native grasslands of Fort Riley consist primarily of tallgrass prairie. Some elements of the mixed-grass prairie exist because Fort Riley is located near the transition zone between the tallgrass prairie and the mixed-grass prairie to the west (Kuchler, 1974).

The native grasslands on Fort Riley generally do not exhibit classic tallgrass prairie, which would be composed of big bluestem, indiagrass, switchgrass, or the mid-grass prairie, such as little bluestem and sideoats grama. Past land use activities, minimal management, lack of large herbivore grazing, and military training exercises have produced native grasslands that exhibit a less than pristine species composition, and that have been invaded by woody species. The grasslands with the least disturbance contain the highest percentages of native warm-season grasses and associated forbs.

Delisle et al. (2013) located, evaluated, and mapped locations of native prairie fields on Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.6). They identified 120 Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairies ranging in size from 12-2,172 acres, 78% of which were considered to be A-grade or B-grade, indicating low to moderate impact by humans. This was a significant increase from the 33.6% that were identified in the 2002/2003 surveys (Freeman and Delisle 2004). The largest prairies generally graded the highest, and were concentrated in the south, east, and northwest parts of the installation. The remaining prairie fields were C-grade or D-grade. Most of these prairies were small, isolated, and moderately to severely impacted by past or ongoing human activities. Prairies are most abundant in those areas with the greatest topographic relief. Areas with comparatively lower relief have experienced a much higher incidence of past cultivation, as in the central part of the installation.

Three kinds of native grassland were delineated; Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie, Sand Prairie, and Limestone Butte Sparse Vegetation.

Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie is the dominant natural community type on the installation. Stands occur primarily on uplands and slopes but may occur infrequently in well-drained sites on floodplains. This community is dominated by a dense cover of tall grasses with a moderate to high richness of forbs. Dominant grasses are big bluestem, indiagrass, and little bluestem. Sideoats grama, switchgrass, and tall dropseed are common but less abundant. Typical forbs include asters, sunflower, roundhead lespedeza, scurfpea, goldenrod, and violet. Shrubs, such as leadplant, and trees usually are infrequent but can be common near watercourses or where fires have been suppressed.

Sand Prairie is restricted to the floodplain of the Republican and Kansas rivers, usually immediately adjacent to the rivers. The best remnants occur in Training Areas 18 and 19. This community is dominated by moderately to widely-spaced mid- to tall-grasses. The dominant species are sand bluestem and prairie sandreed. Other characteristic grasses include blue grama, hairy grama, sandbur, sand lovegrass, prairie junegrass, and little bluestem. Characteristic forbs are sand milkweed, desert goosefoot, winged pigfoot, sunflower, blazing star, cutleaf evening primrose, groundcherry, and wooly plantain. Representative shrubs and vines are rough-leaved dogwood, chickasaw plum, fragrant sumac, and poison ivy.

Limestone Butte Sparse Vegetation is dominated by drought-tolerant herbaceous species. This community is widely distributed on the installation, primarily on the upper slopes along bluffs of the Republican and Kansas rivers, and along their tributaries in association with outcrops of the Fort Riley limestone. Representative species include prairie spurge, Missouri pincushion, greenviolet, lomatium, Missouri evening primrose, fine-leaf gerardia, and yucca. Stands on Fort

Riley are in small patches and were mapped to be included in the Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie GIS layer.

7.1.3.2. **“Go-Back” Grasslands (Abandoned Cropland/Brome Field)**

“Go-back” grassland refers to grassland communities that have been moderately to highly altered by human activities, usually due to past cultivation. Some of the “go-back” areas on Fort Riley ceased to be cultivated prior to their acquisition by the Army. Most ceased to be cultivated after acquisition. The “go-back” lands are in various stages of ecological succession. Early seral stages consisting of annual grasses (prairie threeawn, green brome), Japanese brome) and forbs (Missouri goldenrod, daisy fleabane, snow-on-the-mountain, western ragweed) are present in areas that continue to have frequent vehicular traffic (e.g., parts of Maneuver Areas A, B, D, and E). Most examples are dominated by herbaceous species, but shrubs or trees often are present, and in some cases they dominate.

Other “go-back” grassland areas not as frequently or intensively impacted by military vehicles are in further developed seral stages, and at times are exceedingly difficult to distinguish from prairie in the field. Dominant species in these areas are those typically occurring in the installation's native grasslands (indiangrass and switchgrass) or are mosaics of native tallgrass prairie species and perennial cool season "tame" grasses. Delisle et al. (2013) located, evaluated, and mapped locations of “go-back” grasslands on Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.5).

7.1.4. **Invasive Plants**

7.1.4.1. **Noxious Weeds**

There are five species of noxious weeds that require control by State of Kansas laws that are known to occur on Fort Riley. These are musk thistle, kudzu, field bindweed, Johnsongrass and sericea lespedeza. Both native and “go-back” grasslands, as well as the other vegetative communities present on the fort, are experiencing varying amounts of noxious weed infestations.

Populations of musk-thistle and Johnsongrass on the installation are mostly small and isolated (Exhibit 7.7), with 77 and 218 acres infested, respectively (Freeman & Delisle 2004). Field bindweed is principally a problem on routinely disturbed range sites and areas that are mowed to a height less than four inches. It also is a problem in firebreak and wildlife food plot crop fields. Sericea lespedeza is the most widespread noxious weed; Freeman & Delisle (2004) found it in 94 training areas and infesting an estimated 13,000 acres. Only localized populations were found on prairies; the most extensive sericea lespedeza populations occurred on go-back grasslands in the central and eastern parts of the installation (Exhibit 7.7). Ten years later KBS estimated 21,600 acres were infested with sericea lespedeza (Delisle 2013), with intrusion into grasslands increasing. Conservation Branch surveys have identified approximately 30,000 acres of sericea lespedeza on post. This includes areas that currently have actively growing plants as well as areas that have had infestations in the past and are believed to still contain a significant seed bank in the soil.

7.1.4.2. **Shrublands**

Extensive areas of shrubland are not a natural feature of the prairie environment. The reduction in wildfires, lack of management, past cultivation and ground disturbances from military training activities have contributed to shrubby encroachment. This includes the overgrown condition of windbreaks, the encroachment of woody shrubs into the grasslands, the establishment of single, large trees in the grasslands, and the maturation of large trees in small, shrubby drainage fingers. Shrublands remain a minor, but increasing component of the installation's landscape, covering less than 2 percent of the installation.

Woody encroachment is occurring in all types of grasslands. Shrubs are located along the edges of woodlands, in isolated patches along the smaller intermittent drainages and ravines, and scattered throughout many grassland fields (Exhibit 7.8).

The shrub encroachment generally is dominated by a moderate to dense cover of shrubs, frequently intermixed with a variety of immature trees. Buckbrush is the most common understory shrub, usually associated with plum, rough-leaved dogwood and smooth sumac. Eastern redcedar, cottonwood and elm are the primary tree species invading grasslands, although honey locust, green ash and osage-orange also occur. The herbaceous understory is highly variable from site to site.

An exotic invasive is the black locust tree. Native to the Southern Appalachians and the Southeastern United States, this tree is naturalized throughout America. Once introduced to an area, black locust expands into areas where its shade reduces competition from other sun-loving plants. The tree poses a threat to native vegetation in prairies, oak savannas and upland forest edges outside of its historic range. While present on the installation, it does not appear to be significantly spreading (Delisle et al. 2013)

7.1.5. **Forestlands**

Forestlands comprise approximately 16,400 acres of Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.5). Most of this acreage is associated with the bottomland forests along the Republican and Kansas Rivers and the woodlands within the drainages of Threemile, Sevenmile and Wildcat Creeks. However, upland forests occur along the mainstems of most streams on the installation.

Freeman and Delisle (2004) identified three forest communities (Eastern cottonwood-Willow Forest, Eastern cottonwood-Sycamore Forest, and Green ash-Elm-Hackberry Forest) and one woodland community (Chinquapin oak-Bur oak Ravine Woodland) on Fort Riley. Forest Communities generally had 61–100% tree canopy cover, three distinct canopy layers (overstory trees, understory shrubs, herbaceous layer), and trees >5 m tall. Woodland communities usually had 26–60% canopy cover and trees <5 m tall.

Exhibit 7.8. Locations of shrubs located along the edges of woodlands, in isolated patches along the smaller intermittent drainages, and scattered throughout many grassland fields on Fort Riley.

7.1.5.1. **Riverine Floodplain Forest**

7.1.5.1.1. **Eastern cottonwood-Willow Forest**

The Eastern cottonwood-Willow Forest stands occur on floodplains adjacent to rivers in sites that frequently are flooded. Establishment and maintenance of the community is tied closely to flooding events. This riparian forest community has a closed or nearly closed tree canopy with cottonwood and black willow as the dominant trees. Boxelder, silver maple, green ash, sycamore, and American elm are common associates, but tree diversity is limited due to the dynamics of flooding, scouring, and sediment deposition. The subcanopy usually is dominated by black willow. The shrub layer may be conspicuously absent, and herbaceous growth may be lush but often is patchy, again due to flooding.

7.1.5.1.2. **Eastern cottonwood-Sycamore Forest**

The Eastern cottonwood-Sycamore Forest stands occur in floodplains of rivers, and along large streams as they empty into rivers. This riparian forest community has an open to closed tree canopy with cottonwood and sycamore as the dominant tree species. Boxelder, hackberry, and black willow are common associates. The shrub layer may be poorly developed to well developed, depending on flood frequency and duration. Tartarian honeysuckle has become a dense understory component of many stands of this community. Delisle and Freeman (2004) combined the Eastern cottonwood-Black willow Forest and Eastern cottonwood-Sycamore Forest as riverine floodplain forest when mapping habitat types of Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.5).

7.1.5.2. **Riparian Upland Woodland**

7.1.5.2.1. **Green ash-Elm-Hackberry Forest**

The Green ash-Elm-Hackberry Forest stands occur along the upper floodplain terraces of rivers and streams, and in upland river bottoms. This riparian forest community has an open to closed tree canopy with green ash, hackberry, and American elm as the dominant tree species. Silver maple, black walnut, cottonwood, and basswood are common associates. Red elm may be part of the subcanopy. The well-developed shrub layer includes rough-leaved dogwood, wild gooseberry, wolfberry, and prickly ash, as well as woody vines, such as woodbine, greenbrier, poison ivy, and riverbank grape. The herbaceous layer in the western part of the range includes Virginia wildrye, nodding fescue, and wood nettle.

7.1.5.2.2. **Chinquapin oak-Bur oak Ravine Woodland**

The Chinquapin oak-Bur oak Ravine Woodland stands occur on moderate to steep south-facing and west-facing slopes of ravines and river valleys. This open-canopy, upland community is dominated by chinquapin oak in the driest stands, with bur oak as a subdominant. Bur oak becomes more important in sites where conditions are more mesic until, eventually, the community grades into a forest with relatively little chinquapin oak. Elm species and redbud can be abundant. Shrub cover varies inversely with tree canopy cover. Common shrubs are rough-leaved dogwood and buckbrush. Hackberry and elm species often are in the shrub layer, especially on sites that have not been burned recently. Herbaceous dominants include little bluestem and switchgrass. The surface is not saturated or flooded by groundwater at any time during the year, and drought is relatively common. Drought and fire were common natural disturbances in this community type. Species composition is, however, generally shifting from an oak composition to nearly pure stands of hackberry. The primary factor for the species change is lack of disturbance in forest stands, allowing the shade tolerant hackberry to rise from understory to dominance. Freeman and Delisle

(2004) combined the Green ash-Elm-Hackberry Forest and Chinquapin oak-Bur oak Ravine Woodland when mapping habitat types of Fort Riley (Exhibit 7.5).

7.1.5.3. Invasive Plants

Approximately one percent of the understory vegetation in woodland plots is the noxious weed *sericea lespedeza*. Woodlands are also experiencing invasion by the exotic Tartarian honeysuckle; in some tracts this invasive is achieving nearly 90% dominance of the understory vegetation. The woodlands experiencing the greatest Tartarian honeysuckle invasion are in the southern portion of the installation, and generally along the Kansas and Republican rivers. A pocket of kudzu infesting less than one acre was located along Onemile Creek within the Main Post District. The infestation was initially treated and plant population was reduced by over 99%. A very small infestation remains on the cut-bank of One-Mile Creek. The infestation is monitored and treated yearly to prevent any additional spread. The kudzu will be considered eradicated when no live plants are observed for five consecutive years.

7.1.6. Savannas

The upper regions of some of the Chinquapin oak-Bur oak Ravine Woodland stands produce savanna type habitats. Savannas are defined in this plan as areas that have tree canopy coverage from 5-15% and are one acre or more in size. Fort Riley's savannas have an average of 25 trees per acre. The most common trees are oak, hackberry, American elm and green ash. The most common understory plants are smooth brome grass, big bluestem, Japanese brome grass, and little bluestem. Noxious weeds are rare on the savanna sites. A planning level survey to document locations of savanna habitats was last performed in 1999. Due to the dynamic nature of vegetation resulting from aggressive prairie management actions, savannas on Fort Riley tend to be somewhat transitory. Surveys to determine current locations of savannas have not been performed since 1999 because of a low priority placed on management of this habitat type by the installation and the small quantity of this habitat on Fort Riley.

Agricultural Outleases

Agricultural leases typically run for five years. The Kansas City District, U. S. Army Corps of Engineers, issues and administers the leases, and the Conservation Branch manages them.

7.1.7. Hay Fields

Many grassland fields on Fort Riley are leased for hay harvest (Exhibit 7.9). Hay fields are designated as either warm season or cool season, based upon the dominant grass species present. Most hay is harvested from areas dominated by native, warm-season grasses.

7.1.8. Croplands

A firebreak system has been established around the installation's perimeter to delineate installation boundaries and minimize wildfire spread off the installation onto adjacent privately-owned lands. Nearly 1,300 acres along approximately 44 miles of the boundary are leased for crop production. Leased firebreak fields are maintained as agricultural croplands where soil conditions allow (Exhibit 7.10). In areas where the soil is not arable because of severe slopes or rocky conditions, a

crawler tractor-pulled disc accomplishes that tillage. The firebreak varies in width from approximately 150 feet to in excess of 300 feet.

Exhibit 7.9. Locations of hay field leases on Fort Riley. Leases are for either cool season or warm season grasses. Warm season leases may be hayed in even numbered years only, odd numbered years only, or annually.

Wildlife food plots consist of approximately 800 acres in plots of approximately 1 to 30 acres (Exhibit 7.10). These fields are located throughout the installation. The majority of the food plots have now been planted to alfalfa to reduce long-term costs and provide increased pollinator food sources. Soybean, winter wheat and corn food plots are planted in areas often frequented by elk. Sunflower food plots are planted for mourning doves and passerine birds.

Fauna

Fort Riley habitat supports at least 40 species of mammals, 269 species of birds, 47 species of turtles, reptiles and amphibians, and 60 species of fish.

7.1.9. Game Animals and Furbearers

Fort Riley supports viable populations of all the typical game species found in this region of Kansas. Upland game birds are northern bobwhite, ring-necked pheasant and greater prairie-chicken. Migratory game birds include various duck and goose species, mourning dove, Wilson's snipe and American woodcock. Small game animals in abundance include fox squirrel cottontail rabbit and American crow. Jackrabbits are occasionally seen but hunting jackrabbits is prohibited on Fort Riley. Big game species are white-tailed deer and elk. Wild turkeys are also present. Furbearer species are badger, bobcat, mink, muskrat, opossum, raccoon, red fox, gray fox, striped skunk, coyote and beaver. A description of the distribution and abundance of game animals and furbearers on Fort Riley is in Appendix J.

7.1.10. Non-Game Animals

7.1.10.1. Mammals

Thirty species of non-game mammals have been reported on Fort Riley. Six of those are documented only by Pitts et al. (1987). It is unclear whether the author actually observed these species, or included these as species that should be present based on a literature review of the range for these species. Non-game mammalian species considered abundant on Fort Riley are Elliot's short-tailed shrew, eastern mole, big brown bat, thirteen-lined ground squirrel, plains pocket gopher, western harvest mouse, deer mouse, white-footed mouse, cotton rat, eastern woodrat, prairie vole, and house mouse. The southern bog lemming, a Kansas-listed Species in Need of Conservation, is present. The complete list of mammals is at Appendix I, Table 2.

7.1.10.2. Birds

The avifauna of Fort Riley is rich and diverse, with 269 bird species documented on the installation (Appendix I, Table 3). As is typical for Kansas, most of these species are migrant, non-game passerines. The birds occupy a wide range of habitat types on the installation, from riverine sandbars to interior woodlands.

Numerous inventories of birds have been conducted on Fort Riley, and are described in Appendix K. Surveys have documented 134 bird species on Fort Riley during "breeding safe dates", i.e., periods when migrants of that species are expected to be absent from Kansas (Appendix I, Table 4). Of these, 110 are confirmed or probable breeders. The most abundant breeding birds are brown-headed cowbird, dickcissel, grasshopper sparrow, eastern meadowlark and mourning dove. Other notable breeding birds include Henslow's sparrow, loggerhead shrike, and the interior

woodland species ovenbird, wood thrush and prothonotary warbler. Common woodland species include blue jay, black-capped chickadee and northern cardinal. Common shrubby edge species include brown thrasher, common yellowthroat and field sparrow.

Common raptors are red-tailed hawk, northern harrier, great horned owl, barred owl, bald eagle, eastern screech-owl and American kestrel. Common shorebirds are killdeer, greater yellowlegs, lesser yellowlegs, least sandpiper, and spotted sandpiper. Common wading birds are great blue heron, great egret and little blue heron. Common winter birds are Harris's sparrow, American tree sparrow and dark-eyed junco.

7.1.10.3. Reptiles and Amphibians

Fort Riley supports the variety of snakes, turtles, lizards, frogs, and toads commonly found in the tallgrass prairie region (Busby et al, 1994). Forty-seven species of reptiles and amphibians (21 species of snakes, 9 lizards, 7 turtles, and 10 amphibians) have been captured or observed on Fort Riley (Appendix I, Table 5). The most common species are ringneck snake and western chorus frog. No listed threatened or endangered species are known to occur. The venomous copperhead is common in woodlands on Fort Riley. In 2005, there was a report of a massasauga in Maneuver Area N. However, the snake was not captured, no picture was taken to confirm the identification, and the individual was not certain of the identification. Thus, the species is not included. A photo of a timber rattlesnake reportedly taken from Fort Riley in Training Area 33 on March 31, 2010 has been received by the Conservation Branch. The species is considered rare on Fort Riley.

7.1.11. Fish

Fish habitat on Fort Riley comprises perennial and intermittent streams, rivers, and man-made and natural impoundments. Overall, 60 species of fish have been documented in Fort Riley's streams, lakes, and ponds (Appendix I, Table 6).

Surveys of Fort Riley streams have documented 45 fish species (Appendix I, Table 7) and produced a general portrait of fish assemblages. Fish species in streams that drain into Milford Lake show a lake effect, being dominated by centrarchids (sunfish family). Largemouth bass, green sunfish, and bluegill are the major representatives. Streams on the eastern side of the installation are dominated by cyprinids (minnow family), such as redbfin shiners, bluntnose minnows, fathead minnows, and central stonerollers. The endangered Topeka shiner occurs in some of these eastern streams.

Surveys have documented 40 species in the three rivers on Fort Riley (Appendix I, Table 6). These include the shovelnose sturgeon, suckermouth minnow, red shiner, sand shiner, emerald shiner and river carpsucker.

Fish in ponds and lakes are largely represented by species managed for recreational fishing. Sport fish species introduced or supplemented by periodic stocking consist of channel catfish, rainbow trout, largemouth bass, flathead catfish, redear sunfish, and hybrid bluegill. Other unstocked game fish species inhabiting some ponds include white bass, yellow bullhead, black bullhead, green sunfish and white crappie. Appendix I, Table 8, lists the species found in each of the 29 managed lakes and ponds.

7.1.12. Invertebrates

Generally, invertebrate data is lacking for Fort Riley. KDWPT surveys found 19 orders/families of aquatic insects in Timber Creek and 14 orders/families of aquatic insects in Fourmile Creek. Conservation Branch surveys documented 17 mussel species that have resided on Ft. Riley, of which seven species were found extant (Appendix I, Table 9). The other 10 species are apparently extirpated from the installation. One of the ten (hickorynut) is apparently extirpated from the entire state. The most common species collected alive were the pondhorn, fragile papershell, pink papershell, and mapleleaf.

Terrestrial invertebrate surveys have occurred looking specifically for listed species, or ancillary to other field activities. Specific surveys have located prairie mole crickets and various burying beetles (but not American burying beetle). Location sightings for regal fritillary have been recorded as ancillary information collected during other wildlife surveys.

In 2013, Fort Riley funded a two-year research project to 1) provide spatially explicit estimates of the distribution and abundance of the regal fritillary and its host plant, prairie violet; 2) provide models that identify habitat features and management practices that influence the density of regal fritillary adults; and 3) produce information on the effectiveness of management strategies for the regal fritillary populations on Fort Riley.

In 2015, Fort Riley further funded the above project to provide baseline population estimates of adult monarch and population trend estimates of adult regal fritillary. The study also identified environmental attributes such as hay removal and fire land management practices that influence those species, including an analysis of land management implications.

Threatened and Endangered or Rare Species

Inventories have documented the presence of three Federally-listed and seven Kansas-listed threatened and endangered species, and ninety-one rare species. Fourteen other listed or rare species have never been observed but could possibly occur on Fort Riley (Appendix I, Table 10).

7.1.13. Federal Threatened or Endangered Species

The three Federally-listed species documented on Fort Riley are the least tern and Topeka shiner (endangered), and the piping plover (threatened). The bald eagle, delisted in 2007, is a year-around resident.

The Topeka shiner has been found in Wildcat, Sevenmile, Wind, Honey, Silver and Little Arkansas creeks (Exhibit 7.11). It is believed that Topeka shiners potentially may immigrate into Fourmile, Threemile, and Forsyth creeks. The least tern and piping plover are uncommon, primarily transient migrants, but are also potential breeders along the Republican and Kansas rivers' sandbars. The least tern has been observed along the Kansas River and Milford Lake shorelines. The piping plover has been observed along the Republican and Kansas rivers sandbars. Potential habitat for these species is shown at Exhibit 7.12. The primary migratory path for a fourth species, the endangered whooping crane, occurs within 100 miles of Fort Riley. It remains possible that this species may be encountered within the installation's boundaries or air space.

Topeka Shiner Streams

Exhibit 7.11. Streams with documented Topeka shiner captures, or that are identified as possessing habitat apparently suitable for Topeka shiners.

The bald eagle, while no longer federally-listed as threatened, still receives federal protection under the Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act (16 U.S.C. 668-668c), enacted in 1940. Five locations with eagle nests occur on and around Fort Riley. Three eagle nests occur near Madison Creek Cove, Milford Lake on Fort Riley. This area has had one pair of nesting eagles annually since 2004. The second area with an eagle nest is on Corps of Engineers property along Farnum Creek, adjacent to Fort Riley. This nest was first used in 2005, was occupied annually for eleven years, but is unoccupied in 2016. Meanwhile, a new, active bald eagle nest was located on Fort Riley (TA 54) in 2016, approximately 3.5 miles from the Farnum Creek nest. Fort Riley pursued and obtained an Eagle Nest Take Permit for, and subsequently removed the TA 54 nest on November 6, 2017 due to the location of the nest and its proximity to frequent military training. The fourth area is around the confluence of the Kansas River, where four nests exist. Two nests are along the Kansas River on Fort Riley, and two nests are along the Smoky Hill River just upstream from the installation. One pair of nesting eagles have been active in this locale annually since 2009. A fifth eagle nesting location exists approximately one mile west of the installation along the old channel of the Republican River below Milford Dam. Additionally, a sixth eagle nest location has been observed directly across the Kansas River from the Southeast corner of the installation on property owned and managed by the Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism. Bald eagles roost along the Kansas and Smoky Hill rivers, and are frequently observed perched along the Republican River, Kansas River, and Milford Lake shorelines, and flying over Fort Riley. Important bald eagle habitat areas are shown in Exhibit 7.13. Additionally, Fort Riley has documented sightings of golden eagles in Maneuver Areas A, G, and H (Exhibit 7.13). Golden eagles also are protected by the Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act.

7.1.1. Kansas Threatened or Endangered Species

The Kansas-listed species documented on Fort Riley are the least tern (endangered), and the plains minnow, piping plover, snowy plover, sturgeon chub, Topeka shiner, and eastern spotted skunk³ (threatened). Kansas lists Fort Riley as being within the historic range of six additional species; the American burying beetle, silver chub, shoal chub, eastern spotted skunk, Eskimo curlew, and whooping crane. The American burying beetle, Eskimo curlew and whooping crane also are federally-listed as endangered.

7.1.2. Rare Species

Scientific names, designations and status of the rare species that are documented on Fort Riley are provided in Appendix I, Table 10. Rare species habitats, abundances and distributions are described in Appendix I, Table 11.

7.1.2.1. Species at Risk (SAR)

The Army created a SAR list to identify imperiled species that would have a significant impact on military missions if federally-listed as threatened or endangered. The objective of creating the SAR list is to proactively conserve these species now and thereby preclude the need for a future listing. Army resources were budgeted for SAR management. Army-designated SARs that occur on Fort Riley are the Henslow's sparrow, regal fritillary, rusty blackbird and Texas horned lizard.

³ The eastern spotted skunk is documented only by Pitts et al. (1987). It is unclear whether the author actually observed this species, or included it as a species that should be present based on a literature review of the range for the species.

7.1.2.1. **Birds of Conservation Concern 2008**

The 1988 amendment to the Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act (Public Law 100-653, Title VIII) requires the Secretary of the Interior, through the USFWS, to “identify species, subspecies, and

populations of all migratory nongame birds that, without additional conservation actions, are likely to become candidates for listing under the Endangered Species Act of 1973.” *Birds of Conservation Concern 2008* (BCC 2008), the most recent effort by the USFWS to carry out this proactive conservation mandate, identifies migratory and non-migratory birds that are of conservation concern due to population declines, naturally small ranges or population sizes, threats to habitat, or other factors. Birds on the BCC 2008 list that have been documented on Fort Riley are the Acadian Flycatcher, American Bittern, Bald Eagle, Bell's Vireo, Bewick's Wren, Black-billed Cuckoo, Black-crowned Night-Heron, Black Rail, Black Tern, Buff-breasted Sandpiper, Dickcissel, Field Sparrow, Grasshopper Sparrow, Henslow's Sparrow, Horned Grebe, Hudsonian Godwit, Kentucky Warbler, Loggerhead Shrike, Marbled Godwit, Northern Flicker, Peregrine Falcon, Pied-billed Grebe, Prothonotary Warbler, Red-headed Woodpecker, Rusty Blackbird, Short-eared Owl, Solitary Sandpiper, Upland Sandpiper, Whimbrel, Whip-poor-will, and Wood Thrush.

7.1.2.2. Species in Need of Conservation (SINC)

SINC is a Kansas designation given to any nongame species in the state deemed to require conservation measures in an attempt to keep the species from becoming a threatened or endangered species. SINC species do not have the level of statutory protection as those species listed as threatened or endangered in Kansas. Species on the SINC list that have been documented on Fort Riley are the prairie mole cricket, blue sucker, common shiner, Johnny darter, southern redbelly dace, timber rattlesnake, western hognose snake, black rail, black tern, bobolink, ferruginous hawk, golden eagle, Henslow's sparrow, short-eared owl, whip-poor-will, and southern bog lemming.

7.1.2.3. Species of Greatest Conservation Need

Species of Greatest Conservation Need is a Kansas-generated list of species revised during development of the Kansas State Wildlife Action Plan. The Plan is based upon guidance provided by Congress, the USFWS, and the International Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. All species of fish and wildlife in Kansas were evaluated using eight selection criteria, resulting in the identification of 285 species of greatest conservation need. The species of greatest conservation need were prioritized into two categories. Tier 1 includes species listed as endangered or threatened, or with global conservation status rank of G1 or G2; all remaining species are assigned into Tier 2. Tier 1 species that have been documented on Fort Riley are snowy plover, least tern, piping plover, sturgeon chub, Topeka shiner and plains minnow. Fort Riley has documented 83 Tier 2 species (Appendix I, Table 10 and 11).

7.1.3. Listed Habitats

There is no federally-listed critical habitat on Fort Riley. The Department of the Interior initiated a policy to exclude military facilities from critical habitat if there was an approved INRMP for that facility which addressed the species in question. The rationale for this policy was that an INRMP is a planning document that allows the military to implement landscape-level management of its natural resources while coordinating with various stakeholders. The National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2004 codified this policy by amending the Endangered Species Act. Specifically, section 4(a)(3)(B)(i) of the Act (16 U.S.C. 1533(a)(3)(B)(i)) now provides: “The Secretary shall not designate as critical habitat any lands or other geographical areas owned or

controlled by the Department of Defense, or designated for its use, that are subject to an integrated natural resources management plan prepared under section 101 of the Sikes Act (16 U.S.C. 670a), if the Secretary determines in writing that such plan provides a benefit to the species for which critical habitat is proposed for designation.” However, the state of Kansas has designated critical habitat on the installation for three species: piping plover, least tern and Topeka shiner.

Designated critical habitat for the least tern and piping plover is all waters within the corridor along the main stem of the Kansas River. Designated critical habitat for the Topeka shiner is the mainstem and tributary reaches of Wildcat, Little Arkansas, Wind, Honey, Silver and Sevenmile creeks.

8.0 LAND USE AND MANAGEMENT UNITS

Land Uses

The Training/Range land use category is the dominant one on Fort Riley. Cantonment areas that provide housing, community/recreation, and industrial and transportation operations are mostly in the southern portion of the installation in six distinct areas (Exhibit 8.1).

8.1.1. Training/Range Land Use Areas

8.1.1.1. Training Areas

One hundred three designated training areas, 76 of which are combined into 17 larger maneuver areas, comprise approximately 70,000 acres;

8.1.1.2. Impact Area

The main impact area and the surrounding training live-fire ranges in the eastern portion cover approximately 16,200 acres. These areas are off-limits to maneuver training, public use, and most management activities.

8.1.1.3. Douthit Gunnery Complex

The Douthit Gunnery Complex in the northwestern portion includes approximately 2,000 acres. Training and maneuvers that usually occur within the Douthit Gunnery Complex Safety Fan cease when either the DMPRC or DMPTR is active. The Douthit Gunnery Complex live-fire danger fan covers approximately 30,500 acres and includes Training Areas 40-46, 57-62, 66-74, 77, 78, 83, 84, 88, 89, and 93-96.

8.1.2. Cantonment Land Use Areas

Cantonment (or developed) areas total approximately 12,000 acres and are Main Post, Camp Forsyth, Camp Funston, Camp Whitside, Custer Hill, and Marshall Army Airfield.

8.1.2.1. Improved Grounds

Improved grounds include improved and semi-improved areas. Improved grounds contain many native and non-native trees, shrubs, and groundcovers on approximately 5,613 acres. Improved areas are maintained as mowed turf and planted with ornamental and native trees and shrubs. Semi-improved areas are grassy fields and larger groves of trees that receive periodic mowing and maintenance.

8.1.2.2. Outdoor Recreational Facilities

Custer Hill Golf Course is an eighteen-hole course. Approximately 125 of the course's 170 acres are maintained as rough. Three parks/picnic areas totaling approximately 60 acres are maintained in a semi-natural condition; they are Moon Lake and McCormick and Wyman parks.

8.1.2.3. Borrow Areas

Soil borrow is used for two major purposes on Fort Riley; as fill material and as topsoil, and is generally associated with construction projects. Borrow sites on Fort Riley are controlled under a National Pollutant Discharge Elimination Program (NPDES) permit authorized under the Clean Water Act. Active soil borrow sites are depicted in Exhibit 8.2.

9.0 NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

Grassland Management

9.1.1. Grassland Management Strategy

9.1.1.1. Native Grassland

The tallgrass prairie is the most altered ecological community in North America, with less than 4% left. Not coincidentally, grassland animal species have experienced a more consistent, steeper, and widespread decline than any other group in North America (Samson and Knopf 1994, Knopf 1994, Johnson 1995). Factors involved in these declines include habitat loss, habitat fragmentation, and woody vegetation encroachment. Many of the species experiencing the greatest declines, such as the greater prairie-chicken and Henslow's sparrow, are area sensitive (i.e., there is a minimum area size below which the species will not occur). The habitats needed by grassland species vary from short or recently burned grass to dense grass unburned for 3-4 years.

The overall strategy is to protect, propagate, and conserve the native tallgrass prairie where it occurs on and off of the installation, and the fauna species associated with it. Native prairie evolved under the influences of fire and grazing, and these or similar disturbances are required to maintain the grasslands. Fire is especially effective in retarding the spread of woody vegetation into the prairie. However, burning entire landscapes can be detrimental to a number of species. Greater prairie-chickens prefer to nest in unburned fields located within ½ mile of the lek (Horak 1985). Management actions will focus on smaller parcels of land, juxtaposing vegetative conditions in varying stages of time since last disturbance treatment to create more heterogeneous habitat conditions.

9.1.1.2. Go-Back Grassland

The "go-back" grasslands are mosaics of native tallgrass prairie plant species, annual grasses and perennial "tame" grasses. The strategy is to encourage and facilitate the return of native grass and forb species into these areas.

9.1.1.3. *Sericea lespedeza*

Until eradicated or controlled, large *sericea lespedeza* infestations in the central and eastern parts of the installation will continue to serve as seed reservoirs that will allow the species to spread into other parts of the installation, and to surrounding private lands. The dual strategy for *sericea lespedeza* control is to minimize its spread into native prairie areas while controlling or eradicating it in other parts of the installation. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) principles will be used, to include education, cultural control, mechanical control, and the judicious use of low-toxicity pesticides. Aggressive control measures involving chemical spraying are warranted to stem the spread of this noxious weed. Generally, aerial spraying to control *sericea lespedeza* will be restricted to those fields identified as "go-back" or brome by Freeman and Delisle (2004). Spot and patch or direct, ground-spraying by truck, ATV, or backpack equipment will generally occur in fields identified as native prairie. Recently, Fort Riley has increased the frequency and acreage of late summer/early fall burning in areas containing *sericea*. The goal is to reduce or eliminate annual seed production and decrease vigor of the plant over time.

9.1.1.4. **Woody Encroachment**

Significant woody invasion and maturation has occurred on Fort Riley rangelands over the past 50 years. Reducing this invasive woody component will be an integral component to maintaining and restoring the tallgrass prairie and increasing the occurrence and production of grassland nesting birds.

Some grassland fauna benefit by increases in woody vegetation, such as the Bell's vireo or orchard oriole. However, these species do not appear to be area sensitive (Fitzgerald 1997). There is no belief or desire that execution of this plan will result in the eradication of the shrubby component from Fort Riley grasslands, especially in the smaller grassland tracts. Thus, sufficient areas of suitable shrub habitat will remain for the grassland/shrub ecotone suite of species installation-wide. The shrub habitat will not, however, be distributed uniformly across the installation. So some areas will be deficient in this habitat as compared to prime habitat for grassland/shrub species. When evaluating habitats for these species, a patchwork pattern of shrubs scattered throughout a grassland will be generally considered preferable to shelterbelts and windbreaks. Shelterbelts and windbreaks fragment grasslands, preclude certain grassland species from an area, provide perches for raptors and cowbirds, and are travel lanes for mammalian predators (Fitzgerald 1997, Johnson 1995).

The overall strategy for woody encroachment into grasslands will be to remove or thin brush in many locations. Exhibit 9.1 depicts a series of iso-lines indicating a range of predicted shrub densities based on the percentage of land area covered by shrubs, as calculated by Environmental Sensitivities Research Institute's GeoStatistical Analyst toolbox applied to Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) data. The iso-lines represent areas of high and low concentrations of shrub densities based on the percentage of land area covered by shrubs on individual 160 acre plots. Appendix L provides additional details of how this map was generated and verified. Generally, in grasslands with a landscape level shrubby component $\leq 0.4\%$, prescribed burning will be the only management tool used for shrub control. In grasslands with a landscape level shrubby component between 0.41 and 0.82%, prescribed burning, rotary mowing and chemical treatment will be used to reduce the woody encroachment. In grasslands with a landscape level shrubby component exceeding 0.82%, prescribed burning, various mechanical controls, and chemical control will be used to combat woody encroachment.

9.1.2. **Grassland Management Tools**

The overall goal is to integrate prescribed burning, hayfield cutting, mechanical control, herbicide application and land rehabilitation actions to sustain the training mission, enhance Soldier safety, maintain, enhance or reclaim native prairie, reverse or control undesirable invasive plants, and provide suitable habitat for the potential natural fauna typically associated with tallgrass prairie.

9.1.2.1. **Prescribed Burning**

The time during which a prescribed burn occurs determines which species are benefited and which are harmed. For example, conducting prescribed burns during the March through early May timeframe promotes the growth of warm season grasses and their associated forb community at the expense of the annual and tame, cool-season grasses. However, burns at this time of the year

generally do not harm shrubby vegetation nor control sericea lespedeza seed production to the degree that burns occurring in late August through early October do.

The goals of prescribed burning include maintenance of open space for military training, reduction of wildfire potential, reduction and suppression of woody plant encroachment onto the prairie, maintenance of wildlife resting and breeding cover, and sericea lespedeza control. To achieve these goals, prescribed burns will usually be conducted from approximately August 15 through April 30 annually, avoiding the natal period of most wildlife species, with the objective that every grassland area not managed for Henslow's sparrows will burn at least 2 out of every 5 years. Henslow's sparrow habitat areas will be managed for three year old grassland stands.

The most common exception for conducting prescribed burns from May 1 through July 31 will be to directly support the military mission. Examples include to support construction activities, scheduled weapons firing, or to compartmentalize grasslands to reduce wildfire dangers. Such burns may compete and conflict with natural resources objectives but will be completed, as necessary. Other exceptional burns may be performed to damage woody vegetation in an area determined to be badly over-run by shrubs. Exceptional burns will be limited to as small an area as can be practically burned considering manpower and equipment constraints and objectives of the burn.

Prescribed burns accomplished from late-August to mid-winter will be limited to as small an area as can be practically burned considering manpower and equipment constraints and objectives of the burn. Particular consideration will be given to the provision of fall and winter habitat needs of small nongame and game wildlife and the erosion potential of locations burned.

Prescribed burns of individual areas accomplished during late-winter through early spring will be of portions or entire Training Areas and throughout the installation. Little consideration will be given to provision of residual wildlife habitat and erosion potential of burned areas.

Prescribed burning and wildland firefighting have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these actions will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.2.1.1. Prescribed Burning Management Actions

- Annually update the Prescribed Burn Strategic Plan, incorporating invasive plant control, identifying areas for spring, fall and winter burns, and areas left unburned. The Annual Wildland Fire Management Plan shall focus on small patch size (generally less than 640 acres), juxtaposition and timeliness of burns.
- Annually, retain 10,000 acres as No-burn areas within identified Henslow's sparrow habitats. These areas will not intentionally be burned, and efforts to fight wildfires in them will be aggressive. The No Burn areas will be incorporated into the Annual Wildland Fire Management Plan. Areas considered to be suitable for Henslow's sparrows are shown in Exhibit 9.2.

- Prescribed burning will generally not occur in areas likely to contain nesting greater prairie-chickens between mid-April and mid-August. Areas likely to contain nesting greater prairie-chickens are identified in Exhibit 9.3.

- Maintain firebreaks to better implement the focus on smaller patch size and managing training areas in smaller parcels.
- Seasonally, update Annual Wildland Fire Management Plan to account for unforeseen circumstances, special requests, ensure that sufficient breeding habitat for Henslow's sparrow will exist, and to redevelop the plan's third year.
- The Conservation Branch will collaborate with the Directorate of Emergency Services (DES), Fire Department and DPTMS, Range Support Branch to draft the Prescribed Burn Strategic Plan.
- The Annual Wildland Fire Management Plan, including any firebreak/fuelbreak maintenance and installation, shall be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- DPTMS staff will review firebreak operations conducted by Conservation Branch staff to identify potential erosion concerns and potential impact to ITAM studies.
- All prescribed burning and wildland firefighting shall be conducted only by personnel certified for such actions.
- A safety bulletin and newspaper articles regarding Soldier safety during the prescribed burning season will be published each spring.
- All personnel who conduct prescribed burning, wildland firefighting, or both will receive training in accordance with Fort Riley's Integrated Wildland Fire Management Plan.
- Approximately 20,000-25,000 acres will be burned annually.
- In grasslands having interspersed woodlands in which oaks or black walnuts are the most common pole-sized or larger trees, prescribed burns will occur in such a manner as to avoid damaging the pole-sized and larger trees that are within the woodlands. To accomplish this, prescribed burns of grasslands containing any such woodland will not be set so that a headfire enters a woodland that is unprotected from the headfire by a rock rim, wide shrub corridor, or firebreak. Woodlands protected by a rock rim, wide shrub corridor, or firebreak will not be deliberately protected from headfires. Little or no protection for other woody plants within the woodlands will be provided, and damaging woody plants outside of the woodlands will not be avoided.
- In grasslands having interspersed woodlands in which neither oaks nor black walnuts are the most common pole-sized or larger trees, prescribed burns will also occur in such a manner as to minimize, to the degree practical, damaging the pole-sized and larger trees that are within the woodlands. However, these woodlands may not be deliberately protected from headfires. Little or no protection for other woody plants within the woodlands will be provided, and damaging woody plants outside of the woodlands will not be avoided.

9.1.2.2. **Haying**

See Section 9.3.1.1.

9.1.2.3. **Integrated Pest Management (IPM)**

The Pest Management Program at Fort Riley is designed to employ IPM principles to achieve effective control with minimal environmental effects. IPM uses the best mix of available non-chemical and chemical control methods to achieve the most effective, economic, and environmentally safe pest management possible.

Non-chemical control is the preferred method of control and will be used to the maximum extent practical. The non-chemical control methods used in grassland are prescribed burning and mechanical cutting.

Chemicals are used when necessary and in combination with prescribed burning and mechanical control. Chemical applications are made in an effective and specific manner. Non-chemical and chemical treatments are combined to provide the greatest overall benefits. Chemical control methods include aerial, ATV, truck and tractor spraying, and wicking.

Mechanical control includes mowing and hand-cutting to remove unwanted invasive vegetation. While mechanical control by itself will not generally kill vegetation, it can be a useful stop-gap measure to control invasive vegetation and interrupt the development of viable noxious weed seed when other management tools are not available.

Fort Riley's Integrated Pest Management Plan⁴ (IPMP) provides guidance for operating and maintaining an effective pest management program. The principles of IPM serve as the foundation for all activities described within the IPMP. The IPMP is incorporated by reference into this plan. It is revised each year as required by Army Regulation.

Prescribed burning and mechanical removal of vegetation have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.2.3.1. IPM Actions

- Scattered trees will be removed from grassland areas as part of the prairie restoration program. Areas chosen for tree removal are in greater prairie-chicken or Henslow's sparrow habitats. Activities will consist of the mechanical removal of trees using chainsaws and machine-mounted clippers, grinders and saws. Herbicides may be applied to cut stumps of trees. Tree stumps generally will be cut to 8 inches or less in height. Those cut taller will be conspicuously marked soon after cutting if they present a foreseeable potential for vehicular damage through collision with them. All trees not associated with a riparian area, tree plantation or hedgerow targeted for renovation in these areas are candidates to be cut. Tree and brush cutting will typically be avoided during the primary migratory bird nesting season.
- Implement, evaluate and amend Shrub Reduction Strategic Plan to combat shrub encroachment into grassland. The Plan integrates GIS technology with prescribed burning, rotary mowing, mechanical clipping, grinding of trees and brush, and chemical use to achieve the most effective and economic control. The plan will prioritize treating areas

⁴ The IPMP is consistent with current military standards and criteria and is designed to be consistent with the mission of the installation. Compliance with the plan will ensure that proper regulatory procedures have been followed. The plan prescribes the roles and responsibilities of the various departments, organizations, and personnel actively involved in the application, storage, and use of pesticides at Fort Riley. It also identifies the existing pests at Fort Riley and characterizes their destructive abilities, so appropriate decisions can be made to satisfy any particular level of control.

where the woody invasion impacts Soldier use of the landscape for dismounted training, Henslow's sparrow habitat, or regal fritillary prairie.

- Any amendments to the Shrub Reduction Strategic Plan, including any mechanical removal of woody vegetation that has the potential to cause ground disturbance, shall be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Rotary mowing and chemical control of 150 acres of shrub infested grasslands will be completed annually.
- Ground spraying of 150 acres of shrub infested grasslands will be completed annually.
- The Franklin tree and brush machine will be used to rehabilitate 150 acres of shrub-infested grasslands annually.
- Large trees in shrubby areas of forest edge/upland shrub habitat will be cut to improve northern bobwhite habitat conditions.
- Update GIS data layers of tree clipping activities annually.
- Hedgerows rated to be ten years or less from a commercial size are to be retained for contractual sales. The remaining hedgerows are to be evaluated jointly by Conservation Branch and DPTMS for possible renovation cutting or removal.
- Tactical Concealment Island plantings that were established in or adjacent to grasslands are to be evaluated jointly by Conservation Branch and DPTMS for possible removal to increase the value of those areas to grassland-dependent fauna.
- Aerial and ground spraying of herbicides, mechanical removal and prescribed burning are used to control noxious weeds. Plans and methods of control are discussed in IPMP.
- Ground spray areas infested with musk thistle, Johnson grass, or field bindweed.
- Prepare pesticide report annually.
- All personnel who apply pesticides will receive training sufficient to be certified for such actions.

9.1.2.4. Partnerships

Many organizations have interest in conserving and preserving prairie habitats on public and private lands surrounding Fort Riley. These include government agencies such as the USFWS, KDWPT and U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA)-Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS), and non-government agencies such as the Kansas Land Trust, Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation, National Wild Turkey Federation and Pheasants/Quail Forever. Cooperating, collaborating and sharing resources with these organizations to enhance grassland management on lands surrounding Fort Riley will help retain healthy populations of wildlife fauna, and may preclude future listings of grassland species as threatened or endangered, thereby helping to maintain and sustain Fort Riley's mission.

9.1.2.4.1. Partnerships Management Actions

- Implement Fort Riley's ACUB program.
- Participate in regional conservation management workshops, planning meetings, and business meetings that are conducted by government and non-government organizations.
- Assist with management programs that perform on-the-ground habitat enhancement actions on public and private lands around Fort Riley.

9.1.2.5. Soil Management

Soil resources management is the foundation upon which land sustainability depends. Soil management is integrated through ITAM among the DPW and DPTMS. The overall soil conservation strategy is to repair and improve training lands by planning and applying preventative and corrective land management practices that address erosion and damage caused by military training. ITAM Management Objectives and Goals are summarized in Appendix M.

Soil management practices include filling, grading, and seeding abandoned defilades and hardened assembly areas; controlling road ditch erosion by seeding, constructing earthen gradient diversions that divert storm water to established stands of grass, or by placing riprap in ditches; and contour ripping heavily compacted areas to increase air and water infiltration.

LRAM activities such as grading abandoned defilades and hardened assembly areas, controlling road ditch erosion by constructing earthen gradient diversions, contour ripping compacted areas, and maintaining and establishing hardened, low-water fords have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

As a component of its NPDES permit, Fort Riley is required to develop and annually update a Borrow Area Management Plan. The purpose of the plan is to provide instructions so that borrow-related actions occur in a manner that ensures availability of materials, maintains sustainability of resources, meets environmental compliance, and minimizes conflicts with military day-to-day training operations. The Borrow Area Management Plan is at Appendix N.

9.1.2.5.1. Soil Management Actions

- Repair gully erosion to include construction of check dams, as necessary.
- Excavate rock for erosion control structures, ford maintenance, road and parking lot base material, and other LRAM and DPW projects.
- Close off unauthorized stream crossings and repair sites, as needed.
- Repair lands damaged by maneuver training, which may include grading, shaping, seeding and mulching.
- Harden drainage ditches at locations that repeatedly are damaged during training events.
- Monitor soil erosion and soil compaction as part of the ITAM program.
- Continue constructing hardened stream fords, as needed, following approved protocol (see 9.3.2.1, Topeka shiner).
- Maintain fords following approved protocol (see 9.3.2.1, Topeka shiner).
- Implement plan for establishing, operating, closing and reutilizing borrow areas to increase troop safety, increase available training space, improve wildlife habitat, and improve the appearance of the installation.
- Coordinate LRAM projects with the Cultural Resources manager through the GIS database and by coordinated planning meetings.
- Manage digging permit program, whereby military units must coordinate with the DPW prior to conducting any tactical excavation or other ground disturbing activity during training exercises.
- Conduct soil borrow actions in accordance with the Borrow Area Management Plan.

9.1.2.6. **Native Grass Plantings/Restoration**

Planting of native grass is mainly conducted by ITAM personnel to replace cover lost during construction activities or to repair maneuver damage of specific sites. ITAM uses NRCS standards for mulching, fertilizing, and reseeding. Native plant species are preferred in any revegetation plans. ITAM staff generally use a combination of native grass species and western wheatgrass when planting to repair maneuver damage. Western wheatgrass provides early stand development to ward off invasive plants, but is easily outcompeted by the native grass mix within five years.

Conservation Branch personnel will also plant native grass to meet specific wildlife management objectives, such as to restore riparian buffer strips. However, planting native plants in large scale prairie renovation or reclamation projects will not be performed.

Forest Management

9.1.3. **Forest Management Strategy**

9.1.3.1. **Riverine Floodplain Forest**

Most riverine floodplain forests in Kansas have been lost. Historically, riverine forests were linear and provided a different type of habitat than upland forests. Riverine forests were large stands of mature woodlands with tall trees and high canopy closure. The fact that linear, floodplain forests were interspersed with sloughs, oxbows, and marshes did not seem to negatively affect the presence of species normally associated with large, unfragmented woodlands. This resulted in different species assemblages when compared to uplands. Species such as the pileated woodpecker, prothonotary warbler and red-shouldered hawk occurred in riverine forests. On Fort Riley, these species have been found only in floodplain forests.

Cottonwood, sycamore and bur oak trees are preferred eagle perch trees. While trees of these species comprise a significant proportion of the overstory canopy, little regeneration of these species is occurring due to infrequent flooding and a closed canopy. The majority of sapling and pole-sized trees in these woodlands are shade-tolerant hackberry, boxelder and American elm. This, coupled with the Tartarian honeysuckle infestation, has created a closed sub-canopy condition. The overall usefulness of these areas to eagles may begin to decline when the large cottonwood and sycamore trees senesce and fall over, and preferred trees do not replace them.

The overall strategy for riverine forests is to increase the width of forested floodplain corridors, promote large, mature to overmature stands, and maintain large, downed woody material⁵. These stands will have high canopy closure and an open to intermediate sub-canopy to favor species typically occurring in floodplain forests (Evans and Fischer 1997, Schroeder 1982, Crocoll 1994, Stauffer 1994, Moldenhauer and Regelski 1996). Additional strategies for stands within the riverine floodplain forest are to investigate and address Tartarian honeysuckle infestations, maintain or enhance the abundance and distribution of trees suitable for bald eagles, and manage established tree plantations.

⁵ Maintaining large, downed woody material within riverine forests is done to provide foraging locations for pileated woodpeckers.

9.1.3.2. **Riparian Upland Woodlands**

9.1.3.2.1. **Oak Woodlands**

The forest condition typical for the Flint Hills ecoregion is for relatively open forest stands having low basal areas. However, many of the installation's forests have transitioned to a more closed condition with higher stem and understory densities. This successional change to a higher climax stage is due in large part to reduced fire pressure on the forestlands from that of the pre-settlement period and the concurrent aging of the stands.

The overall strategy is to develop, maintain, and enhance open oak woodland in areas of the installation with site conditions appropriate for burning, and creating a ground cover with forbs, grasses, and oak sprouts. The prairie and woodland ecotone will be maintained through the use of periodic prescribed fire, encouraging oak and other shade intolerant species.

9.1.3.2.2. **Riparian, Mixed Hardwood Woodlands**

The strategy in forest stands where use of fire is problematic is to develop the stands into a late successional woodland habitat featuring leaf litter, forbs, shrubs, and shade tolerant species in the understory. A gradual shift toward dominance by hackberry can be expected in these woodlands over the next century. Large stands of deciduous woodland, especially those with a core habitat area greater than 10 ha, will be managed for area-sensitive woodland species. These woodlands will be managed to maintain a minimum canopy height of 16 m, and greater than 54% canopy closure. Where possible, these stands will be connected with other hardwood stands.

9.1.3.3. **Savannas**

Implementing the strategy described for oak woodlands in section 9.2.1.2.1 will effectively maintain and promote savannas on Fort Riley. The strategy to combat woody encroachment into prairie described in section 9.1.1.4 will not impact areas defined as savannas. Savannas typically have oak, American elm and green ash trees, 5-15% canopy coverage and average 25 trees/acre. Areas targeted for woody encroachment management actions generally have Siberian elm, cottonwood, locust and osage-orange trees, 0.1-5% canopy coverage, and average less than 20 trees/acre.

9.1.4. **Forest Management Tools**

The overall goal is to integrate prescribed burning, timber stand improvement (TSI), IPM and commercial harvest actions to sustain the training mission, promote Soldier safety, provide improved forest stand health, and achieve the desired end-state forest conditions.

9.1.4.1. **Prescribed Burning**

The goals of prescribed burning of woodlands are to promote oak regeneration within woodlands, maintain the grassland/prairie ecotone, and to suppress woodland expansion into the grasslands. Damaging woody plants in tree plantations and woody wildlife plantings will be avoided unless a specific prescription for removal of any such area is developed and approved as part of a training area-specific management plan.

9.1.4.1.1. Prescribed Burning Management Actions

- See section 9.1.2.1.1.
- Prescribed burns of woodlands in which oaks or black walnuts are the most common pole-sized or larger trees will occur in such a manner as to avoid damaging the pole-sized and larger trees that are within the woodlands.
- Prescribed burns of woodlands in which neither oaks nor black walnuts are the most common pole-sized or larger trees will also occur in such a manner as to minimize, to the degree practical, damaging the pole-sized and larger trees that are within the woodlands.
- Fires will be suppressed in riverine, floodplain forest stands to maintain large, downed woody material.
- Prescribed burns will be conducted within oak woodlands to favor oak regeneration and discourage competition from shade tolerant species.
- Wildfires and prescribed prairie burns may be excluded from some riparian mixed hardwood stands.

9.1.4.2. TSI

TSI actions are undertaken to develop, maintain, and enhance woodlands in a perpetually productive state. Trees determined inferior due to their health status, form, and/or species are removed from woodlands through TSI practices. Such practices may include mechanical thinning by felling or girdling trees, and chemical or mechanical treatments to control understory vegetation. Thinnings may be used to improve the diffuse light environment near the forest floor, or to release dominant and co-dominant trees as the woodland approaches conditions that are overstocked. Trees selected for removal generally will not be immediately adjacent to stream channels.

9.1.4.2.1. TSI Management Actions

- A 50-year Forest Stands Management Plan will prescribe specific management actions for each of the installation's forest stands. Actions will consist of near-term management activities, predicted condition of each forest stand throughout the 50-year period, and forecasted long-term management activities within each stand. Plans will be implemented as they are completed.
- Thinning oak woodlands from below will target non-oaks in the understory and mid-story to favor oaks.
- A minimum of 40 square feet of basal area/acre and approximately 20-pole size trees/acre will be retained throughout the regime of prescribed burns and/or thinnings conducted on oak woodland stands.
- Crown cover of at least 50% will be maintained throughout the regime of prescribed burns and/or thinnings conducted on oak woodland stands.
- Dominants and co-dominants will be released by thinning riparian mixed hardwood stands. Those include hackberry, green ash, black walnut, chinquapin oak, bur oak and other trees exhibiting good form and high vigor.
- TSI practices will retain a minimum of 30 percent of existing mast and fruit bearing trees within a stand.

- TSI practices will retain snags, and trees with cavities or other attributes benefiting wildlife, when thinnings are performed.
- TSI tree felling will be completed for training support or safety.
- A number of mature trees that are in decline and are scarred, injured and have cavities, but are still wind firm, will be retained in the timber management areas for future snags within riparian mixed hardwood stands.
- Basal area per acre may be reduced to 65 square feet per acre during the initial thinning of a riparian mixed hardwood stands. The areas to manage for riparian mixed hardwood stands are shown in Exhibit 9.4.

9.1.4.3. **Commercial Harvest**

Commercial harvests will be employed to thin or regenerate a stand when merchantable timber is present and market conditions are favorable. Harvests will be performed by contract. Preparation and implementation of commercial timber harvests will occur according to the Forest Stand Management Plan.

Commercial timber harvests have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.4.3.1. **Commercial Harvest Management Actions**

- Timber harvest conducted within riverine, floodplain forest will favor older, larger diameter living and dead trees in closed canopied stands.
- Trees to be commercially harvested will be selected and marked.
- The location of skid trails, log decks, and erosion control features will be identified.
- Each timber sale applicant will meet in person with Conservation Branch staff to discuss the proposed sale conditions and pertinent contract stipulations prior to being granted right-of-entry to the site.
- Timber harvests will be monitored and specifications consistent with contractual obligations will be enforced.
- Site impacts will be evaluated, and negative impacts to sites will be resolved.
- All proposed timber sales will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Fuelwood cutting will be prohibited within riverine, floodplain forest (except in tree plantations).

9.1.4.4. **Tree Planting**

Tree plantings may be used to restore cover after soil mining projects are performed, to widen existing woodlands, or to rehabilitate degraded eagle habitat. New plantings may be performed by either contractor or in house staff, dependent upon the size of the planting and the scope of maintenance desired.

Planting and maintenance of trees have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.4.4.1. **Tree Planting Management Actions**

- Increase width of riverine, floodplain forests to increase species richness; the most beneficial effects will occur when forests are 200-600 m wide.
- Where possible, connect riverine, floodplain forest stands with other hardwood stands.
- Maintain walnut forest plantings to include TSI thinnings and selective harvest.
- All proposed tree planting and tree plantation maintenance activities will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.

- Supplemental tree plantings made within riverine floodplain forests will use cottonwood, sycamore and bur oak tree species.
- Maintain firebreaks around new tree plantings for the initial 5-8 years after first planted.

9.1.4.5. **Integrated Pest Management (IPM)**

See Section 9.1.2.3.

9.1.4.5.1. **IPM Management Actions**

- Perform forest pest surveillance and control.
- Implement Tartarian honeysuckle control plan, by applying foliar herbicide spray in late fall while other trees are dormant, yet Tartarian honeysuckle remains active. Control sericea lespedeza established within woodland tracts.
- Survey for location of kudzu plants.
- Control kudzu plants.
- Emerald ash borer: Develop protocol and emerald ash borer response plan to implement if emerald ash borer is determined to be present on, or near Fort Riley.

Specialized Management

Fort Riley generally practices ecosystem-based habitat management practices to achieve the overall natural resources goals. The focus of ecosystem-based management activities is to manipulate vegetation and vegetative communities so that the floral and faunal community associated with that ecosystem is favored rather than targeting specific wildlife species. However, certain activities will be performed with the intended benefit of specific species, or select groups of species or to support the installation's military training and testing missions. These activities, generally, will not conflict with the general policies established in Section 2.2 of adaptive ecosystem-based management practices accepted for use in the Flint Hills ecoregion. The overall strategy in performing these activities is to comply with the Endangered Species Act of 1973; with Executive Order 11990, *Protection of Wetlands*; with the North American Wetlands Conservation Act of 1989; with the Sikes Act (P.L. 86-797) and the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 (P.L. 105-85); to meet specific military, terrain, fisheries and wildlife management objectives; and to enhance hunting and fishing opportunities.

9.1.5. **Agriculture Outleases**

9.1.5.1. **Hay Fields**

Hay cutting in contracted leases is allowed on Fort Riley. The goals of hay-cutting are to maintain open space for military training, reduce the potential for wildfires, reduce and suppress woody plant encroachment onto the prairie, maintain wildlife nesting and brood rearing cover, control sericea lespedeza, reduce the installation's expense for grounds maintenance mowing, and respond to local and regional demand for livestock feedstock or possibly bio-cellular production. Hay-cutting is timed to reduce detrimental effects on breeding birds, provide adequate forage quality, provide adequate regrowth, and interrupt the development of viable noxious weed seed. Large, warm-season grasslands are mowed on a rotational system with some subunits left idle in each

year rather than annually cut for hay. This not only provides rest and recovery for grasslands, but also provides habitat for species requiring litter build up and residual standing dead vegetation, such as the Henslow's sparrow and western harvest mouse.

Hayfields are harvested by contract within the terms of the Land Use Regulations of leases. Warm season grasses may be cut during the period of July 15 to August 15 each year. Designated areas may only be harvested in either odd calendar years or even calendar years. Those currently so designated are shown on Exhibit 7.9. Lessees are to follow the schedules designated on the Tract Maps they are provided.

Cool season grasses may be cut during the period May 1 to September 30 except in those areas infested by sericea lespedeza. In areas infested by sericea lespedeza, cool season grasses may be cut only during the period of May 1 to August 15. Only those areas harvested prior to June 20 are allowed to be cut a second time each season.

A strip of unmowed vegetation that is at least 25-feet wide is left around the perimeter of firebreaks and food plots that occur in areas cut for hay if the vegetation in that strip is not experiencing shrub encroachment. If an unmowed strip contains higher than desired quantities of shrubby vegetation, that entire strip may be mowed or otherwise treated in order to reduce the shrub component.

Lessees may improve or restore grassland areas within their respective leases, upon approval of the Conservation Branch. Restoration and improvement of grassland work may include brush control by mowing, reseeded of areas that were previously cultivated, overseeding of existing stands of grass, constructing permanent structures, removal of undesirable trees by cutting or clipping, and spraying noxious weeds, other undesirable plants or both.

Hay-cutting activities and activities to restore or improve grassland areas have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.5.2. **Croplands**

The firebreak crop fields are generally grown and harvested by contracted producers (lessees) within the terms of the Land Use Regulations of leases. These crops are to be managed in a manner that provides for year-round fire protection, does not unduly expose the leasehold to erosion or infestation with noxious weeds, provides wintertime food for wildlife, provides reasonable opportunity for profit by lessees, and increases the biodiversity of the installation. Under normal circumstances, alfalfa or cereal grain is planted to no more than one-half of the width of the firebreak. The other half of the firebreak is planted to row crops such as grain sorghum, corn, soybeans, or sunflowers and shall not be left fallow. No-till farming may be utilized only if soybeans were the previous year's crop and only if the lessee receives prior approval.

To supplement the winter food supply of wildlife, currently issued contracts require that the lessee shall leave twenty-percent (20%) of the total acreage of the crop grown standing in the field. Unharvested grain is left standing at least until March 15 of the year after it is planted. Within 10 days of harvest, the lessee tills a strip along the boundary edge of the field no more than one-half

the width of the field, or 100-feet wide, whichever is less. The untilled portion of the field remains untilled until March 15 of the following year.

Repair of erosion that does occur is considered required firebreak maintenance. The leasehold shall be leveled periodically by the lessee using normal farm equipment. In addition, the lessee shall control any Kansas-listed noxious weed within the leasehold.

The lessee will plow the entire length of each constructed terrace in the first, third, and fifth year of the lease. Plowing will be conducted so as to move soil upward on both faces of each terrace. The requirement to mow waterways is removed from firebreak field leases. Conservation Branch staff or others contracted by the Conservation Branch will accomplish this work, as required.

Planting, cultivation and harvest of existing fields, firebreak maintenance activities, and activities to establish new firebreak fields have the potential to affect cultural resources. Thus, these activities will be reviewed prior to execution in accordance with the procedures described in Appendix G.

9.1.5.3. **Agriculture Outleases Management Actions**

- Conduct prebid lease meeting open for all potential bidders.
- Meet, in person, with each lessee, to discuss the lessee's management plan, lease conditions, and Land Use Regulations, prior to granting the lessee right-of-entry to the leased property. Provide lessees an up-to-date access map.
- Monitor leases and enforce specifications consistent with Land Use Regulations.
- Provide a map of known sericea lespedeza infested areas within lease to each lessee, as requested.
- Consult with and advise lessees that desire to perform conservation work associated with their lease.
- Hay-cutting activities and planned activities to restore or improve grassland areas will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Provide lessees a list of personnel within the DPTMS Range Support staff who are authorized to give access to the leased areas by February 1 of each year.
- Notify lessees of Army plans to perform maintenance or construction activities that would impact their lease.
- Annually inspect all firebreaks for renovation needs; plan to renovate structures, as needed, in all fields of one firebreak unit per year.
- Review each firebreak field to ensure that existing buffer strips are functional. Establish functional filter strips where any are found to be inadequate.
- Complete scheduled repairs to existing structures (mostly terraces) in firebreak fields.
- Construct new firebreaks, as needed, to protect new ranges or other facilities.
- Planting, cultivation and harvest of existing fields, firebreak maintenance activities, and activities to establish new firebreak fields will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Continue incentive rental abatement program to reduce the quantity of pesticides applied on firebreaks.
- Establish terraces, silt traps, and waterways, as appropriate, on firebreak areas not leased.

- Annually review, amend and update the Land Use Regulations.
- Communicate with Command Group on hay harvest extension issue.
- Inspect firebreak waterways and mow as needed.

9.1.6. Rare Species

Protection and management of rare species is conducted in accordance with the Endangered Species Act, the Kansas Nongame and Endangered Species Conservation Act, and the Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act. The strategy is to implement the installation's management plans (Appendix C).

9.1.6.1. Threatened & Endangered (T&E) Species Management Actions

- Consult with the USFWS on actions that may affect federally-listed species.
- Confer with the USFWS on actions that may affect federally proposed or candidate species.
- Consult with KDWPT on actions that may affect state-listed species.
- Obtain collection permits, as required, to possess any state or federally-listed T&E species.
- Maintain updated GIS habitat maps and data layers for all T&E species.
- Report all observations of state-listed species to KDWPT.

9.1.6.1.1. Least Tern and Piping Plover

- Establish a "*no disturbance*" buffer zone to protect nesting least terns or piping plovers, if found.
- Construction, operations and maintenance activities, demolition, operation of vehicles, detonation of explosives, and recreational pursuits will be controlled to protect sandbars from adverse impacts.
- Report to the USFWS Kansas Field Office and KDWPT all observations of least terns and piping plovers on Fort Riley.

9.1.6.1.2. Topeka Shiner

- Consult with the USFWS and KDWPT prior to construction of water-impounding structures on any stream identified in Exhibit 7.11.
- Enforce prohibition of bait-fish seining.
- Protect all streams shown in Exhibit 7.11 from activities that result in channel destruction or alteration, increase water turbidity, or remove vegetation filter strips.
- Control construction, operations and maintenance, demolition, operation of vehicles, timber harvest, detonation of explosives, and recreational pursuit activities within 50 feet on either side of the streams shown in Exhibit 7.11.
- Monitor stream habitat and restore as needed. Restoration actions that may be required include bank reconstruction, establishing revetments, and/or planting vegetative filter strips at least 50-foot wide. When applicable, restoration projects will incorporate NaturalChannel Design and identify reference reaches.
- Activities to restore or improve stream banks will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.

- Construction and maintenance of roads and hardened, low water fords will follow protocol approved by the USFWS and KDWPT in road maintenance consultations conducted in 2001 (see Appendix C, section 3.4.2.5).
- Modify Beck Pond to reduce escape of largemouth bass into Wind Creek. Remove fish from Beck Pond prior to the breaking of the pond dam.
- Remove largemouth bass and green sunfish over 5 inches length from Wind Creek.
- Partner with the Riley County Conservation District to achieve actions off-post within the Wildcat Creek watershed that will improve habitat conditions on Fort Riley.

9.1.6.1.3. Northern Long-eared Bat

- Conservation Branch personnel will be educated in identification of northern long-eared bats. All observations, including sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel, will be maintained in maps and GIS databases.
- Adhere to protocol identified within the national plan to address slowing the spread of white-nose syndrome. Under no circumstances should clothing, footwear, or equipment that was used in bat hibernacula from a white-nose syndrome affected region be used on Fort Riley.
- If a northern long-eared bat is documented on Fort Riley, implement the conservation practices described in Section VI of the 2015 U.S. Army Environmental Command Biological Evaluation (see Appendix C) concerning military smoke and obscurants, pesticide use and pest control. In instances where a desired action is not described in the Biological Evaluation, or effects are anticipated that are different from those described, the installation will consult with USFWS prior to initiating that action.

9.1.6.1.4. Whooping Crane

- Monitor local bird sighting reports to stay apprised of incidents when whooping cranes are present in areas where Fort Riley aircraft may operate. Additionally, Fort Riley staff requests USFWS and KDWPT provide similar confidential reports received.
- Restrict aircraft flight when whooping cranes are present. A "*no fly*" buffer zone will be established and maintained around the area being used by one or more whooping cranes. An altitude restriction of 2,000 AGL will be in effect for the "*no fly*" zone, with the width ranging from 0.5 NM (nautical miles) to 1.5 NM.
- Inform pilots when "*no fly*" zones are in effect through Local NOTAMS.
- Educate Fort Riley personnel to recognize whooping cranes, and be made aware of the importance of promptly reporting encounters with this bird in the field.
- Any projects to construct new or modify existing aerial structures will be reviewed by Conservation Branch prior to project implementation for need of re-siting or incorporating line markers.

9.1.6.2. Bald Eagle Management Actions

- Establish and maintain firebreaks to protect eagle roost and nest trees from fire.
- Any firebreak maintenance and installation will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Maintain updated GIS habitat maps and data layers for eagle species.

- Any projects to construct new or modify existing aerial structures will be reviewed by Conservation Branch prior to project implementation for need of re-siting or incorporating line markers.
- Any projects to construct new or modify existing electric transmission lines will be reviewed by Conservation Branch prior to project implementation for need to incorporate construction guidelines specified to protect eagles against electrocution.
- Construction, demolition, off-road operation of vehicles, timber harvest, detonation of explosives and recreational pursuits will be controlled within “*minimum disturbance*” buffer zones when eagles are in the Fort Riley area.
- A 200-m minimum flight altitude buffer will be established over the “*minimum disturbance*” buffer zones when eagles are in the Fort Riley area.
- “*No disturbance*” buffer zones will be maintained around established communal bald eagle roosts and nests.
- Protect trees required to maintain integrity of communal roosts.
- Minimize nesting conflicts on human-made structures.
- Protect bald eagles from chemical impacts.
- Provide information to aviators through Local NOTAMS (Notices to AirMen).
- Avoid clear cutting or removal of overstory trees within 100 m of a nest at any time.
- Selective thinning and other silviculture management practices designed to conserve or enhance habitat, including prescribed burning close to the nest tree, will be undertaken outside of the nesting and breeding seasons. Precautions will be taken to prevent crown fire or fire climbing the nest tree.
- Timber harvesting operations, including road construction and chain saw operations, will be avoided within 200 m of a nest during the breeding season.

9.1.6.3. SAR Management Actions

9.1.6.3.1. Henslow’s Sparrow

- Tracts of land known to be used for nesting will be designated as Henslow’s sparrow breeding habitat. Fort Riley will retain 10,000 acres of unburned grasslands within Henslow’s sparrow habitat areas annually. Specific locations selected for habitat protection will vary annually, to allow all grasslands to receive appropriate management actions.
- Woody encroachment into grasslands reduces the habitat quality of grasslands. Woody encroachment will be reduced through cutting of trees scattered through grasslands, and mechanical and chemical treatments to reduce shrub encroachment into grasslands, to the extent appropriate.

9.1.6.3.2. Regal Fritillary

- Prairie areas containing a variety of wildflowers, particularly the species identified as preferred food plants for regal fritillaries, will be identified and maintained.
- The increasing percentage of sericea lespedeza in grasslands is believed to cause a decline in habitat quality for regal fritillaries. Sericea lespedeza will outcompete native forbs. Dense, monoculture stands of sericea lespedeza will reduce the numbers of milkweed and violets growing in grasslands, apparently creating conditions less suited for regal

fritillaries. Therefore, the presence of sericea lespedeza will be monitored throughout regal fritillary habitat areas.

- Woody encroachment into grasslands reduces the habitat quality of grasslands. Woody encroachment will be reduced to reduce shrub cover, to the extent appropriate.
- Implement management practices to control invasion by woody or noxious weed species. Infestations will be controlled through the use of mechanical and chemical treatments, to the extent feasible. Practices may include burning, mowing, spot-spraying herbicides, or a combination of these. Late winter and early spring burns will favor growth of wildflowers. Regal fritillary grassland tracts may be best maintained by prescribed burning two out of every five years.
- Generally, aerial spraying to control sericea lespedeza will be restricted to those fields identified as “go-back” or brome by Freeman and Delisle (2004). Spot and patch, or direct, ground-spraying by truck, ATV, or backpack equipment will generally occur in fields identified as native prairie. When circumstances require aerially spraying in tallgrass prairie parcels, the spraying action will occur in late summer, when most violets and many milkweed plants have already senesced, to minimize the effects on these important food plants to regal fritillaries.

9.1.6.3.3. Texas Horned Lizard

- Visit locations of reported Texas horned lizard sightings to obtain habitat description of sighting location. Maintain log of habitats from which sightings are recorded to create more specific description of actual habitats used by this species on Fort Riley. Such information can then be referenced when considering future actions that require NEPA documents.
- Refrain from using insecticides in settings away from cantonment areas.

9.1.6.3.4. Rusty Blackbird

- All Conservation Branch personnel will be educated to recognize rusty blackbirds. All observations, including sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel, will be maintained in GIS databases.
- Locations of reported sightings will be visited to obtain habitat descriptions of the sighting location. Data collected will be recorded in order to create more specific description of actual habitats used by this species on Fort Riley so specific habitats utilized by the species can be tracked and identified. Such information can then be referenced when considering future actions that require NEPA analysis.
- Implement protocol to effectively control Tartarian honeysuckle within woodlands.
- Rusty blackbirds are known to forage in agricultural fields during migration and on their wintering grounds. Activities that establish agricultural crops and maintain available grain throughout the winter benefit rusty blackbirds by providing a winter food source while this species is present on the installation. Fort Riley will maintain cropped fields to serve as firebreaks around the installation’s perimeter in such a manner as to retain grain throughout the winter.

9.1.7. Terrestrial Habitat

The strategies to enhance terrestrial habitat characteristics are to provide supplemental food for wildlife, manage forbs, provide nesting and roost structures, remove obstructions and safety hazards, and report abandoned concertina wire to Range Control. Additional terrestrial habitat strategies center on locating and controlling noxious weed infestations.

Smooth brome dominated landscapes tend towards monoculture stands with little to no forb species. In an effort to improve grassland habitat, Fort Riley staff will continue to selectively spray stands of smooth brome with glyphosate. Applications of glyphosate (41%) at a rate of 36-40oz in 10-20 gallons of solution per acre were broadcast in early winter after temperatures were cold enough to ensure that the native, warm-season grasses and forbs were dormant. Field assessments were done in all of the areas sprayed. Reduction in smooth brome competition was observed. The reduced competition resulted in exceptional, diverse stands of healthy native warm-season grasses and forbs. Areas with severe infestations of brome had markedly increased compositions of annual forbs while areas with moderate brome infestations supported an increased composition of perennial warm-season grasses and forbs, to include milkweed species. Due to the recolonization of brome into treated areas, subsequent treatments are deemed necessary.

9.1.7.1. Terrestrial Habitat Management Actions

- Prepare an annual plan for planting of each food plot.
- Plant elk plots (totaling approximately 130 acres) in traditional elk travel corridors entirely to corn, soybeans or wheat for crop rotation and weed management.
- All foodplots will be managed in conformance with the USFWS regulations concerning baiting, promulgated under Title 50 Code of Federal Regulations, Part 20.11.
- Alfalfa food plots (158 plots totaling 500 acres) will be mowed/sprayed two to three times per year.
- Continue to use glyphosate in smooth brome dominated landscapes in order to improve composition and diversity of perennial warm-season grasses and annual and perennial forbs.
- Planting and cultivation of existing food plots, activities to establish new food plots, and using glyphosate in non-native grass areas will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- DPTMS staff will review glyphosate-treatments to identify potential erosion concerns and potential impact to ITAM studies.
- Korean lespedeza will be planted in selected areas to enhance brood habitat for upland game birds, or to provide food for upland game birds and mammals.
- Nesting structures will be cleaned and prepared prior to the start of the respective breeding season for eastern bluebird and purple martin.

9.1.8. Pond and Lake Habitat

The strategy for enhancing pond and lake habitat revolves around maintaining or increasing angling opportunities.

9.1.8.1. Pond and Lake Habitat Management Actions

- Place discarded Christmas trees into fishing ponds to provide structure and cover for fish.

- Mechanically remove trees from pond dams, as needed. Apply herbicides to cut stumps to prevent re-sprouting.
- Perform necessary modifications so that Rush Pond retains water.
- Chemically-control cattails where necessary. When possible, mow cattails prior to chemical application to enhance effectiveness of herbicide.
- Implement measures to correct fish populations, bio-mass and species assemblages, as indicated by results of annual fish monitoring actions.
- Renovate existing, degraded ponds.

9.1.9. Stream Habitat

The installation complies with all state and Federal management requirements in projects that either directly or indirectly affect the water quality of its streams. The primary water quality strategy on Fort Riley is to minimize sedimentation of installation streams from both point source and non-point sources.

9.1.9.1. Stream Habitat Management Actions

- See 9.3.2.1.2., Topeka shiner.
- Establish vegetated filter strips, where needed, along streams.
- All proposed filter strip planting and maintenance activities will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Use best management practices to reduce silt transport during repair and construction of infrastructure.

9.1.10. Wetlands Habitat

The strategies for wetland habitat management are to comply with wetlands laws and regulations, protect existing wetlands, create new wetlands, rehabilitate degraded wetlands, and use moist soil management principles to manage wetlands.

9.1.10.1. Wetlands Habitat Management Actions

- Plant native grasses to provide wildlife nesting habitat adjacent to wetlands.
- All proposed grass planting and maintenance activities will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Cultural Resources manager.
- Perform NEPA documentation and obtain applicable federal and state permits for any action affecting wetlands other than wetland management actions (e.g., seasonal draw-downs, re-flooding, and planting native grasses).
- Seasonally conduct draw-down and re-flooding of shallow-water wetlands, managing these according to standard moist soil principles.
- Manage appropriate portion of Firebreak 3-11 wetland as an ephemeral or vernal pool wetland.
- Small vernal pools less than ½-acre in size will be created with a front-end bulldozer blade. The focus will be creation of pools with an adequate watershed and maintenance of existing structures. Potential areas for vernal pool development are shown at Exhibit 7.3.

9.1.11. Nuisance Animal Control and Management

Wildlife and feral animals on occasion conflict with Fort Riley inhabitants. Nuisance complaints are most commonly received about birds in buildings, and skunks, raccoons and opossums in garbage cans or beneath buildings. Other complaints include snakes, bats, foxes, coyotes, rodents, and burrowing mammals. Feral cats and dogs are not considered major problems. There are no other known exotic animal species present on Fort Riley that require control. However, feral swine were formerly present until extirpated in 2000. If they were to become reestablished, their extirpation would again be attempted through all means practically available.

The strategies to control nuisance wild animals are to apply techniques that suppress or control damage caused by wild animals deemed injurious to agriculture, natural resources, property, or human health and safety, and to manage wild animals that are reservoirs of zoonotic diseases. Wild animals include wildlife (as defined by the state of Kansas) and feral animals (swine, dogs and cats).

9.1.11.1. Nuisance Animal Control and Management Actions

9.1.11.1.1. Birds

- Fort Riley's Residential Communities Initiative partner (Corvias) hires local pest control contractors to resolve bird issues in housing areas.
- USDA-Wildlife Damage Control (WDC) Staff obtain special purpose permit from USFWS allowing personnel to handle migratory birds, and to take a limited number of nests (depredation) in garrison and tenant buildings.
- Removal of animals, insects, and their associated debris from buildings and structures will be reviewed by and coordinated with the Historic Architect, where appropriate.
- USDA-WDC will transport injured raptors to rehabilitators.
- USDA-WDC will investigate calls concerning alleged abandoned fledgling birds in garrison and tenant buildings; Corvias's contractor will handle similar calls from housing areas.
- USDA-WDC will conduct a non-lethal harassment program to move large roosts. The program will use pyrotechnics to move the roost, and is effective for 2,000-3,000 birds.
- USDA-WDC will use toxic bait to control European starlings and rock pigeons in hangars. Bait used will be species specific to blackbirds, and effective for pigeons, and will not provide secondary poisoning opportunities.
- USDA-WDC will use a pellet rifle to take individual, non-native birds that are a problem. Generally these birds are rock pigeons.
- USDA-WDC will install bird exclusion apparatus to minimize bird habitation of buildings.
- USDA-WDC will remove active, non-native bird nests whenever building occupants register complaints.
- Barn swallow nests generally will not be removed. Exceptions may be made for nests near hospital entrances or food service areas, where bird excrement and territorial displays may lead to human health concerns.
- USDA-WDC will remove cliff swallow nests from structures only after fledglings have left nest.

9.1.11.1.2. Urban Coyote and Fox Management Plan

- USDA-WDC, in coordination with DES Conservation Officers, will conduct surveillance of cantonment areas for problem coyotes and foxes. Problem coyotes are animals that have lost their fear for humans. Problem foxes are animals that den in or near areas frequented by children.
- A removal campaign will be implemented when bold coyote behaviors are exhibited. If disease is suspected, the animals will be tested for rabies and canine distemper.
- An education campaign will be initiated with nearby residents to warn parents of the dangers of children playing with fox kits, as needed. If the education campaign is unsuccessful in keeping children from the kits, the foxes will be removed.

9.1.11.1.3. Skunks, opossums, raccoons

- USDA-WDC responds to complaints of skunks, opossums and raccoons. The response will vary dependent on the nature of the complaint. In cases where an animal is reported to be sick or cornered in a location, USDA-WDC is to get to the complaint location as soon as possible and capture the animal. In most other instances, the USDA-WDC will go to the complaint location the next working day to set traps for the intruding animal. Animals that are captured will be euthanized. Where rabies is suspected, samples will be taken for laboratory analysis.

9.1.11.1.4. Feral and Exotic Animals

- Feral cats and dogs, when captured, will be taken to the Fort Riley Veterinary Clinic. The clinic will determine if an animal is fit for adoption or should be euthanized.
- Baseline surveillance for sign will be continued to detect the presence of feral hogs on Fort Riley. Aerial elk and deer surveys will also be used to look for feral hogs.

9.1.11.1.5. Beavers

- USDA-WDC consults with the Conservation Branch on a case by case basis to address beavers in wetlands. The following options are considered: removing all beavers and associated beaver construction projects; allowing all beavers to remain and adjust level of beaver pond by use of Clemson pond levelers; or selectively removing some, but not all of the beavers.

9.1.11.1.6. Bats

- Corvias's Pest Contractor will handle all bat issues in housing areas. USDA-WDC will respond to all bat issues in garrison and tenant buildings.
- Bats will be excluded from buildings. Minor exclusion procedures, e.g., installing foam and screens, will be performed by USDA-WDC and the pest contractor. More complex procedures will be implemented by pest control contractors.

9.1.11.1.7. Deer/elk

- USDA-WDC will act as Fort Riley ambassador and meet with adjacent landowners who complain of elk depredation that occurs off of the installation.
- USDA-WDC will conduct deer removal actions for problem animals at the Custer Hill Outdoor Adventure Park.

9.1.11.1.8. Gophers

- USDA-WDC will conduct integrated control measures in cantonment areas where gophers create health and security hazards, or where excessive activity leads to aesthetic concerns. Such areas include parade fields, athletic fields, berms, and the golf course. Control measures will include trapping and subterranean placement of strychnine baits. Control efforts will target the entire area of local infestation rather than only the area of immediate

concern. For example, rather than treating only the perimeter of parade fields where gopher mounds are visible from the road, the entire parade field will be treated.

9.1.11.1.9. Ground squirrels, badgers

- USDA-WDC will remove problem ground squirrels and badgers from the flood levees, MAAF and other problem areas.

9.1.12. Cantonment Area Management

The Installation Design Guide and the Landscape Master Plan (LMP) are Fort Riley’s principal planning documents for cantonment area management (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, September 1987). The LMP presents background information on landscape maintenance, planting techniques, pruning, fertilization, disease and pest treatment, and planting design guidelines. The strategy is to improve the appearance of the installation and facilities by appropriate landscape development and develop, initiate and maintain progressive programs for grounds management, utilization, and conservation.

A Programmatic Agreement (PA) has been negotiated between Fort Riley and Kansas’ State Historic Preservation Officer on management of the Historic District. This agreement incorporates the Historic Landscape and Cultural Resource Management Plans by reference into the PA. The Historic Landscape Management Plan delineates the boundaries and targeted landscape objectives applied to the District. The overall strategy in the Historic District is to plant and maintain the landscape to coincide with historic landscape design, plant palettes, and possible use patterns.

9.1.12.1. Cantonment Area Management Actions

- Landscape plantings will include fruit and seed producing trees, shrubs and flowering plants. All plantings will be planned and conducted to minimize shelter for skunks, raccoons, and snakes, and to increase viewing and diversity of migratory songbirds.
- Removing and replacing plant materials that occur within the Historic District will be reviewed by the Cultural Resources manager and coordinated through the Management Agronomist.
- Update urban forestry inventory and management database, identifying hazard trees for pruning or removal as funding is provided.
- Spray tree species for pest infestations, as needed and evaluated through Integrated Pest Management principles.
- Coordinate mosquito control with the Medical Activity (MEDDAC) Preventive Medicine Branch. Preventive Medicine monitors mosquito levels, and orders that control actions be initiated when mosquito populations exceed threshold levels.
- Manage pest control contract to control “weedy” species along roads, parking areas, and other cantonment areas, and to control trees along levees.

Landscape-Scale Management Summary

All of Maneuver Areas E, H, J, K, L, O and Q, the Douthit Gunnery Complex Box and parts of Maneuver Areas A, B, D, G, and N (Exhibit 9.6) will be managed to favor tallgrass species and native prairie in a predominately open grassland of large field size. Wooded areas will be restricted predominately to the riparian corridor of the larger streams and drainage channels that bisect the grasslands. The spatial extents of the wooded areas associated with streams and drainage features

and shrub patches will be reduced moderately overall. The number of individual wooded features present within these maneuver areas will be moderately reduced. Hedgerows bisecting grassland fields and woodlots associated with formerly used home sites that are surrounded by grassland fields will be commonly eliminated or converted to shrubby features. Individual shrub fields greater in size than one acre will be severely reduced, with the objective to reduce the landscape level shrub component outside of woodlands to less than 0.35%. Almost all trees that are scattered within grassland fields and many of the larger trees within and along shrubby drainage channels will be eliminated. It is anticipated that the overall spatial extent of wooded areas in these areas will be reduced by less than 10% during the life of this plan, with most of the decrease being due to reduction of spatial extent of shrub patches. The area comprising cropland in these areas will remain nearly constant during the life of this plan. Water resources such as ponds will not be developed in areas that drain to Topeka shiner streams.

All of Maneuver Areas C, F, I, M and P, all of Training Areas 3-17, and 19-24, and parts of Maneuver Areas A, B, D, G, and N (Exhibit 9.6) will be managed to favor tallgrass species and native prairie in grassland fields of a variety of sizes. These grassland areas will be interspersed, sometimes extensively, with wooded areas composed predominately of trees. The spatial extents of woodland areas currently present within these areas will be reduced slightly. Most trees that are scattered within grassland fields will be eliminated, while only a few hedgerows bisecting grassland fields, and woodlots associated with formerly used home sites will be removed. Such wooded features generally will only be eliminated when necessary to allow construction of desired infrastructure and when a single such feature bisects a grassland field that is considered not to be high-quality habitat for a species in decline only because it is bisected by that wooded feature. Individual shrub fields greater in size than one acre will be severely reduced, with the objective to reduce the landscape level shrub component outside of woodlands to less than 0.50%. It is anticipated that the overall spatial extent of wooded areas in these areas will be reduced by less than 15% during the life of this plan, with almost the entire decrease being due to reduction of spatial extent of the invasive shrubs. The area comprising cropland in these areas may increase by up to 5% during the life of this plan. Water resources such as ponds may be developed in these areas, but will not increase in overall coverage by more than 10% during the life of this plan. If developed, ponds will generally be for the principal purpose of enhancing erosion control and will not impound waters inhabited by Topeka shiners.

All of Training Areas 1, 2 and 18 (Exhibit 9.6) will be managed to favor riverine floodplain forest. The spatial extents of woodland areas currently present within these areas will be increased. It is anticipated that the overall spatial extent of wooded areas in these areas will be increase by approximately 5% during the life of this plan, with almost the entire increase being due to expansion of spatial extent of the invasive shrubs.

9.1.13. Individual Training Area Management Pages

See Appendix O for Training Area by Training Area management plans.

10.0 INVENTORY AND MONITORING

Strategy

Continued monitoring of species and habitats is necessary to provide data about the effects of management actions and military training on the land. Inventory is conducted to attain indicators of overall ecosystem integrity, capability of lands to sustain military missions, renewable product surpluses, and status of sensitive species and habitats. The strategy is to regularly monitor the important resources to determine trends, distribution, and impact of land uses upon those resources, and apply resultant data to implement adaptive ecosystem management strategies.

Inventory and Monitoring Actions

General inventory and monitoring actions that will annually be performed to implement this INRMP are described in detail in Section 10.3. Section 10.4 describes specific, unfunded inventory and monitoring actions desired for out years.

Annual Inventory and Monitoring Actions

10.1.1. Flora Inventory and Monitoring

- The ITAM program will monitor bare ground and herbaceous vegetation (i.e., grasses and forbs) cover to derive reliable estimators of grassland community structure. The target is to use remote sensing to monitor all training areas annually.
- The RTLA program will monitor soil quality in grasslands using an ocular estimate to generate a soil disturbance index using a rotating sampling plan at approximately 80 plots per year. High to moderate quality soils with minimal erosion are fundamental to retention and/or maintenance of desirable non-woody vegetation in grassland communities.
- The status of LRAM-rehabilitated sites will be monitored until non-woody vegetation exceeds 50% ground cover. Monitoring will consist of analyzing ground-truthed aerial photographs taken from a camera mounted on a low-flying drone with GIS computer software to assess the amount of bare ground and herbaceous vegetation cover.
- Re-evaluate installation-wide density and coverage of sericea lespedeza.
- Identify and measure extent of vegetation disturbance caused by military training with use of ITAM drone.
- Conduct forest stands inventories.

10.1.2. Faunal Inventory and Monitoring

10.1.2.1. Fish

- Electroshock to sample fish communities in Moon and Breakneck lakes and Beck and Vinton ponds.
- Electroshock to sample fish communities in LaGrange, Avery and Stone ponds.
- Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish communities in Funston Lake and Dale, Goens, Pritchard, Stortz, Blue, Gaches and Rich ponds.
- Analyze data of fish inventory and recommend actions based upon the data collected.

10.1.2.2. **Upland Game**

- Conduct spring whistle counts for northern bobwhite.
- Conduct spring crow counts for ring-necked pheasant.
- Conduct lek counts for greater prairie-chicken from late March to late April. Standardized routes will not be established. Lek counting routes will be driven in each Maneuver Area with large grassland tracts, with each Maneuver Area surveyed twice. Any active lek located by sound will be visually confirmed and marked on a map. If time and circumstance allow, flush counts will be made on each lek.
- Conduct fall covey counts for northern bobwhite.

10.1.2.3. **Big Game**

- Conduct elk aerial surveys each winter to determine total population size, antlered-to-antlerless ratios, and the breakdown of age classes of bulls.
- Conduct annual nocturnal deer spotlight surveys following standardized routes, late in the autumn.

10.1.2.4. **Threatened and Endangered Species**

- Surveys to locate least terns and piping plovers will be performed every 7-10 days between April 15 and May 15 and between July 10 and August 31. Survey sites view approximately 40% of Milford Reservoir's shoreline on Fort Riley and more than 76% of riverine sandbar habitat.
- Annually monitor existing sandbar habitat, documenting suitability for least terns and piping plovers.
- Update GIS map layer.
- Float the Kansas and Republican rivers before July 1 to search for nesting least terns and/or piping plovers. If a nesting attempt is confirmed, monitor it weekly to determine its status and outcome.
- Surveys for Topeka shiners will be conducted every other year in streams in which this species has been found. Surveys will be conducted a minimum of one out of every five years in streams in which Topeka shiners have not been found.
- Execute surveys for northern long-eared bats, as described in Section 8.5 of Appendix C.

10.1.2.5. **Bald Eagles**

- Search for nesting bald eagles in February. Monitor any active eagle nest to determine the status and outcome of the nesting attempt. Notify the USFWS Kansas Field Office of the nest discovery and updates of nesting activity.
- Weekly, survey bald eagle use of diurnal habitat when wintering eagles are expected to be present on Fort Riley.
- Monitor nocturnal roosts when bald eagles are in the area, generally from October 15 to March 15 annually.

10.1.2.6. **Rare Species**

- Surveys for Henslow's sparrows will be conducted during the breeding season, approximately May 15 to August 31. A quantitative survey methodology will be used to locate Henslow's sparrows.
- Loggerhead shrikes and regal fritillary butterflies abundance data will be collected incidentally while performing other surveys.
- Conduct surveys for regal fritillaries in native tallgrass prairies. Record the numbers of regal fritillaries seen, as well as areas containing appropriate food plants for both adults and caterpillars.
- Data collected will be maintained in a database updated annually.
- Sighting records for all rare species, such as the black rail, rusty blackbird, Texas horned lizard and white-faced ibis, will be collected and maintained when these species are observed incidentally to other fieldwork.

10.1.2.7. **Migratory Birds**

- Conduct surveys for breeding birds.
- Conduct winter raptor surveys along four standardized routes each year from January 1 to mid-March.
- Monitor use of nesting structures (eastern bluebird, purple martin).
- Conduct Christmas Bird Counts on Fort Riley following standard protocol.

10.1.2.8. **Small Mammals**

- Monitor use of bat roosting structures.

10.1.2.9. **Amphibians and Reptiles**

- Conduct amphibian calling survey.
- Conduct installation-wide one day survey in early May.
- Annually survey vernal pools for species' use.

10.1.2.10. **Aquatic Surveys**

- KDWPT monitors selected streams on Fort Riley as part of a state-wide program to monitor and assess streams throughout the state. These surveys have been conducted every two years since 1990.

10.1.2.11. **Invertebrate Surveys**

- Coordinate annually with USDA-APHIS (Animal and Pest Health Inspection Service) to install traps on Fort Riley for invasive, non-native insects, at targeted movement areas.
- Conservation Branch personnel inspect woodlands to determine extent of spread when forest pests are present.

10.1.3. Wildlife Harvest Monitoring

- All persons hunting small game, waterfowl, deer, elk and turkey are required to submit harvest records each day they hunt. This data is submitted electronically via iSportsman. Game harvest and angler/hunter participation will be monitored to assess a variety of biological and non-biological elements related to harvest management strategies.
- Manage and update iSportsman web portal.
- Angler activity and fish harvest will be monitored via iSportsman.
- Firearms deer hunters are required to report harvested deer data via iSportsman. Data collected from harvested deer include gender, antler measurements, and harvest location of deer.
- Hunters are required to report beard size, and spur length of all spring turkeys harvested. These data will be compiled and summarized and used to make comparisons from year to year.

Out Year Projects

- Perform 10-year review and update of installation's floristic Planning Level Survey (PLS).
- Update sericea lespedeza coverage.
- Perform 10 year review and update of installation-wide Forest Planning Level Survey.
- Perform a PLS to document the extent of salt cedar (Tamarisk) invasion along the Kansas River and its woodlands.
- Perform timber rattlesnake survey
- Perform hognose snake survey
- Perform and update Urban Forest and Plant Inventory.

11.0 RESEARCH AND SPECIAL PROJECTS

Research is conducted on Fort Riley to provide scientific and statistically rigorous data for analysis to assess effects of the military mission on natural resources, assess and evaluate the effects of natural resources management decisions, and enhance the understanding of natural resources functions for adaptive management.

Research Mechanisms

Fort Riley cooperates with various entities to conduct scientific research directed to installation specific natural resources management issues. The two primary mechanisms have been academic institutions and the Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education.

11.1.1. Academic Institutions

The Kansas State University (KSU) Division of Biology, KSU-Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit (CO-OP Unit) has collaborated with the ITAM program to operate and implement the RTLA program. The KSU CO-OP Unit has also performed research projects for the Conservation Branch.

11.1.2. Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education (ORISE)

The Conservation Branch participates in the ORISE Postgraduate Environmental Management Participation Program. The ORISE program provides participating environmental scientists to support Fort Riley's Natural Resources management program. ORISE participants are assigned one or more research projects on which to work.

Research Projects

11.1.3. Academic Institution Research Projects

- KSU CO-OP Unit study to evaluate regal fritillary habitat and perform density estimate on Fort Riley.
- Provide access and assistance for a SERDP (Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program) study spearheaded by the University of Nebraska-Lincoln investigating global climate change. The study objectives are to develop models to detect ecological regime shifts, identify components of adaptive capacity relevant to resilience, and identify species and techniques that may serve as leading indicators of thresholds of changing ecological regimes.

11.1.4. ORISE Research Projects

ORISE research projects have emphasized applied natural resources management. Projects involve research on topics including fish and wildlife habitat, wildlife population management, forest inventory, noxious weed surveys and habitat restoration.

11.1.5. In-house Conservation Branch Research Projects

Certain research projects initiated by ORISE participants have been continued by Conservation Branch staff after the ORISE personnel moved on to other positions. Other times, Conservation Branch staff initiate its own studies. Currently:

- Evaluate effectiveness of glyphosate treatments in smooth brome dominated areas.

11.1.6. Forest Ecosystem Inventory

The most recent planning level survey of forest vegetation was initiated in 2012 and completed in 2015. This is the third forest inventory performed on Fort Riley. This project updated previous inventories that were performed initially in 1988-1989 and also during 1998-2000. The second forest inventory was the primary effort that incorporated measurement of wildlife habitat characteristics of the woodlands.

11.1.7. Urban Forest and Plant Inventory

This 1994 project identified trees and perennial plants located in Fort Riley cantonment areas. This inventory is outdated.

11.1.8. ITAM Research Projects

Currently nothing.

12.0 LAW ENFORCEMENT

Effective conservation law enforcement is a critical component of an overall natural and cultural resources management program. Effective enforcement maximizes compliance with Federal and state laws and regulations and Army and Fort Riley regulations. The most important aspects are protecting fish and game populations from over-harvest, protecting threatened and endangered species from harassment, preventing felony theft of timber, protecting cultural resource sites from being damaged or looted, and protecting sensitive habitats. Law enforcement officers also play a critical role in public safety, installation force protection, ensuring non-interference with the military mission by recreationists, and education of the public.

Objectives

The objectives of an effective conservation law enforcement program at Fort Riley are as follows:

- Support the mission by providing law enforcement, security, and protection of natural/cultural resources and facilities.
- Enhance the quality of outdoor recreation on the installation by providing timely emergency response.
- Protect Soldiers and recreationists by providing effective law enforcement.
- Provide environmental education to outdoor recreationists.
- Assist in collection of research and biological survey data.
- Provide trend analysis for law enforcement violations pertaining to conservation.

Authority, and Operations

The Fort Riley Police Department will provide, when available, a Criminal Investigator for conservation and two Civilian Police Officers (Game Wardens). All staff members when providing law enforcement support are under the authority of the Chief of Police. Military Police personnel may augment the Game Warden section at the request of the Chief of Police to provide additional coverage during peak hunting periods.

Jurisdiction

Law enforcement officers from the KDWPT and the USFWS have the authority to come onto Fort Riley and enforce applicable Federal and state laws and regulations. They do not have the authority to cite individuals for violations of Fort Riley regulations. Only Military and Department of the Army Civilian Police (DACP) officers have that particular authority. KDWPT Conservation Officers frequently interact with DES personnel and USFWS special law enforcement agents to cooperatively investigate poaching cases on-post and cases of poaching by Soldiers off-post. KDWPT Conservation Officers may not enter Fort Riley for the sole purpose of arresting a violator without prior coordination of the Staff Judge Advocate and the Fort Riley Police Department except as authorized under federal authority.

Federal magistrate court is used to adjudicate civilian violators who are issued Central Violation Bureau (CVB) Notices, formally known as a DA 1805. Military violators are cited either under the Uniformed Code of Military Justice (UCMJ) or issued a CVB notice. The Staff Judge Advocate may assist in determining the charges when dealing with all violators.

The Environmental Division Chief, DPW, under authority delegated by the Garrison Commander, may administratively suspend or revoke the hunting, fishing, and/or trapping privileges of violators in accordance with the suspension schedule in FR 210-15.

Enforcement Activities

Law Enforcement staff will routinely patrol the installation, including the range area north of Vinton School Road. These personnel routinely check hunters and anglers for possession of required licenses and permits as well as bag and creel checks. Special operations such as check points during hunting seasons and the use of decoy deer missions during the firearms deer season may be conducted. It is anticipated that these types of activities will continue.

Evidence and observations indicate that the most frequent violations of laws and regulations have involved failure of hunters to complete daily registration forms, failure of anglers to abide by creel limits, recreating in unauthorized areas, and theft of timber and fuelwood. Failure to possess state and installation permits occurs more frequently with anglers than with hunters.

Training

Law Enforcement staff may have the basic knowledge in the scientific principles of fisheries and wildlife biology, animal damage control, botany, forestry and cultural resources. Staff assigned to these positions will attend an approved Law Enforcement Academy and be in compliance with AR 190-56. In addition, staff will attend the Fort Riley Police Department's two week police training program.

In-service training is an important part of maintaining proficiency and certification of Police Officers. In-service will be offered on a semi-annual basis provided support can be acquired from the Military Police Battalion. In addition, Police Officers will be afforded the opportunity to attend workshops sponsored by the KDWPT and the National Military Fish and Wildlife Association, budget permitting.

Specialized training for Military Police who augment the Game Warden staff will be provided from staff within the Fort Riley Police Department.

Investigative Priorities

Investigative priorities will be determined by the Fort Riley Chief of Police.

13.0 ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Fort Riley recognizes the critical importance of education and environmental awareness to a comprehensive natural resources management program. Fort Riley is committed to education for Soldiers within the training scenarios and community outreach as well as the specific objectives listed below.

Military Personnel Awareness

Many venues for educating the Soldiers about natural resources management exist. The ITAM SRA program is intended to minimize damage to training lands and to protect the environment by fostering a conservation ethic in Soldiers and their leaders. Additionally, the Public Affairs Office (PAO) supports educational outreach by publishing articles in the weekly installation newspaper.

13.1.1. Actions

- Enhance educational efforts as a compliance element within the installation's rare species management plans.
- The ITAM SRA program makes available ITAM materials on-line to attendees of the weekly Range Safety Officer Course. These materials include maps, range SOPs, and Range and Safety Regulations.
- The Conservation Branch provides attendees of the weekly Range Safety Officer Course information about natural and cultural resources management and protection.
- The Conservation Branch personnel provide Hazardous Plants and Animals briefings to Soldiers. Information about hunting and fishing and other natural resources-related recreation also is presented.
- Some classes taught as part of the DPW Environmental Management System training program cover aspects of natural and cultural resource protection. Classes such as Environmental Team Training, Hazard Communication, and others devote small portions of instruction to natural resources protection measures.
- ITAM or the Conservation Branch will take any unscheduled opportunity to speak to Soldiers on environmental protection. Avenues include Officer Professional Development, NCO Professional Development and Unit Safety Days.

Community Outreach

Proper implementation of a natural resources management program requires the cooperation of surrounding communities.

13.1.2. Actions

- News articles are submitted for publication in Fort Riley's weekly newspaper, "*FORT RILEY POST*."
- News releases are distributed through the PAO to area newspapers and other media, when applicable.
- PAO covers high-interest events for "In-Step with Fort Riley", a television program shown on local cable and broadcast stations.
- Honor requests from local radio stations for interviews with Conservation Branch personnel.

- Provide information and educational materials to the military, general public, and other requesters regarding Fort Riley's native ecosystem and its management within the mission framework and DoD and Army policy.
- The Conservation Branch produces many publications for distribution to Fort Riley outdoor recreationists. These include booklets, brochures, hunting/fishing maps, fact sheets, regulation summaries, and hunting/fishing tips.
- The Conservation Branch also distributes brochures, pamphlets, and other publications produced by the KDWPT, USFWS, the KSU Cooperative Extension Service, and other conservation organizations.
- The Conservation Branch staff presents briefings, slide shows, tours and talks to various conservation and civic organizations and professional groups, as requested.
- The Conservation Branch provides natural resource education programs to school groups, as requested.
- Children's Fishing Derbies are supported.
- Conservation Branch staff provides presentations and information to meetings of the Fort Riley Outdoorsmen Group.

14.0 OUTDOOR RECREATION (QUALITY OF LIFE)

Quality of Life is the installation's key process supporting Soldiers and Family. Hunting, angling, fuelwood-cutting, and non-consumptive recreation (e.g., bird watching) are among the natural resource-based recreational activities pursued on Fort Riley that enhance quality of life.

Army regulation (AR) 200-1 provides the primary guidance for outdoor recreation programs and opportunities. Army regulations specify that "the appropriate environmental directorate will address the biological management of game species and natural resources while the Directorate of Community Activities addresses the movement of persons, special events, and organization elements of outdoor recreation". Army Regulations define outdoor recreation as those programs and activities that depend on natural resources, such as hunting, fishing, hiking, and bird watching.

Quality of Life Strategy

The strategy to enhance the quality of life for Fort Riley's Soldiers and Families is to provide optimal opportunity for sustainable, high quality hunting, angling, fuelwood cutting and non-consumptive uses to the maximum number of users, taking into account safety and the military mission. This strategy would support at least 5,000 hunting trips and 20,000 angling days while maintaining other consumptive and non-consumptive uses.

Hunting, Fishing and Trapping Authority

The Sikes Act (P.L. 86-797) and the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 (P.L. 105-85) establishes policy for hunting, fishing, and trapping on military installations. The law covers access, issuance of hunting and fishing permits, and use of fees generated from the sales of installation hunting and fishing permits. Hunting and fishing are consistent with all applicable Federal and state laws and regulations and FR 210-15.

All KDWPT regulations for lawful hunting methods, equipment, bag limits, hunting hours, and season lengths are enforced on Fort Riley. All USFWS laws and regulations for migratory bird hunting also are in force. All KDWPT regulations for lawful fishing methods, equipment, creel limits, length limits, and season lengths are enforced on Fort Riley. Fort Riley's Hunting and Fishing Regulations (FR 210-15) are, in some aspects, more restrictive than state and Federal regulations and are in no case more liberal.

Public Access

Fort Riley policy regarding public access, as stated in FR 210-15, is consistent with the Sikes Act, as amended (P.L. 105-85), DoD Instruction 4715.03, and AR 200-1.

The military mission takes priority over all outdoor recreation. The installation or portions of it may be closed, without prior notice, for mission and security considerations. Fort Riley is not a public recreation area but is instead a military training installation that allows natural resources-based recreation only when it is compatible with the military mission and security.

Fort Riley currently allows the public, as well as Soldiers and their dependents, to participate in natural resources-based recreation. Fort Riley has a policy allowing certain forms of recreation to

coexist with some types of military training. Access for recreation is precluded for safety or security reasons, or if a bona fide impairment of the military mission would occur, as determined by the Installation Commander.

14.1.1. Outdoor Recreation Areas

Outdoor Recreation Areas are established to provide regulated, safe access for recreationists and fuelwood cutters and to prevent interference with the military mission. One of the most critical functions is to make boundaries easily identifiable. They correspond, generally, with Military Training Areas and Maneuver Areas, and are generally delineated by improved, hardened roads. The Fort Riley Outdoor Recreation and Fuelwood Cutting Map is shown as Exhibit 14.1.

14.1.2. Access Procedures

The access procedures protect Soldiers and recreationists and minimize interference with the military mission by limiting recreationists' access and munitions based upon scheduled training and security considerations. Access is prohibited to any area not listed as open for recreation. Live-fire training, aerial artillery, and demolition are the main types of training that preclude access. Shotgun hunting (using size 2 shot or smaller), archery hunting, angling, fuelwood cutting, and non-consumptive recreation can coexist with maneuver training unless the training presents a safety or security risk.

Natural resources-based outdoor recreational activities on Fort Riley take place only in areas authorized by the Conservation Branch in coordination with the DPTMS, Range Safety Office. The authorized areas can change daily, depending on the schedule of the installation's military trainers. Access to any area that is not listed as open for hunting, fishing, trapping, non-consumptive outdoor recreation, or fuelwood cutting is prohibited. Outdoor recreationists may learn of open areas via iSportsman. iSportsman is an automated check-in-out system by which recreationists are able to view open areas and check-in/check-out via the world-wide web, smart phones and other compatible electronic devices. Individuals can register at the Fort Riley iSportsman webpage www.fortriley.isportsman.net.

Any person accessing Fort Riley, including recreationists who will traverse areas north of Vinton School Road, who appears to be over the age of 16, is required to possess a valid DoD ID card, Riley Access Pass, or Riley Access Badge. The only exception to this requirement is for individuals who wish to access the Fort Riley Marina area of Milford Lake. People who do not have the required ID or access pass can apply for one at the installation's Visitor Control Center, (Building 885, adjacent to Marshall Army Air Field, exit 301, U.S. Interstate 70), which is open 24-hours-a-day, 7-days-a-week. Passes may be available in advance. Issued passes are good from one day to one year.

A form of government issued photo identification is required to obtain an access pass or badge. Additionally, any non-DoD person entering the installation, regardless of affiliation, must pass a criminal background check. Vehicle registration and proof of insurance are required for every vehicle that is driven on the installation.

**Fort Riley Outdoor Recreation and Fuelwood Cutting Map:
2012 Edition**

Vehicular access to any area North of Vinton School Road and East of U.S. Highway 77 requires people to use Old Highway 77 south gate. Vehicular access may sometimes be available through the Douthit Range Complex entrance gates. To access an area west of U.S. Highway 77, people can use any existing road.

Privately-owned vehicle access to Fort Riley (including the areas north of Vinton School Road) for recreational activities is allowed. All vehicles operated on Fort Riley for recreational purposes must display a Fort Riley Recreation Motor Vehicle Permit. These permits are free of charge and may be picked up at the Conservation Branch office or at Information Station marked on the Fort Riley Outdoor Recreation Map.

Everyone recreating in a Fort Riley training area must use iSportsman. Check-in and Check-out may be done with any personal device with internet access or by visiting the iSportsman Kiosk at 1st Division and Vinton School roads or the Conservation Branch office, 407 Pershing Ct., during normal business hours.

14.1.3. Access Restrictions

Rifle hunting and shotgun hunting that use shot larger than #2 are restricted to those areas that do not have Soldiers training in them. Access for firearms deer hunting generally is not an issue because this season is established concurrent with the Thanksgiving and Christmas training holidays. During those training holidays, the installation is, generally, fully accessible.

Human population density and the number of improved facilities require that all parts of the installation south of Vinton School Road be closed to rifle hunting. Exceptions to this restriction concern the use of .22 rimfire rifles loaded with "short" cartridges to take treed raccoons and the use of muzzleloaders (black powder rifles) and shotgun with slugs to take deer. The portion of the installation south of Vinton School Road is open only to shotgun and archery hunting outside of the firearms deer season.

14.1.4. Handicapped Access

Access to hunting and angling recreational opportunities by disabled persons is required to comply with the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990, and to provisions within the Sikes Act that ensure disabled veterans and persons with disabilities have access to the same outdoor recreation opportunities as the public. This includes activities such as fishing, hunting, trapping, wildlife viewing, boating and camping on military lands. Fort Riley currently supports access by disabled persons by waiving some installation regulations that are potentially impediments to recreation. Specific regulations that directly address Fort Riley access by disabled persons are:

- Any disabled person who holds an approved special permit from the KDWPT is not required to purchase a Fort Riley Hunting Permit.
- A permanently disabled person who holds an approved special permit from the KDWPT may hunt from a motor vehicle.
- Any disabled person with a handicap placard on their vehicle is authorized to use secondary trails not marked on the Outdoor Recreation Map to include any pathway on which the vegetation is absent or markedly reduced across the entire width of the trail.
- The authorization to hunt from a vehicle does not permit any person to shoot from any improved road.
- All other state or Federal laws or regulations or Fort Riley regulations are enforced. Disabled persons may hunt from a motor vehicle only when in compliance with license and permit requirements, seasons, and bag limits, and other related laws and regulations.

Wildlife Harvest Management

Animals hunted on Fort Riley include northern bobwhite, ring-necked pheasant, greater prairie-chicken, waterfowl, mourning dove, Wilson's snipe, American woodcock, fox and gray squirrels, cottontail rabbit, white-tailed deer, elk and wild turkey. Furbearer species are badger, bobcat, mink, muskrat, opossum, raccoon, red fox, gray fox, striped skunk, coyote, otter and beaver.

14.1.5. Management Strategy

Game harvest management combines an ecosystem approach with harvest control. Ecosystem management influences the availability of game species for harvest and the biological carrying capacity of each species. For example, management that favors native grasses and reduces woody vegetation will likely benefit greater prairie-chickens.

Harvest control influences the number of game animals removed from the population each year. Harvest control objectives are based on sociological carrying capacity and desired population dynamics. For example, deer and elk populations are maintained below their respective biological carrying capacities to reduce the incidence of deer and elk collisions with vehicles and limit crop depredation on lands adjacent to Fort Riley.

The KDWPT establishes harvest regulations that are applicable on Fort Riley. Bag limits established by KDWPT may be further restricted by the Conservation Branch to ensure a sustainable harvest of game species. In no case will Fort Riley regulations be less restrictive than Kansas regulations.

The overall strategy is to harvest wildlife species based on the concept of sustained yield, in harmony with the military mission. Sustained yield harvest management seeks to balance the sustained production of animals with hunter satisfaction. Hunting opportunity may be limited by military training, security measures, safety considerations, and qualitative aspects.

14.1.5.1. Upland Game

- Fort Riley follows season dates, bag limits and shooting times established by KDWPT, except that hunting jackrabbits is prohibited on Fort Riley.

14.1.5.2. Deer

- Establish and coordinate firearms deer season dates under Kansas Regulation KAR 115-25-9a.
- Establish and print the annual Fort Riley Deer Hunting Fact Sheet.
- Fort Riley will make available for issue an appropriate number of archery and firearms deer permits based on survey data, harvest information and deer management goals.
- An annual harvest of at least 180 animals with at least 60% of those antlerless is considered necessary to achieve desired population control. A firearms hunter success rate (percent of tags successfully filled) of at least 40% annually is desired.
- Harvest goals include that at least two animals each year should have antlers that score a minimum of 145 points (Boone & Crockett typical) or 170 points (Boone & Crockett non-

typical); at least 40% of the harvested males should be 2 1/2 years and older;; and the antlers of at least 60% of the adult males should have eight or more points.

14.1.5.3. **Elk**

- Fort Riley will coordinate with KDWPT in establishing annual numbers of elk permits and season dates.

14.1.5.4. **Wild Turkey**

- Fort Riley follows season dates, bag limits and shooting times established by KDWPT.
- An unlimited number of fall wild turkey hunters will be allowed. There will be no permit allocation system among user groups for these.
- Access procedures for spring wild turkey hunting will be announced in the Spring Turkey Fact Sheet that is published prior to the season.

14.1.5.5. **Furbearer**

- Furbearer management will consist of establishing trapping regulations and seasons, and issuing trapping permits on Fort Riley according to the FR 210-15 and the annual Fort Riley Trapping Fact Sheet.

14.1.5.6. **Migratory Bird**

- Fort Riley follows season dates, bag limits and shooting times established by KDWPT and the USFWS.

Fish Harvest Management

The overall objective for sport fishing is the active management of 29 ponds and lakes to sustain a biomass of fish in harvestable-sizes to support 20,000 fishing trips annually on the installation.

14.1.6. **Management Strategy**

The KDWPT establishes harvest regulations that are applicable on Fort Riley. Creel limits established by KDWPT may be further restricted by the Conservation Branch to ensure a sustainable harvest of fish species. In no case will Fort Riley regulations be less restrictive than Kansas regulations.

The overall strategy is to harvest fish species based on the concept of sustained yield, in harmony with the military mission. Sustained yield harvest management seeks to balance the sustained production of fish with angler satisfaction. Sustained yield is not always the appropriate harvest strategy. Some lakes are managed on a put-and-take concept. Angling opportunity may be limited by military training, security measures, safety considerations, and qualitative aspects.

14.1.6.1. **Sport Fish**

- Eighteen of the ponds will be managed as put and take catfish fisheries (Sevenmile, Campbell, Chestnut, Miller, Farnum, Halasz, Stortz, Roblyer, Williams, Sinn, Rush, Dale, Goens, Bravo, CACTF, Blue, Gaches and Cameron Springs). Annual stockings of 8,000

to 13,000 pounds of harvestable-sized channel catfish will be conducted to support this strategy. Eight lakes and ponds will be managed as largemouth bass fisheries (Breakneck, Pritchard, Rich, Avery, Stone, Lagrange, Moon, and Vinton). Fingerling largemouth bass will be stocked as necessary to augment existing populations.

- Moon Lake and Cameron Springs will be managed as put-and-take rainbow trout fisheries. Annual stockings of 12,000 pounds of harvestable-sized rainbow trout will be conducted to support this strategy.
- Mowing will be performed around fishing ponds to better provide angler access to the water body.
- Large predatory fish (e.g., flathead catfish and largemouth bass) will be stocked into ponds and lakes to control population imbalances, such as overcrowded shad and excess crappie.
- Any water body that experiences any environmental concern, or is suspected to have a problem, will be closed immediately to angling. The water will not be reopened to angling until the problem is fixed and the water is deemed safe after testing by MEDDAC Preventative Medicine personnel.

Permits and Fee Structure

Permits and fees for hunting and fishing shall be required in accordance with applicable state and federal laws and military regulations in accordance with the Sikes Act.

14.1.7. Fishing Permits

Fort Riley entered into a Community Fisheries Assistance Program agreement with the KDWPT beginning in January 2004. As part of the agreement, Fort Riley would no longer charge a separate fee for fishing on the installation. The loss of fishing permit revenue is reimbursed by the KDWPT through no-cost fish stockings of catfish and trout. Subsequently, the only permit needed to fish on Fort Riley is a Kansas Fishing License, unless fishing for trout in Cameron Springs or Moon Lake, in which case a Kansas Trout Stamp is also needed during the Kansas Trout Season.

14.1.8. Hunting Permits

Installation hunting permits are not required for individuals under age 16, age 65 and older, and persons who hold an approved special permit from the KDWPT for a physical handicap. A fee is charged to each individual wishing to hunt on Fort Riley who is between the ages 16 and 64 that are otherwise not excluded from purchase. An administrative fee of no more than 10% of the total permit cost may be charged by the installation's Special State Permit vendor. As directed by Army regulations, all Special State Permit fees collected will be deposited directly into the installation's Fish and Wildlife Receiving Account.

The fee for a Fort Riley Hunting Permit was set at \$25 in 2006. Separate, additional, no cost Fort Riley access permits are required to trap furbearers, to deer and elk hunt, and spring turkey hunt.

The possession of a Fort Riley permit and appropriate state and federal licenses and stamps entitles the permittee to hunt in areas open to such recreation until the end of the calendar year. The Fort Riley permits do not constitute a guarantee of access on any or all days during the period for which it is issued.

Fort Riley permits are generally allocated equally among user groups. Most permits are available to an unlimited number of permittees. However, when restricting the overall number of permittees is necessary to achieve natural resources management objectives or maintain a safe installation, permits are distributed by impartial procedures, such as a first-come, first-serve basis or by a random drawing. Priority for distribution of any Fort Riley Permit may, however, be given to Active Duty Military Personnel when they are deemed to be at a disadvantage in accessing hunting areas or fully utilizing a set hunting season

Fort Riley sold 862 hunting permits in 2017, 1,174 hunting permits in 2016, 1,326 hunting permits in 2015, 1,321 hunting permits in 2014, 1,352 permits in 2013, 1,373 permits in 2012, and 1,353 hunting permits in 2011. The declining trend could be attributable to many factors including national trends and number of soldiers interested in hunting being stationed at Fort Riley.

14.1.9. Hunter Education

State and Fort Riley regulations require that all individuals born on or after July 1, 1957 complete an approved (State or Canadian Province issued) Hunter Education Course prior to purchasing any Kansas Hunting License. Certain exemptions are permitted by the state of Kansas. Youth younger than 16 may hunt without hunter education if directly supervised by a licensed adult 18 or older. Anyone 16 or older may purchase a deferral of hunter education, called an apprentice hunting license, for the same price as a regular hunting license. The holder must be under the direct supervision of a licensed adult 18 years or older and may be purchased no more than two times.

Other Natural Resources Related Outdoor Recreation

Fort Riley supports multiple-use outdoor recreation that includes consumptive and non-consumptive uses. Other consumptive uses, besides hunting and angling, are fuelwood-cutting, wildflower and mushroom gathering, and shed antler collecting. Non-consumptive pursuits include hiking, photography, bird watching, and mountain biking.

- A \$20 Fuelwood Cutting Permit is required to obtain fuelwood from across the installation. Permits are purchased through the Fort Riley iSportsman website.
- All persons in areas open for outdoor recreation during the installation's firearms deer season must wear the following safety clothing, which must be colored blaze (international) orange: a cap or hat and an outer cover of a coat, vest, sweater, coveralls, or shirt. The outer cover must have at least 200 square inches of orange-colored surface visible, covering both front and back.
- Flowers, berries, nuts, fruits, and stems of plants may be taken for human consumption without a permit.
- Flowers and foliage of plants (excluding trees and shrubs) may be taken for ornamental purposes without a permit, provided that not more plant material is taken by any one individual each day than can fit into a standard "three-pound coffee can" (six-inch diameter opening). Plants may not be dug or otherwise uprooted from Fort Riley.
- Camping on Fort Riley is prohibited.

- Open fires (campfires, barbecue pits, bonfires, etc.) are prohibited on Fort Riley, except in specially designated areas.
- Swimming in the installation's streams, lakes, and ponds is prohibited.
- Use of metal detectors is prohibited for recreational uses.
- Operation of Off-Road Vehicles is permitted only in designated portions of Training Area 10 and as outlined for specific uses in annual Fact Sheets and FR 210-15. Off-Road Vehicles are motorized vehicles (excluding boats) not registered and licensed for highway use.

Safety

Fort Riley's safety record for natural resources-related recreation is excellent. Only two reported hunting accidents have occurred on Fort Riley since 1988 despite more than 6,000 hunting trips taken annually. Both of these occurred during upland game bird hunting as a result of hunters "swinging through" a flushed bird, firing, and hitting another hunter. Neither accident was fatal or resulted in severe injury. No drownings have occurred on Fort Riley lakes and ponds. No recreationists have been injured during training activities. No Soldiers while on-duty have been injured by recreationists.

Safety requires that hunting access be limited because of hunter density as well as military training. Access permission during the spring turkey season is staggered throughout the season to limit the number of hunters. Firearms deer hunting is limited by assigning hunters to one of three hunting areas, and hunters must remain in their assigned area to prevent overcrowding and to distribute hunter density.

Effective law enforcement of access restrictions and safety checks of firearms and boats contributes toward making opportunities to recreate safer.

Quality of Life Management Actions

- Seek Conservation Partnerships to leverage installation funds to support hunting and fishing recreation at current levels.
- Collect and manage income from the sales of hunting permits.
- Provide basic information and explanatory material to users on recreational opportunities at Fort Riley.
- Provide recreational briefing for all individuals wishing to recreate on the installation.
- Provide web-based deer hunter briefing for all individuals wishing to hunt deer, elk and spring turkey on the installation, focusing on game management, safety, and access procedures.
- Conduct hunter education classes for children and adults.
- Conduct boating safety course.
- Provide self-service information and educational materials to recreational users on safety and non-interference with the military mission.
- Provide staff during regular duty hours to answer the questions and concerns of customers.
- Manage hunter and angler access.
- Manage archery range.
- Collect and analyze harvest data.

- Operate fuelwood program.

15.0 IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter describes the organization, manpower, actions, and budget requirements necessary to implement this INRMP.

Organization, Roles, and Responsibilities

The Conservation Branch is the principal implementing agent of this INRMP. The Conservation Branch coordinates with the other operations responsible for implementing specific portions of the plan to ensure an orderly and coordinated implementation.

The DPW and the DPTMS are the directorates responsible for management of natural resources at Fort Riley. The specific responsibilities of the Conservation Branch are forestry, agronomy, rangeland, fish and wildlife, and pest management, as well as establishing partnerships with outside entities. The DPTMS is responsible for soil and erosion management and evaluating the mission effects on the natural resources.

Hunting and Fuelwood permits are available over the internet through the Fort Riley iSportsman website. The Conservation Branch issues any additional special, no cost permits to recreate on the installation via the iSportsman website.

The DES, Fire Department is responsible for controlling wildfires and leads, with a Conservation Branch staff member embedded as the Wildland Fire Manger, prescribed burning. The DES is also responsible for enforcing hunting and fishing regulations on Fort Riley through civilian conservation officers.

The Veterinary Activity, a subactivity of the MEDDAC, is responsible for the prevention and control of communicable diseases of wildlife on Fort Riley in cooperation with the Conservation Branch. Zoonotic diseases, pests, and wildlife borne diseases are monitored cooperatively between the MEDDAC's Preventive Medicine Service and the Conservation Branch.

Manpower

A mix of professional and non-professional series government employees, contractors, military personnel, and university staff currently implement the activities related to this INRMP.

Ongoing training of personnel involved in the implementation of this plan will continue to be undertaken. That training is provided by various professional societies. Subject to budget and manpower constraints, installation staff will attend each of the following:

- National Military Fish and Wildlife Association annual training sessions.
- North American Wildlife and Natural Resources Conference.
- Society of American Foresters annual national and regional conferences.
- The Wildlife Society conferences.
- The Kansas Arborists' Association Conference.
- The North American Weed Management Conference.
- Weed Science Society of America Conference.

- The DoD Triennial Pest Management Conference.
- The Kansas Natural Resources Conference.

Other conferences and workshops may be included depending on availability of funds and their direct applicability to specific projects and program priorities. An example would be continued participation in Partners in Flight.

Priority will be given to training required to maintain certifications, such as certification for DoD pesticide applicator and Federal Wildland Firefighter (“Red Card”). Technical training in GIS, prescribed burning, wetlands management, pest management, and other skills-enhancement programs directly applicable to fundamental resources management are the types of training that will be given secondary priority in funding.

Program Priorities

Preparation and implementation of this INRMP is required by the Sikes Act and Army Regulations and thus must be funded according to DoD Instruction 4715.3, OMB Circular A – 106 rules and Department of Army Policy. This document is a Federal Facilities Compliance Agreement for which a NEPA document has been completed prior to its final approval.

Funding is not unlimited, however, and projects and programs described in this Plan must be prioritized. The metrics below (Exhibit 15.1) list the programs and projects, and their priorities. These priorities reflect funding guidelines provided by IMCOM, other installation Operation, Management and Administration (OMA) supported actions, and projects implemented with program specific funds (Ag/grazing, Forestry, and Hunting and Fuelwood Permit Fee funds).

Program Administration Costs

- Personnel salaries (government and contractor)
- Natural resources management supplies and equipment
- Providing routine computer upgrades
- Updating GIS equipment and coverages
- Obtaining updated aerial photography
- Provision of required training

Implement Funding Options

Implementation of this INRMP is financed from the following sources:

- Installation OMA budgetary allocations funding Common Levels of Support, particularly areas 41, 58, 59, 64 and 304.
- Installation OMA funding for non-recurring environmental projects and sustainment, revitalization and maintenance of facilities.
- Revenues generated from the sale of fuelwood, timber, and other forest products.
- Revenues generated from the sale of installation hunting and fishing permits.
- Revenues generated from the agricultural outlease program.
- Funds donated to the installation from non-governmental organizations.

- The annual cost to implement this INRMP is estimated to be approximately \$4.6 million. The single largest funding requirement is that for the implementation of the installation's ITAM program, which is projected to average \$3.2 million annually over the next five years.

Exhibit 15.1. Prioritized metrics list of INRMP tasks to be accomplished.			
From 9.1. Grassland Management	Priority		
From 9.1.2.1.1. Prescribed Burning Actions	1	2	3
Annually update Prescribed Burn Strategic Plan.		2	
Seasonally adjust Prescribed Burn Strategic Plan.		2	
Annually retain 10,000 acres Henslow's sparrow habitat.			3
Collaborate with DES & DPTMS on prescribed burn plan.			3
Coordinate the Prescribed Burn Plan with Cultural Resources.			3
<i>Coordinate</i> firebreak maintenance with Cultural Resources.	1		
DPTMS review firebreak operations.	1		
Incorporate Henslow's sparrow habitat into Burn Strategic Plan.		2	
Do not burn prairie-chicken areas, mid-April to mid-August.			3
Maintain firebreaks to manage areas in smaller parcels.			3
Only certified personnel conduct burning and firefighting.		2	
Each spring publish bulletin re: Soldier safety during burning.		2	
Each spring publish articles re: safety during burning.		2	
Burn Crew training will be IAW Integrated Wildland Fire MGMT Plan	1		
Burn approximately 25,000-30,000 acres annually.	1		
Protect oak/walnut woodlands from headfires.			3
From 9.1.2.3.1. IPM Actions			
Remove scattered trees from grassland areas.	1		
Implement Shrub Reduction Strategic Plan.		2	
Evaluate and amend, as needed, Shrub Reduction Strategic Plan.		2	
Coordinate Shrub Reduction Plan amendments with Cultural Resources.	1		
Rotary mow 150 acres of shrub infested grasslands annually.		2	
Ground-spray 150 acres of shrub infested grasslands annually.		2	
Franklin tree and brush machine treats 150 acres annually.		2	
Cut large trees in shrubby areas of forest edge/upland ecotone.			3
Annually update GIS data layers of tree clipping activities.		2	
Evaluate hedgerows for possible cutting or removal.			3
Evaluate TCI plantings in grasslands for removal.			3
Ground-spray musk thistle-infested areas.	1		
Ground-spray johnson grass-infested areas.	1		
Ground-spray bindweed-infested grasslands annually.	1		
Update the IPMP.	1		
Annually prepare pesticide report.		2	
All pesticide applicators will be certified for such actions.	1		
From 9.1.2.4.1. Partnerships Management Actions			

Manage Fort Riley's ACUB program.		2	
Participate in regional conservation workshops and meetings.		2	
Assist with management programs on lands around Fort Riley.		2	
From 9.1.2.5.1. Soil Management Actions			
Gully erosion repair, as necessary.		2	
Excavate rock for LRAM projects.		2	
Coordinate LRAM projects with Cultural Resources.	1		
Close off unauthorized stream crossings and repair sites.		2	
Repair lands damaged by maneuver training.		2	
Harden drainage ditches damaged during training events.		2	
Monitor soil erosion and soil compaction.		2	
Construct hardened fords, following approved protocol.		2	
Maintain fords, following approved protocol.		2	
Implement plan on borrow areas.		2	
Manage digging permit program.		2	
Conduct soil borrow actions in accordance with Borrow Area Mgmt plan.	1		
From 9.2. Forest Management			
From 9.2.2.1.1. Prescribed Burning Management Actions			
Suppress fire from riverine, floodplain forest stands.			3
Conduct prescribed burns within oak woodlands.			3
Exclude burns from riparian mixed hardwood stands when prescribed			3
From 9.2.2.2.1. TSI Management Actions			
Perform Forest Stands Management Plan actions.			3
Target non-oaks when thinning oak woodlands.			3
Retain a minimum 40 sq. ft. of basal area/ac in oak woodlands.			3
Retain at least 20-pole size trees/acre in oak woodlands.			3
Retain a crown cover of at least 50% in oak woodlands.			3
Retain at least 30% of existing mast and fruit bearing trees.			3
Retain snags and trees with cavities when thinning.			3
Retain a number of mature trees in decline for future snags.			3
Retain minimum 65 sq. ft. of basal area/ac in mixed hardwoods.			3
TSI tree felling for training support or safety.		2	
From 9.2.2.3.1. Commercial Harvest Management Actions			
Harvest within floodplain forest will favor larger diameter trees.	1		
The Cultural Resources reviews proposed timber sales.	1		
Select and mark trees to be commercially harvested.			3
Meet, in person, with each timber sale applicant.			3
Monitor timber harvest and enforce specifications.			3
Prohibit fuelwood cutting in floodplain forest.			3
Identify skid trails, log decks, and erosion control features.			3
Conduct site impact evaluation; resolve negative impacts.			3
From 9.2.2.4.1. Tree Planting Management Actions			
Increase width of floodplain forests.			3

Connect floodplain forest with other stands, where possible.			3
Maintain walnut forest plantings.			3
Plant cottonwoods, sycamores and oaks within floodplain forests			3
Maintain firebreaks around newer tree plantings for 5-8 years.			3
Cultural Resources manager reviews tree planting & maintenance	1		
From 9.2.2.5.1. IPM Management Actions			
Perform forest pest surveillance and control.		2	
Implement tartarian honeysuckle control plan.	1		
Control sericea lespedeza established within woodland tracts.	1		
Survey for kudzu plants.	1		
Control kudzu plants.	1		
Develop protocol to survey for emerald ash borer.	1		
Develop/implement response plan for positive emerald ash borer findings.	1		
From 9.3. Specialized Management			
From 9.3.1.3. Agriculture Outleases Actions			
Conduct prebid lease meeting open for all potential bidders.			3
Cultural Resources reviews hay-cutting activities.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews activities to improve grasslands.	1		
Meet with each lessee prior to granting right-of-entry.			3
Provide lessees an up-to-date access map.			3
Monitor leases and enforce specifications IAW LUR's.		2	
Provide a sericea lespedeza infestation map to lessee, as asked.			3
Advise lessees on conservation work associated with lease.			3
Provide lessees staff list authorized to grant access before 1 Feb.			3
Notify lessees of Army activities impacting leases.		2	
Annually inspect all firebreaks for renovation needs.	1		
Renovate structures, as needed, in one firebreak unit per year.	1		
Review firebreaks for functioning buffer strips.	1		
Repair filter strips found to be inadequate.	1		
Continue incentive program to reduce firebreak pesticide use.			3
Construct new firebreaks for new ranges or other facilities.		2	
Cultural Resources reviews firebreak activities.	1		
Establish structures, as needed, on firebreak areas not leased.	1		
Annually review, amend and update the LUR's.		2	
Communicate with Command on hay harvest extension.		2	
Inspect firebreak waterways.	1		
Mow firebreak waterways, as needed.	1		
From 9.3.2.1. T&E Species Actions			
Consult with FWS on actions that may affect listed species.	1		
Confer with FWS when actions may affect proposed or candidates sp.	1		
Consult with KDWPT on actions that may affect listed species.	1		
Obtain collection permits to possess any listed species.	1		

Maintain updated GIS data layers for all T&E species.	1		
Report to KDWPT observations of state-listed species.	1		
Least Tern and Piping Plover			
Protect nesting least terns or piping plovers, if found.	1		
Protect sandbars from adverse impacts.	1		
Report to FWS observations of least terns and piping plovers.	1		
Topeka Shiner			
Consult prior to constructing dams on a stream in Exhibit 7.11.	1		
Enforce prohibition of bait-fish seining.	1		
Protect streams from channel destruction.	1		
Protect streams from increases in water turbidity.	1		
Protect streams from removal of vegetative filter strips.	1		
Control operations within 50 feet of Topeka shiner streams.	1		
Monitor stream habitat.	1		
Restore stream habitat, as needed.	1		
Remove largemouth bass and green sunfish from Wind Creek.			3
Cultural Resources reviews activities to improve stream banks.	1		
Road & ford work will follow approved protocol in 2001 BO.	1		
Continue RCCD Partnership actions off-post in Wildcat Creek	1		
Northern Long-eared Bat			
Educate Conservation personnel to identify no. long-eared bats.	1		
Where possible, retain dead/dying trees in woodlands.	1		
Fort Riley personnel adhere to WNS prevention national plan.	1		
Implement practices in Biological Evaluation if species documented.	1		
Whooping Crane			
Monitor reports for whooping crane sightings.	1		
Establish "no fly" zones when whooping cranes are present.	1		
Issue local NOTAMS when "no fly" zones are in effect.	1		
Educate Fort Riley personnel to identify whooping cranes.	1		
Review aerial structures projects for need of line markers.	1		
From 9.3.2.2. Bald Eagle Management Actions			
Maintain firebreaks to protect roost and nest trees.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews firebreak maintenance.	1		
Update GIS data layers for eagles.	1		
Review aerial structures projects for need of line markers.	1		
Review transmission line projects to prevent electrocution.	1		
Control operations within " <i>minimum disturbance</i> " buffer zones	1		
Establish 200-m flight altitude buffer over buffer zones.	1		
Maintain " <i>no disturbance</i> " buffer around communal roosts.	1		
Maintain " <i>no disturbance</i> " buffer zones around nests.	1		
Protect trees required to maintain integrity of communal roosts.	1		
Minimize nesting conflicts on human-made structures.	1		
Protect bald eagles from chemical impacts.	1		

Provide information to aviators through Local NOTAMS.	1		
Avoid removal of overstory trees within 100 m of nest at any time.	1		
Management near nest trees occur outside of nesting season.	1		
Avoid timber operations within 200 m of nest during breeding.	1		
From 9.3.2.3. Species At Risk (SAR) Management Actions			
Henslow's Sparrow			
Designate Henslow's sparrow breeding habitat.		2	
Retain 10,000 acres Henslow's sparrow habitat.		2	
Reduce woody encroachment into grasslands.		2	
Regal Fritillary			
Identify & maintain areas containing a variety of wildflowers.		2	
Reduce woody encroachment.		2	
Monitor sericea lespedeza infestations in fritillary habitats.	1		
Control sericea lespedeza infestations in fritillary habitats.	1		
Restrict aerially-spraying.	1		
Texas Horned Lizard			
Document habitat of reported Texas horned lizard sightings.			3
Maintain log of Texas horned lizard sightings habitats.			3
Minimize insecticide use away from cantonment areas.			3
Rusty Blackbird			
Educate Conservation personnel to recognize rusty blackbirds.			3
Document habitat of reported rusty blackbird sightings.			3
Maintain log of rusty blackbird sightings habitats.			3
Maintain updated GIS data layers for rusty blackbirds.		2	
Implement protocol to control tartarian honeysuckle in woods.			3
From 9.3.3.1. Terrestrial Habitat Actions			
Annually develop food plot plan.			3
Implement food plot plan.			3
Cultural Resources reviews planting existing food plots.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews actions to create new food plots.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews glyphosate-treatment areas.	1		
DPTMS reviews glyphosate-treatment operations.		2	
Maintain compliance with regulations concerning baiting.	1		
Mow alfalfa food plots once in July.			3
Mow alfalfa food plots once in August.			3
Apply glyphosate to smooth brome, non-native grass areas.			3
Clean and set out nesting structures for eastern bluebird.			3
Clean and set out nesting structures for purple martin.			3
From 9.3.4.1. Pond and Lake Management Actions			
Place discarded Christmas trees into fishing ponds.			3
Remove trees from pond dams, as needed.			3

Modify Rush Pond to hold water.			3
Control cattails in fishing ponds.			3
Implement measures to correct fish populations, as needed.			3
Renovate existing, degraded ponds.			3
Modify Beck Pond to keep largemouth bass from Wind Creek.			3
Remove fish in Beck Pond prior to breaking of the dam.			3
From 9.3.5.1. Stream Management Actions			
Repair stream filter strips, as needed.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews filter strip planting activities.	1		
Reduce silt transport during construction actions.	1		
From 9.3.6.1. Wetlands Management Actions			
Plant native grasses adjacent to wetlands.			3
Historic Architect reviews grass planting and maintenance actions.	1		
Perform NEPA and obtain permits, as needed.	1		
Seasonally draw-down and reflood shallow-water wetlands.			3
Manage Firebreak 3-11 as an ephemeral or vernal pool wetland.			3
Create small vernal pools.			3
From 9.3.7.1. Nuisance Animal Control Management Actions			
Obtain permits to handle migratory birds.	1		
Cultural Resources reviews animal and insect removal from buildings.	1		
Obtain permits to take nests (depredation).	1		
Transport injured raptors to rehabilitators.			3
Investigate calls concerning fledgling birds.	1		
Conduct non-lethal harassment to move large roosts.		2	
Use toxic bait to control starlings and pigeons in hangars.		2	
Use a pellet rifle to take problem, non-native birds.	1		
Install bird exclusion apparatus on buildings.	1		
Remove non-native bird nests, when problem.	1		
Survey cantonment areas for problem coyotes and foxes.		2	
Remove bold coyotes.		2	
Educate residents to not play with kit foxes, as needed.			3
Respond to complaints of skunks, opossums and raccoons.		2	
Take captured feral cats and dogs to Vet Services.			3
Address problem beavers in wetlands.		2	
Exclude bats from buildings.		2	
Meet with landowners who complain of elk depredation.			3
Remove problem deer from the Custer Hill Golf Course.			3
Control gophers in cantonment areas.		2	
Remove problem ground squirrels and badgers.		2	
From 9.3.8.1. Cantonment Area Actions			
Prioritize fruit and seed producing trees, shrubs and plants.			3
Cultural Resources reviews plantings within the Historic District.	1		
Update urban forestry inventory, identifying hazard trees.	1		

Spray tree species for pest infestations, as needed.			3
Coordinate mosquito control with Preventive Medicine.	1		
Manage pest control contract.	1		
From 10.0. INVENTORY & MONITORING			
From 10.3.1. Flora Inventory and Monitoring			
ITAM monitors bare ground and vegetation cover.		2	
Conduct remote sensing to monitor soil disturbance.		2	
Monitor LRAM-repaired sites.		2	
ITAM uses drone to measure vegetation disturbance.			3
Conduct Forest stand inventories.			3
From 10.3.2.1. Fish			
Electroshock to sample fish in Moon Lake.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in Breakneck Lake.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in Beck Pond.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in Vinton Pond.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in LaGrange Pond.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in Avery Pond.			3
Electroshock to sample fish in Stone Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Dale Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Goens Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Pritchard Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Stortz Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Blue Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Gaches Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample fish in Rich Pond.			3
Every fifth year, electroshock to sample Funston Lake.			3
Write report of fish inventory.			3
From 10.3.2.2. Upland Game			
Spring whistle counts for bobwhite quail.			3
Spring crow counts for ring-necked pheasant.			3
Lek counts for greater prairie-chicken.			3
Conduct fall covey counts for northern bobwhite.			3
From 10.3.2.3. Big Game			
Elk aerial surveys each winter.		2	
Annual nocturnal deer spotlight surveys.		2	
From 10.3.2.4. Threatened & Endangered Species			
Surveys for least terns and piping plovers.	1		
Monitor existing sandbar habitat, update GIS map.	1		
Update GIS map.	1		
Float the Kansas and Republican rivers before July 1.	1		
If a nesting attempt is confirmed, weekly monitor it.	1		
Surveys in streams in which Topeka shiners are known.	1		
Surveys in streams without known Topeka shiners.	1		

Surveys for northern long-eared bats.	1		
From 10.3.2.5. Bald Eagles			
Search for nesting bald eagles.	1		
Monitor any active eagle nest.	1		
Notify the FWS of updates of nesting activity.	1		
Winter weekly survey of diurnal habitat.	1		
Monitor nocturnal roosts.	1		
From 10.3.2.6. Rare Species			
Survey for Henslow's sparrows.		2	
Document loggerhead shrike sightings.			3
Document regal fritillary sightings.		2	
Survey for regal fritillary butterflies in native prairies.		2	
Maintain data collected in a GIS database.		2	
Document Texas horned lizard sightings.		2	
Document rusty blackbird sightings.			3
Document white-faced ibis sightings.			3
Document black rail sightings.			3
From 10.3.2.7. Migratory Birds			
Conduct surveys for breeding birds.			3
Conduct Winter raptor surveys.			3
Monitor use of nesting structures.			3
Conduct Christmas Bird Count survey for winter birds.			3
From 10.3.2.8. Small Mammals			
Monitor use of bat roosting structures.			3
From 10.3.2.9. Amphibians and Reptiles			
Amphibian calling survey.			3
Installation wide survey in early May.			3
Annually survey vernal pools.			3
From 10.3.2.11. Invertebrate Surveys			
USDA-APHIS install traps for invasive, non-native insects.		2	
Inspect woodlands to determine spread of forest pests.		2	
From 10.3.3. Wildlife Harvest Monitoring			
Collect hunting harvest data.			3
Manage and update iSportsman web portal.			3
Collect fish harvest data via iSportsman.			3
Collect deer harvest data via iSportsman.		2	
Collect data from harvested spring turkeys.			3
Write spring turkey harvest report.			3
From 10.4. Out Year Projects			
Perform 10-year update of floristic PLS.		2	
Update sericea lespedeza coverage.	1		
Perform 10 year update of Forest PLS.			3
PLS of Tamarisk invasion along the Kansas River.			3

Timber rattlesnake survey			3
Hognose snake survey			3
From 11.0. RESEARCH PROJECTS			
From 11.2.1. Academic Institution Research Projects			
KSU Coop Study to evaluate regal fritillary habitat on Fort Riley.			3
Support UNL SERDP global climate change study.			3
From 11.2.2. ORISE Research Projects			
Update forest ecosystem inventory.			3
From 11.2.3. Conservation Research Projects			
Evaluate effectiveness of glyphosate in smooth brome fields.			3
From 11.2.5. ITAM Research Projects			
From 12.0. LAW ENFORCEMENT			
Provide environmental education to outdoor recreationists.			3
Assist in collection of research and biological survey data.			3
Analyze violation trends.			3
Interact with KDWPT staff to investigate poaching cases.			3
Routinely patrol the installation.		2	
Check recreationists for licenses and bag and creel limits.			3
Special operations, such as check points and decoy deer.			3
Obtain in-service training.			3
From 13.0. Environmental Awareness			
From 13.1.1. Military Personnel Awareness			
Enhance education within the rare species management plans.	1		
ITAM materials on-line to attendees of Range Safety Officer Course.		2	
Provide natural resources information at Range Safety Officer Course.		2	
Provide Hazardous Plants and Animals briefings.		2	
Unscheduled opportunity to speak on environmental protection.		2	
From 13.2.1. Community Outreach Actions			
Submit news articles to the Fort Riley Post.			3
PAO events for "In-Step with Fort Riley", a television program.			3
Submit a weekly column to the Fort Riley Post.			3
Distribute news releases through the Public Affairs Office.		2	
Honor requests for radio station interviews.			3
Mail information and educational materials to requesters.			3
Produce publications to Fort Riley outdoor recreationists.			3
Distribute publications produced by other organizations.			3
Present talks to organizations, as requested.			3
Provide programs to school groups, as requested.			3
Provide information to the Fort Riley Outdoorsman Group.			3
Support Children's Fishing Derbies.			3
From 14.0. OUTDOOR RECREATION			
From 14.1. Quality of Life			

Support at least 5,000 hunting trips.			3
Support at least 20,000 angling days.			3
From 14.3.2. Access Procedures			
Manage open area notifications via iSportsman.		2	
Operate self-service check-in/out via iSportsman.			3
Distribute vehicle access permits.		2	
From 14.4.1.2. Deer			
Establish deer season dates and hunting regulations.		2	
Establish and print deer hunting fact sheet.			3
From 14.4.1.3. Elk			
Cooperate with KDWPT in elk permit numbers and season dates.			3
From 14.4.1.4. Turkey			
Provide spring turkey hunting fact sheet			3
From 14.4.1.5. Furbearer			
Update the annual Fort Riley Trapping Fact Sheet.			3
Issue trapping permits.			3
From 14.5.1. Sport Fish			
Stock 8,000-13,000 lbs of harvestable channel catfish.			3
Stock fingerling largemouth bass, as needed.			3
Stock 12,000 lbs of harvestable rainbow trout.			3
Mow around fishing ponds.			3
Stock large predatory fish to control population imbalances.			3
Close any water body for environmental concerns.	1		
From 14.9. QOL Management Actions			
Seek partnerships to leverage installation funds.		2	
Manage income from the sales of hunting permits.			3
Provide information to recreational users.			3
Provide general recreational briefing for all recreational users on the installation.		2	
Provide species specific briefing for all deer, elk and spring turkey hunters.		2	
Provide informational materials to recreational users.			3
Provide staff to interact with customers as resources allow.			3
Conduct hunter education classes.			3
Conduct boating safety courses (DFMWR performs).			3
Manage recreational access			3
Manage archery range			3
Operate fuelwood program			3
From 15.0. IMPLEMENTATION			
From 15.4. Program Administration Costs			
Personnel salaries (government and contractor)		2	
Natural resources management supplies and equipment		2	

Providing routine computer upgrades		2	
Updating GIS		2	
Obtaining updated aerial photography		2	
Provision of required training		2	

16.0 NATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY ACT

The National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) of 1969, as amended, was created to identify negative environmental effects from Federally-funded projects and activities, and then provide a decision mechanism as to whether the project or activity should proceed. Any Federally-funded action that could have an impact on human health, any natural system (air, water, soil, plant, animal, or other resources) or any social or economic system (to include Environmental Justice), must have some level of environmental analysis to determine its effects.

NEPA and Natural Resources Management

Natural resources activities, including implementation of this INRMP, must be properly planned, coordinated, and documented using NEPA. All natural resources management activities are considered and implemented according to the requirements of NEPA. Appropriate NEPA documentation for this plan will be completed following its approval by the USFWS, KDWPT, and Fort Riley's Garrison Commander prior to implementation of the INRMP. Fort Riley will use the lowest level of appropriate NEPA documentation to minimize paperwork. This INRMP will only be implemented if that NEPA documentation finds no significant adverse impacts. During implementation of this INRMP, NEPA documentation will be prepared and maintained on file for actions that are directed by the INRMP but that are not specifically described in the INRMP prior to their accomplishment.

17.0 ACRONYMS

ACUB	Army Compatible Use Buffer
AGL	Above Ground Level
APHIS	Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service
AR	Army regulation
ATV	All-terrain vehicle
BCC	Birds of Conservation Concern
BRAC	Base Realignment and Closure
CACTF	Combined Arms Collective Training Facility
CEC	Commission for Environmental Cooperation
CERL	United States Army Construction and Engineering Research Laboratory
CO-OP Unit	Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit
CVB	Central Violation Bureau
DES	Directorate of Emergency Services
DMPRC	Digital Multipurpose Range Complex
DMPTR	Digital Multipurpose Training Range
DPTMS	Directorate of Planning, Training, Mobilization and Scheduling
DPW	Directorate of Public Works
DoD	Department of Defense
EO	Executive Order
FORSCOM	U. S. Army Forces Command
FR	Fort Riley Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
gpm	Gallons per minute
ha	Hectares
IAW	In Accordance With
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan
ICT4	Incident Commanders Type IV
IMCOM	Installation Management Command
INRMP	Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan
IPM	Integrated Pest Management
IPMP	Fort Riley's Integrated Pest Management Plan
ITAM	Integrated Training Area Management
KBS	Kansas Biological Survey
KDHE	Kansas Department of Health and the Environment
KDWPT	Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism
KSU	Kansas State University
LURs	Land Use Regulations
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LMP	Landscape Master Plan
LRAM	Land Rehabilitation and Maintenance
MAAF	Marshall Army Airfield
MEDDAC	Medical Activity
mgd	Million gallons per day
MOU	Memorandum of understanding
NCO	Non-commissioned Officer

NEPA	National Environmental
NM	Nautical Miles
NOTAMS	Notices to Airmen
NRCS	Natural Resources Conservation Service
OMA	Operation, Management and Administration
ORISE	Oak Ridge Institute for Science and Education
PA	Programmatic Agreement
P.L.	Public Law
PLS	Planning Level Survey
RMEF	Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation
RTLA	Range and Training Land Assessment
RxB2	Burn Boss Type II
SAR	Species at Risk
SERDP	Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program
SHPO	Kansas' State Historic Preservation Officer
SINC	Species in Need of Conservation
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SRA	Sustainable Range Awareness
T&E	Threatened & Endangered
TRI	Training Requirements Integration
TSI	Timber stand improvement
UCMJ	Uniform Code of Military Justice
USAEC	United States Army Environmental Command
UNL	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
U.S.C.	United States Code
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USFWS	U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service
WDC	Wildlife Damage Control
WNS	White-nose Syndrome
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

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APPENDIX A**Governing Conservation Laws and Executive Orders**

- Bald and Golden Eagle Protection (Eagle) Act of 1940 [16 USC 668]
- Bob Stump National Defense Authorization Act for FY 2003, Public Law 107-314
- Clean Air Act (CAA) (1955) [42 USC 7401]
- Clean Water Act (CWA) (1972) [33 USC 1251] [PL 92-500]
- Conservation and Rehabilitation Program on Military and Public Lands (PL 93-452)
- Conservation Programs on Military Reservations (Sikes Act) [16 USC 670] [PL 86-797]
- Emergency Wetlands Resources Act of 1986 [16 USC 3901]
- Endangered Species Act (ESA) [PL 93-205]
- Federal Actions to Address Environmental Justice in Minority and Low-Income Populations (EO 12898)
- Erosion Protection Act [33 USC 426]
- Facilitation of Cooperative Cooperation [EO 13352]
- Facilitation of Hunting Heritage and Wildlife Conservation (EO 13443)
- Federal Insecticide, Fungicide and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA), as amended [7 USC 136]
- Federal Land Policy and Management Act of 1976 [43 USC 1701]
- Federal Noxious Weed Act of 1974, as amended [7 USC 2801]
- Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act of 1980 [16 USC 2901] [PL 96-366]
- Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act of 1934 [16 USC 661]
- Food, Agricultural, Conservation and Trade Act of 1990 (Pesticide Reporting) [7 USC 136I]
- Hunting, Fishing and Trapping on Military Lands
- Invasive Species [EO 13112]
- Lacey Act of 1900
- Migratory Bird Treaty Act (1918) [16 USC 703] [PL 65-186]
- Multiple-Use Sustained Yield Act of 1960 [16 USC 528]
- National Environmental Policy Act of 1969 (NEPA) [42 USC 4321] [PL 91-190]
- North American Wetlands Conservation Act [16 USC 4401]
- Outdoor Recreation on Federal Lands
- Outleasing for Grazing and Agriculture on Military Lands [10 USC 2667]
- Protection and Enhancement of Environmental Quality [EO 11514]
- Protection of Wetlands [EO11990]
- Recreational Fisheries [EO 12962]
- Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds (EO 13186)
- Safe Drinking Water Act of 1974, as amended [42 USC 300] [PL 93-523]
- Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 {P.L. 105-85}
- Soil and Water Resources Conservation Act of 1977 [16 USC 2001]
- Timber Sales on Military Lands [10 USC 2665]
- Watershed Protection and Flood Prevention Act [16 USC 1001] [33 USC 701]
- Exotic Organisms [EO 11987]
- Floodplain Management [EO 11988]
- Intergovernmental Coordination Act (1968) [42 USC 4231] [PL 90-577]
- Protection of Wetlands [EO 11990]

APPENDIX B

List of activities occurring on a regular basis at Fort Riley to conduct and support the installation's assigned training mission

Training Activities

Training activities typically scheduled each year include the following.

- **Douthit Gunnery Complex gunnery exercises.** Digital Multi-Purpose Range Complex (DMPRC) and Digital Multi-Purpose Training Complex gunnery exercises are typically scheduled six times annually. Each unit has up to 58 combat vehicles (M1 or M2) firing throughout the gunnery exercise. Battalions use approximately 58 square miles (145 square kilometers) of training area that includes the Impact Area and the western strip training area. Gunnery exercises include live-fire training events.
- **Range 18 gunnery exercises.** Gunnery exercises at Range 18 are typically scheduled seven times annually. Each unit has up to 58 combat vehicles (M1 or M2) firing throughout the gunnery exercise. Battalions use approximately 28 square miles (70 square kilometers) of training area during MPRC gunnery exercise training at Range 18 (including the impact area and training areas 6 through 9). Range 18 gunnery exercises are live-fire training events.
- **Brigade Battle Simulation Exercises.** Brigade Battle Simulation Exercises are typically scheduled six times annually. The simulated battles are conducted on computers inside the battle simulation center, and information is passed back and forth between the subordinated commanders and tactical operation centers. Brigades use approximately 1.6 square miles (4 square kilometers) of training area during a Brigade Battle Simulation Exercise. Brigade Battle Simulation Exercises are conducted without ammunition.
- **Company/Team Situational Training Exercise.** Company/Team Situational Training Exercises are typically scheduled twice annually. These exercises are conducted to prepare the subordinate units within the brigade, which is scheduled to conduct a National Training Center rotation. A brigade may have up to 174 combat vehicles (M1 or M2), along with its combat support units, maneuvering throughout the training area during the exercise. Thus, brigades use approximately 40 square miles (100 square kilometers) of maneuver training area during Company/Team Situational Training Exercises. Company/Team Situational Training Exercises are blank-fire training events.
- **Field Artillery External Evaluation.** Field Artillery External Evaluations are typically scheduled twice each year. During these Evaluations, Field Artillery battalions evaluate their M109 howitzer crews, fire direction centers, and forward observers on Artillery tables and call for fire procedures. Field Artillery battalions may have up to 24 M109 howitzers firing throughout the exercise. Battalions use approximately 44 square miles (110 square kilometers) of training area during Field Artillery External Evaluations (including the Impact Area and Training Areas 5 through 16). Field Artillery External Evaluations are live-fire training exercises.
- **Engineer/Field Artillery MPRC and Range 18 gunnery training.** Douthit and Range 18 gunnery-training exercises are typically scheduled six times for Engineer/Field Artillery use each year. Engineer and Field Artillery battalions qualify their combat vehicle crews on the

50 caliber machine gun tables. Each unit has up to 34 combat vehicles (M113 or M109) firing throughout the gunnery training. Battalions use approximately 28 square miles (70 square kilometers) of training area during Range 18 gunnery training, including the impact area and training areas 6 through 9. During Douthit Complex gunnery training, battalions use approximately 58 square miles (145 square kilometers) of training area, including the impact area and the western strip training areas. Douthit Complex and Range 18 gunnery training exercises are live-fire training events.

- **Annual Training (AT).** Only one annual training period is scheduled during most years. During an annual training period, a brigade-sized unit uses all of Fort Riley's training areas and ranges. A brigade may have up to 174 combat vehicles (M1 or M2), along with its combat support units, maneuvering throughout Fort Riley training areas. AT periods use approximately 126 square miles (315 square kilometers) of training area, including both of the impact areas. AT periods are both live-fire and blank-fire training events.
- **Expert Infantryman's Badge and Expert Field Medical Badge training events.** Expert Infantryman's Badge and Expert Field Medical Badge training events are each typically scheduled once a year. Infantry and medical Soldiers participate in the training and testing of common tasks expected of each. Combat vehicles (M1 or M2) are not used to support either event. Both events require approximately 1.6 square miles (4 square kilometers) of training area. Soldiers participating in both events are required to qualify expert with their individual weapon prior to the training event. Both training events are conducted with a small amount of blank ammunition.
- **Platoon Situational Training Exercises.** Each battalion conducts Platoon Situational Training Exercises to prepare for Company/Team Situational Training Exercises (which, as discussed above, are typically scheduled twice each year). Platoon Situational Training Exercises last typically three weeks and precede each Company/Team Situational Training Exercise. A battalion may have up to 58 combat vehicles (M1 or M2) maneuvering throughout the training area during the exercise. Battalions use approximately 18 square miles (45 square kilometers) of maneuver training area during Platoon Situational Training Exercises. Platoon Situational Training Exercises are blank-fire training events.
- **Combat Aviation Brigade Training Exercises.** Rotary wing aircraft operations on Fort Riley include Helicopter Landing Zone operations and Nap of the Earth flight operations, wherein aircraft may fly as low as 3 feet above ground level. Aircraft also conduct firing exercises on the Douthit Gunnery Complex Screening Range. Aircraft conduct training flights over both government- and private-owned lands, generally at 500 feet above ground level or higher. Fort Riley's CAB typically executes 21,200 helicopter flight hours annually and air traffic counts in and around the airfield usually exceed 10,000 a month.

Support Activities

Many "ongoing activities" support the public works and commercial service functions required to allow people to live and work on the installation. Such activities are similar to those conducted in any non-military community of equal size, and include the following types:

- **Administrative operations.**
- **Airfield operations.**
- **Facilities repair, maintenance, construction, and alteration.**
- **Fuel and petroleum storage and dispensing.**
- **Grounds maintenance.**
- **Hospital, medical, and dental clinic operations.**
- **Installation and community support services.**
- **Natural and cultural resources management and environmental protection.**
- **Recreation.**
- **Road and right-of-way maintenance.**
- **Utility operations including infrastructure maintenance, repair, construction, and alteration.**
- **Warehousing and supply storage.**
- **Vehicle and equipment maintenance and repair.**

APPENDIX C

Rare Species Management Plans For Fort Riley, Kansas

1.0 EAGLE MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

This management plan is based on and is consistent with the Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act (Eagle Act) of 1940. It is consistent with the National Bald Eagle Management Guidelines. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) developed these Guidelines to advise land managers with bald eagles when and under what circumstances the protective provisions of the Eagle Act may apply to their activities. The Guidelines are intended to help people minimize impacts to bald eagles, particularly where they may constitute “take¹” or “disturbance²” of eagles, which is prohibited by the Eagle Act. Before performing any action that may take or disturb bald eagles, the proponent must first coordinate with the USFWS through the Fort Riley Conservation Branch, Directorate of Public Works.

Eagle Information

1.1.1. Description

Bald Eagle. Adult bald eagles are unmistakable in the field, with their white heads and tails contrasting sharply with the dark brown body plumage. Immature bald eagles are all dark with some degree of white mottling occurring on the body, and may be confused with golden eagles, turkey vultures and osprey.

Golden Eagle. Golden eagles are as large as bald eagles, much larger than other raptors. All ages of birds display a golden nape, from which the species derives its name. Adult golden eagles are all dark, while juvenile birds typically have white wing patches and a white tail with a dark, terminal band. In flight, golden eagles show a relatively small head soar with wings slightly in a dihedral, whereas bald eagles have a larger head and keep wings nearly flat when soaring.

1.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

Bald eagles are most frequently observed using riverine or lacustrine habitats, particularly those with large trees in close proximity. Bald eagles feed primarily on fish, with injured or sick waterfowl and carrion also being taken as opportunity presents. Generally, prey availability is not a problem as long as eagles have access to open water feeding areas.

Isolation and protection from human disturbances are factors that generally appear important to bald eagles. The amount of isolation necessary is not completely clear. Stalmaster and Newman (1978) recommended protecting areas 75-100 m wide to minimize disturbances to wintering eagles. The tolerance to human disturbance appears to vary greatly among individual bald eagles

¹ The Act defines “take” as “pursue, shoot, shoot at, poison, wound, kill, capture, trap, collect, molest or disturb.”

² “Disturbance” means: “to agitate or bother a bald or golden eagle to a degree that causes, or is likely to cause, based on the best scientific information available, 1) injury to an eagle, 2) a decrease in its productivity, by substantially interfering with normal breeding, feeding, or sheltering behavior, or 3) nest abandonment”.

(Mike Lockhart, USFWS, pers. comm.), with older birds, generally, being more intolerant than juveniles or subadults (Stalmaster and Newman 1978).

Specific perch sites preferred by bald eagles vary depending on time of day and weather conditions. Selected daytime perches are most often the tallest trees, particularly those with open branches that are near water.

Bald eagle roosting habitat consists of tall trees that provide protection from the wind. Eagles may use several roosts on a single wintering site, with use of the different roosts dependent upon weather conditions (Edwards 1969, Ingram 1965). Communal roosts are used annually.

Bald eagle nesting habitat is similar to its wintering habitat. A good area has a suitable nest tree, many perches that provide a view of the territory, and a feeding area. Nest trees are large, dominant trees, and are relatively isolated from human disturbance. Primary habitat for bald eagles on Fort Riley exists in the riverine woodlands that border the Kansas, Republican, and Smoky Hill rivers, as well as the shorelines of Milford Lake which have large trees.

Three communal roost sites have been identified on Fort Riley; two along the Kansas River, and the other located along Madison Creek upstream from Milford Lake. The number of eagles using the roosts varies nightly. The highest documented count occurred in 1999, when 388 bald eagles were counted along the Kansas River roost. The highest number of eagles counted at the Madison Creek roost was 253. Roosting bald eagles are generally expected to be in the Fort Riley area from about October 15 to about March 31.

Eagles generally have returned to the same roosting areas on Fort Riley (1993-2015). The primary river roost has suffered a loss of trees due to high water events, straight line winds, ice storms, and a tornado. As a result, roosting eagles have moved approximately 200 m downstream. In 2009, a pair of eagles built a nest at the primary roost site. On most nights, roosting eagles moved upstream along the Smoky Hill River, or further downstream on the Kansas River. On extremely cold nights, however, many eagles returned to the main roost even though nesting eagles were present.

In 2004, a nesting pair of eagles established their territory in the Madison Creek Area. Once the nest was established, this area was no longer used as a communal roost. It is not known to where this roost has moved.

Six locations with eagle nests occur on and around Fort Riley. The first was the 2004 nest built along Madison Creek. Three eagle nests now exist in this area on Fort Riley, and one of the nests has been active annually since 2004. The second area with an eagle nest is on Corps of Engineers property along Farnum Creek, adjacent to Fort Riley. This nest was first used in 2005, was occupied annually for eleven years, but is unoccupied in 2016. Meanwhile, a new, active bald eagle nest was located on Fort Riley (TA 54) in 2016, approximately 3.5 miles from the Farnum Creek nest. Fort Riley pursued and obtained an Eagle Nest Take Permit for and subsequently removed the TA 54 nest on November 6, 2017 due to the location of the nest and proximity to military training. Potentially, these are the same birds relocated onto the installation. The fourth area is around the confluence of the Kansas River, where four nests exist. Two nests are along the Kansas River on Fort Riley, and two nests are along the Smoky Hill River just upstream from the installation. One pair of nesting eagles have been active in this locale annually since 2009. The

fifth eagle nest location exists approximately one mile west of the installation along the old channel of the Republican River below Milford Dam. No nests from this area are located on Fort Riley. The sixth eagle nest location is approximately one half mile to the east of the installation along the Kansas river on property owned and managed by the Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism. No nests from this area are located on Fort Riley.

Golden eagles are a western bird, nesting in mountains and on cliffs. In migration and during winter, the species will move into valleys and plains, and infrequently is observed on Fort Riley. Golden eagles primarily eat small mammals and birds, but will also consume snakes and carrion.

Eagle Conservation Goals

1.1.3. Establish procedures to protect bald eagles while they are present on Fort Riley

1.1.4. Protect bald eagle nest and roost locations on Fort Riley

Eagle Management Prescriptions and Actions

1.1.5. Protect eagles from human-induced injury and mortality

Many well-publicized laws and regulations exist to protect eagles against shooting or trapping, and to minimize lead-poisoning by requiring the use of non-toxic shot when hunting waterfowl. Additional restrictions against shooting eagles seem unwarranted, as does further education about these restrictions.

Other hazards to eagles include electrocution on power lines, tower and line strikes, and exposure to chemicals. Many transmission lines, poles, and towers exist on Fort Riley that may pose some degree of threat to eagles.

1.1.5.1. Prescription. Minimize the risk of eagle electrocution on power lines

Action. To safeguard against eagle electrocution, any projects to construct new or modify existing electric transmission lines on Fort Riley will be reviewed by the Conservation Branch prior to project implementation. Techniques protecting eagles from electrocution employing industry-accepted best management practices will be incorporated into the project designs when needed.

1.1.5.2. Prescription. Minimize the risk of eagle collisions with aerial structures

Action. Techniques employing industry-accepted best management practices are available to mark or otherwise design aerial structures so that the hazard of eagles colliding with them is eliminated or greatly reduced. Line markers, such as aviation balls and colored spiral dampers, and similar markers for towers and guy lines will be used as needed to make these structures more visible to eagles. Any projects to construct new or modify existing aerial structures on Fort Riley will be reviewed for need of re-siting or using line markers, incorporating guidelines established by the USFWS for the siting of communication towers and wind-powered generators. Areas of particular concern are within one mile of a river or Milford Lake shoreline because eagles use rivers and lakes as travel lanes.

1.1.5.3. Prescription. Minimize nesting conflicts on human-made structures

Action. Where bald eagles are likely to nest in human-made structures (e.g., cell phone towers), and such use could impede operation or maintenance of the structures or jeopardize the safety of the eagles, the structures will be equipped with either (1) devices engineered to discourage bald eagles from building nests, or (2) nesting platforms that will safely accommodate bald eagle nests without interfering with structure performance.

1.1.5.4. Prescription. Protect eagles from chemical impacts

Action. The storage and use of all pesticides, herbicides, fertilizers, and other chemicals on Fort Riley shall be conducted in strict accordance with label directions and restrictions. All general use and military chemicals on Fort Riley shall be used, stored, and disposed of in accordance with directions, restrictions and/or guidelines established by the manufacturer and/or Department of the Army.

1.1.6. Protect eagles from human activity

Disruption, destruction, or obstruction of roosting and foraging areas can negatively affect bald eagles. Disruptive activities in or near eagle foraging areas can interfere with feeding, reducing chances of survival. Wintering bald eagles rely on established roost sites where the eagles are somewhat sheltered from the wind and weather. Activities that permanently alter communal roost sites and important foraging areas can altogether eliminate the elements that are essential for feeding and sheltering bald eagles. Where a human activity agitates or bothers eagles to the degree that causes injury or substantially interferes with breeding, feeding, or sheltering behavior and causes, or is likely to cause, a loss of productivity or nest abandonment, the conduct of the activity constitutes a violation of the Eagle Act's prohibition against disturbing eagles.

Eagles are unlikely to be disturbed by routine use of roads, homes, and other facilities where such use pre-dates the eagles' successful nesting, roosting and foraging activity in a given area. Therefore, in most cases *ongoing* existing uses may proceed with the same intensity with little risk of disturbing eagles. Thus, vehicle traffic on established, hardened roads and bridges, Army aircraft flight on established arrival and departure routes, and established Army aircraft traffic pattern flight within the protected area are not subject to this requirement.

1.1.6.1. Prescription. Protect foraging eagles on Fort Riley from disturbance

Action. "*Minimum disturbance*" buffer zones are in effect in primary bald eagle habitat on Fort Riley. Based on the research of Stalmaster and Newman (1978), the buffer zones extend 75 m from the normal high-water mark along each riverbank (Exhibit C.1). Additional restrictions may be established around any large concentration of foraging bald eagles on lands controlled by Fort Riley. Application of those restrictions will depend on the size and location of the roost and the likelihood of the proposed action to cause significant disturbance

Certain exceptions to these general "*minimum disturbance*" buffer zones are established.

- South of Main Post (centered on grid PU 915 258), the 75 m "*minimum disturbance*" buffer zone is adjusted so that it does not extend across Stuart Avenue, and does not include Buildings 246, 248 or 252, or the parking lots of these buildings (Exhibit C.2).

- At Marshall Army Airfield, the “*minimum disturbance*” buffer zone is adjusted so that it does not contain family housing units and other buildings, or the parking and roadways associated with these buildings (Exhibit C.3).
- Portions of the Union Pacific Railroad's right of way lie within the minimum disturbance buffer zone. Activities of the Union Pacific Railroad on that right of way are not controlled by Fort Riley.

“*Minimum disturbance*” buffer zones are not a sanctuary in which no human activity occurs. Rather, they are areas in which activities are reviewed to prevent disturbance of bald eagles. All activities including: construction and maintenance, demolition, off-road operation of vehicles, timber harvest, detonation of explosives and recreational pursuits that are proposed to occur within the “*minimum disturbance*” buffer zone will be reviewed by the Conservation Branch for potential impacts to bald eagles. Coordination with the USFWS is not required if the Conservation Branch determines that the action is not likely to take or disturb bald eagles.

1.1.6.2. **Prescription. Protect roosting eagles on Fort Riley from disturbance**

Action. Additional restrictions may be established around any active bald eagle roost on lands controlled by Fort Riley. Application of those restrictions will depend on the size and location of the roost and the likelihood of the proposed action to cause significant disturbance

1.1.6.3. **Prescription. Protect nesting eagles**

Action. A “*no disturbance*” buffer zone will be established around any active eagle nest on lands controlled by Fort Riley. The size, duration and limitations of the zone will be determined after contact with the USFWS.

Fort Riley cannot impose buffer zones on adjacent lands to protect nesting eagles. However, access through Fort Riley property to adjacent lands on which nesting occurs will be controlled.

1.1.6.4. **Prescription. Educate installation’s personnel about requirement to protect eagles**

Action. Information is provided to aviators through Local NOTAMS (Notices to AirMen) regarding eagle concentrations and behaviors in an attempt to minimize aircraft conflicts with eagles. Additional programs will be developed, as needed.

1.1.7. Protect and conserve eagle habitat on Fort Riley

The presence of bald eagles on Fort Riley depends primarily on maintenance of riparian woodland habitat that provides the isolation from humans and perches required by the species. Surveys demonstrate that bald eagles utilize virtually every stretch of the Kansas, Republican, and Smoky Hill rivers' riparian woodlands and the tree-lined, Milford Lake shoreline within the installation’s boundaries. Golden eagles use open fields for hunting and perch on the ground or in trees. Habitat is not considered limiting for golden eagles, and no specific measures to protect or create habitat will be undertaken.

1.1.7.1. Prescription. Protect bald eagle nest and roost trees on Fort Riley

Action. Trees whose presence is required to maintain the integrity of communal eagle roosts or nest sites on Fort Riley will be protected and preserved by retaining mature trees and old growth stands, particularly within ½ mile from water. The strategy for riverine forests is to increase the width of forested floodplain corridors and promote large, mature to overmature stands. These stands will have high canopy closure and an open to intermediate sub-canopy to favor species typically occurring in floodplain forests.

Action. Avoid clear cutting or removal of overstory trees within 100 m of a nest at any time.

Action. Selective thinning and other silviculture management practices designed to conserve or enhance habitat, including prescribed burning close to the nest tree, will be undertaken outside of the breeding season. Precautions will be taken to prevent crown fire or fire climbing the nest tree.

Action. Timber harvesting operations, including road construction and chain saw operations, will be avoided within 200 m of a nest during the breeding season.

Eagle Monitoring Plan

1.1.8. Search for bald eagle nesting attempts on Fort Riley

Surveys for eagle nesting attempts on Fort Riley will be conducted each year. Surveyors will scan riparian timber to look for pairs of eagles and also for nests.

1.1.9. Monitor nesting pairs of bald eagles found on Fort Riley

If an active nest is confirmed, it will be monitored to determine the status and outcome of the nesting attempt. Monitoring will be carried out from a vantage point as far from the nest as possible that allows good visibility with optical equipment. Activity of the eagles, including any indications of stick placement, copulation, incubation, or feeding will be documented at each visit. The USFWS Kansas Field Office will be notified promptly upon the discovery of any suspected nesting bald eagles on Fort Riley.

1.1.10. Monitor wintering eagles on Fort Riley

Diurnal habitat of bald eagles on Fort Riley will be surveyed weekly when wintering eagles are expected to be present (about October 15 to about March 31). Information recorded will be number and age ratios of eagles at specific locations, weather conditions, snow or ice cover, and time of day. Roosts will be monitored when bald eagles are in the area. This time is variable from year to year, but generally occurs from about October 15 to about March 31. Monitoring frequency for each roost will vary. Species-specific surveys for golden eagles will not occur, but all incidental sightings of this species will be recorded and maintained within GIS databases.

Literature Cited

Edwards, C.C. 1969. Winter behavior and population dynamics of American eagles in western Utah. Ph.D. Thesis, Brigham Young Univ. Provo, UT. 142 pp.

Ingram, T.N. 1965. Wintering bald eagles at Guttenburg, IA-Cassville, WI, 1964-65. IA Birdlife. 35:66-78.

Stalmaster, M.V., and J.R. Newman. 1978. Behavioral responses of wintering bald eagles to human activity. J. Wildl. Manage. 42:506-513.

2.0 LEAST TERN AND PIPING PLOVER MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

This management plan is based on and is consistent with the Endangered Species Act of 1973 (ESA), the Kansas Endangered Species and Nongame Conservation Act of 1975, and Army Regulations. This plan does not supersede ESA Section 7 consultation requirements with the USFWS or replace the need to obtain special permits from the KDWPT. Any action that may directly or indirectly affect the piping plover or least tern, or their preferred habitat, must be coordinated with the USFWS and KDWPT by the Conservation Branch.

Least Tern and Piping Plover Species Information

2.1.1. Description

Least Tern. The least tern is the smallest North American tern, 8-10 inches in size. Least terns have a black-capped crown with a white forehead patch and a black-tipped, orange or yellow bill during the breeding season.

Piping Plover. The piping plover is a tiny shorebird, 6-7 inches in size. Piping plovers have a back the color of dry sand. They have a white rump, breast, and belly. Breeding adults possess a black forehead patch, orange legs, a short, black-tipped, orange bill, and a black breast band, which may be complete or incomplete.

2.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The piping plover and least tern occur in the same types of habitats. Nesting habitat is usually unvegetated sandbars or islands that provide good visibility in wide, riverine channels (Sidle and Harrison 1989; Whyte 1985). Vegetation should not exceed 25% of the ground cover for optimal use. Both species' nests are shallow and inconspicuous depressions in an open, sandy area or gravelly patch. Least terns nest in colonies. Piping plovers nest as solitary pairs.

Both least terns and piping plovers use areas similar to their breeding habitats during migration. Least terns feed on small fish; piping plovers feed on aquatic invertebrates at or near the surface of the sand.

Conservation Branch personnel observed two piping plovers on Fort Riley in April, 1996, and one in September, 1996 (see INRMP, Exhibit 7.12). The piping plovers were observed on sandy beaches of both the Kansas and Republican rivers. Two least terns were observed along the Kansas River in May, 1996, and one in May, 1997. A least tern was observed in the former Military Marina area of Milford Lake in May, 2001. The birds were not seen on subsequent trips to the site.

River channelization, irrigation, and the construction of mainstem dams have eliminated much of the sandbar-nesting habitat used by these species throughout their range (Haig et al. 1988). These practices remove sandbars from river systems and degrade the sandbars that remain. Regulating river flow for navigation eliminates the scouring action of high water flow that removes vegetation from sandbars. The ensuing vegetation encroachment results in poor to no habitat on the remaining sandbars.

Least Tern and Piping Plover Conservation Goals

2.1.3. Protect individual least terns and piping plovers while they are present on Fort Riley**2.1.4. Protect least tern and piping plover habitat on Fort Riley**

Least Tern and Piping Plover Management Prescriptions and Actions

2.1.5. Protect individual least terns and piping plovers from human-induced injury

The presence of unmarked power lines, towers and other structures into which least terns and piping plovers may fly is hazardous. Many transmission lines, poles, and towers exist on Fort Riley. All may pose some degree of threat to these species. However, techniques are available to mark such structures to eliminate or greatly reduce the hazard.

Human disturbance at nesting areas may inhibit courtship, incubation and brooding behaviors, and can trample nests and destroy young.

2.1.5.1. Prescription. Minimize the risk of least tern or piping plover collisions with aerial structures

Action. Techniques are available to mark or otherwise design aerial structures so that the striking hazard is eliminated or greatly reduced. Line markers, such as aviation balls and colored spiral dampers, and similar markers for towers and guy lines may be used to make these structures more visible to least terns and piping plovers. Any projects to construct new or modify existing aerial structures on Fort Riley will be reviewed by Conservation Branch at least 30 days prior to project implementation to determine whether line markers are needed. Areas of particular concern are within one mile of a river or Milford Lake shoreline because these may be used as travel lanes.

2.1.5.2. Prescription. Protect least terns and piping plovers on nesting territories

Action. A "no disturbance" buffer zone will be established without delay around any piping plover or least tern pair that exhibits courtship or breeding behavior on lands controlled by Fort Riley. Nesting sites will be similarly protected from human disturbance. All human activity not specifically approved by the USFWS will be excluded from the buffer zone until two weeks after the adults and any young produced there leave the nest vicinity. The size of the zone will be determined after conference with the USFWS.

Fort Riley cannot impose buffer zones on adjacent lands to protect courtship or nesting. However, if Fort Riley controls access to those portions of the Kansas and Republican rivers where nesting or courtship activity occurs, Fort Riley will prohibit all access to the nesting site through the installation until said access is specifically approved by the USFWS.

2.1.6. Protect and maintain least tern and piping plover habitat

Least tern and piping plover observations along the Kansas and Republican rivers indicate the rivers' potential as migratory habitat. The Kansas River is state-designated critical habitat for both

species. Protecting and conserving least tern and piping plover habitat on Fort Riley requires protecting the habitat from adverse physical destruction.

2.1.6.1. Prescription. Protect existing riverine habitat

Action. All sandbars and shorelines of the Kansas and Republican rivers that are on Fort Riley are protected from adverse impacts. Adverse impacts include activities that result in channel destruction or alteration, or sandbar and beach destruction or alteration (impacts from water flow are excluded). The following activities are controlled within the normal river channel of the Kansas and Republican rivers on Fort Riley: construction; operations and maintenance activities; demolition; operation of vehicles; detonation of explosives; and recreational pursuits. Routine vehicle traffic on established bridges is not subject to this action. Fort Riley generally prohibits ORVs on installation lands, allowing them only in a small, non-riverine area.

2.1.6.2. Prescription. Educate Fort Riley personnel of the requirement to protect riverine habitat

Action. Programs will be developed, as needed, to publicize the requirements of riverine habitat conservation and off-limits areas to all Department of Army personnel and contractors, and outdoor enthusiasts, who work, train or recreate on Fort Riley.

Least Tern and Piping Plover Monitoring Plan

2.1.7. Map existing least tern and piping plover habitat on Fort Riley

The least tern and piping plover habitat map will document state-designated critical habitat and any location with a documented least tern or piping plover sighting.

Mapped information will be incorporated into the Conservation Branch and ITAM programs' Geographic Information Systems (GIS). This information will be consulted when planning actions for the operation and maintenance of the installation and tactical training events during Training Requirements Integration (TRI).

2.1.8. Search for least tern or piping plover nesting attempts on Fort Riley

The Kansas and Republican rivers on Fort Riley will be floated to search for nesting least terns and piping plovers. The survey should occur 2-3 weeks after the springtime high water flow has subsided. This period varies from year to year, but usually occurs after mid-June. Suitable habitat will be walked to better locate the cryptic-colored birds.

2.1.9. Monitor nesting least terns and/or piping plovers found on Fort Riley

Confirmed nests will be monitored weekly to determine their status and outcome. Monitoring will be carried out from a vantage point as far from the nests as possible that allows good visibility with optical equipment. Activity of the birds, including any indications of courtship feeding, copulation, incubation, or feeding of the young, will be documented at each visit.

The USFWS Regional Kansas Field and KDWPT offices will be notified promptly upon the discovery of any suspected nesting least terns or piping plovers on Fort Riley.

2.1.10. Monitor migrating least terns and piping plovers on Fort Riley

Least tern and piping plover habitat on Fort Riley will be surveyed every 7-10 days when migrating least terns and piping plovers are expected to be present (March 21 - May 31 and July 7 – September 15). Information recorded will be number of birds observed, location of birds, behavior of birds, and any bands or markings noticed on birds. Sightings will be reported to the USFWS Regional Kansas Field Office.

Literature Cited

Haig, S., W. Harrison, R. Lock, L. Pfanmuller, E. Pike, M. Ryan and J. Sidle. 1988. Recovery Plan for Great Lakes and Northern Great Plains Piping Plover.

Sidle, J.G., and W.A. Harrison. 1989. Recovery plan for the interior population of the least tern (*Sterna antillarum*). USFWS. 107 pp.

Whyte, A.J. 1985. Breeding ecology of the piping plover (*Charadrius melodus*) in central Saskatchewan. M.S. Thesis, Univ. Sask. Saskatoon, SK.

3.0 TOPEKA SHINER MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

This management plan is based on and is consistent with the ESA, the Kansas Nongame and Endangered Species Conservation Act of 1975 and Army Regulations. This plan does not supersede Section 7 consultation requirements with the USFWS, or replace the need to obtain special permits from the KDWPT. Any action that may directly or indirectly affect the Topeka shiner or its preferred habitat must be coordinated with the USFWS and KDWPT by the Conservation Branch, except under the circumstances described below.

Topeka Shiner Species Information

3.1.1. Description

The Topeka shiner grows to a length of 2.25 inches. Its body is silvery, with a dark streak along each side, a dark chevron mark at the base of the tail fin, and a reddish dorsal fin. Breeding males may change colors, with bodies turning blue and all fins turning red. The Topeka shiner's scales have a distinct cross-hatching outline. Topeka shiners may be confused with sand shiners, suckermouth minnows and creek chubs, other minnow species that have a dark spot at the base of their tail fins and/or crosshatched scales.

3.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The Topeka shiner typically occurs in small, low order³, prairie streams with high water quality and cool temperatures (USFWS 1993). These streams generally are perennial. However, Topeka shiners may also occur in streams that become intermittent during the summer. Streams containing Topeka shiners are relatively undisturbed. They have not been impounded or channelized and usually do not drain areas subject to high silt loads in water runoff (Drilling 1986). These streams usually have clear water with a predominantly gravel or sand substrate. There is little rooted aquatic vegetation associated with Topeka shiner populations (Minckley and Cross 1959, Cross and Collins 1975).

Habitat conditions become unsuitable for this species when increased water turbidity creates a silt layer along the streambed, excess nutrient enrichment leads to stream eutrophication, or stream dewatering eliminates stable water levels of pools (USFWS 1993). Reduction in water quality due to groundwater depletion, artificial regulation of flows, and certain agricultural practices are detrimental to this species (USFWS 1993).

Topeka shiners have been found in six streams on Fort Riley. These are Wildcat, Sevenmile, Silver, Honey, Wind and Little Arkansas (INRMP, Exhibit C.4).

KDWPT established state-designated critical habitat for the Topeka shiner to include the main stem and tributary reaches of Wildcat, Little Arkansas, and Sevenmile creeks in 2000. Although Kansas has not officially designated Silver, Wind and Honey creeks critical habitat for the Topeka

³ Stream order is a classification based on branching of streams. The smallest, unbranched, tributary streams that appear on a topographic, 7 1/2 minute quadrangle map (1:24,000 scale) are designated order 1.

shiner, these streams do have recent collection records (2008) and therefore are considered to be state-designated critical habitat for the Topeka shiner by KDWPT.

Topeka shiners have not been found in Rush, Timber and Madison creeks. No historical Topeka shiner collections are known from these three streams. These streams and Farnum Creek are not considered likely to support populations of Topeka shiners due to their discharge into Milford Lake. The USFWS (1998) cited mainstem reservoir development as a significant factor negatively affecting Topeka shiner populations. A recent study of fish fauna on Fort Riley found a definite “lake effect” influence on species in these streams (Quist 1999), where high populations of predatory fish inhibit the growth of native minnow populations. Milford Lake is not believed to be a “harbor” or “source” for Topeka shiners (Tabor pers. comm.). Consequently, Timber, Rush, Farnum and Madison creeks are not considered to contain Topeka shiner habitat.

Topeka shiners have not been found in Threemile, Fourmile and Forsyth creeks. However, all those streams, apparently, contain suitable habitat for the species and are interconnected with other streams where the Topeka shiner occurs. Consequently, they are considered potential habitat for the species. Exhibit C.4 shows the streams and drainages on Fort Riley that are considered as actual and potential Topeka shiner habitat.

3.1.3. Conservation Measures

Current conservation actions involve monitoring known Topeka shiner populations, maintaining habitat in watersheds containing these populations, and searching for additional populations. Reintroduction methodology is being developed.

Topeka Shiner Conservation Goals

3.1.4. Protect individual Topeka shiners present on Fort Riley

3.1.5. Maintain abundance and quality of Topeka shiner habitat

Topeka Shiner Management Prescriptions and Actions

3.1.6. Protect individual Topeka shiners from human-induced injury

Pesticides and other chemicals, if introduced into stream waters, may adversely affect Topeka shiners or the invertebrates upon which the fish feed. Mainstem reservoir developments and tributary impoundments have adversely impacted the species. Topeka shiner populations have been eliminated from streams both above and below dams following the construction of stream impoundments in Kansas and Missouri (USFWS 1993). Impoundment of streams is also deleterious to congeneric species of Topeka shiners (Winston et al. 1991). Pond and lake construction has several negative impacts. The dams eliminate the scouring floods that create pool habitat downstream and maintain a rocky, silt-free substrate (USFWS 1993). Upstream habitat may be converted to deep, open water habitat behind the dam. Upstream populations seeking refuge in the impoundment during drought may be eaten by predatory fish. These predatory fish also move upstream and downstream from the impoundment where they pose a predatory threat to Topeka shiners that did not naturally exist (USFWS 1993).

3.1.6.1. **Prescription: Protect Topeka shiner streams from pesticides and other chemicals**

Action: Compliance with the Clean Water Act, the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide and Rodenticide Act, DoD Directives and Army Regulations protect against chemical contamination. These laws and regulations provide sufficient protection for Topeka shiners.

A 100-foot no-spray buffer is in effect around all Topeka shiner streams during aerial spray events, to guard against the possibility of any pesticide entering the streams during these spray events. Aerial spraying is conducted to control sericea lespedeza and to reduce the number of annual forbs growing around targets on firing ranges.

3.1.6.2. **Prescription: Control construction of permanent, water impounding dams on streams of Fort Riley**

Action. Consultation with the USFWS and KDWPT will occur during the planning process for construction of water impounding structures on any stream identified in Exhibit C.4.

3.1.6.3. **Prescription: Protect Topeka shiners from bait-fish seining**

Action. Prohibit bait-fish seining in Fort Riley Regulation 210-15 (Fort Riley Hunting and Fishing Regulations). Enforcement will be conducted by MP game wardens and Fort Riley's civilian conservation officers. Educate Fort Riley anglers of the prohibition, and post in fishing brochures and on the Fort Riley Internet Page.

3.1.7. Protect, maintain, and restore small stream habitat

Topeka shiners require streams with high water quality to meet all of their needs throughout the life cycle (USFWS 1993). High water quality requires minimal disturbance to the streambed. Stream quality also is directly related to maintaining a vegetative filter strip along the streambed to capture soil runoff before it reaches the stream. Protection and maintenance of high quality water in all streams will be a priority.

3.1.7.1. **Prescription. Prevent degradation of existing streams**

Action. All streams shown in Exhibit C.4 that have recent documentation of Topeka shiners (currently Wind, Wildcat, Sevenmile, Honey, Silver and Little Arkansas) will be protected from adverse impacts. Adverse impacts include activities that result in channel destruction or alteration, increase water turbidity or eutrophication, or destroy vegetation filter strips. The following activities will be controlled within 50 feet on either side of the streams shown in Exhibit C.4: construction, operations and maintenance activities, demolition, operation of vehicles, timber harvest, detonation of explosives, and recreational pursuits. Vehicle traffic on improved stream crossings and bridges are not subject to this action. Actions affecting all other streams shown in Exhibit C.4 (currently Threemile, Fourmile, and Wind) will not require consultation with the USFWS and KDWPT if Conservation Branch deems the action is not likely to adversely affect Topeka shiners.

3.1.7.2. **Prescription. Educate Fort Riley personnel about the requirement to protect Topeka shiner habitat**

Action. A brochure describing Threatened and Endangered (T&E) species on Fort Riley has been developed. In the summer of 2003, Conservation Branch became permitted by the USFWS to display live Topeka shiners. The fish were acquired from a long-term experiment at the University of Kansas. A sign explaining the display and an informative bookmark are part of the display. Information regarding the Topeka shiners has been placed on the Fort Riley web page.

The prohibition of bait fish seining has been posted in fishing brochures and on the Fort Riley Internet Page. Additional programs will be developed, as needed, to publicize the requirements of Topeka shiner habitat conservation to all Department of Army personnel and contractors who work or train on Fort Riley.

The streams on Fort Riley identified as providing apparently suitable habitat for Topeka shiners have been incorporated into the GIS database. This information will be consulted when planning actions for the operation and maintenance of the installation and tactical training events.

3.1.7.3. **Prescription. Restore degraded stream habitat**

Action. Streams shown in Exhibit C.4 will be restored, as needed, by reshaping damaged banks or channels, establishing revetments, or reestablishing vegetative filter strips. When applicable, restoration projects will incorporate NaturalChannel Design and identify reference reaches.

Action. Modify Beck Pond to reduce escape of largemouth bass into Wind Creek. Remove fish from Beck Pond prior to the breaking of the pond dam.

Action. Remove largemouth bass and green sunfish over 5" in length from Wind Creek.

3.1.7.4. **Prescription: Implement USFWS non-discretionary terms and conditions**

Action. Fort Riley consulted with the USFWS and KDWPT in 2002 concerning road maintenance actions that may occur in or nearby streams that contain, or potentially contain, Topeka shiners. Because the USFWS made a determination that those actions may adversely affect the Topeka shiner, the USFWS provided in a Biological Opinion non-discretionary terms and conditions which implement the reasonable and prudent measures that are necessary and appropriate to minimize the take of Topeka shiners. Those non-discretionary terms and conditions are:

- During any activities utilizing a rock translocation option in a known Topeka shiner stream, extreme caution should be exercised to avoid damage to the natural stream channel and its habitat. If rock retrieval from the downstream channel using a motor grader blade is determined likely to adversely impact habitat within the stream channel, this option should be avoided. In such a case, the rock which has been moved off the hardened ford by streamflow should be left in the downstream channel, and new rock used to rehabilitate the ford.
- During installation and/or maintenance of either a culvert or a hardened low water ford, the streambed gradient should be unaltered. The finished installation should not back water

upstream of the structure, create any measurable plunge pool on the downstream side, nor create a ponded or pooled situation over the face of the crossing.

- Construction activities below the water's surface shall not be permitted in Topeka shiner streams during the spawning period of May 15 to July 31, inclusive. This prohibition includes any known Topeka shiner stream. If ongoing surveys discover Topeka shiners in other streams on Fort Riley, notification shall be made to the Service and these streams shall be added to the prohibited list. The lone exception to this condition is if a documented emergency situation exists, where inactivity during this time period would result in a verifiable jeopardy to human safety.
- The Service's Manhattan Field Office should be notified in writing in advance of any activities which have the potential to affect any Topeka shiner habitat. This includes activities proposed for any known Topeka shiner stream, as well as those for which potential Topeka shiner habitat exists, including Threemile, Fourmile, and Forsyth creeks.
- Only clean, uncontaminated rock or broken concrete (no rebar, asphalt, or soil) shall be used for temporary or permanent within all stream channels of any known Topeka shiner stream, or Threemile, Fourmile, and Forsyth creeks.
- Long-term degradation to stream banks shall be avoided by keeping road and ramp building and channel reshaping to the absolute minimum necessary to complete the work, and downstream sedimentation shall be minimized during all activities. Downstream silt screens or fences may be appropriate in some circumstances, at the Army's discretion.
- Best management practices for erosion control shall be implemented and maintained throughout the duration of all project activities located in runoff areas to streams.
- Seeding and/or mulching shall occur within all stream runoff areas as soon as grading allows, following the end of construction or maintenance activities at any site.
- Storage facilities for petroleum products, fuels and other chemicals shall be located so that discharge and runoff into the streams is not possible.

3.1.7.5. **Prescription: Continue development of hardened, low water fords**

Action. Construction and maintenance of hardened, low water fords will precisely follow protocol approved by the USFWS and KDWPT (below) in the 2002 road maintenance consultation. Important components of this protocol are: constructing hardened, low water fords level with the natural streambed, limiting ford width to approximately 30 feet, and using best management practices to control silt entering streams from construction actions. Deviation from this protocol will degrade, rather than improve, stream quality.

- Direct adverse impacts to Topeka shiner reproduction will be minimized because no construction activity will take place at crossing sites with flowing water between the dates of May 15 and July 31, inclusive, except in emergency situations.
- Approaches on each side of the crossing will be cut where necessary such that a grade of ten percent is not exceeded. The approaches will be a minimum of eighteen feet wide (thirty feet on tank trails) and extend from the ford a minimum of one hundred feet.
- A layer of geotextile fabric will be laid down on the surface of the graded approaches. A one-foot layer of 8-12 inch diameter rock will be applied to the geotextile. An additional six-inch layer of 3-4 inch diameter top rock will be used on approaches that occur on tank

trails to serve as a wearing surface. Top rock used during construction shall contain a minimal amount of fines.

- V-ditches will be constructed on both sides of the approaches to provide drainage for them. The side slopes of the V-ditches will not be less than 3:1. A layer of riprap will be applied to the drainage ditches of approaches with grades that exceed five percent.
- Methods used to construct low water fords will be dependent upon the typical water-flow conditions expected for each site.
 - Construction will occur during no flow conditions at ephemeral stream crossing sites. Soil in the stream at the ford site will be excavated to a minimum depth of two feet or until bedrock or a clay pan is reached. The minimum width of the excavation will be eighteen feet. The length of the excavation will equal the width of the stream channel plus ten feet. A geotextile fabric will be laid down to cover the surface of the excavated area. The excavated area will then be filled with 8-12 inch diameter rock. Rock will be added and compacted until the original streambed elevation is reached. A layer of 3-4 inch top rock will be used on fords that occur on tank trails to fill voids in the larger rock. Materials used shall be free from excessive amounts of fines.
 - A backhoe will be used to excavate a hole in streams with perennial water flow. The holes that are created will have riprap of 24-inch diameter or larger emptied into them. Large vehicles will drive across this material forcing it into the ground. The large riprap will be emptied into the site until the vehicles are no longer able to force the rocks deeper, i.e., the riprap is at bedrock or a clay pan.
- Soil removed during construction that is suitable for reuse may be utilized to build berms and diversion ditches. Soil removed during construction that is not used for berm or diversion ditch construction shall be spread over a relatively level area outside of the construction area and at least 50 feet from a stream channel.
- A motor grader will improve or develop a trail in locations where trails leading to stream crossings are inadequate for travel by construction vehicles. All transport roads created during construction shall be tilled and planted to grass after ford construction is complete.
- Best management practices for erosion control (e.g., hay bales, silt fences, etc.) will be implemented and maintained throughout the duration of all project activities located in runoff areas to streams. Temporary seeding and/or mulching will occur within all stream runoff areas as soon as grading allows, followed by permanent seeding of native or brome grasses as soon as practical.
- Additional stream crossing sites that were created by military maneuvers but will no longer be needed with the availability of hardened stream crossings will be reclaimed and remediated, or protected from further use and allowed to naturally recover.
- Grubbing and stream channelization will be minimized.

Topeka Shiner Monitoring Plan

3.1.8. Determine Topeka shiner status in Fort Riley streams.

Surveys will be conducted in all streams that have, or apparently have, suitable Topeka shiner habitat. Biental surveys will be conducted in streams in which Topeka shiners have been found. These are Wildcat, Wind, Little Arkansas, Silver, Honey and Sevenmile creeks. Surveys will be conducted one out of every five years in streams in which Topeka shiners have not been

documented. This will include Threemile, Fourmile, Timber, Madison, Rush, and Forsyth creeks. Surveys will concentrate on pools and runs in these streams.

Topeka shiner capture sites will be maintained in the GIS database.

3.1.9. Long-term monitoring of small-stream fish populations.

Fish assemblages present at each sample location will be recorded to document any changes in community structure over time. Numbers of each species captured will provide estimates of the density of Topeka shiner and other fish populations on the installation.

Topeka Shiner Literature Cited

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4.0 HENSLOW'S SPARROW MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

The purposes of this management plan are to present information on the Henslow's sparrow, define conservation goals, and describe actions that will enable achievement of those conservation goals.

Henslow's Sparrow Species Information

4.1.1. Description

Small birds (length 5 inches), Henslow's sparrow males and females appear identical. Adults have a buff-colored breast with fine, dark streaking that contrasts with their dark chestnut-colored wings and back. Their napes and large heads are olive-colored, with a central stripe across the crown. Juveniles are similar, but yellower, and with less streaking. Song is a short, quiet *se-lick*, with accent on second syllable; it is easily missed.

4.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

Preferred breeding habitat for Henslow's sparrows is large tracts (> 30 ha) of grasslands that have remained unburned for 2-5 years. Grasslands should be dense (Robins 1971), with a well-developed litter layer (Zimmerman 1987) and standing dead vegetation over 30 cm tall (Smith 1992). Fields that have been burned, mowed or heavily impacted during the previous year are seldom used due to the lack of standing dead vegetation and accumulated litter. Henslow's Sparrow habitat also is characterized by a high percentage of grass cover with scattered forbs and little shrubs.

Henslow's sparrows arrive on their breeding grounds from late March to late April, and nest from May to mid-August (Graber 1968, Robins 1971, Winter 1998). Henslow's sparrows apparently will re-nest after a first nest fails, and nests found with eggs in mid-August or dependent young in September suggest that the species may be double-brooded (Graber 1968). Fall migration begins in September, and most birds have vacated the breeding grounds by late October (Graber 1968, Robins 1971).

Periodic disturbance is necessary to maintain suitable habitat for Henslow's sparrows, although disturbance reduces habitat available to Henslow's Sparrows for one or two breeding seasons (Zimmerman 1988, Herkert 1994, Melde and Koford 1996). Nests and fledglings may be destroyed by mowing during the breeding season. Therefore it is recommended that mowing not be allowed in areas with nesting Henslow's sparrows until after the breeding season (about August 15).

Surveys on Fort Riley indicate that Henslow's sparrows are most abundant in Maneuver Areas H, K and O. They also have been located in Maneuver Areas A-F, J, L, M, and N, and Training Areas 12, 14, 20, and 22-24 (Exhibit C.5).

Henslow's Sparrow Conservation Goals

4.1.3. Protect, maintain, and enhance Henslow's Sparrow habitat on Fort Riley

4.1.4. Provide long-term monitoring of Henslow's sparrow populations on Fort Riley**4.1.5. Initiate conservation partnerships with adjacent landowners**

Henslow's sparrow Management Prescriptions and Actions

4.1.6. Estimate Size of Breeding Population

Data for this species indicate it has experienced significant declines range wide over the past 25 years, and of 30 species of nongame migratory birds studied by the Cornell Laboratory of Ornithology, the Henslow's sparrow was rated as one of two most in danger of extinction (Butcher 1989). Because of its status as an Army Species At Risk, additional status information from throughout the range is, therefore, of critical importance.

4.1.6.1. Prescription. Estimate the number of Henslow's sparrows breeding on Fort Riley

Action. Grassland tracts, both native and go-back areas, will be surveyed during the breeding season, approximately May 15 to August 31. A quantitative survey methodology will be used to locate Henslow's sparrows.

Action. Locations with Henslow's sparrows will be mapped and incorporated into GIS programs. This information will be consulted when planning actions for the operation and maintenance of the installation and tactical training events.

4.1.7. Protect, Maintain, and Improve Nesting Habitat

Tallgrass grasslands are abundant on Fort Riley. The suitability of these grasslands for Henslow's sparrows is dependent upon the time since last disturbance, which may include fire, hay-cutting, or intensive training maneuvers. The presence of sericea lespedeza may also negatively affect this species.

4.1.7.1. Prescription. Maintain and improve condition of nesting habitat for successful reproduction by Henslow's sparrows

Action. Tracts of land known to be used for nesting will be designated as Henslow's sparrow breeding habitat (Exhibit C.5). Fort Riley will retain 10,000 unburned acres within Henslow's sparrow habitat areas annually. Specific locations selected for habitat protection will vary annually, to allow all grasslands to receive appropriate management actions.

Action. Grassland habitat will be maintained or enhanced by periodically setting back succession to maintain dense herbaceous vegetation with little woody invasion. Controlled burning or mowing will be conducted to manage for 3-year old grasslands within Henslow's sparrow habitat areas.

Action. The increasing percentage of sericea lespedeza in grasslands is believed to cause a decline in habitat quality for Henslow's sparrows. Sericea lespedeza tends to outcompete native grasses, and become dominant within grassland stands. Dense stands of sericea lespedeza grow without

substantial litter buildup, apparently creating conditions unsuitable for Henslow's sparrow breeding. Therefore, the presence of sericea lespedeza will be monitored throughout Henslow's sparrow habitat areas. Infestations will be controlled through the use of mechanical and chemical treatments, to the extent feasible.

Action. Woody encroachment into grasslands reduces the habitat quality of grasslands. Woody encroachment will be reduced through cutting of mature trees scattered through grasslands, and mechanical and chemical treatments to reduce shrub encroachment into grasslands, to the extent feasible.

4.1.8. Initiate conservation partnerships with adjacent landowners

4.1.8.1. Prescription. Partner with other organizations to promote grassland conservation actions and initiatives on private lands across the Fort Riley region

Action. Private lands adjacent to Fort Riley contain quality tallgrass prairie, low quality prairie, cultivated grassland and tilled ground. These private lands are considered an opportunity to provide additional habitat to support Henslow's sparrows within the region. A private lands initiative implemented in cooperation with partners will promote grassland stewardship in the region. Regional lands will be evaluated for the potential to improve or maintain habitat for Henslow's sparrows and other grassland species through mutual agreements for actions such as woody plant removal, noxious weed control, conservation grazing and prescribed burning.

4.5 LITERATURE CITED

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Herkert, J. R. 1994. Status and habitat selection of the Henslow's Sparrow. Wilson Bulletin 106:35-45.

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5.0 TEXAS HORNED LIZARD MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

The purposes of this management plan are to present information on the Texas horned lizard, define conservation goals, and describe actions that will enable achievement of those conservation goals.

Texas Horned Lizard Species Information

5.1.1. Description

The Texas horned lizard is a small lizard, ranging 2-4 inches in length. Its appearance differs from any other lizard on Fort Riley, as it has rough raised scales all over its body. These scales appear as ragged points along each side and down the short tail, down the chin, and especially large spines resembling horns protruding from the back of its head. Its coloration is basically some shade of brown with a dark brown blotch on each side of the neck and a series of dark spots or blotches on each side of the back, separated by a light-colored median line. Its belly is white with small gray spots.

5.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The Texas horned lizard occurs in dry, flat areas with a sandy, loamy, or rocky surface with little vegetation, where its diurnal activities include basking in the sun, foraging for ants, or hiding just below the soil surface (Collins 1982).

On Fort Riley, Texas horned lizards are observed in areas with little vegetation, such as well-drained upland slopes, gravelly ridges, road cuts, active or abandoned quarry sites, and other eroded areas (Busby et al. 1996). While these types of areas occur throughout the installation, Texas horned lizards have most often been observed south of Vinton School Road, or east of the Impact Area in Maneuver Areas C and I.

There has been no systematic attempt to quantify the population of Texas horned lizards on Fort Riley. This species has been surveyed for only as part of installation wide surveys that seek all reptile, amphibian and turtle species. Incidental sightings of individuals are reported from Training Areas 14, 15, 17, 22, 23, 33, 35, 46 and 92 and Maneuver Areas C and I (Exhibit C.6). The species is not believed to be abundant, but occurs in small numbers at a variety of locations.

Texas Horned Lizard Conservation Goals

5.1.3. Document all occurrences of Texas horned lizard on Fort Riley

5.1.4. Protect Texas horned lizards from human-induced injury or mortality

Texas Horned Lizard Management Prescriptions and Actions

5.1.5. Document Texas Horned Lizard Occurrences

Because of its status as a declining species and subsequent designation as an Army Species At Risk, the Conservation Branch will document any sighting of a Texas horned lizard.

5.1.5.1. Prescription. Improve detection and reporting of Texas horned lizards

Action. All Conservation Branch personnel will be made aware of the importance of recording encounters with this lizard in the field. All observations, including verified sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel, will be maintained on maps, so specific habitats utilized by the species can be tracked and identified.

Action. Locations of reported sightings of Texas horned lizards will be visited to obtain a habitat description of the sighting location. A log of habitats from which sightings are recorded will be maintained to create more specific description of actual habitats used by this species on Fort Riley. Such information can then be referenced when considering future actions that require NEPA documents.

5.1.6. Minimize the Risk of Injury and Mortality to Texas Horned Lizards

Because it is insectivorous, pesticide use may adversely affect its invertebrate food supply, and should be restricted in most terrestrial habitats.

5.1.6.1. Prescription. Protect Texas horned lizards from chemical impacts

Action. The storage and use of all insecticides on Fort Riley shall be conducted in strict accordance with label directions and restrictions. All general use and military chemicals on Fort Riley shall be used, stored, and disposed of in accordance with directions, restrictions and/or guidelines established by the manufacturer and/or Department of the Army.

Action. Refrain from using insecticide control measures in settings away from cantonment areas.

Texas Horned Lizard Monitoring Plan

Other than maintaining sighting records, there is no need for additional monitoring of this species at this time. Habitat use should be characterized at any sighting locations.

Texas Horned Lizard Literature Cited

Busby, W.H., J.T. Collins & J.R. Parmelee. 1996. The Reptiles and Amphibians of Fort Riley and Vicinity. Univ. of Kansas Printing Service.

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6.0 REGAL FRITILLARY MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

The purposes of this management plan are to present information on the regal fritillary, define conservation goals, and describe actions that will enable achievement of those conservation goals.

Regal Fritillary Information

6.1.1. Description

The regal fritillary is a relatively large butterfly (3-4 inch wingspan), similar in size and overall coloration to the familiar monarch. The forewings of the regal fritillary are considerably more rounded and less pointed and elongated than the monarch. The forewings are a burnt orange color, with irregular black markings and, in the female, white spots along the forward and outer edges. Both males and females have relatively dark hindwings, with a double row of light colored spots, orange on males and white on females. The underside of the hindwings has large silver spots.

6.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The regal fritillary utilizes wet meadows and moist tallgrass prairies, especially virgin grasslands. Caterpillars feed on violets, whereas adults typically feed on nectar from butterfly milkweed, common milkweed, pale-purple coneflower (Richard and Heitzman 1987), and thistles (Pyle 1986).

Regal fritillary eggs are laid in late summer. Caterpillars emerge late in summer, overwinter beneath leaves on the ground, and begin eating violets the following spring. They are black and yellow with short branching spiny hairs. The adults emerge in early summer and may be seen through September. Only one generation appears in a year.

Adult regal fritillary adults are common in the remnant tallgrass prairie tracts that occur throughout Fort Riley (see INRMP, Exhibit 7.6). Additionally, adult regal fritillaries have been observed in “go-back” grassland areas in which some wildflowers have reestablished, particularly cone-flowers and milkweeds. The regal fritillary has been observed to occur throughout Fort Riley training areas (Exhibit C.7). In 2013, Fort Riley funded a two-year research project to 1) provide spatially explicit estimates of the distribution and abundance of the regal fritillary and its host plant, prairie violet; 2) provide models that identify habitat features and management practices that influence the density of adult regal fritillary; and 3) produce information on the effectiveness of management strategies for the regal fritillary populations on Fort Riley. Sightings also are recorded incidentally while Fort Riley staff perform other work on the installation. In 2015, Fort Riley further funded this project to provide baseline population estimates of adult monarch and population trend estimates of adult regal fritillary. The study also identified environmental attributes such as hay removal and fire land management practices that influence those species, including an analysis of land management implications.

Regal Fritillary Conservation Goals

6.1.3. Assess regal fritillary population on Fort Riley

6.1.4. Protect, maintain, and enhance habitat**6.1.5. Protect individuals and populations from human-induced injury****6.1.6. Initiate conservation partnerships**

Regal Fritillary Management Prescriptions and Actions

6.1.7. Assess Regal Fritillary Populations

Assessment of approximate population size of this butterfly, and the extent and area of habitat currently utilized, should be determined. Such baseline data will also assist in targeting specific areas for habitat manipulations and protections.

6.1.7.1. Prescription. Assess regal fritillary populations and extent of habitat used

Action. Surveys of select native tallgrass prairie parcels will be conducted in June and July. Areas which have any history of conversion from prairie to other land use, then reversion back to grassland, will not be surveyed formally. The survey will record numbers of regal fritillaries seen, as well as areas containing appropriate food plants for both adults and caterpillars. Data will be maintained in a GIS database which can be updated annually.

6.1.8. Protect and Maintain Existing Habitat

Prairie areas containing a variety of wildflowers, particularly the species identified as preferred food plants for regal fritillaries, should be identified and maintained. Management practices may need to be implemented to maintain prairie in this condition, particularly to prevent invasion by woody or noxious weed species while maintaining wildflower diversity. This may be accomplished through burning, mowing, spot-spraying herbicides, or a combination of all.

6.1.8.1. Prescription. Protect and maintain diverse tallgrass prairies with good wildflowers

Action. Early successional grassland tracts will be best maintained by prescribed burning two out of every five years. Late winter and early spring burns will favor growth of wildflowers.

Action. Woody encroachment into grasslands reduces the habitat quality of grasslands. Woody encroachment will be reduced through cutting of mature trees scattered through grasslands, and mechanical and chemical treatments to reduce shrub encroachment into grasslands, to the extent feasible.

Action. The increasing percentage of sericea lespedeza in grasslands is believed to cause a decline in the habitat quality for regal fritillaries. Sericea lespedeza tends to outcompete native grasses and forbs, and become dominant within grassland stands. Dense, monoculture stands of sericea lespedeza will reduce the numbers of milkweed and violets growing in grasslands, apparently creating conditions less suited for regal fritillaries. Therefore, the presence of sericea lespedeza will be monitored throughout regal fritillary habitat areas. Infestations will be controlled through the use of mechanical and chemical treatments, to the extent feasible.

6.1.9. Minimize Human-Induced Mortality

The regal fritillary is very susceptible to the use of pesticides in its habitat, both insecticides which may kill it outright, as well as herbicides which may destroy its food base. The threat of chemical contamination must be controlled if this valued species is to persist on the installation.

6.1.9.1. **Prescription. Protect regal fritillary from chemical impacts**

Action. The storage and usage of all insecticides and herbicides on Fort Riley will be conducted in strict accordance with label directions and restrictions. All general use and military chemicals on Fort Riley shall be used, stored, and disposed of in accordance with directions, restrictions and/or guidelines established by the manufacturer and/or Department of the Army.

Action. Generally, aerial or non-targeted spraying to control sericea lespedeza will be restricted to those fields identified as “go-back” or brome by Freeman and Delisle (2004). Targeted, ground-spraying by truck, ATV, or backpack equipment will generally occur in fields identified as native prairie. When circumstances require non-targeted spraying tallgrass prairie parcels, the spraying action will occur in late summer, when most violets and many milkweed plants have already senesced, to minimize the effects on these important food plants to regal fritillaries.

Action. Limit use of insecticide control measures in settings away from cantonment areas.

6.1.10. Initiate conservation partnerships with adjacent landowners

6.1.10.1. **Prescription. Partner with other organizations to promote grassland conservation actions and initiatives on private lands within the Fort Riley region.**

Action. Private lands adjacent to Fort Riley contain some quality tallgrass prairie, low quality prairie and tilled ground. These private lands will be considered as an opportunity to provide additional quality prairie to support the local population of regal fritillaries within the region. A private lands initiative implemented in cooperation with partners will promote grassland stewardship in the region. Regional lands will be evaluated for the potential to improve or maintain habitat for regal fritillaries through mutual agreements such as woody plant removal, noxious weed control, conservation grazing and prescribed burning.

Regal Fritillary Literature Cited

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Pyle, R.M. 1986. The Audubon Society field guide to North American butterflies. Alfred A. Knopf, Inc. New York, NY.

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7.0 RUSTY BLACKBIRD MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

The purposes of this management plan are to present information on the Rusty blackbird, define conservation goals, and describe actions that will enable achievement of those conservation goals.

Rusty Blackbird Information

7.1.1. Description

In fall and winter plumage, rusty blackbirds are characterized by rust-tipped edges on otherwise black feathers. All adult birds have conspicuous yellow irises. Immature birds resemble adults except for brown irises, which become pale yellow during the first winter. During breeding season, adult males become uniformly black above with a blue-green to greenish gloss, and adult female are slate gray, darker above with a bluish green gloss.

7.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The Rusty Blackbird breeds in northern boreal forests along bogs, muskeg swamps, beaver ponds, and streams. It occurs on Fort Riley during winter. In winter, the rusty blackbird is often located in woodlands associated with water, such as hardwood bottomlands, stream and pond borders, and their adjacent open fields (Avery 1995).

In winter and during migration, vegetative foods consist mainly of crops (corn, oats, wheat) and weed seeds, as well as grape and oak mast. Throughout the year, a variety of invertebrates also is eaten, including aquatic beetles and their larvae, grasshoppers, spiders, snails and crawfish. Rusty blackbirds feed mostly on the ground, particularly along edges of ponds and streams, but also in open pasture and agricultural fields (Avery 1995).

Expected habitat for this species on the installation occurs in riparian woodlands of rivers and streams, as well as food plot and firebreak agricultural fields that occur adjacent to the woodlands.

There has been no systematic attempt to quantify the occurrence of rusty blackbirds on Fort Riley. This species has been documented only as part of other winter-time surveys that have occurred (raptor and eagle surveys, Christmas Bird Count). Incidental sightings of small groups of rusty blackbirds are reported from Training Areas 19 and 27. The species is not believed to be abundant, but occurs in small numbers at a variety of locations.

Rusty Blackbird Conservation Goals

7.1.3. Document all reported sightings of rusty blackbirds on Fort Riley

7.1.4. Protect, maintain, and enhance habitat

Rusty Blackbird Management Prescriptions and Actions

7.1.5. Document Rusty Blackbird Occurrences

The Rusty Blackbird has suffered population declines of 90–98% since 1966 (Greenberg and Droege 1999, Greenberg et al. in review). Due to its decline, this once abundant bird has been identified as a high priority for conservation by several groups, including the international Partners in Flight initiative (Rich et al. 2005) and the USFWS (USFWS 2007), and has been designated as an Army Species At Risk. The Conservation Branch will document any sighting of a rusty blackbird.

7.1.5.1. **Prescription. Improve detection and reporting of rusty blackbirds**

Action. All Conservation Branch personnel should learn to recognize rusty blackbirds, and be made aware of the importance of recording encounters with this bird in the field. All observations, including verified sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel, will be maintained on maps, so specific habitats utilized by the species can be tracked and identified.

Action. Visit locations of reported sightings to obtain habitat description of sighting location. Maintain log of habitats from which sightings are recorded in order to create more specific description of actual habitats used by this species on Fort Riley. Such information can then be referenced when considering future actions that require NEPA documents.

7.1.6. **Protect and Maintain Existing Habitat**

Invasive plants that diminish the quality of riparian woodlands and compete with trees that may provide mast and structure in woodlands adversely affect the rusty blackbirds. Agricultural practices that allow grain seed to be available throughout the winter may benefit the species by providing feeding areas for migrating and wintering birds.

7.1.6.1. **Prescription. Investigate and address Tartarian honeysuckle infestations**

Fort Riley woodlands are experiencing invasion by the exotic Tartarian honeysuckle; in some tracts this invasive is achieving nearly 90% dominance of the understory vegetation, outcompeting growth of shade intolerant trees such as oaks. The woodlands experiencing the greatest Tartarian honeysuckle invasion are in the southern portion of the installation, and generally along the Kansas and Republican rivers.

7.1.6.2. **Prescription. Maintain agricultural crop fields**

Action. Rusty blackbirds are known to forage in agricultural fields during migration and on their wintering grounds. Activities that establish agricultural crops and maintain available grain throughout the winter may benefit rusty blackbirds by providing a winter food source while this species is present on the installation. Fort Riley will achieve this goal by maintaining cropped fields to serve as firebreaks around the installation's perimeter.

Rusty Blackbird Literature Cited

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Greenberg, R., and S. Droege. 1999. On the decline of the Rusty Blackbird and the use of ornithological literature to document long-term population trends. *Conservation Biology* 13:553–559.

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Rich, T. D., C. J. Beardmore, H. Berlanga, P. J. Blancher, M. S. W. Bradstreet, G. S. Butcher, D. W. Demarest, E. H. Dunn, W. C. Hunter, E. E. Inigo-Elias, J. A. Kennedy, A. M. Martell, A. O. Panjabi, D. N. Pashley, K. V. Rosenberg, C. M. Rustay, J. S. Wendt, T. C. Will. 2004. Partners in Flight North American Landbird Conservation Plan. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY.

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8.0 NORTHERN LONG-EARED BAT MANAGEMENT PLAN

On April 2, 2015, the USFWS published in the Federal Register a final rule to list the northern long-eared bat (*Myotis septentrionalis*) as a threatened species throughout its range under the ESA. It was determined that critical habitat for this species is not determinable, and therefore none listed, at this time. Additionally, an interim rule under section 4(d) of the Act was described to provide exceptions to the prohibitions for some activities with threat factors that may cause cumulative effects to the species, but are deemed necessary and advisable for the conservation of the species. (Federal Register 2015). However, this interim rule does not remove or alter in any way the consultation requirements of federal agencies with the USFWS under Section 7 of the Act if an action may affect a northern long-eared bat.

To fulfill its Section 7 consultation obligations, the U.S. Army Installation Management Command submitted a Biological Evaluation (USAEC 2015) with its request for informal consultation with the USFWS on April 24, 2015 concerning northern long-eared bats. In its concurrence response letter dated May 04, 2015, USFWS wrote “The Service was part of, and worked to help construct the biological evaluation, including all analysis and design of conservation measures.” Table 1 of that evaluation lists the status of northern long-eared bats at Fort Riley as verified absence. Section XI of that evaluation lists in summary form Activities/ Areas not subject to conservation measures, which includes ‘any area where northern long-eared bat absence has been verified’ and ‘all activities involving the use of aircraft’. Therefore, unless the presence of northern long-eared bats is verified on Fort Riley, the implementation of conservation measures to protect this species are not deemed necessary within installation boundaries. Aircraft outside of installation boundaries do not perform low level flights or other operations that would adversely affect bats in a manner not described already in the biological evaluation, so will continue without additional consultation.

Introduction

This management plan is based on and is consistent with the Endangered Species Act of 1973, the Kansas Endangered Species and Nongame Conservation Act of 1975, and Army Regulations. This plan does not supersede ESA Section 7 consultation requirements with USFWS or replace the need to obtain special permits from the KDWPT. Any action that may directly or indirectly affect the northern long-eared bat, or its known habitat, must be coordinated with the USFWS and KDWPT by the Conservation Branch.

Northern Long-eared Bat Information

8.1.1. Description

The northern long-eared bat (*Myotis septentrionalis*) has also been known as the northern myotis and Keen’s myotis. It is a medium-sized bat about 3 to 3.7 inches in length with a wingspan of 9 to 10 inches. Its fur color is medium to dark brown on the back and tawny to pale-brown on the underside. Northern long-eared bats are similar in color to big brown and little myotis bats. As its name suggests, however, this bat can be distinguished by its long ears, particularly as compared to other bats in its genus, which are bats noted for their small ears (USFWS 2013).

8.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

8.1.2.1. Range:

The northern long-eared bat ranges widely across much of the eastern and north central United States, and all Canadian provinces, but it is patchily distributed and rarely found in groups of more than 100. Within the United States, this includes the area from Maine through Florida, and west to Montana, Wyoming, Kansas and Oklahoma (USFWS 2013). In Kansas, this bat is documented from eight counties (Ellis, Graham, Leavenworth, Marshall, Osborne, Phillips, Rooks, Russell, Washington), but may occur in other riparian woodlands throughout the northern half of the state. More thorough sampling is needed (Sparks et al. 2011).

8.1.2.2. Summer Habitat:

The northern long-eared bat is associated with mature, interior- forest environments. On the western edge of its range, this species is found in wooded riparian zones within prairie habitats. At summering sites, the presence of northern long-eared bats is correlated with the availability of features most often found in older forests, e.g., uneven forest age, a multi-layered canopy, single and multiple tree-fall gaps, standing snags and abundant woody debris (CBD).

8.1.2.3. Feeding Habits:

Northern long-eared bats emerge about half an hour after sunset. They tend to forage in forested areas, even if the woodlands are only a few acres in size, flying through the understory of forested hillsides and ridges (Sparks et al. 2011). Like other *Myotis* species, the northern long-eared bat feeds opportunistically on insects, using both “hawking” and “gleaning” to obtain prey (CBD). Some animals occupy a night roost and re-emerge to forage a second time immediately before dawn (Sparks et al. 2011).

8.1.2.4. Winter Habitat:

Northern long-eared bats across most of their range overwinter in caves, abandoned/inactive mines or other such structures in multi-species hibernacula and generally comprise a small proportion (generally less than 25 percent) of the total number of animals hibernating at each site. The bat seems to favor deep crevices for hibernation, often with only the nose and ears visible (CBD). Some suspect that in Kansas, northern long-eared bats may hibernate in rock crevices of rocky outcrops (Sparks et al. 2011).

8.1.2.5. Breeding:

Mating takes place in late summer or early fall and females store sperm until they emerge from hibernation in the spring, when ovulation and fertilization occur. After fertilization, pregnant females migrate to summer areas where they roost in small colonies and give birth to a single pup. Maternity colonies, with young, generally have 30 to 60 bats (USFWS 2013).

8.1.2.6. Migration:

The migratory status of the northern long-eared bat is unclear. Some consider the species to not be migratory, with individuals traveling no more than 35 miles between winter hibernacula and summer roosting sites (CBD). Others assume in Kansas the species is present primarily as a migrant, with some small breeding populations also being present. However, this bat is one of the species most often captured along riparian corridors in north central Kansas during summer sampling. Thus, some suspect that the species may be increasing in Kansas in both range and

numbers, and that northern long-eared bats may migrate long distances in order to reach summer areas (Sparks et al. 2011).

8.1.3. Northern Long-eared Bat Conservation Measures

No other threat is as severe and immediate as the disease white-nose syndrome. If this disease had not emerged, it is unlikely the northern long-eared population would be declining so dramatically (USFWS 2013). Of the seven species known to be affected by this deadly bat-disease to date, the northern long-eared bat is among the hardest hit (CBD).

Northern Long-eared Bat Conservation Goals

- 8.1.4. Document occurrences of northern long-eared bats on Fort Riley**
- 8.1.5. Assess any northern long-eared bat population, found on Fort Riley**
- 8.1.6. Protect habitat areas used by northern long-eared bats on Fort Riley**
- 8.1.7. Protect individual northern long-eared bats, if they are present on Fort Riley**
- 8.1.8. Protect northern long-eared bat roost locations, if found, on Fort Riley**
- 8.1.9. Provide long-term monitoring of northern long-eared bat populations on Fort Riley**

Northern Long-eared Bat Management Prescriptions and Actions

8.1.10. Document northern long-eared bat occurrences

Fort Riley has conducted bat surveys since 2011 using the Anabat SD2 bat detector paired with a directional broad spectrum microphone. Bat echolocation calls are recorded by the detector. Several software programs are used to analyze the calls, beginning with Echoclass and BCID. These programs automatically analyze each call recorded, identify which species the call most closely resembles, and assign a probability that the classification is correct. After this automated process is complete, the program AnalookW can be used to manually view any calls of interest. AnalookW generates a spectrogram of the call, allowing the user to visually compare the call in question to known spectrograms for the species, and therefore determine if the classification was correct. Several call files collected on Fort Riley were classified as northern long-eared bats using both Echoclass and BCID. However, upon examination of spectrograms produced by AnalookW, it was determined that these calls were of eastern red bats. The presence of the northern long-eared bat has not been confirmed on the installation. The Conservation Branch will continue surveys for northern long-eared bats.

8.1.10.1. Prescription. Improve detection and reporting of northern long-eared bats

Action. Expand Anabat-enhanced bat surveys across the installation; see Section 8.5, Monitoring Plan, for details.

Action. Conservation Branch personnel will be educated in identification of northern long-eared bats, and be made aware of the importance of encounters with this bat in the field. All

observations, including verified sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel, will be maintained on maps, so specific habitats utilized by the species can be tracked and identified.

8.1.11. Assess northern long-eared bat populations

Assessment of approximate population size of this bat, and the extent and area of habitat currently utilized, should be determined if a northern long-eared bat is confirmed on Fort Riley.

8.1.11.1. Prescription. Assess northern long-eared bat populations *that occur on Fort Riley*

Action. If the presence of northern long-eared bats is confirmed on Fort Riley, more intensive surveys for this species will be conducted, both to further delineate where this species occurs on the installation, and to better understand when, where and how this species is using Fort Riley habitats. The surveys may include Anabat technology, drift nets, visual inspections of potential roost sites, or other survey technologies that may come available.

Action. Locations with suspected northern long-eared bat detections and any future confirmed sightings will be mapped and incorporated into GIS programs. This information will be consulted when planning actions for the operation and maintenance of the installation and tactical training events.

Action. Locations of suspected and documented sightings of northern long-eared bats will be visited to obtain a habitat description of the sighting location. A log of habitats from which sightings are recorded will be maintained to create more specific description of actual habitats used by this species on Fort Riley. Such information can then be referenced when considering future actions that require NEPA documentation.

8.1.12. Protect and conserve northern long-eared bat habitat

Northern long-eared bats' presence and activity levels are highest in forest stands with old-growth characteristics, which the species may favor for the large, partially dead or decaying trees on which this bat roosts (CBD). During summer, northern long-eared bats roost singly or in colonies underneath bark, in cavities, or in crevices of both live and dead trees. Males and non-reproductive females seem opportunistic in selecting roosts, using tree species based on suitability to retain bark or provide cavities or crevices. They have also been found, rarely, roosting in structures like bridges, bat boxes, and abandoned buildings (USFWS 2013). Maternity colonies usually form in hollow trees, although exfoliating bark may also be used. Females exhibit high site fidelity to maternity roosts, returning annually to their natal sites. Because of the species' strong association with large blocks of older forests, forest fragmentation and conversion (such as clearing trees for agriculture or development) are threats (CBD).

8.1.12.1. Prescription. Protect known northern long-eared bat roost trees

Action. Any tree which is confirmed to be used as a roost site by northern long-eared bats will be marked to protect that tree from harvest, fuelwood-cutting, deer tree stands, firefighter training, or any other activity that may damage or down the tree. If deemed appropriate, firebreaks may be maintained to slow the advance of fire into the area containing the tree.

Action. Where possible and not a safety hazard, dead and dying trees will be left standing within woodlands that appear to meet the appropriate habitat requirements for providing potential roost sites for northern long-eared bats.

Action. Where it is not possible to leave dead and dying trees standing, and in locations where trees suitable for bat roosting are in short supply, bat boxes will be established to provide additional roost sites.

8.1.12.2. **Prescription. Protect northern long-eared bat hibernacula**

Action. A "no disturbance" buffer zone will be established around any known northern long-eared bat hibernacula. The size, duration and limitations of the zone will be determined after consultation with the USFWS.

8.1.12.3. **Prescription. Protect habitat areas used by northern long-eared bats**

Action. Once a northern long-eared bat is documented on Fort Riley, all conservation practices described in Section VI of the Biological Evaluation (USAEC 2015) will be fully implemented on the installation. In instances where a desired action is not described in the Biological Evaluation, or effects are anticipated that are different from those described, the installation will consult with USFWS prior to initiating that action.

Action. Tracts of woodland *documented as used by this species* will be designated Northern Long-Eared Bat Habitat.

Action. All areas designated as Northern Long-Eared Bat Habitat will be protected from adverse impacts. Adverse impacts include activities that result in destruction or removal of large, mature trees. The following activities shall be controlled within a woodlot designated as Northern Long-Eared Bat Habitat: construction; operations and maintenance activities; demolition; and detonation of explosives.

8.1.12.4. **Prescription. Educate Fort Riley personnel of any requirement to protect Northern Long-Eared Bat Habitat.**

Action. Inform pilots if "no disturbance" buffer zones are in effect around hibernacula. Information will be provided to aviators through Local NOTAMS (Notices to AirMen) regarding "no disturbance" zones to minimize aircraft conflicts with roosting bats.

Action. Programs will be developed, *if needed*, to publicize the requirements of northern long-eared bat conservation to all Department of Army personnel and contractors, and outdoor enthusiasts, who work, train or recreate on Fort Riley.

8.1.13. Protect northern long-eared bats from human-induced injury and mortality

Since first observed in New York in 2006, white-nose syndrome has spread rapidly from the Northeast to the Midwest and Southeast; an area that includes the core of the northern long-eared bat's range and where it was most common before this disease. Northern long-eared bat numbers have declined by 99 percent in the Northeast. Although there is uncertainty about the rate that

white-nose syndrome will spread, it is expected to spread throughout the United States (USFWS 2013).

Although significant population declines have not been observed due to human-induced sources of mortality, those may now be important factors after the declines caused by white-nose syndrome. Northern long-eared bats are unlikely to be disturbed by routine uses of roads, homes, and other facilities where such use pre-dates the initial finding of activity in a given area. Therefore, in most cases *ongoing*, existing uses may proceed with the same intensity with little risk of disturbing the species.

8.1.13.1. **Prescription. Protect against the spread of white-nose syndrome**

Action. A national plan was prepared by the USFWS and other agencies that details actions needed to investigate, manage, and slow the spread of white-nose syndrome through human transmission (USFWS 2011). Fort Riley managers will adhere to protocol within that plan when conducting actions for the northern long-eared bat. Under no circumstances should clothing, footwear, or equipment that was used in bat hibernacula from a white-nose-syndrome-affected region be used on Fort Riley.

8.1.13.2. **Prescription. Ensure northern long-eared bats are not affected during irregularly scheduled activities**

Action. Once a northern long-eared bat is documented on Fort Riley, all conservation practices described in Section VI of the Biological Evaluation (USAEC 2015) concerning construction, forest management, prescribed burning, and tree removal will be fully implemented on the installation. In instances where a desired action is not described in the Biological Evaluation, or effects are anticipated that are different from those described, the installation will consult with USFWS prior to initiating that action.

8.1.13.3. **Prescription. Protect northern long-eared bats from pesticides and other chemicals**

Action. Once a northern long-eared bat is documented on Fort Riley, all conservation practices described in Section VI of the Biological Evaluation (USAEC 2015) concerning construction, forest management, prescribed burning, and tree removal will be fully implemented on the installation. In instances where a desired action is not described in the Biological Evaluation, or effects are anticipated that are different from those described, the installation will consult with USFWS prior to initiating that action.

8.1.13.4. **Prescription. Protect from disturbance roosting northern long-eared bats, if they occur on Fort Riley**

Action. If a northern long-eared bat roost is located on Fort Riley, a "*no disturbance*" buffer zone will be established around the roost if required to protect the species. The size, duration and limitations of the zone will be determined after consultation with the USFWS.

Action. If hibernating northern long-eared bats are discovered on Fort Riley, they will not be disturbed by human intrusion into hibernacula without prior consultation with the USFWS.

8.1.13.5. **Prescription. Educate Fort Riley personnel of any requirement to protect northern long-eared bats**

Action. Inform pilots if “*no disturbance*” buffer zones are in effect around hibernacula. Information will be provided to aviators through Local NOTAMS (Notices to AirMen) regarding “*no disturbance*” zones to minimize aircraft conflicts with roosting bats.

Action. Develop programs, *if needed*, to publicize the requirements of northern long-eared bat conservation to all Department of Army personnel and contractors, and outdoor enthusiasts, who work, train or recreate on Fort Riley.

Northern Long-eared Bat Monitoring Plan

These surveys are intended to determine presence or probable absence of northern long-eared bats on Fort Riley during the summer. There are no protocols currently available to survey during migration. Summer presence/absence surveys will be conducted following guidance⁴. Supplemental survey efforts, if any, will be coordinated with USFWS if any northern long-eared bats are encountered to further evaluate use of the area.

Fort Riley will use a tiered survey plan. Type 1 surveys will be performed to search for northern long-eared bats across Fort Riley. Type 2 surveys will be performed only after Type 1 surveys document presence of northern long-eared bats. Type 2 surveys will evaluate presence or probable absence of northern long-eared bats when future actions on Fort Riley may affect potential habitat when northern long-eared bats are expected to occupy such habitat. Negative presence results from Type 2 surveys obtained following this protocol will be considered valid for a minimum of two years.

The following provides a step-by-step outline of how Fort Riley will conduct northern long-eared bat summer surveys. The summer survey period will be from May 15 through August 15. The presence or probable absence of northern long-eared bats may be determined by conducting either acoustic or mist-netting surveys, as outlined below. Surveys will be conducted in the best suitable habitat possible to increase the likelihood of detection.

8.1.14. Acoustic surveys for northern long-eared bat breeding on Fort Riley

The acoustic sampling period begins at sunset and ends at sunrise each night of sampling.

8.1.14.1. Acoustic Survey Types

8.1.14.1.1. Type 1 Surveys

- Stationary surveys will consist of at least two detector nights in each of eight locations, as depicted in Exhibit C.8.
- Mobile surveys will consist of at least two nights each of vehicle-mounted detectors driven along two monitoring routes, as depicted in Exhibit C.9. Survey speed is not to exceed 20 mph.

⁴ The northern long-eared bat Interim Conference and Planning Guidance (<http://www.fws.gov/midwest/conservation/mammals/nlba/index.html>) states surveys should follow guidance for Indiana Bat Summer Survey. It is expected USFWS will inform Fort Riley if changes to this guidance occurs.

8.1.14.1.2. Type 2 Surveys (performed as needed)

- In linear habitats, surveys will consist of a minimum of two detector nights per km of suitable summer habitat potentially affected by the project.
- In non-linear habitats, surveys will consist of a minimum of 4 detector nights per 50 ha of suitable summer habitat potentially affected by the project. Two detector locations per 50 ha site shall be sampled until at least 4 detector nights have been completed over the course of at least 2 calendar nights (may be consecutive). For example:
 - Two detectors for 2 nights each (can sample same location or move within site).
 - One detector for 4 nights (must sample at least 2 locations).

8.1.14.2. Personnel

Acoustic surveyors will have a working knowledge of the equipment, acoustic analysis programs and northern long-eared bat ecology. Surveyors will be able to identify appropriate detector placement sites and establish those sites in the areas that are most suitable for recording high-quality calls.

8.1.14.3. Acoustic Sampling Protocol

8.1.14.3.1. Detector and Microphone Required Characteristics

Several factors were considered when selecting hardware for the acoustic monitoring program. A suitable detector must work with both stationary and mobile monitoring, must have the ability to detect Fort Riley's bat species, and should collect/process data that can be managed easily. A general literature search revealed that Anabat detectors are commonly used by researchers to detect many species of bats all around the world. Species with relatively quiet calls, such as the northern long-eared bat, can be difficult to detect. Several peer reviewed journal articles are published detailing the detection of this species using Anabat (Ford et al. 2011; Jachowski et al. 2014). Kim Livengood from Titley Scientific stated that Anabat detectors will readily detect northern long-eared bats provided that proper techniques are used and suitable habitat is sampled (personal communication).

Anabat uses a zero crossing algorithm to extract the primary frequency of a bat call. One benefit of zero crossing is that a small file is created for each bat call. This allows the user to collect a large amount of data in the field without concern for data storage limitations. Conversely, full spectrum detectors capture more details of the call, but require more data storage space and time for processing. Allen et al. (2011) found that it took 200 hours to process a batch of full spectrum files and only 2 hours to process a similar batch of zero crossing files.

After comparing features of multiple brands and types of bat detectors, the Anabat SD2 bat detector from Titley Scientific was selected because it best met Fort Riley's general research needs and is sufficient for difficult to detect species such as the northern long-eared bat.

Directional microphones are the only type accepted for acoustic surveys at this time, although omnidirectional microphones that have been converted to directional microphones are also acceptable. Microphones attached to detectors via a cable are also acceptable.

8.1.14.3.2. Detector/Microphone Placement

Suitable set-up of the equipment should result in high-quality call sequences that are adequate for species identification. Nights of sampling at individual sites that produce no bat calls may need to be re-sampled. Modifications of the equipment (e.g., changing the orientation) at the same location on subsequent nights may improve quantity and quality of call sequences recorded, which can be determined through daily data downloads. If modifications to the equipment do not improve call identification, then the detectors should be moved to a new location.

The Anabat SD2 is a good option for mobile transects. It accepts a corded microphone that can mount on the roof of a vehicle and can be used with a GPS enabled handheld computer (PDA) to see and hear calls in real time, tagging each call file with a GPS location.

Suitable sites for detectors at stationary surveys are forest-canopy openings, water sources, wooded fence lines adjacent to large openings or that connect two larger blocks of suitable habitat, road or stream corridors with open tree canopies or canopy height of more than 10 meters, and woodland edges (Britzke et al. 2010). When selecting acoustic sites, detectors should be: at least 1.5 meters in any direction from vegetation or other obstruction (Hayes 2000; Weller and Zabel 2002); in areas without, or with minimal⁵ vegetation within 10 meters in front of the microphone; parallel to woodland edges; and at least 15 meters from known or suitable roosts (e.g., trees/snags, buildings, bridges, or bat houses). Elevating a detector greater than 1.5 meters above ground level vegetation can improve recording quality. The Anabat SD2 is a good option for stationary monitoring. The corded microphone is easily elevated on an extension pole to capture higher quality calls.

Once acoustic sites are identified, photographs documenting the orientation, detection cone and relative position of the microphone should be taken.

Surveyors should distribute acoustic sites throughout the area. In most cases, acoustic sites should be at least 200 meters apart.

8.1.14.3.3. Orientation

Detectors deployed near the ground (e.g., on a tripod) should be aimed 45 degrees or more above horizontal. Microphones deployed higher within the flight path/zone (e.g., on a pole) should be oriented horizontally. In some circumstances (e.g., forest openings), it might be desirable to aim a detector's microphone vertically.

8.1.14.3.4. Verification of Deployment Location

GPS units will record accurate location coordinates for each acoustic site that is paired with the acoustic data files.

⁵ Surveyors can remove small amounts of vegetation (e.g., small limbs, saplings) from the estimated detection cone at a site, as is done while setting up mist-nets. Deployment of detectors in closed-canopy locations that typically are good for mist-netting are acceptable as long as the area sampled below the canopy does not restrict the ability of the equipment's detection cone to record high-quality calls (i.e., the vegetation is outside of the detection cone).

8.1.14.3.5. Verification of Proper Functioning

Surveyors will ensure equipment is working during set-up in the field. This can be done by producing ultrasound (e.g., finger rubs) in front of the microphone at survey start and survey finish. This documents that the equipment was working when deployed and when picked up (and by assumption throughout the period).

Detector field settings (e.g., sensitivity, frequency, etc.) should follow the recommendations provided by the manufacturer. Surveyors should also save files produced by detectors (e.g., log files, status files, sensor files) to provide documentation when equipment was functioning within the survey period.

8.1.14.3.6. Weather Conditions

At a minimum, nightly weather conditions for survey sites should be checked. If any of the following weather conditions existed during acoustic sampling, repeat the acoustic sampling effort for that night.

- Temperatures fall below 50°F during the first 5 hours of survey period.
- Precipitation, including fog, exceeding 30 minutes or occurs intermittently during the first 5 hours of the survey period.
- Sustained wind speeds greater than 9 miles/hour (3 on Beaufort scale) during the first 5 hours of the survey period.

8.1.14.3.7. Weatherproofing

The decision to use weatherproofing will be based on the likelihood of precipitation. The Anabat SD2 is a good option for weatherproofing. The corded microphone allows the user to detach the microphone from the detector so that the detector is placed in a weatherproof container while the microphone remains unobstructed.

8.1.14.4. Analysis of Recorded Echolocation Calls

8.1.14.4.1. Acoustic Analysis

The number of bat calls recorded in a single survey night can be in the hundreds, and it is not feasible to identify all of the calls manually. The USFWS approved BCID East, EchoClass, Kaleidoscope Pro and SonoBat for acoustic analyses.

- Acoustic analysis will be conducted on all data collected from Type 1 and Type 2 surveys using the acoustic ID programs 'EchoClass' and 'BCID'.
- If northern long-eared bat presence is considered unlikely by both programs, then no further summer surveys of that area will be conducted and it will be assumed none are present.
- If northern long-eared bat presence is considered likely at least once, then proceed to Qualitative Analysis.

8.1.14.4.2. Qualitative Analysis.

- For each site/night a program considered northern long-eared bat presence likely, review all files from that site/night. A program such as AnaloookW will be used to create spectrograms of the calls. These spectrograms will be visually compared to species-specific spectrograms from a known call library.
- Qualitative analysis will compare the results of each acoustic ID program by site and night, including: the number of call files flagged as probable northern long-eared bat by each

program; an evaluation of other species identified; individual file level agreements and disagreements on northern long-eared bat between programs; a qualitative analysis of all probable northern long-eared bat call sequences to further evaluate whether the correct ID has been made by the program(s) used.

- If no visual confirmation of probable northern long-eared bat is detected during qualitative analysis, then no further summer surveys of that area will be conducted and it will be assumed no northern long-eared bats are present.
- If visual confirmation of probable northern long-eared bat is detected during qualitative analysis, then assume presence and coordinate with the USFWS.

8.1.15. Mist-netting surveys for northern long-eared bat breeding on Fort Riley

Mist-netting can be used as a presence or probable absence method or it can be conducted for the purpose of attempting to capture northern long-eared bat after detection during acoustic surveys. The same protocol applies for both uses of mist-netting surveys. Capture of reproductive adult females (i.e., pregnant, lactating, or post-lactating) and/or young of the year confirms the presence of a maternity colony in the area. The survey period for each net shall begin at sunset and continue for at least five hours.

8.1.15.1. Mist-Netting as Type 2 presence/probable absence surveys

- In linear habitats, surveys will consist of a minimum of 4 net nights per km of suitable summer habitat
- In non-linear habitats, surveys will consist of a minimum of 9 net nights per 50 ha of suitable summer habitat. For example:
 - 3 sites⁶, 1 net⁷/site for 3 calendar nights = 9 net nights
 - 1 sites, 3 nets/site for 3 calendar nights = 9 net nights
- There is a maximum of 3 nights of consecutive netting at any given net location. After 3 consecutive nights of netting at the same location, surveyors must change net locations or wait at least 2 calendar nights before resuming netting at the same location.
 - If no capture of northern long-eared bat, then no further summer surveys are necessary and it will be assumed none are present.
 - If northern long-eared bat is captured then Fort Riley will notify USFWS and stop mist-netting.

8.1.15.2. Mist-netting After Positive Acoustic Finding

If mist-netting was not conducted as the presence or probable absence method, then it may be conducted to capture and characterize (e.g., sex, age, reproductive condition) the northern long-eared bat presence in an area. Fort Riley will work with the USFWS to develop mist-netting plans. There are no minimum requirements for this phase as this is not a presence or probable absence survey.

⁶ A site is defined as a geographic area to be sampled. It can include one or more nets.

⁷ A net is defined as any combination of individual panels and poles (e.g., single, double, triple high) to fill the area (e.g., corridor) being sampled.

8.1.15.3. Personnel

A qualified biologist⁸ will select or approve mist-net set-ups in areas that are most suitable, be physically present at each mist-net site throughout the survey period, confirm all bat species' identifications, and oversee and manage mist-net set-ups in close proximity to one another if the net-check timing (i.e., every 10 minutes) can be maintained while walking between nets.

8.1.15.4. Equipment.

Surveys will use the finest, lowest visibility mesh mist-nets as practicable. Currently, the finest net on the market is 75 denier, 2 ply, denoted 75/2 (Arndt and Schaetz 2009); however, the 50 denier nets are still acceptable for use. The preferred mesh size available is approximately 1½ inches (38 millimeters). There are many suitable systems of ropes and/or poles to hold nets. The system of Gardner et al. (1989) has been widely used.

To minimize potential for disease transmission, any equipment that comes in contact with bats should be cleaned and disinfected, following approved protocols; this is particularly a concern in white-nose syndrome areas. Protocols are posted at <http://www.whitenosesyndrome.org/>.

8.1.15.5. Net Placement.

Potential travel corridors (e.g., streams, trails) typically are the most effective places to net (although other places may also be productive; see Carroll et al. 2002). Place nets approximately perpendicular across the corridor, filling the corridor from side to side, extending beyond the corridor boundaries when possible, and from stream (or ground) level up to the overhanging canopy. Nets of varying widths and heights may be used as the situation dictates. If over water, there is to be enough space between the net and the water so that captured bats will not get wet.

Occasionally it may be necessary or desirable to net where a suitable corridor is lacking. In these situations, the surveyors will use their experience and best judgment to employ an alternative net design, such as in Humphrey et al. (1968) and Kiser and MacGregor (2005).

Surveyors will distribute net set-ups throughout suitable habitat. Net set-ups may be repeatedly sampled throughout the project, but generally no more than 2-3 nights at a single location. Photos to document placement of nets will be taken.

8.1.15.6. Checking Nets

- Each net should be checked every 10 minutes, never exceeding 15 minutes.
- Surveyors will minimize noise, lights and movement near the nets.
- Monitoring the nets with a bat detector can be beneficial.
- Biologists should be prepared to cut the net if a bat is severely entangled and cannot be safely extracted within 3 or 4 minutes.

⁸ A qualified biologist is an individual who holds a USFWS Recovery Permit for NLEB in the state in which they are surveying and/or has been authorized by the state agency to net and handle NLEB.

8.1.15.7. **Handling Bats**

Capture and handling are stressful for bats. Northern long-eared bats should not be held for more than 30 minutes after capture. See Kunz and Kurta (1988) for general recommendations.

8.1.15.8. **Weather and Light Conditions**

Negative surveys combined with any of the following weather conditions throughout all or most of a sampling period may require an additional night of mist-netting:

- Temperatures that fall below 50°F.
- Precipitation, including heavy fog, which exceeds 30 minutes or continues intermittently during the survey period.
- Sustained wind speeds greater than 9 miles/hour (3 on Beaufort scale).

It is best to place net set-ups under the canopy where they are out of moonlight, particularly when the moon is half-full or greater. Net set-ups illuminated by artificial light sources should also be avoided.

8.1.15.9. **Documentation of NLEB Captures**

Species of bats from the genus *Myotis* share common physical characteristics, making identification difficult. Therefore, photo-documentation of all bats identified as northern long-eared bats and the first 10 little brown myotis captured per area will verify the identifications made in the field. Photo-documentation should include; a $\frac{3}{4}$ -view of face showing ear, tragus and muzzle, a view of calcar showing presence/absence of keel, and a transverse view of toes showing extent of toe hairs.

If a bat from the genus *Myotis* is captured that cannot be readily identified to the species level, then species verification may be attempted through fecal DNA analysis.

- Collect fecal pellets from the bat in question by placing it temporarily in a holding bag (no more than 30 minutes).
- Place pellets collected in a small vial with silica gel desiccant.
- Store pellets from individual bats in separate vials and out of direct light.
- A list of available laboratories that analyze fecal pellets is at (<http://www.fws.gov/midwest/Endangered/mammals/inba/index.html>).

If a northern long-eared bat is captured, the USFWS and KDWPT offices will be notified of the capture within two business days (or in accordance with permit conditions).

8.1.16. Submission of survey results

Fort Riley will provide results of acoustic and mist-netting surveys to the USFWS.

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Exhibit C.8. Stationary acoustic survey locations for NLEB on Fort Riley in 2014. Surveys will consist of at least two detector nights in each of eight locations

Exhibit C.9. Driven acoustic survey locations for NLEB on Fort Riley in 2014. Surveys will consist of at least two nights of vehicle-mounted detectors driven along each monitoring route.

9.0 WHOOPING CRANE MANAGEMENT PLAN

Introduction

This management plan is based on and is consistent with the ESA, the Kansas Nongame and Endangered Species Conservation Act of 1975, and Army Regulations. This plan does not supersede ESA Section 7 consultation requirements with the USFWS or replace the need to obtain special permits from the KDWP. Any action that may directly or indirectly affect the whooping crane must be coordinated with the USFWS and KDWP by the Conservation Branch, except under the circumstances described below.

Whooping Crane Information

9.1.1. Description

The whooping crane (*Grus americanus*) is the tallest bird in North America, standing five feet tall. An adult's snow-white plumage contrasts with its black wing tips, black legs, black facial "mustache", and a crimson patch on the crown of the head. Flying snow geese (*Chen caerulescens*) and American white pelicans (*Pelicanus erythrorhynchos*) resemble whooping cranes as all exhibit white plumage with black wing tips. Whooping cranes are readily distinguished from these species in flight by their long extended neck and legs and greater overall size. Standing whooping cranes may be confused with the great egret (*Casmerodius albus*), another large, white wading bird. Great egrets lack the black moustache and crimson crown patch. Adult sandhill cranes (*Grus canadensis*) have a similar crimson crown patch, but are uniformly gray in color. Juvenile whooping cranes are light cinnamon brown with a white belly, but will be accompanied by adult birds in adult plumage.

9.1.2. Habitat/Ecology

The only natural wild flock of whooping cranes breeds in marshes at Wood Buffalo National Park in Canada, and winters along the Texas coast on salt flats and islands in and around Aransas National Wildlife Refuge (Armbruster 1990). They make biannual, migratory flights between their breeding and wintering grounds. The spring and fall migration paths tend to follow a narrow route that is nearly a straight line between the two areas (Johnson and Temple 1980; USFWS 2007), passing over central Kansas (Exhibit C.10).

Whooping cranes stop during migration to feed and roost. Stopover sites may be used for one or more nights. Sites are selected opportunistically from habitat available when cranes are ready to land. Whooping cranes feed on a variety of aquatic and terrestrial plants and animals. They select wetland habitat for roosting, using rivers and marsh complexes. Preferred riverine roost habitat has a wide channel with low, exposed, barren sandbars, shallow water, low flow velocity, low banks, no riparian timber and isolation from human disturbance (Johnson and Temple 1980, USFWS 1981, Howe 1987, Armbruster 1990).

9.1.3. Distribution

Whooping cranes historically ranged east of the Rocky Mountains in North America. This species apparently was not abundant prior to the Europeans' arrival into North America. The pre-1870 population estimate is 1,300-1,400 birds (Armbruster 1990). Non-migratory populations existed

along the Louisiana and Florida coasts, and migratory populations followed four different routes. The two most important routes travelled between the upper midwestern United States and Louisiana, and between central Canada and the Texas coast (USFWS 2007). Currently, the only self-sustaining population is the population migrating between Canada and Texas, where surveys in March 2015 counted 314 whooping cranes (USFWS 2015a). A migratory flock of whoopers has been established that travels between Wisconsin and the Florida Gulf Coast (USFWS 2007), which numbers around 100 birds (WCEP 2015). A non-migratory flock is being reestablished in Louisiana and currently numbers around 46 cranes (Masson 2015). Approximately 160 birds are housed in captivity (USFWS 2015b).

Whooping cranes occur in Kansas only during migratory stopover periods. These stopover sites occur both within and outside of the primary flight corridor. The species has been recorded in Kansas from February 10 through April 28, and from October 5 through December 6 (Thompson and Ely 1989; KSBIRD-L).

Fort Riley is located approximately 80 miles east of the whooping crane's primary flight corridor. Whooping cranes have been sighted in Geary and Riley counties (Thompson and Ely 1989), but none on Fort Riley. There are six documented records of whooping cranes near Fort Riley since 1991; two from Riley County (Rocky Ford, 3 birds 1998; Zeandale, 5 birds, 2009), one from Wabaunsee County (Kansas River at St. Mary's, 2 birds, 1991), and three from Clay County (Smith Bottoms, 1 bird, 2000; Milford Lake, 1 bird, 2008; Steve Lloyd Wetland, 3 birds, 2015).

USFWS evaluated FRK for whooping crane habitat using habitat variables described in Carlson et al. (1990). The majority of habitat was determined to be of suboptimal quality for use by roosting cranes (USFWS 1992). Poor lateral visibility due to woody riverbank vegetation and lack of isolation from human activity were the two most important criteria resulting in the suboptimal rating.

9.1.4. Reasons for Listing

The number of free-ranging whooping cranes within the Aransas population had fallen to 16 birds by 1942 (USFWS 2007). The loss of nesting and wintering habitat due to human development and agricultural expansion were the primary factors involved in the population decline (Johnson and Temple, 1980). Other factors involved were the increased hazards of migration resulting from human activities, winter storms, the cranes low reproductive rate, and their inability to recolonize suitable habitat within their former range. The whooping crane was listed as endangered in 1970, and was grandfathered into the ESA when it was ratified in 1973 (USFWS 2007).

9.1.5. Conservation Measures

A captive breeding flock of whooping cranes has been developed from eggs taken from the wild and hatched in captivity. These hand-reared birds have been supplemented by birds permanently injured and captured from the wild. Young produced from these captive birds are released back into the wild in attempts to establish additional breeding populations.

Whooping Crane Conservation Goals

9.1.6. Protect individual whooping cranes

9.1.7. Document any occurrence of a whooping crane on Fort Riley

Whooping Crane Management Prescriptions and Actions

9.1.8. Protect individual whooping cranes from human-induced injury

Disruption, intrusion, or obstruction of roosting and foraging areas can negatively affect whooping cranes. Certain activities in or near whooping cranes can interfere with feeding and resting behavior. Airboats, low altitude aircraft, and especially helicopters cause disturbance (USFWS 2007). Where a human activity agitates or bothers whooping cranes to the degree that it interferes with feeding or sheltering behavior, the conduct of that activity constitutes a violation of the ESA prohibition against disturbing an endangered species and may be prosecutable as a taking. While Fort Riley proper does not provide any apparent habitat suitable for whooping cranes, Fort Riley aircraft occasionally has flown over areas that have documented presence of this species. Further, Fort Riley aircraft will continue to fly over areas apparently suitable for whooping cranes into the future.

The presence of unmarked power lines, towers and other structures into which whooping cranes may fly is hazardous. Many transmission lines, poles, and towers exist on Fort Riley. All may pose some degree of threat to this species. However, techniques are available to reduce the hazard.

9.1.8.1. **Prescription. Protect whooping cranes from disturbance by Fort Riley aircraft**

Action. Monitor local bird sighting reports. There are many forums used by bird-watchers to record, report and inform other users of the occurrence of rare or interesting birds. These include eBird, Facebook, and email list-serves. Fort Riley Conservation Staff will monitor these and similar forums to stay apprised of incidents when whooping cranes are present over areas where Fort Riley aircraft may operate. Additionally, Fort Riley staff requests USFWS and KDWP provide similar confidential reports received.

Action. Restrict aircraft flight when whooping cranes are present. A "no fly" buffer zone will be established and maintained around the area being used by one or more whooping cranes. An altitude restriction of 2,000 AGL (610 m) will be in effect for the "no fly" zone. The width of the zone will vary, dependent upon the location and expected use of the area by the cranes. Generally, this width will range from 0.5 NM (926 m) to 1.5 NM (2.78 km). The duration of the "no fly" zone will be for as long as any whooping crane is using that area. Biological survey flights and emergency situations, including unusual weather conditions, are the only exceptions to these restrictions.

Action. Inform pilots when "no fly" zones are in effect. Information will be provided to aviators through Local NOTAMS (Notices to AirMen) regarding "no fly" zones to minimize aircraft conflicts with whooping cranes. Additional programs will be developed, as needed.

9.1.8.2. **Prescription. Protect whooping cranes found on Fort Riley**

Action. A "no disturbance" buffer zone will be established around any whooping crane that is located on lands controlled by Fort Riley. This buffer zone will be enforced for as long as a

whooping crane remains in the area. Initially, the “*no disturbance*” buffer zone will be the training area(s) in which the whooping crane(s) occur, and will include a “*no fly*” zone. The size and limitations of the buffer zones may be adjusted after contact with the USFWS. Biological surveys and emergency situations are the only exceptions to these restrictions.

9.1.8.3. **Prescription. Minimize the risk of whooping crane collisions with aerial structures**

Action. Techniques are available to mark or otherwise design aerial structures so that the striking hazard is eliminated or greatly reduced. Line markers, such as aviation balls and colored spiral dampers, and similar markers for towers and guy lines may be used to make these structures more visible to whooping cranes. Any projects to construct new or modify existing aerial structures on Fort Riley will be reviewed by Conservation Branch staff at least 30 days prior to project implementation to determine whether line markers are needed. Areas of particular concern occur within one mile of a river or Milford Lake because these may be used as travel lanes.

9.1.9. **Improve detection and reporting of whooping cranes**

9.1.9.1. **Prescription. Improve detection and reporting of whooping cranes**

Action. Fort Riley personnel should learn to recognize whooping cranes, and be made aware of the importance of promptly reporting encounters with this bird in the field. Conservation staff will verify sighting reports from non-affiliated personnel prior to establishing “*no fly*” zones, as false reports of great egrets or American white pelicans as whooping cranes are expected.

Additional programs will be developed, as needed, to publicize whooping crane identification to other persons who work, train, or are outdoors during daylight hours on Fort Riley.

Whooping Crane Monitoring Plan

Whooping cranes require foraging and roost sites during migration. They forage in agricultural fields, upland pastures and wetlands during daylight hours. The potential for cranes to occur in a large variety of habitats while foraging makes it inefficient to search for feeding cranes outside of traditionally used locations. Few potential roost sites exist on Fort Riley, as the majority of habitat is deemed to possess suboptimal quality for roosting cranes (USFWS 1992). Therefore, no monitoring other than that described in section 9.4.2.1 will occur.

Whooping Crane Literature Cited

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Exhibit C.10. Whooping crane primary migration corridor between wintering and breeding grounds. (From USFWS Whooping Crane International Recovery Plan, 3rd Revision)

APPENDIX D.**Memorandum Of Understanding between the U.S. Department of Defense and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service to promote the conservation of migratory birds**

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) is entered into between the U.S. Department of Defense (DoD) and the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (FWS) (hereinafter “the Parties”).

A. Purpose and Scope

Pursuant to Executive Order 13186 (January 17, 2001), Responsibilities of Federal Agencies to Protect Migratory Birds, this MOU outlines a collaborative approach to promote the conservation of migratory bird populations.

This MOU does not address incidental take during military readiness activities, which is being addressed in a rulemaking in accordance with section 315 of the National Defense Authorization Act for Fiscal Year 2003 (Pub. L. 107-314, 116 Stat. 2458).

This MOU specifically pertains to the following categories of DoD activities:

- (1) Natural resource management activities, including, but not limited to, habitat management, erosion control, forestry activities, agricultural outleasing, conservation law enforcement, invasive weed management, and prescribed burning;
- (2) Installation support functions, including but not limited to, the maintenance, construction or operation of administrative offices, military exchanges, road construction, commissaries, water treatment facilities, storage facilities, schools, housing, motor pools, non-tactical equipment, laundries, morale, welfare, and recreation activities, shops, landscaping, and mess halls;
- (3) Operation of industrial activities;
- (4) Construction or demolition of facilities relating to these routine operations; and
- (5) Hazardous waste cleanup.

This MOU identifies specific activities where cooperation between the Parties will contribute substantially to the conservation of migratory birds and their habitats. This MOU does not authorize the take of migratory birds.

B. Authorities

The Parties’ responsibilities under the MOU are authorized by provisions of the following laws:

Alaska National Interest Lands Conservation Act of 1980 (16 USC 410hh-3233)

Bald and Golden Eagle Protection Act of 1940 (16 U.S.C. 668-668d)
Endangered Species Act of 1973 (16 U.S.C. 1531 et seq.)
Fish and Wildlife Act of 1956 (16 U.S.C. 742 et seq.)
Fish and Wildlife Conservation Act of 1980 (16 U.S.C. 2901-2911)
Fish and Wildlife Coordination Act (16 U.S.C. 661-667)
Migratory Bird Conservation Act (16 U.S.C. 715-715d, 715e, 715f-715r)
Migratory Bird Treaty Act (16 U.S.C. 703-711)
National Environmental Policy Act of 1969 (42 U.S.C. 4321-4347)
Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997 (16 USC 670a-670o) Agreements to limit encroachments and other constraints on military training, testing, and operations (10 U.S.C. § 2684a)

C. Background

The Parties have a common interest in the conservation and management of America's natural resources. The Parties agree that migratory birds are important components of biological diversity and that the conservation of migratory birds will both help sustain ecological systems and help meet the public demand for conservation education and outdoor recreation, such as wildlife viewing and hunting opportunities. The Parties also agree that it is important to: 1) focus on bird populations; 2) focus on habitat restoration and enhancement where actions can benefit specific ecosystems and migratory birds dependent upon them; and 3) recognize that actions taken to benefit some migratory bird populations may adversely affect other migratory bird populations.

The DoD mission is to provide for the Nation's defense. DoD's conservation program works to ensure continued access to land, air, and water resources for realistic military training and testing while ensuring that the natural and cultural resources entrusted to DoD's care are sustained in a healthy condition.

The DoD is an active participant in international bird conservation partnerships including Partners in Flight (PIF) and the North American Bird Conservation Initiative (NABCI). Military lands frequently provide some of the best remaining habitat for migratory bird species of concern, and DoD plans to continue its leadership role in bird conservation partnerships.

Through the PIF initiative, DoD works in partnership with numerous Federal and State agencies and nongovernmental organizations for the conservation of migratory and resident birds and to enhance migratory bird survival. Through DoD PIF, a list of species of concern (see Definitions) has been developed for each Bird Conservation Region where DoD facilities occur, thus improving DoD's ability to evaluate any migratory bird conservation concerns on respective DoD lands.

Integrated Natural Resources Management Plans (INRMPs) offer a coordinated approach for incorporating habitat conservation efforts into installation management. INRMPs are a significant source of baseline conservation information and conservation initiatives used when preparing National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) documents for all DoD management activities. This linkage helps to ensure that appropriate conservation and mitigation measures are identified in NEPA documents and committed to, when appropriate, in final decision documents.

The DoD PIF program provides a framework for incorporating landbird, shorebird and waterbird habitat management efforts into INRMPs. DoD's strategy focuses on inventorying and long-term monitoring to determine changes in migratory bird populations on DoD installations. Effective on-the-ground management may then be applied to those areas identified as having the highest conservation value. DoD's PIF goal is to support the military's training and testing mission while being a vital and supportive partner in regional, national, and international bird conservation initiatives. DoD strives to implement cooperative projects and programs on military lands to benefit the health and well-being of birds and their habitats, whenever possible. The Department of Defense implements bird inventories and monitoring programs in numerous ways including Monitoring Avian Productivity and Survivorship (MAPS) and Next Generation Radar (NEXRAD) for studying bird movements in the atmosphere. DoD also maintains an integrated pest management (IPM) program designed to reduce the use of pesticides to the minimum necessary.

The mission of the FWS is to work with others to conserve, protect, manage, and enhance fish, wildlife, plants, and their habitats for the continuing benefit of the American people. The FWS is legally mandated to implement the provisions of the Migratory Bird Treaty Act (MBTA), which include responsibilities for population management (e.g., monitoring), habitat protection (e.g., acquisition, enhancement, and modification), international coordination, and regulation development and enforcement. The FWS also promotes migratory bird conservation through its coordination and consultation efforts with other entities.

Many FWS programs are involved in bird conservation activities, including:

- (1) The Division of Migratory Bird Management and Regional Migratory Birds and Habitat Programs serve as focal points in the United States for policy development and strategic planning, developing and implementing monitoring and management initiatives that help maintain healthy populations of migratory birds and their habitat, and providing continued opportunities for citizens to enjoy bird-related recreation.
- (2) The Division of Bird Habitat Conservation is instrumental in supporting habitat conservation partnerships through the administration of bird conservation grant programs and development of Joint Ventures that serve as major vehicles for implementing the various bird conservation plans across the country.
- (3) Ecological Services Field Offices across the country serve as the primary contacts for environmental reviews that include, when requested, projects developed by local military installations and DoD regional offices involving migratory bird issues. The Field Offices coordinate with the Regional Migratory Bird Offices, as necessary, during these reviews regarding permits and overall migratory bird conservation coordination for DoD activities.
- (4) The Office of Law Enforcement is the principal FWS program that enforces the legal provisions of the MBTA.

The Parties agree this MOU shall be implemented to the extent permitted by law and in harmony with agency missions, subject to the availability of appropriations and budgetary limits.

D. Responsibilities

1. Each Party shall:

a. Emphasize an interdisciplinary, collaborative approach to migratory bird conservation in cooperation with other governments, State and Federal agencies, and non-federal partners within the geographic framework of the NABCI Bird Conservation Regions

b. Strive to protect, restore, enhance, and manage habitat of migratory birds, and prevent or minimize the loss or degradation of habitats on DoD- managed lands, by:

(1) Identifying and avoiding management actions that have the potential to adversely affect migratory bird populations, including breeding, migration, or wintering habitats; and by developing and implementing, as appropriate, conservation measures that would avoid or minimize the take of migratory birds or enhance the quality of the habitat used by migratory birds.;

(2) Working with partners to identify, conserve, and manage Important Bird Areas, Western Hemisphere Shorebird Reserve Network sites, and other significant bird conservation sites that occur on DoD-managed lands;

(3) Preventing or abating the pollution or detrimental alteration of the habitats used by migratory birds;

(4) Developing and integrating information on migratory birds and their habitats into outreach and education materials and activities; and

(5) Controlling the introduction, establishment, and spread of non-native plants or animals that may be harmful to migratory bird populations, as required by Executive Order 13112 on Invasive Species.

c. Work with willing landowners to prevent or minimize the loss or degradation of migratory bird habitats on lands adjacent or near military installation boundaries. This cooperative conservation may include:

(1) Participating in efforts to identify, protect, and conserve important migratory bird habitats or other significant bird conservation sites and ecological conditions that occur in landscapes or watersheds that may be affected by activities on DoD lands;

(2) Developing and integrating information on migratory bird resources found on DoD lands into other partners' outreach and education materials and activities; and

(3) Using available authorities to enter into agreements with other Federal agencies, States, other governmental entities, and private conservation organizations to conserve and enhance habitat in a compatible manner so military operations are not restricted.

d. Promote collaborative projects such as:

(1) Developing or using existing inventory and monitoring programs, at appropriate scales, with national or regional standardized protocols, to assess the status and trends of bird populations and habitats, including migrating, breeding, and wintering birds;

(2) Designing management studies and research projects using national or regional standardized protocols and programs, such as MAPS to identify the habitat conditions needed by applicable species of concern, to understand interrelationships of co-existing species, and to evaluate the effects of management activities on habitats and populations of migratory birds;

(3) Sharing inventory, monitoring, research, and study data for breeding, migrating, and wintering bird populations and habitats in a timely fashion with national data repositories such as Breeding Bird Research and Monitoring Database (BBIRD), National Point Count Database, National Biological Information Infrastructure, and MAPS;

(4) Working in conjunction with each other and other Federal and State agencies to develop reasonable and effective conservation measures for actions that affect migratory birds and their natural habitats;

(5) Participating in or promoting the implementation of existing regional or national inventory and monitoring programs such as Breeding Bird Survey (BBS), BBIRD, Christmas Bird Counts, bird atlas projects, or game bird surveys (e.g., mid-winter waterfowl surveys) on DoD lands where practicable and feasible.

(6) Using existing partnerships and exploring opportunities for expanding and creating new partnerships to facilitate combined funding for inventory, monitoring, management studies, and research.

e. Provide training opportunities to DoD natural resources personnel on migratory bird issues, to include bird population and habitat inventorying, monitoring

methods, and management practices that avert detrimental effects and promote beneficial approaches to migratory bird conservation.

f. Participate in the Interagency Council for the Conservation of Migratory Birds to evaluate implementation of this MOU.

g. Promote migratory bird conservation internationally, as it relates to wintering, breeding and migration habitats of birds that breed on DoD lands.

h. Promote and undertake ecologically sound actions to curb the introduction in the wild of exotic or invasive species harmful to migratory birds.

2. **The Department of Defense Shall:**

a. Follow all migratory bird permitting requirements for non-military readiness activities that are subject to 50 CFR Parts 21.22 (banding or marking), 21.23 (scientific collecting), 21.26 (special Canada goose permit), 21.27 (special purposes), or 21.41 (depredation). No permit is required to take birds in accordance with Parts 21.43 - 21.47 (depredation orders).

b. Encourage incorporation of comprehensive migratory bird management objectives in the preparation of DoD planning documents, including Integrated Natural Resource Management Plans, Pest Management Plans, Installation Master Plans, NEPA analyses, and non-military readiness elements of Bird Aircraft Strike Hazard documents. Comprehensive planning efforts for migratory birds include PIF Bird Conservation Plans, the North American Waterfowl Management Plan, U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, and North American Waterbird Conservation Plan and associated regional plans where available.

c. Incorporate conservation measures addressed in Regional or State Bird Conservation Plans in INRMPS.

d. Consistent with imperatives of safety and security, allow the FWS and other partners reasonable access to military lands for conducting sampling or survey programs such as MAPS, BBS, BBIRD, International Shorebird Survey, and breeding bird atlases.

e. Prior to starting any activity that is likely to affect populations of migratory birds:

(1) Identify the migratory bird species likely to occur in the area of the proposed action and determine if any species of concern could be affected by the activity;

(2) Assess and document, through the project planning process, using NEPA when applicable, the effect of the proposed action on species of

concern. Use best available demographic, population, or habitat association data in the assessment of effects upon species of concern;

(3) Engage in early planning and scoping with the FWS relative to potential impacts of a proposed action, to proactively address migratory bird conservation, and to initiate appropriate actions to avoid or minimize the take of migratory birds.

f. Manage military lands and non-military readiness activities in a manner that supports migratory bird conservation, giving consideration to the following factors:

(1) Habitat protection, restoration, and enhancement. Military lands contain many important habitats for migratory birds. Some unique, sensitive, endangered and/or declining habitat types that may require special management attention include:

(a) Grasslands. Many native grassland communities require intensive management to maintain and restore vigor and species diversity and to provide habitat for migratory birds and other wildlife dependent on native grasslands. Grassland management and restoration tools include controlled burning, mowing, grazing, native species planting, and exotic plant removal. Many grasslands have evolved with a natural fire regime, and the management activities often emulate this fire regime.

(b) Riparian and wetland habitats. Military lands contain riparian and wetland habitats that may be critical for migratory birds. DoD will strive to prevent the destruction or degradation of wetlands and riparian vegetation, and also restore those habitats, when feasible, where they have been degraded.

(c) Coastal beach, salt marsh, and dune habitats. Military lands support some of the best remaining undisturbed coastal habitats. DoD will strive to protect, restore and prevent the destruction of coastal and island habitats that are important to breeding, migrating and wintering shorebirds, salt marsh land birds and colonial water birds.

(d) Longleaf pine ecosystem. Some of the best remaining examples of the longleaf pine ecosystem occur on military lands. Such habitats benefit from prescribed fire and other management measures which DoD regularly implements on thousands of acres in the Southeast. The DoD manages and will continue to manage this ecosystem to benefit and promote migratory bird conservation.

(2) Fire and fuels management practices. Fire plays an important role in shaping plant and animal communities and is a valuable tool in restoring

habitats altered by decades of fire suppression. Fire management may include fire suppression, but also involves fire prevention and fuels treatment, including prescribed burning and monitoring, to protect communities and provide for healthy ecosystems. Fire management planning efforts will consider the effects of fire management strategies on the conservation of migratory bird populations.

(3) Invasive Species and Aquatic Nuisance Species management practices. Invasive Species and Aquatic Nuisance Species are a threat to native habitats and wildlife species throughout the United States, including military lands. Efforts to control/contain these species must take into account both the impacts from invasive species and the effects of the control efforts on migratory bird populations. Invasive Species and Aquatic Nuisance Species that can threaten migratory birds and their habitats include, but are not limited to, exotic grasses, trees and weeds, terrestrial and aquatic insects and organisms, non-native birds, and stray and feral cats.

(4) Communications towers, utilities and energy development. Increased communications demands, changes in technology and the development of alternative energy sources result in impacts on migratory birds. DoD will review wind turbine and powerline guidelines published by FWS and the Avian Power Line Interaction Committee, respectively, and consult with FWS as needed, in considering potential effects on migratory birds of proposals for locating communications towers, powerlines or wind turbines on military lands. Construction of new utility and energy systems and associated infrastructure should be designed to avoid and minimize impacts on migratory bird populations. Existing utilities may also be considered for retrofitting to reduce impacts.

(5) Recreation and public use. The demand for outdoor recreational opportunities on public lands is increasing. Impacts on migratory birds may occur both through direct and indirect disturbances by visitors and through agency activities associated with providing recreational opportunities to visitors and installation personnel and morale facilities (e.g., facilities construction). DoD provides access to military lands for recreation and other public use, such as Watchable Wildlife and bird watching, where such access does not compromise security and safety concerns or impact migratory birds, other species, or their habitats.

Many conservation measures have been developed to benefit a variety of migratory bird species and their associated habitats. Some of these conservation measures may be directly applicable to DoD non-military readiness related activities; however, the appropriateness and practicality of implementing any specific conservation measure may have to be determined on a case-by-case basis. The FWS will work cooperatively with DoD in

providing existing conservation measures and developing new ones as needed. Examples of some conservation measures may be found at <http://www.partnersinflight.org/pubs/BMPs.htm> for landbird species.

g. Develop and implement new and/or existing inventory and monitoring programs, at appropriate scales, using national standardized protocols, to evaluate the effectiveness of conservation measures to minimize or mitigate take of migratory birds, with emphasis on those actions that have the potential to significantly impact species of concern.

h. Advise the public of the availability of this MOU through a notice published in the Federal Register.

i. In accordance with DoD INRMP guidance, promote timely and effective review of INRMPs with respect to migratory bird issues with the FWS and respective state agencies. During the INRMP review process, evaluate and coordinate with FWS on any potential revisions to migratory bird conservation measures taken to avoid or minimize take of migratory birds.

3. **The Fish and Wildlife Service Shall:**

a. Work with DoD by providing recommendations to minimize adverse effects upon migratory birds from DoD actions.

b. Through the Division of Migratory Bird Management, maintain a Web page on permits that provides links to all offices responsible for issuing permits and permit application forms for take of migratory birds.

c. Provide essential background information to the DoD when requested to ensure sound management decisions. This may include migratory bird distributions, status, key habitats, conservation guidelines, and risk factors within each BCR. This includes updating the FWS publication of *Birds of Conservation Concern* at regular intervals so it can be reliably referenced.

d. Work to identify special migratory bird habitats (i.e., migration corridors, stop-over habitats, ecological conditions important in nesting habitats) to aid in collaborative planning.

e. Through the Ecological Service Field Office, provide to DoD, upon request, technical assistance on migratory bird species and their habitats.

f. In accordance with FWS Guidelines for Coordination with DoD and Implementation of the 1997 Sikes Act (2005), work cooperatively with DoD in the development, review and revision of INRMPs.

g. Review and comment on NEPA documents and other planning documents forwarded by military installations.

E. It is Mutually Agreed and Understood That:

1. This MOU will not change or alter requirements associated with the MBTA, Endangered Species Act, NEPA, Sikes Act or other statutes or legal authority.
2. The responsibilities established by this MOU may be incorporated into existing DoD actions; however, DoD may not be able to implement some responsibilities identified in the MOU until DoD has successfully included them in formal planning processes. This MOU is intended to be implemented when new actions are initiated as well as during the initiation of new, or revisions to, INRMPs, Pest Management Plans, and non-military readiness elements of Bird Aircraft Strike Hazard plans. It does not apply to ongoing DoD actions for which a NEPA decision document was finalized prior to, or within 180 days of the date this MOU is signed.
3. This MOU in no way restricts either Party from participating in similar activities with other public or private agencies, governments, organizations, or individuals.
4. An elevation process to resolve any dispute between the Parties regarding a particular practice or activity is in place and consists of first attempting to resolve the dispute with the DoD military installation and the responsible Ecological Services Field Office. If there is no resolution at this level, either Party may elevate the issue to the appropriate officials at the applicable Military Service's Chain of Command and FWS Regional Offices. In the event that there is no resolution by these offices, the dispute may be elevated by either Party to the headquarters office of each agency.
5. This MOU is neither a fiscal nor a funds obligation document. Any endeavor involving reimbursement, contribution of funds, or transfer of anything of value between the Parties will be handled in accordance with applicable laws, regulations, and procedures, including those for government procurement and printing. Such endeavors will be outlined in separate agreements that shall be made in writing by representatives of the Parties and shall be independently authorized by appropriate statutory authority.
6. The Parties shall schedule periodic meetings to review progress and identify opportunities for advancing the principles of this MOU.
7. This MOU is intended to improve the internal management of the executive branch and does not create any right or benefit, substantive or procedural, separately enforceable at law or equity by a party against the United States, its agencies or instrumentalities, its officers or employees, or any other person.

8. Modifications to the scope of this MOU shall be made by mutual consent of the Parties, through issuance of a written modification, signed and dated by both Parties, prior to any changes.
9. Either Party may terminate this instrument, in whole or in part, at any time before the date of expiration by providing the other Party with a written statement to that effect.

The principal contacts for this instrument are as follows:

Brian Millsap, Chief	L. Peter Boice, Conservation Team
Division of Migratory Bird Management	Leader
US Fish and Wildlife Service	Office of the Secretary of Defense
4401 N. Fairfax Drive	1225 S. Clark St.
MS4107	Suite 1500
Arlington, VA 22203	Arlington, VA 22202-4336

This MOU is executed as of the last date signed below and expires no later than five (5) years thereafter, at which time it is subject to review and renewal, or expiration.

F. Definitions

Action – a program, activity, project, official policy, rule, regulation or formal plan directly carried out by DoD, but not a military readiness activity.

Breeding Biology Research and Monitoring Database (BBIRD) - national, cooperative program that uses standardized field methodologies for studies of nesting success and habitat requirements of breeding birds (<http://pica.wru.umt.edu/BBIRD/>).

Breeding Bird Survey (BBS) – a standardized international survey that provides information on population trends of breeding birds, through volunteer observations located along randomly selected roadside routes in the United States, Canada and Mexico (<http://www.mbr-pwrc.usgs.gov/bbs/bbs.html>).

Bird Conservation Region – a geographic unit used to facilitate bird conservation actions under the North American Bird Conservation Initiative (<http://www.manomet.org/USSCP/bcrmaps.html>).

Birds of Conservation Concern – published by the FWS Division of Migratory Bird Management, refers to the list of migratory and non-migratory birds of the United States and its territories that are of conservation concern. The current version of the list Birds of Conservation Concern 2002 is available at (<http://migratorybirds.fws.gov/reports/bcc2002.pdf>).

Comprehensive Planning Efforts for Migratory Birds – includes Partners in Flight, North American Waterfowl Management Plan, U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, Western Hemisphere

Shorebird Reserve Network, North American Waterbird Conservation Plan, and other planning efforts integrated through the North American Bird Conservation Initiative.

Conservation Measure – an action undertaken to improve the conservation status of one or more species of migratory birds. Examples include surveys and inventories, monitoring, status assessments, land acquisition or protection, habitat restoration, population manipulation, research, and outreach.

Conservation Planning – strategic and tactical planning of agency activities for the long-term conservation of migratory birds and their habitats.

Council for the Conservation of Migratory Birds – an interagency council established by the Secretary of the Interior to oversee the implementation of Executive Order 13186.

Ecological Condition – the composition, structure, and processes of ecosystems over time and space. This includes the diversity of plant and animal communities, the productive capacity of ecological systems and species diversity, ecosystem diversity, disturbance processes, soil productivity, water quality and quantity, and air quality. Often referred to in terms of ecosystem health, which is the degree to which ecological factors and their interactions are reasonably complete and functioning for continued resilience, productivity, and renewal of the ecosystem.

Effect (adverse or beneficial) – “effects” and “impacts,” as used in this MOU are synonymous. Effects may be direct, indirect, or cumulative, and refer to effects from management actions or categories of management actions on migratory bird populations, habitats, ecological conditions and/or significant bird conservation sites.

Important Bird Areas (IBAs) – a network of sites that provide essential habitat for the long-term conservation of birds. In the United States, the IBA network is administered by the American Bird Conservancy and the National Audubon Society. (<http://www.audubon.org/nird/iba/>)

Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP) – an integrated plan based, to the maximum extent practicable, on ecosystem management that shows the interrelationships of individual components of natural resources management (e.g., fish and wildlife, forestry, land management, outdoor recreation) to military mission requirements and other land use activities affecting an installation’s natural resources. INRMPs are required for all DoD installations with significant natural resources, pursuant to the Sikes Act Improvement Act.

International Shorebird Survey – a monitoring program started in 1974 to survey shorebirds (sandpipers, plovers, etc.) across the Western Hemisphere. (<http://www.manomet.org/programs/shorebirds>).

Management Action – an activity by a government agency that could cause a positive or negative impact on migratory bird populations or habitats. Conservation measures to mitigate potential negative effects of actions may be required.

Migratory Bird – any bird listed in 50 CFR §10.13, Code of Federal Regulations.

Military Readiness Activity – all training and operations of the Armed Forces that relate to combat, including but not limited to the adequate and realistic testing of military equipment, vehicles, weapons and sensors for proper operation and suitability for combat use.

Monitoring Avian Productivity and Survivorship (MAPS) – a program that uses the banding of birds during the breeding season to track the changes and patterns in the number of young produced and the survivorship of adults and young (<http://www.birdpop.org/maps.htm>).

National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) – a Federal statute that requires Federal agencies to prepare a detailed analysis of the environmental impacts of a proposed action and alternatives, and to include public involvement in the decision making process for major Federal actions significantly affecting the quality of the human environment 42 U.S.C. §4321, et. seq.

North American Bird Conservation Initiative (NABCI) – an initiative to align the avian conservation community to implement bird conservation through regionally-based, biologically driven, landscape-oriented partnerships across the North American continent. NABCI includes Federal agencies of Canada, Mexico and the United States, as well as most landbird, shorebird, waterbird, and waterfowl conservation initiatives (<http://www.nabci-us.org>).

North American Waterbird Conservation Plan – a partnership of Federal and State government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and private interests focusing on the conservation of waterbirds, primarily including marshbirds and inland, coastal, and pelagic colonial waterbirds (www.nacwcp.org/pubs/). The vision of the partnership is that the distribution, diversity and abundance of populations and breeding, migratory, and nonbreeding waterbirds are sustained throughout the lands and waters of North America, Central America, and the Caribbean.

North American Waterfowl Management Plan – a partnership of Federal and State agencies, non-governmental organizations, and private interests focusing on the restoration of waterfowl populations through habitat restoration, protection, and enhancement (<http://birdhabitat.fws.gov/NAWMP/nawmphp.htm>).

Partners in Flight (PIF) – a cooperative partnership program of more than 300 partners including Federal and State government agencies, non-governmental organizations, conservation groups, foundations, universities and industry focusing on the conservation of landbirds. DoD was an original signatory to the PIF Federal Agencies' MOA. (<http://www.partnersinflight.org> and <http://www.dodpif.org>).

Species of Concern – refers to those species listed in the periodic report *Birds of Conservation Concern*; priority migratory bird species documented in the comprehensive bird conservation plans (North American Waterbird Conservation Plan, U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan, Partners in Flight Bird Conservation Plans); species or populations of waterfowl identified as high, or moderately high, continental priority in the North American Waterfowl Management Plan; listed threatened and endangered bird species in 50 CFR. 17.11; and MBTA listed game birds below desired population sizes.

Take – as defined in 50 C.F.R. 10.12, to include pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture, collect, or to attempt to pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture, or collect.

U.S. Shorebird Conservation Plan – an effort undertaken by a partnership of Federal and State government agencies, as well as non-governmental and private organizations to ensure that stable and self-sustaining populations of all shorebird species are restored and protected (<http://www.fws.gov/shorebird>).

The Parties hereto have executed this agreement as of the date shown below.

Director
US Fish and Wildlife Service

Assistant Deputy Under Secretary of
Defense (Environment, Safety and
Occupational Health)
US Department of Defense

 7/27/06
Signature Date

 7/31/06
Signature Date

Appendix E

List of INRMP Stakeholders and Duties, Responsibilities, and Coordination**1.0 PRIMARY INSTALLATION PERSONNEL AND ORGANIZATIONS**

Commanding General

Fort Riley's Commanding General (CG) is directly responsible for overall mission accomplishment at Fort Riley. This responsibility includes overseeing the implementation of this INRMP and chairing the Environmental Quality Control Council.

Garrison Commander

The Garrison Commander (GC) is responsible for land and facilities. The GC advises the CG on natural resources issues, with guidance from the DPW, Environmental Division.

Directorate of Public Works

1.1.1. Environmental Division

The Directorate of Public Works (DPW), Environmental Division is responsible to develop, execute, and administer environmental programs and projects. The Chief of the Environmental Division advises the GC and CG on environmental issues, including implementation of this INRMP.

The Conservation Branch within the Environmental Division is responsible for the management of natural and cultural resources on Fort Riley. Accordingly, programs are developed and implemented to ensure that natural and cultural resources are conserved and enhanced for future generations. One of the central functions of natural resources management is the implementation of this INRMP pursuant to Army guidance and the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997. The Conservation Branch is the installation liaison with state and Federal agencies concerning natural resources to meet the INRMP goals and objectives.

Two other Branches (currently combined) under the Environmental Division are Compliance and Pollution Prevention. Compliance Branch personnel conduct motor pool compliance inspections that help prevent releases of contaminants into the environment and conduct environmental training classes, which may include information pertinent to the INRMP. Pollution Prevention Branch personnel investigate water quality issues involving fish kills, assist in disposal of expired shelf-life pesticides, and provide compost to augment soil at wildlife food plots.

1.1.2. Other DPW Divisions

The DPW is the primary organization responsible for maintaining lands and facilities. DPW provides logistical, manpower, and equipment support to construct wildlife habitat projects. Examples of DPW support are the construction of gravel trails to fishing ponds, excavation and surveying of wetland construction projects, and range road construction and maintenance.

Directorate of Emergency Services

1.1.3. Fire and Emergency Services Division

The Directorate of Emergency Services (DES), Fire and Emergency Services Division, is responsible for controlling wildland fires. The Conservation Branch provides assistance for wildfire response. The Fire and Emergency Services Division collaborates with the Conservation Branch in developing annual prescribed burning plans, along with the Range Support Branch, DPTMS. Personnel in the Fire and Emergency Services Division and Conservation Branch implement the plans jointly.

1.1.4. Provost Marshal

The Provost Marshal's Office (PMO) is responsible for enforcing cultural and natural resources laws and regulations on Fort Riley, including fish and game laws of the State of Kansas and the U.S. Government.

Directorate of Family, Morale, Welfare, and Recreation

The Outdoor Recreation Branch of the Directorate of Family, Morale, Welfare and Recreation (DFMWR), in cooperation with the Conservation Branch, is responsible for establishing, planning, and coordinating all recreational aspects of hunting and fishing at Fort Riley

Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobilization and Security

The Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobilization and Security (DPTMS) is a vital coordination and approval point in implementing this INRMP. DPTMS provides review during the decision-making process for implementing management plans, developing Environmental Assessments, and establishing firearms deer season dates. This activity provides information about planned military training missions for review relative to compliance with the Endangered Species Act, NEPA and permits for tactical digging. DPTMS, through its Range Support Branch, implements the ITAM program.

The Range Support Branch collaborates with the Conservation Branch and Fire and Emergency Services Division in developing annual prescribed burning plans. The Range Support Office: coordinates with the Conservation Branch concerning availability of areas and times for natural resources management activities; assists contractors and lessees concerning access to training and maneuver areas; and provides Conservation Branch with information concerning access times and locations for outdoor recreationalists and fuelwood cutters.

Staff Judge Advocate

The Staff Judge Advocate (SJA) interprets and enforces natural and cultural resources laws and regulations. SJA provides legal opinions and guidance in interpreting and complying with Federal and State laws and Federal, State, Army, and Fort Riley regulations. SJA reviews and approves Fort Riley regulations that are promulgated to protect natural resources. SJA also reviews contracts and pertinent documents or actions requiring Command Decision or Approval/Signature. SJA assists with prosecuting violators of installation, Kansas, and Federal statutes and regulations concerning natural and cultural resources protection.

Public Affairs Office

The Public Affairs Office (PAO) helps disseminate information to soldiers, their families, and the general public about natural resources management and recreational opportunities on Fort Riley. PAO publishes a weekly article written by Conservation Branch staff on natural resources topics in the installation newspaper, as well as other articles as requested. PAO coordinates media requests for interviews, including television and radio, and issues news releases to the civilian media regarding various natural resources management activities on Fort Riley.

Medical Department Activity

One of the Medical Department Activity (MEDDAC) functions is to prevent and control communicable diseases of wildlife on Fort Riley. MEDDAC, Preventive Medicine conducts annual tick collections, seasonal mosquito surveys, stored-product pest surveillance in warehouses and commissary locations, cockroach control surveys in mess halls, screening for Lyme disease and human ehrlichiosis, and evaluations of other disease transmission sources. MEDDAC, Veterinary Services supports collection of blood and tissue samples from various wildlife species to monitor parasite and disease occurrence. Veterinary Service also provides technical advice to Conservation Branch personnel regarding the epidemiology of diseases and their control. MEDDAC, Occupational Health provides medical fitness testing for prescribed burning crews, prophylactic rabies vaccines for staff who may handle wild animals, and prescription safety glasses.

Military Units

Military units infrequently provide manpower, equipment, and logistical support for a wide range of natural resources-related activities. For example, engineer support has been used to clear shrubby areas for planting wildlife food. Also, aircraft support has been provided for aerial wildlife surveys.

Environmental Quality Control Committee

The purpose of the Environmental Quality Control Committee (EQCC) is to advise the installation commander on environmental priorities, policies, strategies and programs. The EQCC meets quarterly, sometimes “virtually”. The EQCC meeting is generally chaired by the CG during the first quarter, and chaired by the GC during the last three quarterly meetings. Members of the EQCC are Brigade Commanders, the GC, the MEDDAC Commander, and Directors of the DPTMS, DFMWR, SJA, DPW, Directorate of Logistics, Directorate of Information Management, and the Installation Safety Office.

2.0 HIGHER HEADQUARTERS

Installation Management Command (IMCOM)

The IMCOM mission is to provide the Army the installation capabilities and services to support expeditionary operations in a time of persistent conflict, and to provide a quality of life for Soldiers and Families commensurate with their service.

U. S. Army Forces Command (FORSCOM)

FORSCOM is the Army's Force Provider to joint combatant commanders worldwide. FORSCOM combines the contributions of more than 750,000 Army National Guard, Army Reserve, and active component Soldiers with those of more than 2,400 Army civilians to form a seamless, winning force that operates as a team across services, components and units. FORSCOM trains, mobilizes, deploys, sustains and reconstitutes combat ready Army forces capable of responding rapidly to crises worldwide. FORSCOM tailors the resources and training of its units to meet the specific and ever-changing requirements of combatant commanders and, when directed, those of U.S. civil authorities.

Army Environmental Command (AEC)

AEC, a field-operating activity of the Army, is the central point of coordination of Army environmental programs, including conservation and ACUB programs. AEC oversees, manages, and executes programs and projects. AEC also provides technical advice regarding pest management, endangered species, ITAM, and other related compliance areas.

3.0 OTHER ARMY AGENCIES

Corps of Engineers

3.1.1. Kansas City District

The Corps of Engineers, Kansas City District (KCD) assists Fort Riley by developing, executing, and administering contracts. The KCD is responsible for administering leases for the Agricultural Outleasing program. It is also responsible for issuing permits to conduct activities such as road building that potentially may affect wetlands in accordance with Section 404 of the Clean Water Act.

3.1.2. Waterways Experiment Station

The Corps of Engineers, Waterways Experiment Station (WES) provides general weed control information on request. An expert management software system (*Plant Management Information System*) was provided in 1996 for weed management decisions. WES has assisted Fort Riley through the Conservation Assistance Program, providing designs and specifications of a water control inlet structure for wetlands, and a biologist in training personnel to mist-net and identify bats.

3.1.3. Construction Engineering Research Laboratories

The Corps of Engineers Construction Engineering Research Laboratories (CERL) helped develop the ITAM program on Fort Riley. CERL continues to execute research and management programs through the ITAM program.

Central Region Environmental and Government Affairs Office

The Central Region Environmental and Government Affairs Office focuses on working cooperatively with state rule-writers and legislators to help maintain realistic training environments. Its proactive approach provides solutions that help ensure military readiness.

4.0 OTHER FEDERAL AGENCIES

United States Department of Agriculture

4.1.1. U.S. Forest Service

The U. S. Forest Service (USFS) cooperates with DoD in the Forest Pest Suppression (FPS) program. Through that program, USFS entomologists and plant pathologists consult with installation personnel about potential damage from, and control efforts for, serious outbreaks of insects and disease in the Installation's woodlands and forests.

The installation assists the USFS, North Central Research Station to complete 10-year State Forest Inventories. The Conservation Branch coordinates access to inventory plots on the installation by the Station's personnel. The results of the most recent inventory of Fort Riley plots were published in *An Analysis of the Forest Resources of Kansas, 1999, NC-334*.

4.1.2. Natural Resources Conservation Service

An agreement between the Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) and Fort Riley's ITAM program allows for one full time equivalent NRCS employee to be stationed on Fort Riley. This employee is responsible for oversight and implementation of the programs ITAM undertakes for rehabilitating and monitoring training land.

The NRCS and Department of Defense (DoD) signed an agreement establishing a national partnership in conservation efforts near military bases around the nation. As part of efforts to address urban encroachment concerns, DoD has created programs to work with partners to promote "compatible use buffers" and conservation planning around military bases. Such buffers also provide wildlife habitat and conserve the land. This partnership enables NRCS and the Department of Defense to gain greater efficiency by sharing technical information and services necessary to continued conservation efforts. In cases where priority conservation objectives overlap, NRCS easement programs will add to DoD efforts.

4.1.3. Animal-Plant Health Inspection Service (APHIS)

The Plant Protection and Quarantine Division (PPQ) of APHIS provides research, inspection, and funding to control and eradicate noxious and invasive weeds. Fort Riley serves as a member of the Kansas Biological Control Steering Committee. This committee advises PPQ on priorities for biological control research and recommends funding for projects that will assist landowners throughout Kansas, including the Army.

APHIS also provides interstate and Federal property quarantine designations for alien invasive insects determined to be significantly detrimental.

Fort Riley also is under an Inter-Agency Agreement with APHIS-Wildlife Services to provide nuisance wildlife control.

U.S. Department of the Interior

4.1.4. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS)

The USFWS is given the trust responsibility for management of migratory birds and threatened and endangered species. Through this oversight, USFWS provides Fort Riley guidance and

recommendations to further manage species that fall under these categories. Fort Riley consults and confers with the USFWS Field Office in Manhattan, Kansas, whenever projects arise that may impact threatened and endangered species or their habitat, eagles or their habitat, or that may significantly affect the population of any migratory bird species.

USFWS shares jurisdiction with Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism pertaining to game and fish law enforcement. USFWS Special law enforcement agents have been involved with investigations of poaching on-installation. They also have provided informal training to personnel from the PMO. This shared jurisdiction will continue through the foreseeable future.

The USFWS Partners for Wildlife Program has helped to arrange grassland conservation practices on a prairie land parcel adjacent to the installation. The USFWS, in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, is a signatory cooperator in implementation of this INRMP.

4.1.5. U.S. Geological Survey

The Biological Resources Division, U.S. Geological Survey, operates a Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit at Kansas State University. This Unit has partnered with Fort Riley's ITAM program to help manage and implement its RTLA component, as well as conducted research in support of Fort Riley's Conservation Branch.

5.0 STATE AGENCIES

Kansas Forest Service (KFS)

The KFS is the lead agency in Kansas for coordinating forest surveys on Federal lands. Fort Riley signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) with the KFS in 2006 concerning training of personnel in wildland firefighting. Under this MOU, KFS personnel provide S130 wildland firefighting training to Fort Riley personnel; oversee mandatory endurance testing required for Fort Riley firefighters to maintain their red card eligibility; and coordinate documentation to attain red cards for qualified staff.

The KFS provides seedlings for forest and wildlife habitat plantings at a nominal cost to the installation. Insect and disease updates and general forest management information is given by the agency to assist in maintaining the installation's woodlands and urban forest (cantonment areas). The KFS surveys for invasive and exotic forest insect outbreaks in cooperation with APHIS, PPQ and Fort Riley.

Kansas Department of Agriculture (KDA)

The Federal Noxious Weed Law requires that Federal agencies comply with all state laws governing the control of noxious weeds. The Plant Protection and Weed Control Division of the KDA is responsible for implementing the state's noxious weed protection laws throughout Kansas, including Fort Riley. The State Noxious Weed Coordinator and local county noxious weed officers conduct periodic checks and inspections for noxious weeds and their control. The installation provides an annual report to the state on control efforts and surveys. An annual meeting each fall addresses efforts and plans for future control. Fort Riley has entered into two MOUs that define compliance and relationship between the two agencies.

Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism (KDWPT)

KDWPT is given the responsibility for management of fish and wildlife species in Kansas. Fort Riley consults and confers with the KDWPT whenever projects arise that may impact state-listed threatened and endangered species or their habitat. Fort Riley consults with KDWPT when establishing deer and elk hunting seasons. Under an agreement with KDWPT, that agency provides various sport fish at no cost to stock Fort Riley lakes and ponds. In return, Fort Riley charges no fee to anglers to fish on the installation.

KDWPT shares conservation law enforcement jurisdiction on-post with the USFWS and PMO. KDWPT frequently supports law enforcement during peak hunting seasons, particularly during firearms deer season. KDWPT has investigated incidents of poaching on-post and off-post involving soldiers. KDWPT sponsored the Conservation Officer at the Kansas Law Enforcement Training Center to receive basic law enforcement training.

The KDWPT, in accordance with the Sikes Act Improvement Act of 1997, is a signatory cooperator in implementation of this INRMP

Kansas State Historical Society

Adverse impacts from natural resources management activities on cultural resources are minimized to the greatest extent possible through adherence to a programmatic agreement negotiated with the State Historical Preservation Office (SHPO). Fort Riley's Cultural Resources Manager is the primary contact between the installation and the SHPO.

6.0 OTHER INTERESTED PARTIES

County Governments

6.1.1. County Weed Departments

The Geary and Riley County Weed Departments inspect installation lands periodically for noxious weeds. The Conservation Branch is contacted by County Weed Supervisors to notify the installation of locations of noxious weeds for control.

6.1.2. Riley County Conservation District

The Riley County Conservation District is a government subdivision of the state of Kansas, and is a public body corporate and politic. The District receives funding from Riley County, the State of Kansas, grants and fund-raising activities. Its mission is to work with all county land-owners and residents toward the wise use of the natural resources by providing conservation planning, financial assistance, education and representation in conservation policies and programs. Fort Riley partners with the Riley County Conservation District to implement conservation practices within the Wildcat Creek watershed.

Contractors

Contractors provide services and supplies for the Conservation Branch natural resources management efforts. Contractors range from citizen farmers planting wildlife food plots to local companies spraying weeds and state universities conducting research and planning level surveys. When procuring services and supplies, Fort Riley personnel use local suppliers whenever possible.

Partners in Flight (PIF)

The National Fish and Wildlife Foundation initiated PIF in 1990. Its purpose is to galvanize International, Federal, State, and non-governmental organizations in the conservation and management of migratory birds. DoD joined the PIF initiative in 1991. Fort Riley is located in the PIF Midwest Region. A biologist of the Conservation Branch is a DoD-PIF Midwest representative.

Kansas Land Trust (KLT)

The Army has signed a Cooperative Agreement with the KLT to serve as Fort Riley's partner to implement the Army Compatible Use Buffer (ACUB) program. The KLT procures funding from other sources to match with Army funds. Jointly, Conservation Branch and KLT staffs develop annual work plans. The KLT then implements those plans, negotiating conservation easements with identified landowners, and is the holder and overseer of those easements.

Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation

The Rocky Mountain Elk Foundation has provided funding that has been used to defray the expenses of habitat management projects, such as food plot planting. Funding from the Foundation also has been used to rent commercial aircraft for elk surveys, and to fund research studying movement of the elk herd. All funding is used for "on-the-ground" expenses, and is not used to pay administrative overhead.

Ducks Unlimited

Ducks Unlimited has funded wetland construction on Fort Riley.

Pheasants Forever

Fort Riley has assisted with the development of a Pheasants Forever Habitat Team. This assistance has included equipment, training, funding for start up costs. Pheasants Forever also has provided seed used in installation food plots.

Fort Riley Outdoorsmen Group (FROG)

The FROG is dedicated to creating and sustaining strong interest in Fort Riley's environment, wildlife, and recreational opportunities by educating the public, sponsoring conservation and recreational projects, and promoting outdoor recreation. FROG works especially with the youth and new hunters and anglers to teach safety, ethics, and stewardship. It sponsors conservation and recreational projects that enhance skills and interest in outdoor recreation.

National Wild Turkey Federation

The National Wild Turkey Federation has provided funding that has been used to defray the expenses of habitat management equipment, such as tree shears and prescribed burn equipment. All funding is used for “on-the-ground” equipment, and is not used to pay administrative overhead.

Customers

The customers served by the Conservation Branch are diverse and widely dispersed.

6.1.3. Soldiers and Families

Fort Riley’s Organizational Self-Assessment (Fort Riley, 2000) asserts that the installation’s key customers are units, soldiers, and soldiers’ families. Taking care of these customers is a primary mission of the Conservation Branch. The Quality of Life of the soldiers and their families is enhanced by providing natural resources-based recreation such as hunting, angling, fuelwood cutting, and bird watching. Also, Quality of Life is improved by providing comfortable and pleasant living areas through control of nuisance and pest wildlife and plants.

6.1.4. Local Community Residents

The surrounding cities and towns are home to a population associated with Fort Riley. Many military personnel retire to the Fort Riley area specifically for the opportunity to utilize the natural resources available on and around the installation. Local civilians and retirees are permitted to utilize Fort Riley’s natural resources through hunting, fishing, fuelwood cutting, hay harvesting, and many other consumptive and non-consumptive activities. These customers are also directly or indirectly affected by management activities that may have influences off the installation, such as prescribed burning, pond construction, and erosion control.

6.1.5. Non-residents

Many persons travel to Fort Riley from across the country to hunt on installation lands.

Appendix F

ECOLOGICAL REGIONS OF NORTH AMERICA, *Toward a Common Perspective*. 1997. COMMISSION FOR ENVIRONMENTAL COOPERATION (CEC). <http://www.cec.org>

1.0 PROFILE OF THE CEC

The Commission for Environmental Cooperation (CEC) is an international organization whose members are Canada, Mexico and the United States. The CEC was created under the North American Agreement on Environmental Cooperation (NAAEC) to address regional environmental concerns, help prevent potential trade and environmental conflicts and promote the effective enforcement of environmental law. The Agreement complements the environmental provisions established in the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA).

2.0 BACKGROUND

North America contains numerous natural resources, including air, oceans, rivers, mountains and forests. Together, these natural resources are the basis of a rich network of ecosystems and must be protected. Stewardship of the North American environment is a responsibility shared by Canada, Mexico and the United States. Ecosystems know no political boundaries. The migration of birds, the ranging of animals, the distribution of flora, and defining geographical features transcend state or provincial, territorial, even national borders. Recognizing that environmental issues are complex and not restricted by such jurisdictional boundaries but are shared among nations, the three countries have thus accepted the need to move away from an emphasis on individual environmental and socio-economic concerns, and shift towards a more comprehensive, continental scale approach; one that includes not only assessments of trade, but also strives to foster cooperative work to protect the environment, to insure the sustainability of resources, and to study the effect of human activities on ecosystems.

The present volume and its accompanying maps represent a first attempt at holistically classifying and mapping ecological regions across all three countries of the North American continent.

3.0 ECOLOGICAL REGIONS

This methodology examines North American ecology at multiple scales, from large continental ecosystems to subdivisions of these that correlate more detailed physical and biological settings with human activities on two levels of successively smaller units. The maps and report represent the working group's best consensus on the distribution and characteristics of major ecosystems on all three levels throughout the three North American countries.

Ecological Regions of North America, as presented here, is a view of continental ecological regions that has been developed to enhance the capability of both non-governmental and governmental organizations to assess the nature, condition and trends of the major ecosystems in North America. It is offered for use to a wide range of professionals and the general public. By necessity, the notion of resources is broadly interpreted, embracing the traditional ideas of resources (i.e., timber, arable soils, and water) but also including the ecosystems of which they are a part.

The focus for this project was to develop ecological land classifications suitable for use in continental, national and regional/local environmental reporting and assessment.

LEVEL I

North America has been broken down into 15 broad, level I ecological regions (Exhibit E.1). Fort Riley's Level I ecological region is the Great Plains. The Great Plains ecological region is found in the central part of the continent and extends over the widest latitudinal range of any single North American ecological region. It is a relatively continuous and roughly triangular area covering about 3.5 million square kilometers. The North American prairies extend from Alberta, Saskatchewan and Manitoba in Canada, south through the Great Plains to southern Texas and adjacent Mexico, and from western Indiana to the foothills of the Rockies. This ecological region is distinguished particularly by the following characteristics: relatively little topographic relief; grasslands and a paucity of forests; and sub-humid to semiarid climate.

3.1.1. Physical setting

The Great Plains range from smooth to irregular plains. Sizable portions in the United States are hilly or classified as tablelands with moderate relief (100-175 m). Surficial geology is varied. The soils are commonly deep and throughout most of the region were originally highly fertile. Today, soils of agricultural potential throughout the Great Plains face problems of reduced nutrient potential, increasing salinity and susceptibility to wind and water erosion. The climate is dry and continental, characterized in the north by short, hot summers and long, cold winters. High winds are an important climatic factor in this ecological region. It is also subject to periodic, intense droughts and frosts.

3.1.2. Biological setting

The Great Plains ecological region was once covered with natural grasslands that supported rich and highly specialized plant and animal communities. The interaction of climate, fire and grazing influenced the development and maintenance of the Great Plains. Rainfall increases from west to east, defining different types of native prairies. Short-grass prairie occurs in the west, in the rain shadow of the Rocky Mountains, with mixed-grass prairie in the central Great Plains and tall-grass prairie in the wetter eastern region. Because of the suitability of the Great Plains for agricultural production, many native prairie vegetation types have been radically transformed. The short-, mixed- and tall-grass prairies now correspond to the western rangelands, the wheat belt and the corn/soybean regions, respectively, to the central and eastern Great Plains. The eastern border of the region, stretching from central Iowa to Texas, shows patterns of grassland and forest combinations mixed with oak-hickory forest. Throughout the remainder of the Great Plains there are few native deciduous trees that occur, except in the eastern regions or in very sheltered locations along waterways or at upper elevations. Prior to European settlement, the Great Plains supported millions of bison, pronghorn antelope, elk and mule deer, plains grizzly bears and plains wolves. Today, the Great Plains is home to a disproportionately high number of rare, threatened, vulnerable and endangered species. The draining of wetlands and conversion of wildlife habitat for agriculture, industry and urban development are significant issues in this ecological region.

3.1.3. Human activities

Today, the prairie grasslands are among the largest farming and ranching areas of the Earth. Agriculture is the most important economic activity as well as the dominant land use and the main stressor for this ecological region. While agricultural activities dominate the rural landscape, population is centered in urban areas and rural depopulation is a continuing trend in Canada and the United States. There is a general trend in Canada and the United States away from small and medium-sized farms to large agribusiness operations.

LEVEL II

Fifty-two Level II ecological regions have been delineated within the fifteen Level I regions to provide more detailed descriptions of the larger ecological areas. Level II ecological regions are useful for national and subcontinental overviews of physiography, wildlife, and land use. The Great Plains Ecological Region contains six Level II regions (Exhibit E.2). Fort Riley is within the South-Central Semi-arid Prairies Level II region. The table on the reverse of the level II map provides a synopsis of the major physical and biological attributes along with human activities associated with each of the level II ecological regions.

LEVEL III

At level III, the continent currently contains 182 ecological regions. Seven of these level III regions are within the South-Central Semi-arid Prairies Level II region of the Great Plains. Level III mapping describes smaller ecological areas nested within level II regions. These smaller divisions enhance regional environmental monitoring, assessment and reporting, as well as decision-making. They allow locally defining characteristics to be identified, and more specifically oriented management strategies to be formulated.

Fort Riley lies within the Flint Hills Level III region (Exhibit E.3). The Flint Hills is a region of rolling hills with relatively narrow steep valleys, and is composed of shale and cherty limestone with rocky soils. In contrast to surrounding ecological regions that are mostly in cropland, most of the Flint Hills region is grazed by beef cattle. The Flint Hills mark the western edge of the tallgrass prairie, and contain the largest remaining intact tallgrass prairie in the Great Plains.

Exhibit E.2. The 6 Level II ecological regions of the Great Plains as determined by the Commission for Environmental Cooperation (1997).

Appendix G

Excerpt from the installation-wide cultural resources programmatic agreement (PA) applicable to Natural Resources Management activities. The PA is in effect for five years from the date of execution (09 March 2017).

**PROGRAMMATIC AGREEMENT
AMONG
THE UNITED STATES ARMY GARRISON FORT RILEY,
THE KANSAS STATE HISTORIC PRESERVATION OFFICER, AND
THE ADVISORY COUNCIL ON HISTORIC PRESERVATION
REGARDING
THE OPERATION, MAINTENANCE, AND DEVELOPMENT OF FORT RILEY
CLAY, GEARY AND RILEY COUNTIES, KANSAS**

WHEREAS, The United States Army Garrison Fort Riley (USAG Fort Riley) proposes to coordinate and administer an ongoing program of operation, maintenance, and development (Project); and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley, a federally owned and operated facility, plans to carry out the Project pursuant to Army Regulations, thereby making the undertaking subject to review under Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), 54 U.S.C. § 306108, and its implementing regulations, 36 C.F.R. Part 800; and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley has defined the area of potential effect (APE) as described in Appendix A: Fort Riley Maps (Map I: Fort Riley Installation Boundaries); and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley has determined that the aforementioned Project, including undertakings performed by USAG Fort Riley lessees, permittees, and tenant units, may have an adverse effect on properties listed or eligible for listing on the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP), as listed in Appendix B: Fort Riley Historic Properties and shown on Appendix A: Fort Riley Maps (Map 2: Fort Riley Historic District Boundaries – For Official Use Only), and has consulted with the Kansas State Historic Preservation Officer (SHPO) pursuant to § 800.14(b); and

WHEREAS, pursuant to consultation conducted under 36 CFR § 800.14(b), the signatories have developed this Programmatic Agreement (PA) in order to establish an efficient and effective program alternative for taking into account the effects of the Project on historic properties where routine management of activities are undertaken at Federal installations; and

WHEREAS, the properties listed in Appendix C: Excluded Fort Riley Historic Properties are being covered separately under Nationwide Program Alternatives addressing Capehart-Wherry Era Family Housing, Cold War Era Unaccompanied Personnel Housing, World War II Temporary Structures, World War II and Cold War Era Army Ammunition Plants and Production Facilities, and World War II and Cold War Era Army Ammunition Storage Facilities, and are therefore not this PA; and

WHEREAS, the management of current and future family housing and ancillary facilities at Fort Riley, many of which are historic properties, is governed by the *Programmatic Agreement between the United States Army Fort Riley and Kansas State Historic Preservation Officer for*

the Privatization of Family Housing at Fort Riley, Riley and Geary Counties, Kansas (2015) and is therefore not part of this PA; and

WHEREAS, the management of current and future Army Lodging Facilities at Fort Riley, of which two are historic properties, is governed by the *Programmatic Agreement between the United States Army Fort Riley and Kansas State Historic Preservation Officer for the Privatization of Army Lodging* (2009) and is therefore not part of this PA; and

WHEREAS, districts, sites, buildings, structures, and objects that are 50 years of age or older that have not yet been evaluated for eligibility to the NRHP will be considered eligible to the NRHP for the purpose of this PA; and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley maintains the *Fort Riley Army Installation Design Guide* that includes guidance for operation, repair, and maintenance activities within the Main Post Historic District and for all built historic property; and

WHEREAS, areas identified as containing unexploded ordinance (UXO) and have been listed as impact and/or dud zones, as indicated in Appendix A: Fort Riley Maps (Map 3: Fort Riley Impact Area – For Official Use Only) will not be surveyed for archaeological sites because of human health and safety issues; and

WHEREAS, pursuant to Army Regulation 200-1, *Environmental Protection and Enhancement*, the Department of the Army has designated the Garrison Commander (Commander) to serve as the agency official responsible for compliance with the requirements of Section 106 of the NHPA; and

WHEREAS, in accordance with 36 CFR § 800.6(a)(1), USAG Fort Riley has notified the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP) of its potential adverse effects determination with specified documentation, and the ACHP has chosen to participate in the consultation pursuant to 36 CFR § 800.6(a)(1)(iii); and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley provided notification of the development of this Agreement on June 24, 2015 to the Absentee Shawnee, Cheyenne River Sioux Tribe, Citizen Potawatomi Nation, Delaware Nation, Eastern Shawnee Tribe of Oklahoma, Iowa Tribe of Kansas & Nebraska, Iowa Tribe of Oklahoma, Kaw Nation of Oklahoma, Kickapoo Tribe in Kansas, Kickapoo Tribe of Oklahoma, Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma, Omaha Tribe of Nebraska, Otoe-Missouria Tribe of Indians, Pawnee Nation of Oklahoma, Ponca Tribe of Nebraska, Ponca Tribe of Oklahoma, Prairie Band Potawatomi Nation, Quapaw Tribe of Oklahoma, Sac & Fox Nation of Missouri in Kansas & Nebraska, Sac & Fox Nation, The Osage Nation, Wichita and Affiliated Tribes, and Wyandotte Nation (Tribes), all federally recognized Indian tribes with potential concerns for properties of traditional religious and cultural importance at Fort Riley, and has invited them to provide comment and sign as concurring parties; and

WHEREAS, the consultation procedures between the USAG Fort Riley, the SHPO and the ACHP outlined herein, have no bearing on the required consultation procedures with federally recognized tribes, for which independent agreements or understandings may exist and are therefore not part of or superseded by this PA; and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley has consulted with the Historical and Archaeological Society of Fort Riley, Geary County Historical Society, and Riley County Historical Society, and has invited

them to comment and participate in the consultations to develop this PA and to sign as concurring parties; and

WHEREAS, USAG Fort Riley has published notices in local newspapers and provided a copy of a draft PA to local organizations that may have an interest in historic properties at Fort Riley, provided the public an opportunity to comment on this PA and has considered the recommendations of the public, reviewing agencies and tribes in developing this PA; and

NOW, THEREFORE, USAG Fort Riley, the Kansas SHPO, and the ACHP agree that the undertaking shall be implemented in accordance with the following stipulations in order to take into account potential effects of the undertakings on historic properties.

STIPULATIONS

I. STAFFING

- A. The Commander shall designate an installation "Cultural Resource Manager" (CRM) to coordinate the installation's Cultural Resources Management Program. The CRM shall meet, delegate tasks to or consult with individuals who meet the Secretary of the Interior's *Professional Qualifications Standards* for Historian, Archeologist, Architectural Historian, Architect, or Historic Architect as outlined in 36 CFR 61-Appendix A.
- B. USAG Fort Riley shall ensure that all individuals contracted to perform duties associated with this PA are professionally qualified under the Secretary of the Interior's standards for the tasks appointed to them.
- C. Qualified professionals shall be in place or available upon the execution of this PA and throughout its duration. In instances wherein qualified professional are not in place or available to implement the stipulations of this PA, the SHPO will be immediately notified and the terms of the PA will be suspended, with the Standard Section 106 review process placed into effect, as per 36 C.F.R. Part 800, until stipulated staffing requirements can be met.

II. PLANNING

- A. The Commander shall ensure that Garrison planning documents are analyzed by the CRM to identify undertakings during revisions, changes, or when a new planning document is developed. The documents to be analyzed will include, but are not limited to, the installation master plan, area development plans, military construction plans, Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plans, Integrated Natural Resource Management Plans, tenant activities, historic property renovation and demolition plans, Installation Design Guide, Historic Landscape Management Plan, and military dig permit requests.
- B. The CRM shall ensure all service and work orders associated with identified historic properties are reviewed for compliance with applicable historic preservation laws and regulations.

- C. USAG Fort Riley shall ensure that schedules and priorities are established and documented for identification, evaluation, and treatment of historic properties that might be affected by the undertakings identified pursuant to Stipulation IV.
- D. The Commander shall ensure that all relevant offices at USAG Fort Riley are informed of the schedules of and priorities for undertakings, the potential of these undertakings to affect historic properties, the requirement to ensure that an analysis of alternatives is fully considered as early as possible in project planning, and of the requirement for review of each undertaking pursuant to this PA.
- E. USAG Fort Riley shall make reasonable and good faith efforts during planning efforts to avoid adversely affecting historic properties eligible for or listed on the NRHP. When there are practical alternatives available for accomplishing USAG Fort Riley's needs that allow historic properties to not be adversely affected, USAG Fort Riley will give preference to those alternatives.

III. COMMUNICATION

The primary form of written communication will be via email with submittals, comments and responses provided electronically. Requests by signatories for hard copies of any submittals, comments and/or responses will be provided in a timely manner to facilitate consultation.

IV. PROJECT REVIEW

A. Determine the Undertaking

1. The CRM shall determine if a specific proposed action is a federal undertaking as defined in 36 CFR § 800.16(y) and, if a federal undertaking, whether it is an activity that is listed in Appendix D.
 - a) If the CRM determines the undertaking is an activity that is listed in Appendix D: Exempt Undertakings, the CRM shall determine the undertaking to be an "Undertaking Exempt from SHPO Review." The CRM shall document the determination for this undertaking for inclusion in an annual report (Annual Report), per Stipulation IX; and USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.
 - b) If the CRM determines the undertaking is not an activity that is listed in Appendix D: Exempt Undertakings, the CRM shall continue on in the Project Review process.

B. Define the Area of Potential Effects and Identify Historic Properties

1. The CRM shall determine and document the undertaking's APE, taking into account direct, indirect, and cumulative effects.
 - a) Potential direct effects will include impacts to above and below ground resources, via ground disturbance, alterations, new construction or demolition.

- b) Potential indirect effects will include secondary visual, auditory and experiential impacts.
 - c) Potential cumulative effects will include impacts caused by groupings of separate, but similar undertakings over a short period of time or by adjacent or collocated undertakings.
2. The CRM shall determine if historic properties have been adequately identified within the APE.
- a) Archeological Survey Exemption: If existing survey efforts are not adequate in part or all of the APE for an undertaking that would have ground disturbance directly affecting less than five acres, less than eight inches in depth, AND is in an area of less than 30 percent probability for site discovery, per Map 4: Fort Riley Archeological Probability Map in Appendix A: Fort Riley Maps (For Official Use Only), then the CRM will determine the undertaking to be “Exempt from SHPO Review.” The CRM shall notify the SHPO of the undertaking and this determination in the Annual Report and USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.
 - b) Historic Architectural Survey Exemption: If existing survey efforts are not adequate in part or all of the APE for an undertaking that is limited to either the interior of a building or structure less than 45 years in age and located within a historic district, or any part of a building or structure less than 45 years and not located within a half mile of a historic property, then the CRM will determine the undertaking to be “Exempt from SHPO Review.” This exemption does not apply to associated ground disturbance. The CRM shall retain a record of the undertaking and this determination, and USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.
 - c) If existing survey efforts are not adequate in part or all of the APE and the above survey exemptions do not apply, the CRM shall work with proponents and/or project managers to relocate the undertaking to a previously surveyed area that has been found to be void of historic properties that are either eligible to the NRHP or as yet unevaluated for eligibility.
 - (1) If the undertaking’s APE can be relocated to an area found to be clear of historic properties, per previous consultation with the SHPO, the CRM shall determine there are “No Historic Properties Affected.” The CRM shall notify the SHPO of the undertaking and this determination in the Annual Report and USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.
 - (2) If the undertaking’s APE cannot be relocated to an area found to be clear of historic properties, per previous

consultation with the SHPO, the CRM will continue with the Project Review process.

- d) If existing survey efforts are not adequate in part or all of the APE for an undertaking, above exemptions do not apply and the undertaking cannot be relocated to a cleared area, the CRM shall ensure that identification of historic properties are in accordance with 36 CFR 800.4.
 - e) If there are properties within a previously surveyed area requiring evaluation for eligibility to the NRHP present in the APE, the CRM shall evaluate them in accordance with 36 CFR 800.4 (c). The CRM may opt to not evaluate historic properties in the APE for eligibility to the NRHP, if the resources are treated as if they are eligible to the NRHP and provided all the required protections. In doing so, the CRM need not consult with the SHPO on determination of eligibility and will, instead, continue on to Stipulation III. C. Evaluate Effects of the Undertaking.
 - f) The CRM shall submit all documentation related to Project Review initiated survey, identification and evaluation to the SHPO for review and concurrence. This submission may occur in conjunction with findings of evaluated effects of the undertaking.
 - (1) The SHPO shall be afforded 30 calendar days to respond to the USAG Fort Riley's findings and determinations of eligibility.
 - (2) If USAG Fort Riley and the SHPO do not agree on determinations of eligibility, the CRM will either resolve the disagreement through further consultation with the SHPO or will consult with the Keeper of the National Register pursuant to 36 CFR Part 63.
3. If the CRM does not identify historic properties within an undertaking's APE, the CRM shall document this determination of "No Historic Properties Affected" in the documentation submitted to the SHPO for review that includes the findings of the associated survey, as described in within this stipulation above (Stipulation IV. B. 2. (f)).
4. If the CRM identifies historic properties that may be directly, indirectly, or cumulatively affected within the APE, the CRM shall continue the Project Review process.

C. Evaluate Effects of the Undertaking

- 1. The CRM shall assess the effects of the proposed undertaking, to include direct, indirect, and cumulative effects, on historic properties using the criteria of adverse effects (36 CFR § 800.5(a)(1)) and will make one of the following determinations:
 - a) "No Effect to Historic Properties" – in cases where historic properties are present in the APE, as identified in previous consultation with the

SHPO, but have no discernable potential of being directly, indirectly or cumulatively affected by the undertaking, the CRM shall document this determination for inclusion in the Annual Report and USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.

- b) “No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties” – in cases where historic properties are present in the APE, as identified in previous consultation with the SHPO, and may be impacted by the undertaking, but will not be affected to the extent that their integrity, as it relates to NRHP eligibility, is threatened, the CRM will send the determination and supporting documentation to the SHPO for review.
 - (1) The SHPO will have 30 calendar days to respond to the determination of No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties. If there is no response 30 days after the SHPO has received the determination and documentation. The CRM shall document this determination for those undertakings for inclusion in the Annual Report and in accordance with 36 CFR 800.11. USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking
 - (2) If USAG Fort Riley and the SHPO concur after consultation that the undertaking will have No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties, USAG Fort Riley has no further obligation under this stipulation for the undertaking.
 - (3) If the SHPO objects to the determination of No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties, USAG Fort Riley will attempt to resolve the objection through consultation. If USAG Fort Riley cannot resolve the objection to a determination of No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties through further consultation, USAG Fort Riley will consult to resolve the dispute, per Stipulation X.
- c) If it is determined that any historic properties present in the APE will be adversely affected by the undertaking, the USAG Fort Riley will consult to resolve the adverse effect, per Stipulation VI.

V. EXPEDITED REVIEW REQUESTS

- A. In the event the USAG Fort Riley must modify the scope of an undertaking or address an unforeseen condition during ongoing construction, the CRM shall review the proposed modification and determine if it requires additional SHPO review.
- B. Changes subject to additional SHPO review involve activities that fall outside those described in Appendix D and involve:
 - 1. Additional alterations to character-defining features that were not generally addressed in previous submissions;

2. Reduction of minimization, avoidance or mitigation measures previously agreed upon with the SHPO;
 3. Additional visible modifications that are distracting or non-compatible, regardless of direct impact to historic fabric;
 4. Additional significant modifications to hidden structural elements; or
 5. Additional substitution of materials affecting original intent to replace in-kind.
- C. Only in cases in which the CRM determines the modification requires additional SHPO review and wherein completion of the specific action triggering the change in scope is halting the undertaking's Critical Path tasks, the submittal will be labeled as an "Expedited Review Request." The SHPO shall provide a response within 14 calendar days.

VI. RESOLUTION OF ADVERSE EFFECTS

A. Assess Applicability of Streamlined Process for Resolving Adverse Effect

1. The CRM shall assess the undertaking and affected resources to determine whether to apply the standard Section 106 consultation with the SHPO, pursuant to 36 CFR § 800.6, or the streamlined process described below.
2. If ALL the following criteria are met, the CRM will continue with the alternative process to resolve adverse effects, as described herein:
 - a) Resources are known. APE must be fully surveyed and the identification of resources not occur as a result of an inadvertent discovery.
 - b) Resources are "eligible" to the NRHP. Resources must have been evaluated and found eligible to the NRHP or treated as eligible, if over 50 years old and unevaluated.
 - c) Resolution of adverse effects does not require tribal consultation. Undertaking has no potential to affect resources of value to interested federally recognized tribes, such as listed, eligible or unevaluated prehistoric archeological sites, tribal sacred land or traditional cultural places.
 - d) Resolution of adverse effects occur during planning phase. Adverse effects are foreseeable and did not occur during the execution of an undertaking.

B. Conduct informal SHPO Consultation

1. The CRM will discuss preliminary undertaking information with the SHPO, via in-person, email or telephone communications.

2. The CRM and SHPO will develop an early consensus as to extent of foreseeable effects and where the threshold may be for a finding of adverse effect.
3. The CRM and SHPO will establish an understanding for the level of effort Fort Riley will apply while carrying out the remainder of the process, identifying which options will be omitted or given more analysis.
4. The CRM and SHPO will establish whether avoidance and minimization efforts are sufficient in reducing the effects below the threshold of adverse effect or whether mitigating actions will also be required.

C. Identify Avoidance and Minimization Measures

1. The CRM will identify and determine the reasonable feasibility of avoidance measures, which may include:
 - a) Relocate the area of potential effect for the undertaking or portion of undertaking that has the potential for adverse effect.
 - b) Reduce the scope of the undertaking to avoid an adverse effect by either not triggering a cumulative adverse effect or eliminating effects that are destructive to historic properties or character-defining features.
 - c) Design new construction to be compatible with associated historic properties and easily reversible without damage to those properties, in accordance compliance with the Secretary of Interior's *Standards and Guidelines for Treatment of Historic Properties*.
 - d) Introduce buffers that create a visual screen or spatial separation between the new construction and historic properties.
2. The CRM will identify and determine the reasonable feasibility of minimization measures, which may include:
 - a) Provide archeological monitors that meet the Secretary of Interior's *Minimum Professional Qualification Standards* for undertakings with a potential to affect historic properties for which a spatial or physical buffer cannot be provided.
 - b) Provide the most current standard operating procedure for inadvertent discoveries to all military, civilian and contracted personnel whose work on the undertaking may result in an inadvertent archeological or architectural discovery.
 - c) Repair and stabilize historic features directly or indirectly associated with the undertaking in accordance with Secretary of Interior *Standards and Guidelines for Treatment of Historic Properties*.

- d) Ensure all new design is compatible with historic properties, in accordance with the Secretary of Interior's *Standards and Guidelines for Treatment of Historic Properties*.

D. Explore Mitigation Strategies

1. The CRM will identify all possible mitigation measures appropriate for the resource and undertaking. These may include, but are not limited to:

- a) Standard Mitigation

- (1) Phase IV excavation for Archeological Resources

- i. If data recovery for an archeological site is a selected mitigation method, a Data Recovery Plan will be developed in accordance with the ACHP's *Recommended Approach for Consultation on Recovery of Significant Information from Archeological Sites*, effective June 1, 1999, and consultations under this PA. The Data Recovery Plan will be submitted to the SHPO as part or whole of the proposed Mitigation Strategy, in support of the Formal Notification of Adverse Effect.
 - ii. If Fort Riley chooses archeological data recovery as a mitigation measure, and if applicable to the Historic Properties at risk, Fort Riley may propose to use a previously accepted Research Design to implement the mitigation.

- (2) Historic American Building Survey/Historic American Engineering Record (HABS/HAER) Documentation

- i. If documentation for an architectural or engineered resource is a chosen mitigation method, an appropriate level of HABS/HAER documentation will be selected, or a modified version developed, in accordance with HABS/HAER Standards and Guidelines and consultations under this PA. The proposed level of documentation and any modifications to the standards will be submitted to the SHPO as part or whole of the Proposed Mitigation Strategy, in support of the Formal Notification of Adverse Effect.

- b) Creative mitigation, that may include:

- (1) Restoration of architectural features;
 - (2) Reconstruction of missing architectural features;
 - (3) Relocation of historic properties;

- (4) Salvage of features or materials;
 - (5) Interpretive displays, literature, etc.;
 - (6) Documents for public release;
 - (7) Public participation activities; and/or
 - (8) Off-site mitigation measure(s) performed on other historic property/properties.
2. USAG Fort Riley will explore feasibility of all mitigation measures that have been identified by the CRM.
 - a) The CRM will create a decision-making matrix of possible mitigation
 - b) The CRM will note all the competing factors and indicate which mitigating actions are feasible
 - c) The CRM will propose a Mitigation Strategy, based on the resource, affect to the resource, application of avoidance and minimization measures, appropriateness of additional mitigation, and informal discussion with the SHPO

E. Formally Notify Appropriate Parties

1. The CRM will notify the SHPO, ACHP, identified stakeholders, and interested parties of adverse effect through a formal letter that will assume SHPO concurrence on adverse effect determination, based on informal discussions, and will serve to invite SHPO and ACHP to participate in the development of a memorandum of agreement (MOA). The public will be notified via the NEPA review process.
2. The CRM will provide supporting documentation along with the notification that will include:
 - a) Summary of the Undertaking;
 - b) Identification of all historic properties within the APE;
 - c) Description of effects and what aspect of the undertaking constitutes an adverse effect (i.e. cumulative or threatens integrity); and
 - d) Mitigation Strategy
 - (1) Identification of avoidance and minimization measures, indicating which have already been or will be implemented.
 - (2) Mitigating actions matrix, indicating advantages/disadvantages and which are feasible.

3. The SHPO, ACHP, stakeholders and interested parties will be provided 45 days to review the notification submittal package, provide comment, and confirm an MOA is required. Any requests for additional information or an initial site visit that is required prior to commencement of MOA development, must occur within a review period of 45 days.

F. Develop a Memorandum of Agreement

1. The USAG Fort Riley shall schedule an initial consultation meeting with the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating) at a time that is mutually agreeable to all signatories and no more than 45 calendar days after Formal Notification of Adverse Effect, for the purpose of initiating development of the MOA. The initial discourse will, in the least, address the following objectives:
 - a) Define each agency's goals for the process and MOA content
 - b) Review the status of avoidance and minimization measure that Fort Riley has or intends to implement
 - c) Discuss each agencies' preferred mitigation measures and overall mitigation strategy
 - d) Identify any template upon which the MOA should be structured
 - e) Attempt to reach a consensus for key stipulations of the MOA
2. The USAG Fort Riley shall synthesize the agreed upon mitigation strategy and submit a Preliminary Signatory Review Draft MOA to the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating) for a review and comment period of 30 calendar days.
3. The USAG Fort Riley shall incorporate any required edits and submit to the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating) a Revised Signatory Draft MOA, with all associated attachments and appendices, for a review and comment period of 30 calendar days. If it is determined that small portions of the agreement document will require significant modification or addition of content, this content may be addressed informally, outside the formal draft review process.
4. After consideration of comments and consultation with the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating), the USAG Fort Riley shall submit a revised Public Review Draft MOA to the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating), stakeholders, interested parties and the public for a review and comment period of 30 days.
5. Upon consideration of comments and consultation with the SHPO (and ACHP, if participating), the USAG Fort Riley shall make necessary revisions and submit the Final MOA to signatories for execution of the agreement document.

VII. EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

- A. In the event the USAG Fort Riley proposes an emergency undertaking as an essential and immediate response to a disaster or emergency declared by the

President of the United States or the Governor of Kansas or another immediate threat to life or property, USAG Fort Riley shall address this undertaking in accordance with 36 CFR § 800.12(b)(2).

- B. If the USAG Fort Riley determines that circumstances do not permit an opportunity for SHPO comment on a proposed emergency undertaking, the USAG shall notify the SHPO and provide documentation of the undertaking in the Annual Report.
- C. All cases of emergency undertakings for which implementation occurred within 30 calendar days after the disaster or emergency has been formally declared by the appropriate authority will be documented in the Annual Report.

VIII. POST-REVIEW DISCOVERY

- A. If potential historic properties are discovered or unanticipated effects on historic properties are found, USAG Fort Riley shall address these post-review discoveries in accordance with 36 CFR § 800.13(b).
- B. All cases of inadvertent discoveries will be documented in the Annual Report.

APPENDIX H

Natural/Near-natural vegetation types on Fort Riley. Detailed summaries of the new vegetation classification the Kansas Biological Survey developed for Fort Riley (Freeman, C. C. and J. M. Delisle. 2004).

1.0 FOREST COMMUNITIES

Woodland component has 61–100% tree canopy cover, there is usually three distinct canopy layers (overstory trees, understory shrubs, and herbaceous layer), with numerous trees > 5 m tall.

Green Ash-Elm Species-Northern Hackberry Forest (1)

Description: This riparian forest community has an open to closed tree canopy dominated by *Fraxinus pennsylvanica*, *Celtis occidentalis*, and *Ulmus americana*. Other tree species that may be present include *Acer saccharinum*, *Juglans nigra*, *Populus deltoides*, and *Tilia americana*. *Ulmus rubra* may be part of the subcanopy. The shrub layer in the western part of the range includes *Cornus drummondii*, *Ribes missouriense*, *Symphoricarpos occidentalis*, and *Zanthoxylum americanum*, as well as woody vines, such as *Parthenocissus vitacea*, *Smilax tamnoides*, *Toxicodendron radicans*, and *Vitis riparia*. The herbaceous layer in the western part of the range includes *Elymus virginicus*, *Festuca subverticillata*, *Galium aparine*, *Geum canadense*, and *Laportea canadensis*. Stands occur along the upper floodplain terraces of rivers and streams, and in upland river bottoms. Soils are moderately well-drained to poorly-drained.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on the installation but best represented on the west side along the primary tributaries of Milford Lake, and on the south side along the floodplains of the Republican and Kansas rivers.

Eastern Cottonwood-Sycamore Forest (2)

Description: This riparian forest community has an open to closed tree canopy dominated by deciduous trees. Dominant species are *Populus deltoides* and *Platanus occidentalis*, with *Acer negundo*, *Celtis occidentalis*, and *Salix nigra* common associates. The shrub layer may be poorly developed to well developed, depending on flood frequency and duration. Stands occur in level to undulating floodplains of major rivers and large streams. Soils are deep, silty to clayey or less frequently sandy alluvium, and poorly-drained to well-drained.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on the installation but best represented on the west side along the primary tributaries of Milford Lake, and on the south side along the floodplains of the Republican and Kansas rivers.

Eastern Cottonwood-Willow Forest (3)

Description: This riparian forest community has a closed or nearly closed tree canopy dominated by deciduous trees. *Populus deltoides* and *Salix nigra* are the dominant trees. *Acer negundo*, *Acer saccharinum*, *Fraxinus pennsylvanica*, *Platanus occidentalis*, and *Ulmus americana* are common associates, but tree diversity is limited due to the dynamics of flooding, scouring, and sediment deposition. The subcanopy usually is dominated by *Salix nigra*. The shrub layer may be

conspicuously absent, and herbaceous growth may be lush but often is patchy, again due to flooding. Characteristic species of this layer are *Aster* spp., *Bidens* spp., *Carex* spp., and *Leersia oryzoides*. Stands occur on floodplains of rivers and streams in sites that frequently are flooded and where drainage is poor. Establishment and maintenance of the community is tied closely to flooding events. Soils usually are poorly developed and are moderately well-drained to poorly-drained.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on Fort Riley but best represented on the west side along primary tributaries to Milford Lake and on the south side along floodplains of the Republican and Kansas rivers.

2.0 WOODLAND COMMUNITIES

Woodland component has 26–60% canopy cover and most to all trees < 5 m tall.

Chinquapin Oak-Bur Oak/Big Bluestem Ravine Woodland (4)

Description: This open-canopy, upland community is dominated by *Quercus muehlenbergii* in the driest stands, with *Quercus macrocarpa* as a subdominant. *Quercus macrocarpa* becomes more important in sites where conditions are more mesic until, eventually, the community grades into a forest with relatively little *Quercus muehlenbergii*. *Ulmus* spp. and *Cercis canadensis* can be abundant. *Ulmus* spp. once may have been an important element of this community, but Dutch Elm disease kills most trees before 40-years of age. Shrub cover varies inversely with tree canopy cover, achieving 50–60% in some of the drier stands (Abrams 1986, 1988). Common shrubs are *Cornus drummondii* and *Symphoricarpos orbiculatus*. *Celtis occidentalis* and *Ulmus* spp. often are in the shrub layer, especially on sites that have not been burned recently. Herbaceous dominants include *Schizachyrium scoparium* and *Panicum virgatum*. Stands occur on moderate to steep south-facing and west-facing slopes of ravines and river valleys. The surface is not saturated or flooded by groundwater at any time during the year, and drought is relatively common. Soils are deep, moderately well-drained to well-drained silts and loams. The parent material is loess, glacial till, cherty shales, or limestones. Drought and fire were common natural disturbances in this community type.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on the installation, but best represented along the upper slopes of the Republican and Kansas rivers' drainages, and in the Wildcat Creek drainage.

3.0 HERBACEOUS COMMUNITIES

Woodland component is < 25% canopy cover, graminoids and/or forbs are >25% canopy cover.

Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie (5)

Description: This community is dominated by a dense cover of tall grasses with a moderate to high richness of forbs. Dominant grasses are *Andropogon gerardii*, *Sorghastrum nutans*, and *Schizachyrium scoparium*. *Bouteloua curtipendula*, *Panicum virgatum*, and *Sporobolus compositus* are common but less abundant. Typical forbs include *Aster ericoides*, *Helianthus grosseserratus*, *Lespedeza capitata*, *Psoralidium tenuiflorum*, *Solidago* spp., and *Viola pedatifida*. Shrubs, such as *Amorpha canescens*, and trees usually are infrequent but can be common near

watercourses or where fires have been suppressed. Stands occur primarily on uplands and slopes but may occur infrequently in well-drained sites on floodplains. Soils are shallow to deep, somewhat poorly-drained to somewhat excessively-drained silts, loams, and clays. The parent material is calcareous clayey shale, limestone, cherty limestone, or interbedded limestone and clayey shale.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on uplands and slopes. This is the dominant natural community type on the installation.

Sand bluestem-Prairie sandreed Sand Prairie (6)

Description: This community is dominated by moderately to widely-spaced mid- to tall-grasses. The dominant species are *Andropogon hallii* and *Calamovilfa longifolia*. Other characteristic graminoids include *Bouteloua gracilis*, *Bouteloua hirsuta*, *Cenchrus longispinus*, *Cyperus lupulinus*, *C. schweinitzii*, *Eragrostis trichodes*, *Koeleria macrantha*, *Paspalum setaceum*, and *Schizachyrium scoparium*. Characteristic forbs are *Asclepias amplexicaulis*, *Chamaesyce glyptosperma*, *Chenopodium pratericola*, *Cycloloma atriplicifolium*, *Euphorbia hexagona*, *Helianthus pauciflorus*, *Liatis punctata*, *Lithospermum incisum*, *Oenothera laciniata*, *Physalis heterophylla*, *P. pumila*, *Plantago patagonica*, and *Strophostyles leiosperma*. Representative shrubs and vines are *Cornus drummondii*, *Prunus angustifolia*, *Rhus aromatica*, and *Toxicodendron radicans* (Freeman unpublished data). Stands usually occur on level to undulating sands in valleys of rivers or large streams. Occasionally, the community occurs on uplands immediately adjacent to river valleys. Slopes are gentle to moderate. Soils are sand, loamy-sand, or sandy-loam, and usually are erodible to highly erodible, sometimes with blowouts.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: This community is restricted to the floodplain of the Republican and Kansas rivers, usually immediately adjacent to the rivers. The best remnants occur south and southeast of Camp Forsyth in Training Areas 18 and 19. Most of this community type probably was destroyed long ago as the installation developed along the floodplain of the rivers. Occurrences on Fort Riley are too small to be included in the Kansas Natural Heritage Inventory databases.

4.0 SPARSE VEGETATION COMMUNITIES

Vegetation scattered or nearly absent; total vegetation cover < 10%.

Limestone Butte Sparse Vegetation; Great Plains Limestone Butte (7)

Description: This community is dominated by drought-tolerant herbaceous species. Representative species include *Agalinis aspera*, *Allium canadense*, *Chamaesyce missurica*, *Coryphantha missouriensis*, *Dalea aurea*, *Hedeoma hispida*, *Hybanthus verticillatus*, *Lomatium foeniculaceum*, *Oenothera macrocarpa*, *Pellaea glabella*, *Stenostiphon linifolius*, *Tomanthera densiflora*, *Tragia ramosa*, and *Yucca glauca* (Freeman unpublished data). Stands usually occur on the upper slopes of steep valleys along rivers and streams.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: This community is widely distributed on the installation, primarily along bluffs of the Republican and Kansas rivers, and along Wildcat Creek and its tributaries in association with outcrops of the Ft. Riley Limestone. The best examples occur along Backstop

Ridge (Training Area 21), Sherman Heights (Training Area 17), east of Campbell Hill (Training Area 7), and in training areas immediately south of Wildcat Creek on the northeast side of the installation (particularly Training Areas 31, 32, 33, 91, and 92). Occurrences on Fort Riley are too small to be included in the Kansas Natural Heritage Inventory databases. They are included within surrounding community types, usually Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie.

Riverine Sand Flats-Bars Sparse Vegetation (8)

Description: This riverine community supports sparse vegetation and is highly ephemeral due to constantly changing conditions. Representative graminoids are *Cyperus esculentus*, *C. odoratus*, *C. squarrosus*, *C. strigosus*, *Echinochloa muricata*, *Eragrostis pectinacea*, *E. hypnoides*, *Leptochloa fusca*, *L. panicea*, and *Triplasis purpurea*. Characteristic herbaceous species are *Amaranthus tuberculatus*, *Ammannia coccinea*, *A. robusta*, *Aster subulatus*, *Cycloloma atriplicifolium*, *Leucospora multifida*, *Lindernia dubia*, *Polygonum bicornis*, *P. lapathifolium*, *Portulaca oleracea*, *Strophostyles helvula*, and *S. leiosperma*. (Freeman unpublished data). Stands usually occur along sand bars and islands that form as waters recede. Soils usually are undeveloped due to the ephemeral nature of the community and may be poorly drained to excessively drained, depending on the depth to the water table.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: This community is restricted to the floodplains of the Republican and Kansas rivers. Examples typically can be found along the length of these rivers as they pass through Fort Riley. However, the precise locations of occurrences may vary from one year to the next. The Kansas Natural Heritage Inventory has insufficient data about this community type to include examples at Fort Riley in its databases. They are mapped, however.

5.0 RUDERAL VEGETATION

Vegetation has been highly altered by human activities, and is not identifiable to a natural type based on existing composition or structure.

Cropland-Abandoned (9)

Description: This ruderal community is highly variable on the installation, with local physiognomy and species composition depending on length of time since abandonment, ongoing disturbance, and management practices. Most examples are dominated by herbaceous species, but shrubs or trees often are present, and in some cases they dominate.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on the installation but concentrated on level uplands, especially in the central part. Because of the amount of natural succession that has occurred in some areas, Cropland-Abandoned was at times exceedingly difficult to identify in the field. Aerial photos were useful in helping to identify some tracts.

Brome Field (10)

Description: This ruderal community includes areas intentionally planted to non-native, perennial, cool-season grasses, which are or were cut annually for hay. *Bromus japonicus*, a non-native annual, frequently is a co-dominant invader. Abandoned brome fields are difficult to identify in most training areas, but extant examples exist in the south part of Fort Riley. An excellent example

of this community type occurs on the level floodplain immediately south of Backstop Ridge. It is hayed annually.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Sporadic on the installation. Many areas identified as this types in 1985 (as Grassland-Tame) have undergone considerable natural succession and now are classified as other ruderal, invasive, or managed types. Occurrences in the developed parts of Fort Riley were not mapped.

Ruderal-Mixed (11)

Description: This ruderal community captures a wide variety of vegetation conditions represented on the installation. Most examples are characterized by some type of severe, periodic or one-time disturbance, which has resulted in damage to or destruction of native vegetation or seral vegetation. Topsoil disturbance is a characteristic condition, but herbicide use also can create similar conditions. Species composition of the Ruderal-Mixed community is difficult to characterize. Non-native, ruderal herbs and graminoids are common, but native herbs and graminoids also are regular associates. Many associates exhibit a prostrate or spreading habit and are able to survive repeated compaction, such as results from vehicles.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Widespread on Fort Riley but often highly localized.

6.0 INVASIVE VEGETATION

The prevailing vegetation stratum is dominated by species alien to the ecoregion and dominance of this alien species is not likely to give way to native species without active restoration efforts.

Sericea lespedeza Herbaceous Vegetation (12)

Description: This ruderal community was not mapped per se on Fort Riley, but the name may be applied to sites where *Lespedeza cuneata* infestations have become sufficiently dense to warrant special attention. The necessity of identifying occurrences of *Lespedeza cuneata* Herbaceous Vegetation on the vegetation map was moderated by two factors. First, infestations were identified as a separate part of this study. However, before occurrences of the vegetation type can be delimited, thresholds must be set for determining when *Lespedeza cuneata* has achieved dominance. Canopy cover may be the most direct measure of this. Second, DPW probably will continue to pursue aggressive control of *Lespedeza cuneata*. Eradication efforts likely will cause sudden and dramatic changes in populations of *Lespedeza cuneata*, potentially rendering this component of any vegetation map obsolete.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: *Lespedeza cuneata* was documented in nearly all of the training areas; however, infestations are most severe in formerly cultivated areas. The species has been far less successful invading healthy, native, tallgrass prairies. Estimated mean canopy cover in a majority of five training areas has reached 11–20%; much higher levels of cover, while not uncommon, are exceedingly limited in area.

Smooth brome/Japanese brome Herbaceous Vegetation (13)

Description: This ruderal community was not mapped on Fort Riley, mostly because occurrences are highly localized. While physiognomically similar to the *Bromus inermis*/*Bromus japonicus*-

Lolium arundinaceum Herbaceous Vegetation type, the *Bromus inermis*-*Bromus japonicus* Herbaceous Vegetation type was not planted intentionally for hay production; it occurs spontaneously in sites with repeated disturbance and appropriate microhabitat conditions.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Sporadic on the installation and usually highly localized.

7.0 MODIFIED/MANAGED VEGETATION

The vegetation community is moderately- to highly-altered by human activities, identifiable to a natural type based on composition or structure, the alteration may be physiognomic or compositional but is beyond the range of variation allowed for corresponding natural type.

Yellow indiagrass-Little bluestem-Oldfield threeawn-Sand dropseed Herbaceous Vegetation, Overgrazed Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie (14)

Description: This modified/managed vegetation type represents a disclimax example of the *Andropogon gerardii*-*Sorghastrum nutans*-*Schizachyrium scoparium* Flint Hills Herbaceous Vegetation type. Basically, it is overgrazed Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie. Examples were not mapped, but we discovered numerous areas that appear to have a past history of prolonged and intense grazing by livestock. Suspected examples usually support degraded populations of *Andropogon gerardii*, *Sorghastrum nutans*, and other species characteristic of Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie; all suspected examples were mapped as Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie. Sustained grazing appears to have shifted species composition in favor of more grazing-tolerant and drought-adapted species like *Schizachyrium scoparium*, *Aristida oligantha*, and *Sporobolus cryptandrus*. Characteristic forbs are *Ambrosia psilostachya*, *Croton* spp., *Brickellia eupatorioides*, *Physalis* spp., *Verbena stricta*, and *Vernonia baldwinii*. *Juniperus virginiana* is a frequent where fire has been suppressed, invasive tree; other woody species also may be present. Most occurrences are on rocky uplands on gentle to moderate slopes.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Probably widespread on uplands and slopes, especially in the south, east, and northwest parts of Fort Riley. Natural succession since abandonment of farms and ranches has made it difficult to identify most examples of this community type. Nomenclature: This community type was not recognized in the 1985 vegetation surveys.

Rough-leaf dogwood-Smooth sumac-Elm-Honeylocust Shrubland, Woodland-Brushy (15)

Description: This modified/managed vegetation type captures sites with widely varying physiognomy and floristic composition. We found it exceedingly difficult to determine what kind of disturbance occurred at many sites supporting this community type, and the type undoubtedly encompasses areas representing varied management and disturbance histories. The Woodland-Brushy type generally is dominated by a moderate to dense cover of shrubs, frequently intermixed with a variety of immature trees. Characteristic woody species generally are *Cornus drummondii*, *Rhus glabra*, *Ulmus americana*, *Ulmus pumila*, and *Gleditsia triacanthos*. *Fraxinus pennsylvanica*, *Juniperus virginiana*, *Maclura pomifera*, *Populus deltoides* are other woody species routinely associated with the type. *Symphoricarpos orbiculatus* is the most common understory shrub. The herbaceous understory is highly variable from site to site. At some sites, it

suggests that extreme disturbance of the topsoil occurred. In other places, fire suppression has permitted establishment of the type on formerly cultivated ground or native prairie.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Encountered throughout the installation. The type is a category of convenience, and occurrences may have dramatically different histories.

8.0 PLANTED/CULTIVATED VEGETATION TYPES

Fire Break (16)

Description: Fire breaks are maintained around the perimeter of most of Fort Riley to help contain wildfires, should they occur. These may consist of bare ground or may be planted with row crops. Regardless of condition, they usually support a mixture of non-native, ruderal species during the growing season.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Maintained around the perimeter of most of the installation.

Food Plot (17)

Description: Food plots are planted with a variety of row crops to provide food for wildlife. These may consist of bare ground or may be vegetated with milo, soybeans, or other crop species. Regardless of condition, most support a mixture of non-native, ruderal species during the growing season.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Maintained throughout the installation.

Cultivated Field (18)

Description: Cultivated fields are planted with row crops. Most seem to be located around the periphery of the installation, where they also may be functioning as fire breaks. This vegetation type may not be distinct from Fire Break, but it has been carried forward from the 1985 vegetation surveys. Cultivated fields consist of bare ground or may be vegetated with row crops. Most support a mixture of non-native, ruderal species during the growing season.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Maintained around the perimeter of most of the installation.

Tree Plantation (19)

Description: A few tree plantations are maintained in training units in the south part of Fort Riley. The largest ones are in Training Areas 2, 18, and 19. All support deciduous tree species. Depending on age, understories may be fairly open, dominated by a mixture of non-native, ruderal species, or dominated by a mixture of native and non-native species during the growing season.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Maintained mostly in training areas in the south part of the installation.

Hedgerow/Windbreak (20)

Description: Hedgerows/Windbreaks usually are linear tree plantings, mostly with a single species of deciduous tree, which originally provided shelter and shade around farmsteads and along old roads and farm lanes. Some hedgerows also probably served as living fences. *Maclura pomifera*

is the species encountered most frequently, but others species used include *Juniperus virginiana*, *Robinia pseudoacacia*, and *Ulmus* spp. Many hedgerows and windbreaks have been damaged due to training exercises, and many had deteriorated due to senescence and death of trees. Most support a varied understory of native and non-native shrubs, herbs, and graminoids.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Found throughout the installation, mostly in association with old farmsteads and roads.

Lawn (21)

Description: Lawns are areas usually planted to cool-season grasses or rarely warm-season grasses and maintained by periodic and frequent mowing. They also may support a mixture of non-native and native graminoids and herbs.

Occurrence on Fort Riley: Found largely in the developed parts of the installation, especially in the south, in the vicinity of training complexes around the Impact Areas, and around buildings in the northwest part of the MPRC. Mowed roadsides also could be included in this category.

Appendix I, Table 1. Plants reported from Fort Riley during the 2003 Kansas Biological Survey study. CoC = Kansas coefficient of conservatism. An asterisk (*) in the CoC column indicates the species is non-native.

FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC
ACANTHACEAE			<i>Asclepias sullivantii</i>	smooth milkweed	5
<i>Ruellia humilis</i>	fringe-leaf ruellia	3	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	common milkweed	1
<i>Ruellia strepens</i>	limestone ruellia	4	<i>Asclepias tuberosa</i>	butterfly milkweed	6
ACERACEAE			<i>Asclepias verticillata</i>	whorled milkweed	1
<i>Acer negundo</i>	boxelder	1	<i>Asclepias viridiflora</i>	green milkweed	6
AGAVACEAE			<i>Asclepias viridis</i>	spider milkweed	1
<i>Yucca glauca</i>	small soapweed	4	ASTERACEAE		
ALISMATACEAE			<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	western yarrow	1
<i>Alisma subcordatum</i>	southern water-plantain	4	<i>Ageratina altissima</i>	tall snakeroot	1
<i>Alisma triviale</i> Pursh	northern water-plantain	4	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	common ragweed	0
<i>Echinodorus berteroi</i>	upright burhead	4	<i>Ambrosia psilostachya</i>	western ragweed	3
<i>Sagittaria brevirostra</i>	short-beak arrowhead	4	<i>Ambrosia trifida</i>	giant ragweed	0
<i>Sagittaria cuneata</i>	northern arrowhead	4	<i>Amphiachyris dracunculoides</i>	common broomweed	2
<i>Sagittaria montevidensis</i>	giant arrowhead	3	<i>Antennaria neglecta</i>	field pussy's-toes	2
AMARANTHACEAE			<i>Arnoglossum plantagineum</i>	tuberous Indian-plantain	6
<i>Amaranthus albus</i>	tumbleweed amaranth	0	<i>Artemisia ludoviciana</i>	Louisiana sagewort	2
<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i>	Palmer's pigweed	0	<i>Aster drummondii</i>	Drummond's aster	2
<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	rough pigweed	*	<i>Aster ericoides</i>	heath aster	5
<i>Amaranthus tuberculatus</i>	tall water-hemp	0	<i>Aster lanceolatus</i>	lance-leaf aster	3
<i>Froelichia gracilis</i>	slender snake-cotton	3	<i>Aster oblongifolius</i>	aromatic aster	5
ANACARDIACEAE			<i>Aster pilosus</i>	hairy aster	0
<i>Rhus aromatica</i>	aromatic sumac	3	<i>Aster sericeus</i>	silky aster	8
<i>Rhus glabra</i>	smooth sumac	1	<i>Aster subulatus</i>	saltmarsh aster	0
<i>Toxicodendron radicans</i>	poison-ivy	0	<i>Bidens bipinnatus</i>	Spanish needles	0
APIACEAE			<i>Bidens cernuus</i>	nodding beggar-ticks	3
<i>Berula erecta</i>	cut-leaf water-parsnip	6	<i>Bidens frondosus</i>	devil's beggar-ticks	0
<i>Chaerophyllum procumbens</i>	spreading chervil	0	<i>Brickellia eupatorioides</i>	eastern brickellbush	2
<i>Chaerophyllum tainturieri</i>	southern chervil	2	<i>Carduus nutans</i>	musk plumeless-thistle	*
<i>Conium maculatum</i>	poison-hemlock	*	<i>Cirsium altissimum</i>	tall thistle	2
<i>Daucus carota</i>	Queen-Anne's-lace	*	<i>Conyza canadensis</i>	tall horseweed	0
<i>Eryngium yuccifolium</i>	button snake-root eryngo	7	<i>Conyza ramosissima</i>	spreading horseweed	0
<i>Lomatium foeniculaceum</i>	fennel-leaf desert-parsley	6	<i>Coreopsis grandiflora</i>	big-flower coreopsis	8
<i>Polytaenia nuttallii</i> A103	Nuttall's prairie-parsley	6	<i>Dyssodia papposa</i>	fetid marigold	0
<i>Sanicula canadensis</i>	Canadian sanicle	2	<i>Echinacea angustifolia</i>	black-Sampson purple-coneflower	6
<i>Sanicula odorata</i>	fragrant sanicle	2	<i>Echinacea pallida</i>	pale purple-coneflower	7
<i>Spermolepis inermis</i>	spreading scaleseed	3	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	yerba de tajo	3
APOCYNACEAE			<i>Erechtites hieracifolia</i>	American burnweed	1

<i>Apocynum cannabinum</i>	hemp dogbane	0	<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	annual fleabane	0
ARACEAE			<i>Erigeron strigosus</i>	daisy fleabane	4
ASCLEPIACEAE			<i>Eupatorium altissimum</i>	tall joe-pye-weed	2
<i>Asclepias amplexicaulis</i>	blunt-leaf milkweed	7	<i>Grindelia lanceolata</i>	spiny-tooth gumweed	3
<i>Asclepias incarnata</i>	swamp milkweed	4	<i>Grindelia squarrosa</i>	curly-top gumweed	0
<i>Asclepias speciosa</i>	showy milkweed	2	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	common sunflower	0
<i>Asclepias stenophylla</i>	narrow-leaf milkweed	7	<i>Helianthus grosseserratus</i>	saw-tooth sunflower	4

FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC
<i>Helianthus hirsutus</i>	hairy sunflower	6	BORAGINACEAE		
<i>Helianthus maximiliani</i>	Maximilian's sunflower	3	<i>Hackelia virginiana</i>	Virginia bracted-stickseed	3
<i>Helianthus mollis</i>	ashy sunflower	7	<i>Lithospermum arvense</i>	corn gromwell	*
<i>Helianthus pauciflorus</i>	stiff sunflower	5	<i>Lithospermum incisum</i>	plains gromwell	5
<i>Helianthus petiolaris</i>	plains sunflower	1	<i>Myosotis verna</i>	spring forget-me-not	2
<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	Jerusalem-artichoke sunflower	2	<i>Onosmodium bejariense</i>	western false-marbleseed	4
<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i>	sunflower heliopsis	6	BRASSICACEAE		
<i>Heterotheca subaxillaris</i>	broad-leaf golden-aster	2	<i>Alliaria petiolata</i>	common garlic-mustard	*
<i>Heterotheca stenophylla</i>	narrow-leaf golden-aster	4	<i>Arabis canadensis</i>	Canadian rockcress	4
<i>Hymenopappus scabiosaeus</i>	flat-top white-woolly	4	<i>Camelina microcarpa</i>	little-pod false-flax	*
<i>Krigia cespitosa</i>	weedy dwarf-dandelion	4	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	common shephard's-purse	*
<i>Lactuca canadensis</i>	Canadian lettuce	2	<i>Diploxaxis muralis</i>	stinking wall rocket	*
<i>Lactuca floridana</i>	Florida lettuce	3	<i>Draba reptans</i>	white whitlow-wort	2
<i>Lactuca saligna</i>	willow-leaf lettuce	*	<i>Lepidium densiflorum</i>	prairie pepper-grass	0
<i>Lactuca serriola</i>	prickly lettuce	*	<i>Microthlaspi perfoliatum</i>	perfoliate-pennycress	*
<i>Liatris aspera</i>	button gayfeather	6	<i>Rorippa palustris</i>	blunt-leaf yellowcress	2
<i>Liatris mucronata</i>	eastern dotted gayfeather	5	<i>Rorippa sessiliflora</i>	stalkless yellowcress	1
<i>Liatris punctata</i>	western dotted gayfeather	5	CACTACEAE		
<i>Packera plattensis</i>	prairie ragwort	5	<i>Coryphantha missouriensis</i>	Missouri River coryphantha	7
<i>Pluchea odorata</i>	purple marsh-fleabane	2	<i>Opuntia macrorhiza</i>	big-root pricklypear	3
<i>Prenanthes aspera</i>	rough rattlesnake-root	8	CAMPANULACEAE		
<i>Prionopsis ciliata</i>	wax-goldenweed	1	<i>Campanula americana</i>	American bellflower	4
<i>Pseudognaphalium obtusifolium</i>	fragrant false-cudweed	0	<i>Lobelia cardinalis</i>	cardinal-flower	6
<i>Pyrrhopappus grandiflorus</i>	tuberous false-dandelion	4	<i>Triodanis leptocarpa</i>	slender-fruit Venus'-looking-glass	3
<i>Ratibida columnifera</i>	upright prairie-coneflower	4	<i>Triodanis perfoliata</i>	clasping-leaf Venus'-looking-glass	2
<i>Ratibida pinnata</i>	gray-head prairie-coneflower	3	CANNABACEAE		
<i>Rudbeckia hirta</i>	black-eyed-Susan	2	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	marijuana	*
<i>Silphium integrifolium</i>	whole-leaf rosinweed	3	<i>Humulus lupulus</i>	common hop	3

<i>Silphium laciniatum</i>	compassplant	4	CAPRIFOLIACEAE		
<i>Solidago canadensis</i>	Canadian goldenrod	1	<i>Lonicera maackii</i>	Amur honeysuckle	*
<i>Solidago gigantea</i>	late goldenrod	3	<i>Lonicera tatarica</i>	Tatarian honeysuckle	*
<i>Solidago missouriensis</i>	Missouri goldenrod	5	<i>Sambucus canadensis</i>	American elder	2
<i>Solidago nemoralis</i>	gray goldenrod	2	<i>Symphoricarpos orbiculatus</i>	coral-berry	1
<i>Solidago petiolaris</i>	downy goldenrod	7	<i>Triosteum perfoliatum</i>	clasping horse-gentian	4
<i>Solidago rigida</i>	rough goldenrod	3	CARYOPHYLLACEAE		
<i>Solidago speciosa</i>	showy goldenrod	7	<i>Arenaria serpyllifolia</i>	thyme-leaf sandwort	*
<i>Sonchus asper</i>	prickly sow-thistle	*	<i>Dianthus armeria</i>	Deptford pink	*
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	common dandelion	*	<i>Saponaria officinalis</i>	common soapwort	*
<i>Thelesperma megapotamicum</i>	Rio Grande greenthread	4	<i>Silene antirrhina</i>	sleepy catchfly	0
<i>Tragopogon dubius</i>	western salsify	*	<i>Silene stellata</i>	starry catchfly	4
<i>Verbesina alternifolia</i>	wing-stem crownbeard	4	<i>Stellaria pallida</i>	pale chickweed	*
<i>Vernonia baldwinii</i>	western ironweed	2	CELASTRACEAE		
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	common cocklebur	0	<i>Celastrus scandens</i>	American bittersweet	4
BIGNONIACEAE			<i>Euonymus atropurpureus</i>	eastern wahoo	5
<i>Campsis radicans</i>	common trumpet-creeper	*	CHENOPODIACEAE		
<i>Catalpa speciosa</i>	northern catalpa	*	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	lamb's-quarters goosefoot	0
			<i>Chenopodium berlandieri</i>	pit-seed goosefoot	0
<i>Chenopodium pallescens</i>	pale goosefoot	1	<i>Carex grisea</i>	narrow-leaf sedge	3
FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC
<i>Chenopodium pratericola</i>	field goosefoot	3	<i>Carex hystericina</i>	bottle-brush sedge	7
<i>Chenopodium simplex</i>	maple-leaf goosefoot	2	<i>Carex inops</i>	sun sedge	8
<i>Chenopodium standleyanum</i>	Standley's goosefoot	3	<i>Carex laeviconica</i>	smooth-cone sedge	8
<i>Cycloloma atriplicifolium</i>	tumble ringwing	1	<i>Carex leavenworthii</i>	Leavenworth's sedge	2
<i>Kochia scoparia</i>	broom kochia	*	<i>Carex meadii</i>	Mead's sedge	7
CLUSIACEAE			<i>Carex oligocarpa</i>	straight-fruit sedge	6
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	common St. John's-wort	*	<i>Carex pellita</i>	woolly sedge	5
<i>Hypericum punctatum</i>	spotted St. John's-wort	6	<i>Carex vulpinoidea</i>	fox sedge	3
COMMELINACEAE			<i>Cyperus acuminatus</i>	tape-leaf flat-sedge	0
<i>Commelina erecta</i>	erect dayflower	4	<i>Cyperus erythrorhizos</i>	red-root flat-sedge	4
<i>Tradescantia bracteata</i>	bracted spiderwort	5	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	yellow nut-sedge	0
<i>Tradescantia ohiensis</i>	Ohio spiderwort	5	<i>Cyperus lupulinus</i>	slender-stem flat-sedge	3
CONVOLVULACEAE			<i>Cyperus xmesochorus</i>	intermediate sedge	4
<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	common hedge-bindweed	0	<i>Cyperus odoratus</i>	slender flat-sedge	3
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	field bindweed	*	<i>Cyperus schweinitzii</i>	Schwinitz's flat-sedge	6
<i>Evolvulus nuttallianus</i>	Nuttall's evolvulus	6	<i>Cyperus squarrosus</i>	awned flat-sedge	0
<i>Ipomoea hederacea</i>	ivy-leaf morning-glory	*	<i>Cyperus strigosus</i>	false nut-sedge	4
<i>Ipomoea lacunosa</i>	white morning-glory	0	<i>Eleocharis compressa</i>	flat-stem spike-rush	6
<i>Ipomoea leptophylla</i>	bush morning-glory	5	<i>Eleocharis engelmannii</i>	Engelmann's spike-rush	4

<i>Ipomoea purpurea</i>	purple morning-glory	*	<i>Eleocharis erythropoda</i>	bald spike-rush	4
CORNACEAE			<i>Eleocharis macrostachya</i>	large-spike spike-rush	3
<i>Cornus amomum</i>	pale dogwood	5	<i>Schoenoplectus tabernaemontani</i>	soft-stem twine-bulrush	4
<i>Cornus drummondii</i>	rough-leaf dogwood	1	<i>Scirpus atrovirens</i>	green bulrush	4
CRASSULACEAE			<i>Scirpus pallidus</i>	pale bulrush	5
<i>Penthorum sedoides</i>	ditch-stonecrop	3	<i>Scirpus pendulus</i>	drooping bulrush	3
CUCURBITACEAE			EQUISETACEAE		
<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	watermelon	*	<i>Equisetum laevigatum</i>	smooth scouring-rush	3
<i>Cucurbita foetidissima</i>	buffalo gourd	0	EUPHORBIACEAE		
<i>Sicyos angulatus</i>	wall bur-cucumber	2	<i>Acalypha ostryifolia</i>	rough-pod copperleaf	0
CUPRESSACEAE			<i>Acalypha rhomboidea</i>	rhombic copperleaf	1
<i>Chamaecyparis lawsoniana</i>	Port-Orford-cedar	*	<i>Acalypha virginica</i>	Virginia copperleaf	0
<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	eastern red-cedar		<i>Chamaesyce glyptosperma</i>	ridge-seed mat-spurge	0
CUSCUTACEAE			<i>Chamaesyce humistrata</i>	spreading mat-spurge	3
<i>Cuscuta glomerata</i>	cluster dodder	3	<i>Chamaesyce maculata</i>	spotted mat-spurge	0
CYPERACEAE			<i>Chamaesyce missurica</i>	Missouri mat-spurge	5
<i>Bolboschoenus fluviatilis</i>	river tuberous-bulrush	5	<i>Chamaesyce nutans</i>	eyebane	0
<i>Carex aggregata</i>	cluster sedge	6	<i>Chamaesyce serpens</i>	round-leaf mat-spurge	0
<i>Carex albicans</i>	white-tinge sedge	7	<i>Chamaesyce stictospora</i>	slim-seed mat-spurge	0
<i>Carex austrina</i>	southern sedge	2	<i>Croton capitatus</i>	woolly croton	1
<i>Carex bicknellii</i>	Bicknell's sedge	8	<i>Croton glandulosus</i>	tropic croton	1
<i>Carex blanda</i>	woodland sedge	1	<i>Croton monanthogynus</i>	one-seed croton	1
<i>Carex brachyglossa</i>	yellow-fruit sedge	5	<i>Croton texensis</i>	Texas croton	1
<i>Carex brevior</i>	short-beak sedge	5	<i>Euphorbia corollata</i>	flowering spurge	5
<i>Carex bushii</i>	Bush's sedge	4	<i>Euphorbia cyathophora</i>	painted spurge	3
<i>Carex davisii</i>	Davis' sedge	4	<i>Euphorbia davidii</i>	western toothed spurge	0
<i>Carex emoryi</i>	Emory's sedge	5	<i>Euphorbia hexagona</i>	six-angle spurge	2
<i>Carex gravida</i>	heavy sedge	4	<i>Euphorbia marginata</i>	snow-on-the-mountain	0
<i>Euphorbia spathulata</i>	warty spurge	5	<i>Securigera varia</i>	common crown-vetch	*
<i>Tragia ramosa</i>	catnip noseburn	6	<i>Senna marilandica</i>	Maryland senna	3
FAMILY	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY	Common Name	CoC
Scientific Name			Scientific Name		
FABACEAE			<i>Strophostyles helvula</i>	trailing wildbean	3
<i>Amorpha canescens</i>	leadplant	7	<i>Strophostyles leiosperma</i>	slick-seed wildbean	3
<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	bush wild-indigo	6	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	red clover	*
<i>Amphicarpaea bracteata</i>	America hog-peanut	3	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	white clover	*
<i>Astragalus canadensis</i>	Canadian milk-vetch	4	<i>Vicia americana</i>	American vetch	7
<i>Astragalus crassicarpus</i>	ground-plum milk-vetch	7	FAGACEAE		
<i>Astragalus lotiflorus</i>	lotus milk-vetch	4	<i>Quercus macrocarpa</i>	bur oak	4
<i>Astragalus plattensis</i>	Platte River milk-vetch	7	<i>Quercus muehlenbergii</i>	chinquapin oak	5
<i>Baptisia australis</i>	blue wild-indigo	6	GENTIANACEAE		
<i>Baptisia bracteata</i>	plains wild-indigo	6	<i>Gentiana puberulenta</i>	downy gentian	8

<i>Cercis canadensis</i>	eastern redbud	2	GERANIACEAE		
<i>Chamaecrista fasciculata</i>	showy partridgepea	2	<i>Geranium carolinianum</i>	Carolina crane's-bill	0
<i>Crotalaria sagittalis</i>	arrow rattlebox	4	<i>Geranium pusillum</i>	small crane's-bill	*
<i>Dalea aurea</i>	golden prairie-clover	5	GROSSULARIACEAE		
<i>Dalea candida</i>	white prairie-clover	7	<i>Ribes missouriense</i>	Missouri gooseberry	3
<i>Dalea enneandra</i>	nine-anther prairie-clover	5	HYDROCHARITACEAE		
<i>Dalea leporina</i>	hare-foot prairie-clover	2	<i>Najas guadalupensis</i>	common naiad	1
<i>Dalea multiflora</i>	round-head prairie-clover	7	HYDROPHYLLACEAE		
<i>Dalea purpurea</i>	purple prairie-clover	7	<i>Ellisia nyctelea</i>	water-pod	0
<i>Desmanthus illinoensis</i>	Illinois bundle-flower	2	IRIDACEAE		
<i>Desmodium canadense</i>	Canadian tick-clover	4	<i>Iris germanica</i>	German iris	*
<i>Desmodium canescens</i>	hoary tick-clover	4	<i>Sisyrinchium campestre</i>	prairie blue-eyed-grass	6
<i>Desmodium cuspidatum</i>	long-leaf tick-clover	6	JUGLANDACEAE		
<i>Desmodium glutinosum</i>	large-flower tick-clover	3	<i>Carya cordiformis</i>	bitter-nut hickory	4
<i>Desmodium illinoense</i>	Illinois tick-clover	5	<i>Carya illinoensis</i>	pecan	6
<i>Desmodium perplexum</i>	Dillen's tick-clover	5	<i>Juglans nigra</i>	black walnut	3
<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i>	common honey-locust	0	JUNCACEAE		
<i>Glycyrrhiza lepidota</i>	American licorice	3	<i>Juncus interior</i>	inland rush	2
<i>Gymnocladus dioica</i>	Kentucky coffeetree	4	<i>Juncus torreyi</i>	Torrey's rush	2
<i>Kummerowia stipulacea</i>	Korena low-bush-clover	*	LAMIACEAE		
<i>Lespedeza capitata</i>	round-head bush-clover	6	<i>Agastache nepetoides</i>	catnip giant-hyssop	4
<i>Lespedeza cuneata</i>	sericea lespedeza	*	<i>Hedeoma hispida</i>	rough false-penny-royal	1
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	bird-foot trefoil	*	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	hen-bit dead-head	*
<i>Lotus unifoliolatus</i>	prairie trefoil	3	<i>Lycopus americanus</i>	American water-horehound	3
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	black medic	*	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	field mint	3
<i>Medicago minima</i>	prickly medic	*	<i>Monarda fistulosa</i>	wild bergamot bee-balm	3
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	alfalfa	*	<i>Nepeta cataria</i>	common catnip	*
<i>Melilotus alba</i>	white sweet-clover	*	<i>Pycnanthemum tenuifolium</i>	narrow-leaf mountain-mint	4
<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>	yellow sweet-clover	*	<i>Salvia azurea</i>	blue sage	4
<i>Mimosa quadrivalvis</i>	cat-claw mimosa	6	<i>Salvia reflexa</i>	lance-leaf sage	1
<i>Oxytropis lambertii</i>	Lambert's crazyweed	5	<i>Scutellaria lateriflora</i>	side-flower skullcap	4
<i>Pediomelum argophyllum</i>	silver-leaf scurf-pea	8	<i>Scutellaria parvula</i>	southern small skullcap	5
<i>Pediomelum esculentum</i>	bread-root scurf-pea	7	<i>Teucrium canadense</i>	American germander	1
<i>Psoraleidum tenuiflorum</i>	wild-alfalfa	3	<i>Trichostema brachiatum</i>	flux-weed bluecurls	5
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	black locust	*			
LILIACEAE			<i>Oenothera speciosa</i>	showy white evening-primrose	2
<i>Allium canadense</i>	Canadian onion	5	<i>Oenothera villosa</i>	hairy evening-primrose	0
<i>Allium canadense</i>	Canadian onion	5	<i>Stenosiphon linifolius</i>	stenosiphon	6
FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY Scientific Name	Common Name	CoC

<i>Allium sativum</i>	garlic	*	OPHIOGLOSSACEAE		
<i>Allium stellatum</i>	summer pink onion	6	<i>Botrychium virginianum</i>	rattlesnake fern	4
<i>Allium vineale</i>	field garlic	*	ORCHIDACEAE		
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	garden asparagus	*	<i>Spiranthes cernua</i>	nodding ladies'-tresses	5
<i>Hemerocallis fulva</i>	orange day-lily	*	OXALIDACEAE		
<i>Maianthemum stellatum</i>	starry spikenard	8	<i>Oxalis dillenii</i>	gray-green wood-sorrel	0
<i>Toxicoscordion nuttallii</i>	Nuttall's death-camas	5	<i>Oxalis violacea</i>	violet wood-sorrel	4
LINACEAE			PAPAVERACEAE		
<i>Linum pratense</i>	Norton's blue flax	5	<i>Argemone polyanthemus</i>	plains prickly-poppy	3
<i>Linum sulcatum</i>	grooved flax	6	PHYTOLACCACEAE		
LOASACEAE			<i>Phytolacca americana</i>	American pokeweed	0
<i>Mentzelia oligosperma</i>	stick-leaf	4	PINACEAE		
LYTHRACEAE			<i>Pinus nigra</i>	Austrian pine	*
<i>Ammannia coccinea</i>	purple toothcup	2	<i>Pinus ponderosa</i>	ponderosa pine	*
<i>Ammannia robusta</i>	stout toothcup	2	PLANTAGINACEAE		
<i>Lythrum alatum</i>	winged loosestrife	4	<i>Plantago aristata</i>	bottle-brush plantain	2
MALVACEAE			<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	English plantain	*
<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	common velvetleaf	*	<i>Plantago patagonica</i>	woolly plantain	1
<i>Callirhoë alcaeoides</i>	pale poppy-mallow	6	<i>Plantago rhodosperma</i>	red-seed plantain	2
<i>Callirhoë involucrata</i>	purple poppy-mallow	1	<i>Plantago rugelii</i>	Rugel's plantain	0
<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	flower-of-an-hour	*	<i>Plantago virginica</i>	pale-seed plantain	1
<i>Malvastrum hispidum</i> A473	rough false-mallow	3	PLATANACEAE		
<i>Sida spinosa</i>	prickly sida	*	<i>Platanus occidentalis</i>	common sycamore	4
MENISPERMACEAE			<i>Agrostis hyemalis</i>	winter bent grass	2
<i>Menispermum canadense</i>	Canadian moonseed	4	<i>Alopecurus carolinianus</i>	Carolina foxtail	0
MOLLUGINACEAE			<i>Andropogon gerardii</i>	big bluestem	4
<i>Mollugo verticillata</i>	green carpetweed	*	<i>Andropogon hallii</i>	sand bluestem	5
MORACEAE			<i>Aristida oligantha</i>	old-field threeawn	0
<i>Maclura pomifera</i>	Osage-orange	*	<i>Bothriochloa bladhii</i>	Caucasian bluestem	*
<i>Morus alba</i>	white mulberry	*	<i>Bothriochloa ischaemum</i>	Turkestan bluestem	*
<i>Morus rubra</i>	red mulberry	5	<i>Bothriochloa laguroides</i>	silver bluestem	1
NYCTAGINACEAE			<i>Bouteloua curtipendula</i>	side-oats grama	5
<i>Mirabilis albida</i>	white four-o'clock	5	<i>Bouteloua gracilis</i>	blue grama	5
<i>Mirabilis linearis</i>	narrow-leaf four-o'clock	5	<i>Bouteloua hirsuta</i>	hairy grama	6
<i>Mirabilis nyctaginea</i>	wild four-o'clock	0	<i>Bromus inermis</i>	smooth brome	*
OLEACEAE			<i>Bromus japonicus</i>	Japanese brome	*
<i>Fraxinus pennsylvanica</i>	green ash	0	<i>Bromus pubescens</i>	Canadian brome	4
ONAGRACEAE			<i>Buchloë dactyloides</i>	buffalo grass	3
<i>Calylophus serrulatus</i>	plains yellow evening-primrose	5	<i>Calamovilfa longifolia</i>	prairie sand-reed	7
<i>Gaura longiflora</i>	large-flower butterfly-weed	2	<i>Cenchrus longispinus</i>	field sandbur	0
<i>Gaura parviflora</i>	velvet butterfly-weed	1	<i>Chasmanthium latifolium</i>	broad-leaf wood-oat	4

<i>Ludwigia peploides</i>	floating seedbox	3	<i>Chloris verticillata</i>	whorled windmill grass	0
<i>Oenothera laciniata</i>	cut-leaf evening-primrose	0	<i>Chloris virgata</i>	showy windmill grass	0
<i>Oenothera macrocarpa</i>	Missouri evening-primrose	5	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	common bermuda grass	*
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	orchard grass	*	<i>Saccharum ravennae</i>	Ravenna grass	*
<i>Diarrhena obovata</i>	American beakgrain	6	<i>Schedonnardus paniculatus</i>	tumble grass	3
<i>Dichanthelium acuminatum</i>	pointed dichanthelium	3	<i>Schizachyrium scoparium</i>	little bluestem	5
<i>Dichanthelium linearifolium</i>	slim-leaf dichanthelium	7	<i>Setaria faberi</i>	Chinese bristle grass	*
FAMILY	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY	Common Name	CoC
Scientific Name			Scientific Name		
<i>Dichanthelium oligosanthes</i>	Scribner's dichanthelium	4	<i>Setaria italica</i>	foxtail bristle grass	*
<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i>	southern crab grass	*	<i>Setaria pumila.</i>	yellow bristle grass	*
<i>Digitaria cognata</i>	fall witch grass	3	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	green bristle grass	*
<i>Echinochloa muricata</i>	rough barnyard grass	0	<i>Sorghastrum nutans</i>	yellow Indian grass	5
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	Indian goose grass	*	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	grain sorghum	*
<i>Elymus canadensis</i>	Canadian wild-rye	5	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	Johnson grass	*
<i>Elymus villosus</i>	hairy wild-rye	5	<i>Spartina pectinata</i>	prairie cord grass	4
<i>Elymus virginicus</i>	Virginia wild-rye	3	<i>Sphenopholis obtusata</i>	prairie wedgescale	4
<i>Eragrostis cilianensis</i>	stink grass	*	<i>Sporobolus clandestinus.</i>	southeastern dropeed	6
<i>Eragrostis hypnoides</i>	teal love grass	3	<i>Sporobolus compositus</i>	tall dropseed	3
<i>Eragrostis minor</i>	little love grass	*	<i>Sporobolus compositus</i>	meadow dropseed	3
<i>Eragrostis pectinacea</i>	Carolina love grass	0	<i>Sporobolus cryptandrus</i>	sand dropseed	0
<i>Eragrostis spectabilis</i>	purple love grass	3	<i>Sporobolus heterolepis</i>	prairie dropseed	8
<i>Eragrostis trichodes</i>	sand love grass	4	<i>Sporobolus neglectus</i>	puff-sheath dropseed	1
<i>Eriochloa contracta</i>	prairie cup grass	0	<i>Sporobolus pyramidatus</i>	whorled dropseed	4
<i>Festuca subverticillata</i>	noddig fescue	4	<i>Sporobolus vaginiflorus</i>	poverty dropseed	0
<i>Glyceria striata</i>	fowl manna grass	5	<i>Tridens flavus</i>	purpletop	1
<i>Hesperostipa spartea</i>	porcupine grass	8	<i>Triplasis purpurea</i>	purple sand grass	7
<i>Hordeum jubatum</i>	fox-tail barley	1	<i>Tripsacum dactyloides</i>	eastern gramma grass	3
<i>Hordeum pusillum</i>	little barley	0	<i>Vulpia octoflora</i>	six-weeks annual-fescue	1
<i>Koeleria macrantha</i>	prairie June grass	6	POLYGALACEAE		
<i>Leersia oryzoides</i>	rice cut grass	4	<i>Polygala verticillata</i>	whorled milkwort	3
<i>Leersia virginica</i>	white grass	3	POLYGONACEAE		
<i>Leptochloa fusca</i>	bearded sprangletop	0	<i>Polygonum amphibium</i>	swamp smartweed	2
<i>Leptochloa panicea</i>	red sprangletop	0	<i>Polygonum arenastrum</i>	sand knotweed	*
<i>Lolium pratense .</i>	meadow rye grass	*	<i>Polygonum bicornne</i>	pink smartweed	1
<i>Muhlenbergia cuspidata .</i>	plains muhly	5	<i>Polygonum convolvulus</i>	dull-seed cornbind	*
<i>Muhlenbergia frondosa</i>	wire-stem muhly	3	<i>Polygonum lapathifolium</i>	pale smartweed	2
<i>Muhlenbergia mexicana</i>	Mexican wire-stem muhly	4	<i>Polygonum persicaria</i>	lady's-thumb smartweed	*
<i>Muhlenbergia racemosa</i>	marsh muhly	4	<i>Polygonum punctatum</i>	dotted smartweed	3
<i>Muhlenbergia schreberi .</i>	nimblewill	0	<i>Polygonum ramosissimum</i>	bushy knotweed	2

<i>Muhlenbergia sobolifera</i>	rock muhly	5	<i>Polygonum scandens</i>	hedge cornbind	0
<i>Muhlenbergia sylvatica</i>	forest muhly	6	<i>Polygonum virginianum</i>	jumpseed	2
<i>Panicum capillare</i>	common witch grass	0	<i>Rumex altissimus</i>	pale dock	0
<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	fall panicum	0	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	curly dock	*
<i>Panicum virgatum</i>	switch grass	4	PONTEDERIACEAE		
<i>Pascopyrum smithii</i>	western wheat grass	2	<i>Heteranthera limosa</i>	blue mud-plantain	5
<i>Paspalum pubiflorum</i>	hairy-seed paspalum	4	PORTULACACEAE		
<i>Paspalum setaceum</i>	thin paspalum	2	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	common purslane	*
<i>Poa annua</i>	annual blue grass	*	POTAMOGETONACEAE		
<i>Poa compressa</i>	Canadian blue grass	*	<i>Potamogeton nodosus</i>	long-leaf pondweed	4
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	Kentucky blue grass	*	<i>Potamogeton pusillus</i>	baby pondweed	5
<i>Poa sylvestris</i>	wooland blue grass	4	PRIMULACEAE		
<i>Anagallis arvensis</i>	scarlet pimpernel	*	<i>Salix nigra</i>	black willow	2
<i>Androsace occidentalis</i>	western rock-jasmine	0	SANTALACEAE		
<i>Lysimachia ciliata</i>	fringed loosestrife	6	<i>Comandra umbellata</i>	umbellate bastard toad-flax	6
PTERIDACEAE			SCROPHULARIACEAE		
<i>Pellaea glabella</i>	smooth cliffbrake	8	<i>Agalinis aspera</i>	rough agalinis	7
FAMILY	Common Name	CoC	FAMILY	Common Name	CoC
Scientific Name			Scientific Name		
RANUNCULACEAE			<i>Bacopa rotundifolia</i>	round-leaf water-hyssop	4
<i>Anemone virginiana</i>	tall anemone	4	<i>Buchnera americana</i>	American bluehearts	9
<i>Delphinium carolinianum</i>	plains larkspur	6	<i>Chaenorrhinum minus</i>	lesser dwarf-snapdragon	*
<i>Ranunculus abortivus</i>	early wood buttercup	1	<i>Leucospora multifida</i>	paleseed	0
<i>Ranunculus aquatilis</i>	white water crowfoot	7	<i>Lindernia dubia</i>	false-pimpernel	4
<i>Ranunculus sceleratus</i>	cursed crowfoot	0	<i>Mimulus ringens</i>	Alleghany monkey-flower	5
<i>Thalictrum dasycarpum</i>	purple meadow-rue	4	<i>Penstemon cobaea</i>	cobaea beardtongue	5
RHAMNACEAE			<i>Penstemon digitalis</i>	smooth beardtongue	4
<i>Ceanothus herbaceus</i>	inland ceanothus	8	<i>Penstemon grandiflorus</i>	shell-leaf beardtongue	6
ROSACEAE			<i>Penstemon tubaeformis</i>	tube beardtongue	3
<i>Agrimonia pubescens</i>	downy agrimony	5	<i>Scrophularia marilandica</i>	Maryland figwort	5
<i>Geum canadense</i>	white avens	1	<i>Tomanthera densiflora</i>	fine-leaf hairy-foxtail	8
<i>Potentilla arguta</i>	tall cinquefoil	6	<i>Verbascum blattaria</i>	moth mullein	*
<i>Prunus americana</i>	American plum	3	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i>	flannel mullein	*
<i>Prunus angustifolia</i>	Chickasaw plum	3	<i>Veronica anagallis-aquatica</i>	blue water speedwell	*
<i>Prunus mahaleb</i>	mahaleb cherry	*	<i>Veronica arvensis</i>	corn speedwell	*
<i>Prunus mexicana</i>	big-tree plum	3	<i>Veronica polita</i>	wayside speedwell	*
<i>Pyrus communis</i>	common pear	*	SMILACACEAE		
<i>Rosa arkansana</i>	Arkansas rose	4	<i>Smilax tamnoides</i>	bristly greenbrier	2
<i>Rosa multiflora</i>	leafy rose	*	SOLANACEAE		
<i>Rubus aboriginum</i>	one-flower dewberry	5	<i>Lycium barbarum</i>	common matrimony-vine	*
<i>Rubus bushii</i>	Bush's highbush blackberry	2	<i>Physalis heterophylla</i>	clammy ground-cherry	4
<i>Rubus discolor</i>	Himalayan blackberry	*	<i>Physalis longifolia</i>	long-leaf ground-cherry	2
<i>Rubus hancinianus</i>	Hancin's dewberry	4	<i>Physalis pumila</i>	prairie ground-cherry	4
<i>Rubus laudatus</i>	praiseworthy blackberry	4	<i>Physalis virginiana</i>	Virginia ground-cherry	6

<i>Rubus mollior</i>	soft blackberry	4	<i>Solanum carolinense</i>	Carolina horse-nettle	1
<i>Rubus occidentalis</i>	black raspberry	2	<i>Solanum interius</i>	plains black nightshade	2
RUBIACEAE			<i>Solanum rostratum</i>	buffalo-bur nightshade	0
<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	common buttonbush	4	SPARGANIACEAE		
<i>Galium aparine</i>	catch-weed bedstraw	0	<i>Sparganium eurycarpum</i>	giant bur-reed	5
<i>Galium circaezans</i>	forest bedstraw	3	TAMARICACEAE		
<i>Galium pedemontanum</i>	foothill bedstraw	*	<i>Tamarix ramosissima</i>	salt-cedar	*
<i>Galium triflorum</i>	sweet-scent bedstraw	6	TILIACEAE		
<i>Stenaria nigricans</i>	narrow-leaf bluet	5	<i>Tilia americana</i>	American basswood	6
RUTACEAE			TYPHACEAE		
<i>Zanthoxylum americanum</i>	common prickly-ash	3	<i>Typha angustifolia</i>	narrow-leaf cat-tail	0
SALICACEAE			<i>Typha latifolia</i>	broad-leaf cat-tail	1
<i>Populus deltoides</i>	plains cottonwood	0	ULMACEAE		
<i>Populus nigra</i>	black poplar	*	<i>Celtis occidentalis</i>	common hackberry	1
<i>Salix amygdaloides</i>	peach-leaf willow	3	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	American elm	2
<i>Salix exigua</i>	sandbar willow	1	<i>Ulmus pumila</i>	Siberian elm	*
<i>Salix exigua</i>	sandbar willow	1	<i>Ulmus rubra</i>	slippery elm	3
URTICACEAE					
<i>Boehmeria cylindrica</i>	small-spike false-nettle	3			
<i>Laportea canadensis</i>	Canadian wood-nettle	4			
<i>Parietaria pennsylvanica</i>	Pennsylvania pellitory	0			
<i>Pilea pumila</i>	dwarf clearweed	2			
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	American stinging nettle	1			
FAMILY	Common Name	CoC			
Scientific Name					
VERBENACEAE					
<i>Phryma leptostachya</i>	American lopseed	5			
<i>Phyla cuneifolia</i>	wedge-leaf fogfruit	3			
<i>Phyla lanceolata</i>	northern fogfruit	1			
<i>Verbena bracteata</i>	prostrate vervain	0			
<i>Verbena hastata</i>	blue vervain	4			
<i>Verbena xmoechina</i>	pasture vervain	*			
<i>Verbena simplex</i>	narrow-leaf vervain	2			
<i>Verbena stricta</i>	hoary vervain	1			
<i>Verbena urticifolia</i>	nettle-leaf vervain	2			
VIOLACEAE					
<i>Hybanthus verticillatus.</i>	nodding green-violet	6			
<i>Viola bicolor</i>	Johnny-jump-up	0			
<i>Viola pedatifida</i>	prairie violet	5			
VITACEAE					
<i>Ampelopsis cordata</i>	heart-leaf raccoon-grape	2			
<i>Vitis cinerea</i>	gray-bark grape	5			
<i>Vitis riparia</i>	riverbank grape	2			
ZYGOPHYLLACEAE					
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	goat's-head	*			

Appendix I, Table 2. Complete list of mammals reported from Fort Riley, either from Pitts et al. (1987), or from surveys and sitings performed by Conservation Branch staff.

Species		Pitts	In house
Common Name	Scientific Name	1987	siting
Virginia opossum	<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>	x	x
Elliot's short-tailed shrew	<i>Blarina hylophaga</i>	x	x
Least shrew	<i>Cryptotis parva</i>	x	x
Eastern mole	<i>Scalopus aquaticus</i>	x	x
Big brown bat	<i>Eptesicus fuscus</i>	x	x
Red bat	<i>Lasiurus borealis</i>	x	x
Hoary bat	<i>Lasiurus cinereus</i>	x	
Little brown bat	<i>Myotis lucifugus</i>	x	
Tri-colored bat	<i>Pipistrellus subflavus</i>	x	x
Nine-banded armadillo	<i>Dasybus novemcinctus</i>		x
Black-tailed jackrabbit	<i>Lepus californicus</i>	x	x
Eastern cottontail	<i>Sylvilagus floridanus</i>	x	x
Woodchuck	<i>Marmota monax</i>	x	x
Gray squirrel	<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i>	x	
Fox squirrel	<i>Sciurus niger</i>	x	x
Thirteen-lined ground squirrel	<i>Spermophilus tridecemlineatus</i>	x	x
Plains Pocket gopher	<i>Geomys bursarius</i>	x	x
Hispid pocket mouse	<i>Chaetodipus hispidus</i>		x
Beaver	<i>Castor canadensis</i>	x	x
Prairie vole	<i>Microtus ochrogaster</i>	x	x
Woodland vole	<i>Microtus pinetorum</i>	x	x
Eastern woodrat	<i>Neotoma floridana</i>	x	x
Muskrat	<i>Ondatra zibethicus</i>	x	x
Northern grasshopper mouse	<i>Onychomys leucogaster</i>	x	x
White-footed mouse	<i>Peromyscus leucopus</i>	x	x
Deer mouse	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus</i>	x	x
Western harvest mouse	<i>Reithrodontomys megalotis</i>	x	x
Plain's harvest mouse	<i>Reithrodontomys montanus</i>	x	x
Hispid cotton rat	<i>Sigmodon hispidus</i>	x	x
Southern bog lemming	<i>Synaptomys cooperi</i>	x	x
House mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	x	x
Norway rat	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	x	
Meadow jumping mouse	<i>Zapus hudsonius</i>	x	x
Porcupine	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i>	x	X
Coyote	<i>Canis latrans</i>	x	x
Red fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	x	x
Raccoon	<i>Procyon lotor</i>	x	x
Striped skunk	<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>	x	x
Long-tailed weasel	<i>Mustela frenata</i>	x	x
Mink	<i>Mustela vison</i>	x	X
Eastern spotted skunk	<i>Spilogale putorius</i>	x	
Badger	<i>Taxidea taxus</i>	x	x
Bobcat	<i>Lynx rufus</i>	x	x
Mountain Lion	<i>Felis concolor</i>		X
Mule deer	<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	x	x
White-tailed deer	<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	x	x

Elk	<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	x	x
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Appendix I, Table 3. List of birds documented by Conservation Branch staff on Fort Riley, and each species time and frequency of occurrence.

Common Name	S	W	M	Common Name	S	W	M	Common Name	S	W	M	Common Name	S	W	M
GREBES				Northern harrier	R	C	O	Baird's sandpiper	R	~	O	FLYCATCHERS			
Pied-billed grebe	~	R	C	Sharp-shinned hawk	O	O	O	Pectoral sandpiper	R	~	O	Eastern wood pewee	C	~	C
Horned grebe	~	~	R	Cooper's hawk	O	O	C	Stilt sandpiper	~	~	O	Olive-sided flycatcher	~	~	R
Eared grebe	~	~	O	Northern goshawk	~	O	~	Buff-breasted sandpiper	~	~	R	Yellow-bellied flycatcher	R	~	R
PELICANS				Red-shouldered hawk	~	~	R	Long-billed dowitcher	~	~	C	Acadian flycatcher	R	~	R
American white pelican	R	~	C	Broad-winged hawk	~	~	R	Whimbrel	~	~	R	Willow flycatcher	O	~	O
CORMORANTS				Swainson's hawk	~	~	O	Wilson's snipe	~	O	O	Least flycatcher	~	~	O
Double-crested cormorant	~	~	A	Red-tailed hawk	C	A	C	American woodcock	O	~	O	Say's phoebe	~	~	R
Neotropic cormorant	~	~	R	Ferruginous hawk	~	~	R	Wilson's phalarope	~	~	O	Eastern phoebe	C	~	C
HERONS				Rough-legged hawk	~	C	O	GULLS				Great-crested flycatcher	C	~	C
American bittern	~	~	O	FALCONS				Franklin's gull	~	~	A	Western kingbird	O	~	O
Great blue heron	A	O	A	American kestrel	O	O	C	Bonaparte's gull	~	~	O	Eastern kingbird	C	~	C
Great egret	O	~	C	Merlin	~	R	~	Ring-billed gull	~	A	A	Scissor-tailed flycatcher	O	~	O
Little blue heron	~	~	C	Peregrine falcon	~	R	O	Herring gull	~	A	A	LARKS, SWALLOWS			
Snowy egret	~	~	O	Prairie falcon	~	~	O	TERNs				Horned lark	R	O	O
Cattle egret	~	~	O	FOWL				Caspian tern	~	~	R	Purple martin	C	~	C
Green heron	C	~	O	Ring-necked pheasant	A	A	A	Forster's tern	C	~	C	Tree swallow	O	~	O
Black-crowned night-heron	~	~	O	Greater prairie-chicken	C	C	C	Least tern	R	~	R	No. rough-winged swallow	O	~	C
IBISES				Ruffed grouse	~	~	~	Black tern	~	~	O	Bank swallow	O	~	O
White-faced ibis	~	~	R	Wild turkey	A	A	A	DOVES				Cliff swallow	A	~	A
GEESE				Northern bobwhite	A	A	A	Rock dove	A	A	A	Barn swallow	A	~	A
Greater white-fronted goose	~	~	O	RAILS				Eurasian collared dove	O	O	O	JAYS, CROWS			
Snow goose	~	O	C	Black rail	~	~	R	Mourning dove	A	O	A	Blue jay	A	A	A
Ross' goose	~	O	O	Yellow rail	~	~	R	CUCKOOS				American crow	A	A	A
Canada goose	C	C	C	Virginia rail	~	~	R	Black-billed cuckoo	O	~	O	Fish crow	~	R	R
Cackling goose	~	C	O	Sora	~	~	O	Yellow-billed cuckoo	C	~	C	Black-billed magpie	~	~	R
DUCKs				GALLINULES				OWLS				CHICKADEES, TITMOUSE			
Wood duck	C	~	C	American coot	~	O	C	Eastern screech owl	C	C	C	Black-capped chickadee	A	A	A
Green-winged teal	R	O	C	CRANES				Great horned owl	C	C	C	Tufted titmouse	A	A	A
Mallard	R	C	A	Sandhill crane	~	~	O	Snowy owl	~	R	R	NUTHATCHES, CREEPERS			
Northern pintail	~	~	C	PLOVERS				Burrowing owl	~	~	R	Red-breasted nuthatch	~	O	O
Blue-winged teal	R	~	A	Killdeer	C	~	C	Barred owl	C	C	C	White-breasted nuthatch	C	C	C
Cinnamon teal	~	~	R	Black-bellied plover	~	~	R	Long-eared owl	~	R	R	Brown creeper	~	O	O
Northern shoveler	~	O	C	American golden plover	~	~	R	Short-eared owl	~	O	O	WRENS			
Gadwall	~	O	A	Snowy plover	R	~	R	GOATSUCKERS				Carolina wren	C	C	C
American wigeon	~	C	C	Semipalmated plover	R	~	O	Common nighthawk	C	~	C	Bewick's wren	O	~	O
Canvasback	~	R	O	Piping plover	R	~	R	Common poorwill	O	~	~	House wren	A	~	A
Redhead	~	O	O	SANDPIPERS, PHALAROPES				Chuck-will's-widow	C	~	O	Winter wren	~	O	O
Ring-necked duck	~	O	C	American avocet	~	~	O	Whip-poor-will	O	~	O	Sedge wren	O	~	O
Lesser scaup	~	O	C	Greater yellowlegs	R	~	C	SWIFTS				Marsh wren	~	R	O
Common goldeneye	~	C	C	Lesser yellowlegs	R	~	C	Chimney swift	A	~	A	KINGLETS AND GNATCATCHERS			
Bufflehead	~	O	O	Solitary sandpiper	~	~	O	HUMMINGBIRDS				Golden-crowned kinglet	~	O	O
Hooded merganser	~	O	O	Willet	~	~	O	Ruby-throated hummingbird	O	~	O	Ruby-crowned kinglet	~	~	O
Common merganser	~	C	C	Spotted sandpiper	R	~	C	KINGFISHERS				Blue-gray gnatcatcher	O	~	O
Red-breasted merganser	~	~	R	Upland sandpiper	C	~	C	Belted kingfisher	C	C	C	THRUSH			
Ruddy duck	~	~	O	Hudsonian godwit	~	~	R	WOODPECKERS				Eastern bluebird	C	C	C
VULTURES				Marbled godwit	~	~	R	Red-headed woodpecker	C	R	C	Townsend's solitaire	~	R	~
Turkey vulture	C	~	C	Ruddy turnstone	~	~	R	Red-bellied woodpecker	C	C	C	Mountain bluebird	~	R	~

HAWKS AND EAGLES				Sanderling	~ ~ R	Yellow-bellied sapsucker	~ O R	Wood thrush	O ~ O		
Osprey	~ ~	O		Semipalmated sandpiper	R ~ C	Downy woodpecker	C C C	Veery	~ ~ O		
Mississippi kite	~ ~	R		Western sandpiper	R ~ O	Hairy woodpecker	O O O	Swainson's thrush	~ ~ C		
Bald eagle	~ C	A		Least sandpiper	R ~ O	Northern flicker	C C C	Gray-cheeked thrush	~ ~ O		
Golden eagle	~ ~	R		White-rumped sandpiper	R ~ O	Pileated woodpecker	O O O				
Common Name	S	W	M	Common Name	S	W	M	Common Name	S	W	M
Hermit thrush	~	R	O	Blackpoll warbler	~	~	O	Lark bunting	R	~	R
American robin	A	C	C	Magnolia warbler	~	~	R	Savannah sparrow	~	~	C
THRASHERS				Black and white warbler	R	~	C	Grasshopper sparrow	A	~	A
Gray catbird	A	~	A	American redstart	R	~	O	Henslow's sparrow	O	~	O
Northern mockingbird	O	~	O	Prothonotary warbler	R	~	S	LeConte's sparrow	~	R	O
Sage thrasher	~	~	R	Ovenbird	R	~	O	Fox sparrow	~	O	O
Brown thrasher	A	~	A	Louisiana waterthrush	R	~	O	Song sparrow	R	O	C
PIPITS				Kentucky warbler	O	~	O	Lincoln's sparrow	~	~	C
American Water pipit	~	~	O	Mourning warbler	~	~	O	White-throated sparrow	~	O	O
Sprague's pipit	~	~	R	Common yellowthroat	C	~	C	White-crowned sparrow	~	O	O
WAXWINGS				Virginia's warbler	R	~	R	Harris' sparrow	~	A	A
Cedar waxwing	R	C	C	Wilson's warbler	~	~	C	Dark-eyed junco	~	A	A
Bohemian waxwing	~	R	R	Hooded warbler	R	~	R	Lapland longspur	~	O	O
SHRIKES				Yellow-breasted chat	R	~	R	Snow bunting	~	R	R
Northern shrike	~	O	~	TANAGERS			BLACKBIRDS				
Loggerhead shrike	O	O	O	Summer tanager	O	~	O	Bobolink	~	~	R
STARLINGS				Scarlet tanager	O	~	O	Red-winged blackbird	A	A	A
European starling	A	A	A	GROSBEAKS			Eastern meadowlark				
VIREOS				Northern cardinal	A	A	A	Western meadowlark	O	~	O
White-eyed vireo	~	~	O	Rose-breasted grosbeak	O	~	O	Yellow-headed blackbird	~	~	O
Bell's vireo	C	~	C	Blue grosbeak	R	~	O	Rusty blackbird	~	O	O
Blue-headed vireo	~	~	O	BUNTINGS			Brewer's blackbird				
Yellow-throated vireo	R	~	O	Indigo bunting	C	~	C	Common grackle	A	~	A
Warbling vireo	O	~	O	Lazuli bunting	~	~	R	Brown-headed cowbird	A	C	C
Philadelphia vireo	~	~	O	Painted bunting	R	~	R	ORIOLES			
Red-eyed vireo	A	~	C	Dickcissel	A	~	O	Orchard oriole	C	~	C
WARBLERS				SPARROWS			Baltimore oriole				
Tennessee warbler	~	~	C	Eastern towhee	C	~	C	Bullock's oriole	~	~	R
Orange-crowned warbler	~	~	C	Spotted towhee	~	O	O	FINCHES			
Nashville warbler	~	~	C	American tree sparrow	~	A	A	Purple finch	~	O	O
Northern parula	O	~	O	Chipping sparrow	C	~	C	House finch	O	O	O
Yellow warbler	C	~	C	Clay-colored sparrow	~	~	C	Pine Siskin	~	O	O
Chestnut-sided warbler	~	~	R	Field sparrow	C	~	C	American goldfinch	A	A	A
Yellow-rumped warbler	~	O	C	Swamp sparrow	~	O	C	WEAVER FINCH			
Black-throated green warbler	~	~	O	Vesper sparrow	~	~	C	House sparrow	A	A	A
Prairie warbler	R	~	R	Lark sparrow	C	~	C				

Totals: Species - 269

S=Summer, W=Winter,

M=Migrant

R=Rare, O=Occasional, C=Common, A=Abundant

Appendix I, Table 4. Complete list of birds observed during expected breeding times, and highest confirmation of confirmation of breeding status.

SPECIES	Safe dates	Date seen	P O	P R	C O
American white pelican		Jun8-93	O		
Great blue heron	5/1-7/1	Jun16-94			N Y
Little blue heron	5/30-7/31	Jun17-92	O		
Great egret	5/20-7/31	Jun11-07			O N
Green-backed heron	5/10-7/15	Jun7-93		P	
American bittern	5/25-8/10	My20-93	O		
Canada goose	5/1-8/1	Ap20-97			N E
Wood duck	4/1-8/1	Jun22-90			F L
Mallard*	4/20-8/31	My15-90			F L
Blue-winged teal	5/15-8/15	Jul31-89			F L
Green-winged teal	6/1-8-31	Jul-2002			F L
Common merganser		Jun8-93	O		
Hooded merganser	4/15-7/31	Jun7-93	O		
Lesser scaup		Jun7-93	O		
Turkey vulture	5/1-8/1	Jul5-95			N Y
Mississippi kite	5/1-8/1	Sep8-15			F L
Bald eagle		My5-04			N Y
Northern harrier	5/1-8/1	Ap29-93		A	
Sharp-shinned hawk	5/15-8/15	Jun12-93	X		
Coopers hawk	5/1-8/15				M
Red-tailed hawk	5/5-8/15	Jun1-93			N Y
Broad-winged hawk	5/1-8/31	Jun10-13		P	
Red-shouldered hawk	4/1-8/31	Jun16-13			F L
American kestrel	4/5-7/31	Jul12-93			F L
Ring-necked pheasant	4/15-9/30	My25-94			F L
Gr. Prairie-chicken	4/20-8/31	Jun21-93			F L
Wild turkey	4/30-9/30	Jun28-93			F L
Northern bobwhite	4/20-8/31	Jul20-94			F L
Killdeer	4/20-7/31	Jun21-93			F L
Upland sandpiper	5/5-7/15	Jun18-90			F L
American woodcock	4/15-9/20	My 2010			N E
Ring-billed gull		Jun6-92	O		
Least tern		Jun15-97		C	

SPECIES	Safe dates	Date seen	P O	P R	C O
Belted kingfisher	5/10-7/20	Jun13-99			O N
Red-headed woodpecker	5/15-8/20	Jun29-93			FL
Red-bellied woodpecker	4/15-7/31	Jun28-93			FL
Downy woodpecker	4/15-8/31				M
Hairy woodpecker	4/1-8/31				M
Northern flicker	5/1-7/31				M
Pileated woodpecker	4/15-8/31	Jun17-99		P	
Eastern wood pewee	6/1-8/1				M
Acadian flycatcher	5/20-8/5	Jun8-92	X		
Willow flycatcher	6/1-7/31	1996	X		
Least flycatcher	6/1-7/31		X		
Eastern phoebe	4/1-7/31	Jun1-93			N Y
Gr-Crested flycatcher	5/25-8/1				M
Western kingbird	5/20-8/15				M
Eastern kingbird	5/25-8/15	Jul29-93			FL
Scissor-tailed flycatcher	5/25-7/15	Jun15-89			FL
Horned lark	4/20-7/15	My21-96	O		
Purple martin	5/15-6/25	Jul26-96			N Y
Tree swallow	5/15-7/15	Jun13-13		P	
N. rough-winged swallow	5/25-7/15	Jun4-99			FY
Bank swallow	5/25-7/15	My20-96			O N
Cliff swallow	6/1-7/20	Jun9-93			O N
Barn swallow	5/5-8/5	Jul2-96			N Y
Blue jay	4/20-7/31	My18-95			O N
Black-billed magpie	4/20-7/15	Jun4-97	X		
American crow	4/10-8/31				M
Black-capped chickadee	4/10-7/31	Jun9-93			FY
Tufted titmouse	4/15-8/31	Jun10-93			O N
White-breasted nuthatch	4/5-8/15				M
Brown creeper		Jun15-96	X		
Carolina wren	4/20-8/31				M
Bewick's wren	4/10-7/31	Jun11-93	X		
House wren	5/5-8/15	Jun27-92			O N

SPECIES	Safe dates	Date seen	P O	P R	C O
Red-eyed vireo	6/1-7/31	Jul1-95			F Y
Northern parula	5/15-8/15				M
Prairie warbler	5/25-7/20	Jul15-03	X		
Yellow warbler	5/20-7/31	Jun4-99			F Y
Black-&-white warbler	5/20-7/31	Jun9-92		P	
American redstart	5/20-7/20	Jun9-92	X		
Prothonotary warbler	5/20-7/31	Jun1-00		P	
Ovenbird	5/25-8/5				M
La. waterthrush	5/1-7/10				M
Kentucky warbler	5/15-7/15	Jun29-93			O N
Common yellowthroat	5/15-8/10				M
Yellow-breasted chat	5/25-8/5	Jun19-96		C	
Summer tanager	5/20-8/10	Jul8-95			F L
Scarlet tanager	5/20-8/10				M
Northern cardinal	4/15-9/30	Jul6-93			F L
Rose-breasted grosbeak	5/20-8/10				M
Blue grosbeak	5/25-8/10	Jul5-94	X		
Indigo bunting	5/25-8/15	Jun26-14		T	
Painted bunting	5/20-8/10	Jul5-95			F L
Dickcissel	6/1-8/15	Jul8-93			N Y
Eastern towhee	5/5-8/31				M
Chipping sparrow	5/10-8/15	My20-93			N B
Field sparrow	5/1-8/31				M
Lark sparrow	5/10-7/31	Jun9-93			F Y
Grasshopper sparrow	5/10-8/31	Jun25-93			N E
Henslow's sparrow	5/10-8/31				M
Song sparrow	5/1-9/10	Jun20-96			O N
Bobolink	6/1-7/20	Jun2-92	X		
Red-winged blackbird	5/10-8/31	Jul27-93			F Y
Eastern meadowlark	4/20-8/15	Jun11-93			N E
Western meadowlark	4/20-8/31				M
Common grackle	5/10-7/10	Jul29-93			F Y
Brown-head cowbird	5/1-7/10	Jun11-93			N E

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Rock dove	all year	Jul1-93				ON
Mourning dove	4/10-9/15	My18-93				NE
Black-billed cuckoo	6/1-8/15	Jul12-89				FL
Yellow-billed cuckoo	5/20-9/15	Jul18-92				NE
Eastern screech-owl	4/1-8/15	Jun17-97				FL
Great horned owl	3/1-7/31	My13-94				NY
Barred owl	3/15-8/31					M
Short-eared owl	4/1-7/15	Ap15-06			P	
Common nighthawk	5/20-7/31	Jn23-94				NE
Chuck-will's widow	5/1-8/10	My9-02				NE
Whip-poor-will	5/25-8/10	My28-95	X			
Common poorwill	5/25-8/10	Jun29-93	X			
Chimney swift	5/25-8/15					M
Ruby-throat hummingbird	6/1-7/31					M

Sedge wren	7/1-9/10	Jul27-93	X			
Blue-gray gnatcatcher	4/20-7/31	My3-02				ON
Eastern bluebird	4/15-8/15	Jun9-93				FL
Wood thrush	5/30-8/20					M
American robin	4/15-8/20	My10-93				NE
Gray catbird	5/20-8/31					M
Northern mockingbird	4/25-8/31	My18-93	X			
Brown thrasher	5/10-7/31	My31-93				NY
Cedar waxwing	6/15-7/31					M
Loggerhead shrike	4/15-7/20	My20-95				FY
European starling	4/5-9/5	Jun28-93				FL
White-eyed vireo	5/20-8/15					M
Bell's vireo	5/15-8/15	Jul8-93				FY
Yellow-throated vireo	5/15-8/15	Jul1-05	X			
Warbling vireo	6/1-8/10					M

Orchard oriole	5/20-7/31	Jul12-93				FY
Baltimore oriole	5/15-7/31	Jul31-93				FL
House finch	5/15-8/31	My31-96				NE
American goldfinch	6/20-7/30	Aug8-89				FL
House sparrow	3/15-8/31	My18-89				NY
Total		134	2	1	9	
			4	1	9	

PO=possible PR=probable
 CO=confirmed breeding.
 O=species not in breeding habitat; X=species in breeding habitat; P=pair (male & female) seen; T=bird holding territory; C=courtship/copulation; N=visiting probable nest site;
 A=agitated behavior or anxiety call; B=nest-building (woodpecker or wren); NB=nest building any other species; FL=fledged young; ON=adults enter or leave nest site; FY=adult carrying food; NE=nest with eggs; NY=nest with young
 M=Confirmed by MAPS project 1993-2005

Appendix I, Table 5. Reptiles, amphibians and turtles documented from Fort Riley.

Species	KBS	Fort Riley In-house Surveys													
	1993	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Snapping turtle	x	1	5		1				1		4	2	4	7	
Painted turtle	x	12	2	14			6		5	4	2	10	9	11	
False map turtle	x	4	12					2			6	2	3	14	
Pond Slider	x	4	24	31	6		1	5	6		18	3		36	2
Ornate box turtle	x			1			1			1		2		1	
Smooth softshell	x													1	
Spiny softshell	x														
Softshell Sp.		10	9	4			1	1	2			1			
Eastern collard lizard	x	13	15	30	22	22	24	30	37	36	9	20	38	19	15
Texas horned lizard	x	1		2			20+		2	1	2	3	3		
Prairie lizard		3		1			1								
Great plains skink	x	33	13	34	48	30	26	54	63	42	35	30	48	35	35
Prairie skink			1	2											
Common Five-lined skink			2				1								
Little Brown skink	x	4	1		6	2			2	1		1	2	2	4
Slender Glass lizard	x			1	1		2		1	3	1	2		2	1
Six-lined racerunner	x	30	10	24	7	10	6	2	27	5		19	7	13	15
Western worm snake					2	2	1	7		1		1	4	2	
Ring-necked snake	x	174	57	165	339	463	308	716	552	580	672	132	1,129	495	920
Plains hog-nosed snake	x														
Yellow-bellied kingsnake	x					1	1	1	2			1	1		3
Flat-headed snake	x	6				1		1						1	
Plains black-headed snake	x		1	3											
North American racer	x	3	3	2	4	2	16	5		9	3	2	25	7	13
Great plains ratsnake	x	4	2	6	4	5	13	10	17	18	5	5	23	27	17
Western ratsnake	x	3	1	1			2	2	5	5	1	4	4	7	2
Speckled kingsnake	x							3	1	1		1		2	1
Western milksnake	x	6	6	10	8	17	6	24	11	25	10	10	25	34	22
Gophersnake	x	1			2		10	2	1	5	2	2	3	1	2
Plain-bellied watersnake		2													
Common watersnake	x	10	1	3	6		1	5		2	4	14		7	1
Dekay's Brownsnake	x			1			1		1			2	1	1	3
Western ribbonsnake	x			1											
Plains gartersnake								1	2		1				6
Common gartersnake	x	6	1		2	1	3	7	3	7	7	6	10	8	7
Lined snake	x	2		4	4	4	1	5	1	3	2	6	4	4	4
Eastern Copperhead	x	5	2	2	8	8	7	9	6	5	2		6	3	6
Timber rattlesnake												1			
Eastern Tiger Salamander	x		1												
Plains spadefoot	x											3			
Woodhouse's toad	x	1	2	2		2	1		2	3		2	3		1
Great Plains Toad											1	1			
Blanchard's cricket frog	x	54+	21+	223	101	48	216	85	180	106	233	217	28	109	172
Gray treefrog complex	x	1					1	1	5		1	1		1	
Boreal chorus frog	x	14+	16+	51	6	12	15	31	112	8	3	12	23	111	
American Bullfrog	x	28+	5	51	18	9		7	46	7	128	90	17	10	119
Plains leopard frog	x	26+	26	70	31	7	3	15	53	11	35	21		17	15
W. narrow-mouthed toad	x	49	12	9	3	82	67	12	108	39	10	39	91	22	5

Appendix I, Table 6. List of fishes on Fort Riley, Kansas.

Common Name (<i>Scientific Name</i>)	Streams	Rivers	Ponds
Shovelnose sturgeon (<i>Scaphirhynchus platyrhynchus</i>)	-	X	-
Longnose gar (<i>Lepisosteus osseus</i>)	X	X	X
Shortnose gar (<i>Lepisosteus platostomus</i>)	-	X	X
American eel (<i>Anguilla rostrata</i>)	-	P	-
Gizzard shad (<i>Dorosoma cepedianum</i>)	X	X	X
Goldeye (<i>Hiodon alosoides</i>)	-	X	-
Rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	-	-	X
Common carp (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>)	X	X	X
Golden shiner (<i>Notemigonus crysoleucas</i>)	X	-	X
Creek chub (<i>Semotilus atromaculatus</i>)	X	-	-
Southern redbelly dace (<i>Phoxinus erythrogaster</i>)	X	-	-
Silver chub (<i>Hybosis storeiana</i>)	-	X	-
Speckled chub (<i>Hybosis aestivalis</i>)	-	X	-
Sturgeon chub (<i>Hybosis gelida</i>)	-	E	-
Suckermouth minnow (<i>Phenacobius mirabilis</i>)	X	X	-
Emerald shiner (<i>Notropis atherinoides</i>)	-	X	-
Rosyface shiner (<i>Notropis rubellus</i>)	X	-	-
Redfin shiner (<i>Notropis umbratilis</i>)	X	-	-
Common shiner (<i>Notropis cornutus</i>)	X	-	-
Red shiner (<i>Notropis lutrensis</i>)	X	X	-
Topeka shiner (<i>Notropis topeka</i>)	X	-	-
Sand shiner (<i>Notropis stramineus</i>)	X	X	-
Plains minnow (<i>Hybognathus hankinsoni</i>)	-	X	-
Fathead minnow (<i>Pimephales promelas</i>)	X	X	X
Bullhead minnow (<i>Pimephales vigilax</i>)	X	X	-
Bluntnose minnow (<i>Pimephales notatus</i>)	X	X	-
Central stoneroller (<i>Campostoma anomalum</i>)	X	X	-
Blue sucker (<i>Cycleptus elongatus</i>)	-	X	-
Bigmouth buffalo (<i>Ictiobus cyprinellus</i>)	X	X	X
Black buffalo (<i>Ictiobus niger</i>)	-	X	-
Smallmouth buffalo (<i>Ictiobus bubalus</i>)	-	X	X
Quillback (<i>Carpiodes cyprinus</i>)	-	X	-
River carpsucker (<i>Carpiodes carpio</i>)	X	X	X
Shorthead redhorse (<i>Moxostoma macrolepidotum</i>)	X	X	-
White sucker (<i>Catostomus commersoni</i>)	X	X	-
Black bullhead (<i>Ictalurus melas</i>)	X	X	X
Yellow bullhead (<i>Ictalurus natalis</i>)	X	P	X
Channel catfish (<i>Ictalurus punctatus</i>)	X	X	X
Flathead catfish (<i>Pylodictis olivaris</i>)	X	X	X

Common Name (Scientific Name)	Streams	Rivers	Ponds
Slender madtom (<i>Noturus exilis</i>)	X	-	-
Stonecat (<i>Noturus flavus</i>)	X	X	-
Blackstripe topminnow (<i>Fundulus notatus</i>)	X	-	-
Mosquitofish (<i>Gambusia affinis</i>)	X	X	X
White bass (<i>Morone chrysops</i>)	-	X	-
Wiper (white bass x striped bass)	X	-	X
Smallmouth bass (<i>Micropterus dolomieu</i>)	-	X	-
Spotted bass (<i>Micropterus punctulatus</i>)	X	-	-
Largemouth bass (<i>Micropterus salmoides</i>)	X	X	X
Green sunfish (<i>Lepomis cyanellus</i>)	X	X	X
Redear sunfish (<i>Lepomis microlophus</i>)	-	-	X
Bluegill (<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i>)	X	X	X
Orangespotted sunfish (<i>Lepomis humilis</i>)	X	-	-
Longear sunfish (<i>Lepomis magalotis</i>)	X	-	-
White crappie (<i>Pomoxis annularis</i>)	X	X	X
Black crappie (<i>Pomoxis nigromaculatus</i>)	-	-	X
Walleye (<i>Stizostedion vitreum</i>)	-	-	X
Saugeye (<i>Stizostedion vitreum x Stizostedion canadense</i>)	-	X	-
Logperch (<i>Percina caprodes</i>)	X	-	-
Johnny darter (<i>Etheostoma nigrum</i>)	X	X	-
Orangethroat darter (<i>Etheostoma spectabile</i>)	X	X	-
Freshwater drum (<i>Aplodinotus grunniens</i>)	-	X	X

x = collected in recent surveys; P = possible occurrence; E = extirpated

Appendix I, Table 7. List of fish species that have been documented in each Fort Riley stream.

	Wildcat Cr.	Silver Cr.	Sevenmile Cr.	Fourmile Cr.	Threemile Cr.	Onemile Cr.	Forsyth Cr.	Little Arkansas	Honey Cr.	Wind Cr.	Dry Cr.	Drybranch Cr.	Madison Cr.	Farnum Cr.	Timber Cr.	Rush Cr.
Bigmouth buffalo				X												
Black bullhead	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
Blackstripe topminnow										X						
Bluegill	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
Bluntnose minnow	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		
Bullhead minnow	X		X		X				X	X						
Central stoneroller	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Channel catfish	X			X	X			X					X			
Common carp	X		X	X	X	X							X	X	X	X
Common shiner	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			X	X		
Creek chub	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Fathead minnow	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Flathead catfish	X												X			
Freshwater Drum*						X							X			
Gizzard shad					X		X				X		X		X	
Golden shiner	X				X		X				X		X	X	X	X
Green sunfish	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Johnny darter	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
Largemouth bass	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
Logperch	X	X	X	X	X			X		X			X		X	
Longear sunfish	X	X	X		X			X	X	X						
Longnose gar	X															
Mosquitofish	X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X	X	X	X
Orangespotted sunfish	X	X	X		X		X	X		X			X		X	
Orangethroat darter	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Redear Sunfish										X						
Red shiner	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	
Redfin shiner	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	
River carpsucker	X			X	X											
Rosyface shiner	X	X	X	X	X			X		X						
Sand shiner	X		X	X	X	X	X			X			X			
Shorthead redhorse	X				X			X								
Shortnose gar													X			
Slender madtom	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X			X			
Smallmouth buffalo													X			
Southern redbelly dace			X	X	X		X									
Spotted bass	X	X	X	X	X		X	X		X					X	
Stonecat	X		X	X	X			X	X	X			X			

Common Names	Wildcat Cr.	Silver Cr.	Sevenmile Cr.	Fourmile Cr.	Threemile Cr.	Onemile Cr.	Forsyth Cr.	Little Arkansas Cr.	Honey Cr.	Wind Cr.	Dry Cr.	Drybranch Cr.	Madison Cr.	Farnum Cr.	Timber Cr.	Rush Cr.
Suckermouth minnow	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x		x	
Topeka shiner	x	x	x					x	x	x						
Walleye													x		x	
White crappie	x				x								x	x	x	
White sucker	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x			x		x	x
Wiper					x											
Yellow bullhead	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		x	x		x	x	x	

Appendix I, Table 7. List of fish species that have been documented in each stream on Fort Riley.

Appendix I, Table 8. Species list of fishes in Ft. Riley's 29 fishing ponds and lakes.

Common Name	Pond Names																												
	Avery	Beck	Blue	Bravo	Breakneck Lake	Cameron Springs	Cambell	Chestnut	Dale	Earnum	Funston Lake	Gaches	Goens	Halasz	LeGrange	Marshall Lake	Miller	Moon Lake	CACTF (aka)	Pritchard	Rich	Rohlyer	Rush	Seven-mile	Sinn	Stone	Stortz	Vinton	Williams
Bigmouth buffalo											x																		
Black bullhead											x																		
Black crappie											x																		
Bluegill		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x		x			x	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	
Channel catfish		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x			x	x		x	x		x	x		x	x	x
Common carp											x								x										
Fathead minnow	x		x									x			x		x		x	x	x	x			x	x		x	x
Flathead catfish		x			x	x					x								x										
Freshwater drum											x																		
Gizzard shad					x						x								x										
Golden shiner		x	x			x	x		x						x							x		x	x		x	x	x
Grass carp		x			x	x																							
Green sunfish		x	x	x	x	x	x		x		x		x	x				x			x	x		x	x		x	x	x
Hybrid bluegill																													
Largemouth bass		x			x	x					x				x			x		x	x					x	x	x	
Longnose gar											x																		
Mosquitofish					x						x																		
Rainbow trout							x																						
Redear sunfish					x										x														
River carpsucker											x																		
Shortnose gar											x																		
Smallmouth buffalo											x																		
Walleye																													
White crappie					x	x		x			x								x										
Wiper																													

Appendix I Table 9. Mussel species documented from Ft. Riley's streams, rivers and lakes.

Species:	Live	Recent	Weathered
<i>Amblema plicata</i> - threeridge	-	-	X
<i>Fusconaia flava</i> - Wabash pigtoe	-	-	X
<i>Lampsilis cardium</i> - plain pocketbook	-	-	X
<i>Lampsilis teres</i> - yellow sandshell	-	-	X
<i>Lasmigona complanata</i> - white heelsplitter	X	X	X
<i>Ligumia recta</i> - black sandshell	-	-	X
<i>Ligumia subrostrata</i> - pondmussel	X	X	X
<i>Obovaria olivaria</i> - hickorynut	-	-	X
<i>Fingernail clam</i>			X
<i>Fragile papershell</i>	X		
<i>Potamilus alatus</i> - pink heelsplitter	-	-	X
<i>Potamilus ohioensis</i> - pink papershell	X	X	X
<i>Pyganodon grandis</i> - giant floater	X	X	X
<i>Quadrula quadrula</i> - mapleleaf	X	X	X
<i>Quadrula pustulosa</i> - pimpleback	-	-	X
<i>Toxolasma parvus</i> - lilliput	-	-	X
<i>Unio merus tetralasmus</i> - pondhorn	X	X	X
<i>Tritogonia verrucosa</i> – pistol-grip			X
<i>Strophitus undulatus</i> – creeper			X

Appendix I, Table 10. Complete list of rare species of Fort Riley, the species' Federal, Kansas and Army status, and current Fort Riley status.

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Insects	American burying beetle, <i>Nicrophorus americanus</i>	E	E	**	Historic range
	Prairie mole cricket, <i>Gryllotalpa major</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
	Monarch, <i>Danaus plexippus</i>	Petition ed	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Regal fritillary, <i>Speyeria idalia</i>	Status review	**	SAR	Present all year
Mussels	Pondhorn, <i>Unio merus tetralasmus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
Fish	Blue sucker, <i>Cycleptus elongatus</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
	Common shiner, <i>Luxilus cornutus</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
	Johnny Darter, <i>Etheostoma nigrum</i>	**	SINC	**	Present all year
	Orangethroat darter, <i>Etheostoma spectabile</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Plains minnow, <i>Hybognathus placitus</i>	**	T, SGCN	**	Transient
	Shoal chub, <i>Macrhybopsis hyostoma</i>	**	T, SGCN	**	Historic range
	Shovelnose sturgeon, <i>Scaphirhynchus platyrhynchus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Silver chub, <i>Macrhybopsis storeriana</i>	**	E	**	Historic range
	Slender madtom, <i>Noturus exilis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Southern redbelly dace, <i>Phoxinus erythrogaster</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
	Stonecat, <i>Noturus flavus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Sturgeon chub, <i>Macrhybopsis gelida</i>	**	T, SGCN	**	25 years since found
	Topeka shiner, <i>Notropis topeka</i>	E	T, SGCN	**	Present all year
	White sucker, <i>Catostomus commersonii</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
Reptiles	Massasauga, <i>Sistrurus catenatus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Historic range
	Texas horned lizard, <i>Phrynosoma cornutum</i>	**	SGCN	SAR	Present all year

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Reptiles cont'd	Timber rattlesnake, <i>Crotalus horridus</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
	Eastern hog-nosed snake, <i>Heterodon platirhinos</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Historic range
	Plains hog-nosed snake, <i>Heterodon nasicus</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Present all year
Turtles	Smooth softshell, <i>Apalone mutica</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
Birds	Acadian flycatcher, <i>Empidonax vireescens</i>	BCC	**	**	Summer resident
	American Avocet, <i>Recurvirostra americana</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	American bittern, <i>Botaurus lentiginosis</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Migrant
	American golden plover, <i>Pluvialis dominica</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	American Tree Sparrow, <i>Spizella arborea</i>	**	SGCN	**	Winter resident
	American white pelican, <i>Pelecanus erythrorhynchos</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Baird's Sandpiper, <i>Calidris bairdii</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Bald eagle, <i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	EA	SGCN	**	Winter resident, nesting
	Baltimore oriole, <i>Icterus galbula</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Bell's vireo, <i>Vireo bellii</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Bewick's wren, <i>Thryomanes beweckii</i>	BCC	**	**	Migrant
	Black-bellied plover, <i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Black-billed cuckoo, <i>Coccyzus erythrophthalmus</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Black-crowned night-heron, <i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	BCC	**	**	Migrant
	Black rail, <i>Laterallus jamaicensis</i>	BCC	SINC, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Black tern, <i>Chlidonias niger</i>	BCC	SINC, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Bobolink, <i>Dolichonyx oryzivorus</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Buff-breasted sandpiper, <i>Tryngites subruficollis</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Bullock's oriole, <i>Icterus bullockii</i>	**	SGCN	**	Vagrant

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Birds, cont'd	Burrowing owl, <i>Athene cunicularia</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Canvasback, <i>Aythya valisineria</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Cerulean warbler, <i>Dendroica cerulea</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Migrant, not documented
	Chuck-will's-widow, <i>Antrostomus carolinensis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Common nighthawk, <i>Chordeiles minor</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Common poorwill, <i>Phalaenoptilus nuttalli</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Dickcissel, <i>Spiza americana</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Eared grebe, <i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Eastern kingbird, <i>Tyrannus tyrannus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Eastern meadowlark, <i>Sturnella magna</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Eastern whip-poor-will, <i>Antrostomus vociferus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Eastern wood-pewee, <i>Contopus virens</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Eskimo curlew, <i>Numenius borealis</i>	E	**	**	Historic range
	Ferruginous hawk, <i>Buteo regalis</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Field sparrow, <i>Spizella pusilla</i>	BCC	**	**	Summer resident
	Forster's tern, <i>Sterna forsteri</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Golden eagle, <i>Aquila chrysaetos</i>	EA	SINC, SGCN	**	Transient
	Grasshopper sparrow, <i>Ammodramus savannarum</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Greater prairie-chicken, <i>Tympanuchus cupido</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Greater yellowlegs, <i>Tringa melanoleuca</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
Harris' sparrow, <i>Zonotrichia querula</i>	**	SGCN	**	Winter resident	
Henslow's sparrow, <i>Ammodramus henslowii</i>	BCC	SINC, SGCN	SAR	Summer resident	

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Birds cont'd	Hudsonian godwit, <i>Limosa haemastica</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Kentucky warbler, <i>Oporornis formosus</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Lark bunting, <i>Calamospiza melanocorys</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Lark sparrow, <i>Chondestes grammacus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Least sandpiper, <i>Calidris minutilla</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Least tern, <i>Sterna antillarum</i>	E	E, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Lesser yellowlegs, <i>Tringa flavipes</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Loggerhead shrike, <i>Lanius ludovicianus</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Long-billed curlew, <i>Numenius americanus</i>	**	SINC	**	Transient, not documented
	Long-billed dowitcher, <i>Limnodromus scolopaceus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Marbled godwit, <i>Limosa fedoa</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Mississippi kite, <i>Ictinia mississippiensis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Northern bobwhite, <i>Colinus virginianus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Present all year
	Northern flicker, <i>Colaptes auratus</i>	BCC	**	**	Present all year
	Northern pintail, <i>Anas acuta</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Painted bunting, <i>Passerina ciris</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Pectoral sandpiper, <i>Calidris melanotos</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Peregrine falcon, <i>Falco peregrinus</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Pied-billed grebe, <i>Podilymbus podiceps</i>	BCC	**	**	Migrant
	Piping plover, <i>Charadrius melodus</i>	T	T, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Prothonotary warbler, <i>Protontaria citrea</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Red-headed woodpecker, <i>Melanerpes erythrocephalus</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Rufa red knot, <i>Calidris canutus rufa</i>	T	**	**	Transient, not documented

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Birds cont'd	Rusty blackbird, <i>Euphagus carolinus</i>	BCC	SGCN	SAR	Winter resident
	Scissor-tailed flycatcher, <i>Tyrannus forficatus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Semipalmated sandpiper, <i>Calidris pusilla</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Short-eared owl, <i>Asio flammeus</i>	BCC	SINC, SGCN	**	Winter resident
	Snowy plover, <i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	**	T, SGCN	**	Migrant
	Solitary sandpiper, <i>Tringa solitaria</i>	BCC	**	**	Migrant
	Spotted towhee, <i>Pipilo maculatus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Winter resident
	Sprague's pipit, <i>Anthus spragueii</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Stilt sandpiper, <i>Calidris himantopus</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Swainson's hawk, <i>Buteo swainsoni</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Upland sandpiper, <i>Bartramia longicauda</i>	BCC	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	Western kingbird, <i>Tyrannus verticalis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Summer resident
	White-rumped sandpiper, <i>Calidris fuscicollis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Whooping crane, <i>Grus americana</i>	E	E	**	Transient, not documented
	Wilson's phalarope, <i>Phalaropus tricolor</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
	Wood thrush, <i>Hyocichla mustelina</i>	BCC	**	**	Summer resident
	Yellow rail, <i>Coturnicops moveborancensis</i>	**	SGCN	**	Migrant
Yellow-throated warbler, <i>Dendroica dominca</i>	BCC	SINC	**	Migrant, not documented	
Mammals	Eastern spotted skunk, <i>Spilogale putorius</i>	**	T	**	Historic range, Pitts*
	Franklin's ground squirrel, <i>Spermophilus franklinii</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Historic range
	Northern long-eared bat, <i>Myotis septentrionalis</i>	T	T	**	Historic range
	Southern bog lemming, <i>Synaptomys cooperi</i>	**	SINC, SGCN	**	Resident year round

	SPECIES	Federal	State	Army	Fort Riley Status
Plants	Western prairie fringed orchid, <i>Platanthera praeclara</i>	T	**	**	Historic range
<p>E = Endangered, In danger of extinction throughout all or most of its range. T = Threatened, Likely to become endangered within the foreseeable future. SINC = Species in Need of Conservation. SGCN = Kansas designated as Species of Greatest Conservation Need SAR = Army Species At Risk designation BCC = Birds of Conservation Concern, 2008 list EA = Protected under Eagle Act</p> <p>* It is unclear whether the author actually observed this species, or included it based on a literature review of the range for the species.</p>					

Appendix I, Table 11. Habitat abundance and distribution of rare species occurring on Fort Riley

American burying beetles occur in grass, forest and shrubby habitats that grow in sandy soil. Speculation is that soil type is more important than vegetation for this species. Despite intensive surveys throughout the 1990's, this species has not been documented from the installation.

Prairie mole crickets are restricted to native tallgrass prairie and most generally occur in areas that have not been plowed. This species has been found at sites in Training Areas 10, 52, 58, 75 and 79. Its distribution on the installation is likely more widespread than what is currently known.

Monarchs are seasonally abundant, and are often in association with milkweed plants. This butterfly may be observed May through October, but is most abundant in September during fall migration and may be observed throughout the installation.

Regal fritillaries are endemic to high quality tallgrass prairie sites, and are often in association with milkweed plants. This butterfly is active June through August and is abundant in appropriate habitat throughout the installation.

Pondhorns were located in Sevenmile and Timber creeks during surveys conducted in 1998. This was the fourth most abundant mussel on the installation. Surveys have not been repeated.

Blue suckers occur in swift currents in the main channels of the Kansas River. It has been found during surveys conducted in 1996 and 1997 (Quist unpubl data).

Common shiners occur in small to mid-sized streams with clear water, gravel bottoms, a moderate to swift current, that are within the Kansas River system. It is common in Wildcat, Silver, Sevenmile, Fourmile, Threemile, Forsyth, Little Arkansas, Honey, Farnum, Madison and Wind creeks.

Johnny darters are found in shallow pools with little current, or riffles near the pools, typically in small, spring-fed tributaries of the Kansas River. However, on Fort Riley they have been found in the mainstems of the Kansas and Republican rivers, in Timber, Madison, Rush and Farnum creeks, all of which drain into Milford Lake, as well as in Honey, Threemile, Wind and Fourmile creeks.

Orangethroat darters are found in shallow riffles having bottoms of fine gravel or mixed gravel and sand. On Fort Riley they have been found in all mainstem streams as well as the Kansas and Republican rivers.

Plain's minnows occur in large streams that have broad beds of sand and shallow, braided flow. It is most common in shallow backwaters, gentle eddies, and along the edges of "sand waves" (Cross and Collins 1995). It has been found rarely in the Kansas River.

Shoal chubs live in shallow riffles of large, sandy streams, in the Republican, Missouri and Kansas rivers' watersheds. Previously classified as a subspecies of the speckled chub, the shoal chub has not been collected from Fort Riley.

Shovelnose sturgeons live in rivers with swift currents and broad, sandy bottoms. It has been collected from the Kansas River on Fort Riley.

Silver chubs live in large, sandy rivers, common only in the Missouri and Kansas rivers in Kansas. Documented occurrence exists from the Republican River above Milford Lake (17 July 1984, Kansas Biological Survey Collection). The silver chub is likely extirpated from the Fort Riley area.

Slender madtoms occur in riffles of small, permanent streams with clear, cool water and rocky bottoms. This species is occasional in streams that drain directly into the Kansas and Republican rivers.

Southern redbelly dace occur in small, clear streams, often near the sources of streams. This species is occasional to common in Sevenmile, Fourmile, Threemile and Forsyth creeks.

Stonecats occur in riffles of permanent streams with clear, cool water and rocky bottoms. This species is occasional in streams that drain directly into the Kansas and Republican rivers.

Sturgeon chubs historically occurred in shallow, turbulent areas of the Kansas and Smoky Hill Rivers. Three sturgeon chubs were collected south of Fort Riley in 1964; none have been located in the Fort Riley vicinity since (USFWS 1993).

Topeka shiner pools are near the headwaters of prairie streams that have stable water levels, clear water, and gravel bottoms. Topeka shiners have been found in Little Arkansas, Wind, Wildcat, Honey, Silver and Sevenmile creeks. They are rare in all but Wildcat Creek, in which they annually vary from rare to common.

White suckers occur in small streams that have some area of rocky bottom. This species is occasional in most Fort Riley streams.

Massasaugas occur in a variety of habitats, from rocky, prairie hillsides to open wetlands, and are most abundant in wet grasslands. One unconfirmed report of this species exists for Fort Riley, from Maneuver Area J in 2005. However, the snake was not captured, no picture was taken to confirm the identification, and the individual was uncertain of the identification.

Texas horned lizards occur on dry, flat areas with sandy, loamy, or rocky surfaces and sparse vegetation. Numerous sightings of horned lizards have occurred in Training Units Training Areas 14, 15, 17, 22, 23, 33, 35, 46 and 92.

Timber rattlesnakes occur along heavily vegetated, rocky outcrops on partially forested hills. In 2010, an amateur herpetologist provided a photo of a timber rattlesnake reportedly from a rocky outcrop in Training Area 33. Subsequent surveys of this area have not relocated another rattlesnake.

Eastern hog-nosed snakes occur in a variety of habitats, from eastern forests to open prairies in western Kansas, and are most abundant in sandy areas. While documented specimens occur from Riley and Geary counties, none of this specie has been located on Fort Riley.

Plains hog-nosed snakes occur in sand prairie habitat. This habitat occurs in sandy grasslands along the Kansas and Republican Rivers. Two individuals were discovered in 1993 surveys (Busby et al. 1994).

Smooth softshell turtles are semi-aquatic organisms rarely found far from water. It is commonly found in the Smoky Hill, Republican and Kansas rivers.

Acadian flycatchers are uncommon migrants and rare summer residents, and have only been documented from mature, riverine, floodplain forests. The species' relative breeding abundance ranking is low (RTLA-94th most abundant, BBS-not located).

American avocets are common transients, generally preferring larger wetland complexes than what is found on Fort Riley. Most Fort Riley observations have occurred in association with Milford Lake.

American bitterns are uncommon transients rarely observed on Fort Riley. Generally found in marshes, on Fort Riley observations have occurred in small fishing ponds ringed lightly by cattails.

American golden-plovers are primarily spring migrants, typically occurring in recently burned grasslands. They have been rare on Fort Riley, only documented in 2006 on burned grassland in the Douthit Gunnery Complex.

American tree sparrows are common to abundant winter residents. This species is found in all habitats throughout the installation, and is frequently attracted to backyard feeding stations.

American white pelicans are common migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found loafing on Milford Lake or casually soaring, this species has been observed along the Kansas River as well.

Baird's sandpipers are occasional migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found on open sandbars, observations have occurred along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, and ponds with low water and unvegetated shoreline.

Bald eagles are common winter residents and uncommon summer residents that use mature trees and snags along the Republican, Smoky Hill and Kansas rivers, and the shoreline of Milford Lake. Eagle nests occur along the Madison and Farnum Cove areas of Milford Lake, near the confluence of the Kansas River, and in Training Area 54, approximately 3.5 miles from Milford Lake.

Baltimore orioles are summer residents commonly observed on Fort Riley in woodland, residential and park-like habitats. The species' relative breeding abundance ranking is moderate (RTLA-25th most abundant, BBS-36th most abundant).

Bell's vireos are common summer residents breeding in riparian thickets and short, shrubby patches that are situated within larger grasslands. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is high (RTLA-13th most abundant, BBS-11th most abundant).

Bewick's wrens are uncommon migrants and uncommon summer residents, usually found in woodlands of various sizes. The species relative breeding abundance is moderately low (RTLA-75th most abundant, BBS-91st most abundant).

Black-bellied plovers are uncommon transients that have been observed on Milford Lake mudflats when the lake has been drawn down. Observations have been of single birds during fall migration.

Black-billed cuckoos are uncommon but regular summer residents, in woodlands and woodland edges. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderate to moderately low (RTLA-67th most abundant, BBS-52nd most abundant).

Black-crowned night-herons are uncommon migrants, occurring in shallow water wetlands by night and rookeries by day. Trees along Threemile Creek near the Threemile wetland have been used by black-crowned night-herons.

Black rails are secretive creatures usually found in wet meadows or meadows near marshes. Black rails have been documented during fall migration in grassland and food plot areas located in Maneuver Areas A, B, D, E, H and K. Their exact distribution and abundance are unclear.

Black terns are occasional spring migrants, numbering in the hundreds in some years. This species migrates above grassland and wetland habitats, and has been observed above Milford Lake and the Threemile wetland.

Bobolinks are rare transients, occurring in dense grasslands and alfalfa fields. Only one documented sighting of this species exists, from an unburned grassland in Maneuver Area O.

Buff-breasted sandpipers are rare migrants, generally occurring in dry uplands during migration. They have been rare on Fort Riley, only documented in 2006 on burned grassland in the MPRC training land.

Bullock's orioles are western vagrants rarely observed on Fort Riley. Generally, this species favors habitats frequented by Baltimore orioles.

Burrowing owls are typically found in short grass habitats, often associated with prairie dogs. Little habitat for this species is present. Two confirmed sightings of this species exist, in Maneuver Area B and the Douthit Gunnery Complex.

Canvasbacks are uncommon migrants regularly observed during winter and early spring on Fort Riley on Milford Lake and the Custer Hill Sedimentation Ponds.

Cerulean warblers are rare migrants, not documented on Fort Riley, but could potentially occur in mature, riverine, floodplain forests. Sighting records exist from Riley (Manhattan) and Clay (Wakefield Arboretum) counties.

Chuck-will-widows are summer residents, presumably occurring in woodlands across the installation. Due to its nocturnal vocalizations, current bird surveys are inadequate to capture meaningful data for this species.

Common nighthawks are summer residents, observed flying over grasslands and urban areas. Being more active during daylight than other nightjars, current surveys do encounter this species; its relative breeding abundance is moderate (RTLA-42nd most abundant, BBS-50th most abundant).

Common poorwills seem to be an uncommon summer resident. Documented sightings have been in grassland habitats near the tops of hills, in Training Area 17 and Maneuver Area I. Due to its nocturnal vocalizations, current bird surveys are inadequate to capture meaningful data for this species.

Dickcissels are abundant summer residents, nesting in virtually every type of grassland that occurs on the installation. This is one of the most common breeding birds on the installation, with its relative breeding abundance high (RTLA-1st most abundant, BBS-1st most abundant).

Eared grebes are uncommon migrants regularly observed during migration on Fort Riley, most often on Milford Lake and the Custer Hill Sedimentation Ponds.

Eastern kingbirds are common summer residents, breeding in grassland habitats, although they are also found in woodlands during migration. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately high (RTLA-9th most abundant, BBS-24th most abundant).

Eastern meadowlarks are common summer and winter residents, occurring in open grasslands of all types and sizes. This is one of the most common breeding birds on the installation, with its relative breeding abundance high (RTLA-3rd most abundant, BBS-3rd most abundant).

Eastern whip-poor-wills typically occur in woodland habitats from April to October. Fort Riley occurs at the extreme western portion of their range. Although occasionally encountered, actual abundance on the installation is unknown as current bird surveys are inadequate to capture meaningful data for this species due to the species nocturnal habits.

Eastern wood-pewees are common summer residents in woodland habitats, more frequently encountered in larger blocks of forest. This is a fairly common breeding bird on the installation, with its relative breeding abundance moderately high (RTLA-24th most abundant, BBS-26th most abundant).

Ferruginous hawks may rarely occur as transients during the winter months, occurring in open grassland habitats. Only one confirmed sighting of this species exists.

Field sparrows are common summer residents that occur in grasslands with shrubs and thickets, and on the edge between grasslands and riparian woodlands. It occurs throughout the training areas. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is high (RTLA-8th most abundant, BBS-4th most abundant).

Forster's terns are regular migrants during spring and fall, observed above large marshes, rivers and impoundments. It is regularly observed foraging in and above the Republican River and Milford Lake.

Golden eagles are rare transients and winter visitors, and occur most regularly over open grasslands in western states. Confirmed sighting of this species exists in Training Areas 49, 60 and 64.

Grasshopper sparrows are abundant summer residents, nesting in virtually every grassland with little or no shrubby vegetation, especially shorter grass areas. This is one of the most common breeding birds on the installation, with its relative breeding abundance high (RTLA-4th most abundant, BBS-12th most abundant).

Greater prairie-chickens are common year-round residents, occurring regularly in the larger grassland fields that occur in Maneuver Areas A, D, E, H, K, L, and O, the MPRC box and the Impact Area. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately low (RTLA-59th most abundant, BBS-64th most abundant).

Greater yellowlegs are common migrants observed on Fort Riley, they are generally found in shallow water wetlands wherever those occur, as open sandbars along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, shallow ponds and ephemeral wetlands.

Harris' sparrows are common to abundant winter residents. This species is found in all habitats that provide a shrubby component throughout the installation, and may be attracted to backyard feeding stations.

Henslow's sparrows breed in large, grassland tracts (> 30 ha) that have not been burned or hayed for 2-5 years. This bird is more common in some years than others. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderate (RTLA-28th most abundant, BBS-51st most abundant).

Hudsonian godwits are uncommon migrants rarely observed on Fort Riley. Generally found in marsh and wetland areas, this species has also been observed in burned, upland prairie.

Kentucky warblers are occasional summer residents, occurring in the understory vegetation of mature woodlands. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately low (RTLA-53rd most abundant, BBS-62nd most abundant).

Lark buntings are western vagrants rarely observed on Fort Riley during migration. Generally, this species favors shortgrass and open fields for feeding and loafing.

Lark sparrows are common summer residents that typically occur in ecotones between grassland or shrub and forested habitat types. The species relative breeding abundance ranking on Fort Riley is moderate (RTLA-51st most abundant, BBS-31st most abundant).

Least sandpipers are common migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found on open sandbars, observations have occurred along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, and ponds with low water and unvegetated shoreline.

Least terns use unvegetated sandbars and islands in wide, riverine channels. Other unvegetated, exposed shorelines also may be used. Least terns were frequently observed along the Kansas River following the 1993 Kansas River flood, and along the shoreline of Milford Lake. None have been reported since 2002.

Lesser yellowlegs are occasional migrants observed on Fort Riley, they are generally found in shallow water wetlands wherever those occur, as open sandbars along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, shallow ponds and ephemeral wetlands.

Loggerhead shrikes regularly occur in low numbers throughout the year, with peak sightings typically occurring in spring. Shrikes inhabit grasslands that are interspersed with scattered, woody vegetation. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is low (RTLA-85th most abundant, BBS-89th most abundant).

Long-billed curlews are rare migrants through the area, breeding in high plains rangeland and wintering on coastal mudflats. While sighting records exist for Clay, Geary and Riley counties, no documented sightings are known from Fort Riley.

Long-billed dowitchers are common migrants through the area, foraging primarily on exposed mudflats. This habitat is often scarce on Fort Riley, so they are only occasionally seen. Most sightings of this species have occurred along the shoreline of Milford Lake.

Marbled godwits are uncommon migrants rarely observed on Fort Riley. Generally found in mudflats, documented sightings from Fort Riley occurred on Milford Lake mudflats and a stormwater retention basin in Camp Forsyth.

Mississippi kites' populations are expanding in eastern Kansas, nesting in urban and wild areas, with the only seemingly requirement being the presence of mature trees for the nest. Small grouping of kites are becoming more frequently observed, with one nest documented on the installation. Increasing numbers of this species on the installation is anticipated.

Northern bobwhites are common, year-round residents that typically occur in ecotones between grassland, shrub and forested habitat types. The species relative breeding abundance ranking on Fort Riley is high (RTLA-15th most abundant, BBS-6th most abundant).

Northern flickers are present on Fort Riley throughout the year. Most of the breeding birds probably move southward in the winter; the wintering birds are northern and western individuals. This species occurs across the installation, needing only isolated trees or poles for breeding. The

species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderate (RTLA-39th most abundant, BBS-43rd most abundant).

Northern pintails are common migrants irregularly observed on Fort Riley due to lack of large, emergent wetlands. Areas on Fort Riley more prone to view this species are Milford Lake, and Madison Creek and Foxtrot wetlands.

Painted buntings are a rare summer resident, typically occurring in woodland edge habitats or where extensive cedar encroachment is occurring into grassland. This species has not yet been detected during spring breeding bird surveys, but one breeding pair is documented.

Pectoral sandpipers are regular migrants through the area, frequenting the grassy edges of marshes, flooded fields and exposed mudflats. This species has been observed on mudflat habitat created at Milford Lake during a late summer drawdown.

Peregrine falcons are spring and fall migrants and can occur as occasional winter transients. These falcons most often are observed in wetland environments. The species is rare, with a confirmed sighting being received approximately once every 2-3 years.

Pied-billed grebes are common transients during spring and fall, observed on impoundments. It is regularly observed swimming on installation ponds and Milford Lake.

Piping plovers use unvegetated sandbars and islands that provide good visibility in wide, riverine channels. Other unvegetated, exposed shorelines also may be used. Piping plovers were observed along the Republican and Kansas Rivers in 1996, but have not been seen since then.

Prothonotary warblers are uncommon migrants and rare summer residents, and have only been documented from mature, riverine, floodplain forests. At least one breeding pair is documented.

Red-headed woodpeckers are common summer residents and, in years with abundant oak mast, may overwinter. This species may occur throughout the installation, needing only isolated trees or poles for breeding. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately low (RTLA-55th most abundant, BBS-47th most abundant).

Rufa red knots are unlikely migrants through the area, nesting on the Canadian Arctic and wintering along coasts of the Gulf of Mexico, Caribbean, and South America. Generally, the birds make very brief stops, foraging on exposed mudflats. This species has been observed at Tuttle Creek Reservoir; no other local sightings are known.

Rusty blackbirds are uncommon transients and local winter residents, observed in woodlands and wooded thickets along streams and rivers. They have been documented in Training Area 20 and Maneuver Area F.

Scissor-tailed flycatchers are occasional summer residents, occurring in open habitats with scattered trees. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately low (RTLA-61st most abundant, BBS-57th most abundant).

Semipalmated sandpipers are occasional migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found on open sandbars, observations have occurred along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, and ponds with low water and unvegetated shoreline.

Short-eared owls are regular winter residents, occurring in low numbers on the installation in the large tallgrass prairie tracts of Maneuver Areas A, D, H, K, O and the MPRC box. In one year a pair of owls was observed well into the spring months, but a breeding attempt was never confirmed.

Snowy plovers use unvegetated sandbars and islands that provide good visibility in wide, riverine channels. Other unvegetated, exposed shorelines also may be used. A snowy plover was observed along the Kansas River in 1996.

Solitary sandpipers are uncommon migrants through the area, foraging primarily on exposed mudflats. This species has been observed along the unvegetated shoreline of Milford Lake, along sandbars and mudflats of the Kansas and Republican rivers, and in vernal pools in upland locations.

Spotted towhees are occasional winter residents, occurring in woodland and woodland edge habitats.

Sprague's pipits may be more common than what is observed during migration, but remain obscure due to the species's tendency to not vocalize or sit on perches during migration. Occurring in open grasslands, there is only one documented sighting of this bird.

Stilt sandpipers are uncommon migrants through the area, foraging primarily on exposed mudflats. This species has been observed along the shoreline of Milford Lake and along unvegetated sandbars and mudflats of the Kansas and Republican rivers.

Swainson's hawks are common migrants, usually observed flying over large open fields that are being burned, or recently burned, and have also been observed following tractors that are disking food plots.

Upland sandpipers are common summer residents, breeding in grassland tracts larger than 40 acres in size. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderately common (RTLA-19th most abundant, BBS-21st most abundant).

Western kingbirds are common summer residents, occurring in open habitats with scattered trees as well as in urban settings. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is moderate (RTLA-50th most abundant, BBS-53rd most abundant).

White-rumped sandpipers are occasional migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found on open sandbars, observations have occurred along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, and ponds with low water and unvegetated shoreline.

Whooping cranes are migrants through Kansas. Selected stopover sites generally are wetlands 1 ha or larger in size that provide shallow water and good visibility. Whooping cranes have not been documented on FRK, although they have been along other stretches of the Kansas River.

Wilson's phalaropes are occasional migrants observed on Fort Riley. Generally found on open sandbars, observations have occurred along the Kansas and Republican rivers, Milford Lake shoreline, and ponds with low water and unvegetated shoreline.

Wood thrushes are uncommon summer residents, often heard singing in the larger tracts of floodplain and riparian woodlands. The species relative breeding abundance ranking is low (RTLA-66th most abundant, BBS-72nd most abundant).

Yellow rails are rare on Fort Riley, occurring around the edges of heavily-vegetated wetlands. One sighting is documented from the installation.

Yellow-throated warblers are rare migrants, not documented on Fort Riley, but could potentially occur in mature, riverine, floodplain forests. Sighting records exist from Riley and Geary counties.

Eastern spotted skunks use natural and manmade structures such as fences, embankments, hedgerows, brush piles, abandoned buildings, and woody stream corridors. Pitts et al. (1987) reported sightings of this species. However, none have been documented on the installation since that publication.

Franklin's ground squirrels are associated with the zone where tallgrass prairie and deciduous forest come into contact. While documented specimens occur from Riley County, none of this specie has been located on Fort Riley.

Northern long-eared bats are associated with deciduous forest and has an assumed range that includes Fort Riley. No documented specimens occur from Clay, Geary or Riley counties.

Southern bog lemmings are colonial and inhabit communities of thick matted ground cover with high overhead vegetation in both forests and grasslands. This species has been occasionally captured during small mammal trapping performed on the installation.

Western prairie-fringed orchid occurs in wet areas of native, tallgrass prairies. It has not been documented on Fort Riley, but there is an historic record within the Wildcat Creek watershed north of the installation.

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APPENDIX J

Distribution and Abundance of Wildlife on Fort Riley

1.0 UPLAND GAME

Northern Bobwhite

Northern bobwhite occur throughout the installation but are most plentiful in extensive edge habitat and mosaic vegetation communities. Their preferred habitat is a mixture of grassland, shrubland, woodland, and cropland (or ground dominated by annual plants) interspersed to provide abundant edge. Of those four vegetation types, the first three are present in adequate quantities along the installation's stream courses. Cropland areas are, however, limited and restricted to those firebreak areas leased for crop production (less than 1,600 acres) and wildlife food plots (approximately 800 acres).

Northern bobwhite populations fluctuate annually and are susceptible to adverse weather. Spring auditory counts and other empirical evidence have suggested that bobwhite populations were generally stable from 1995-2017. However, overall abundance has not reached numbers observed between 1987-1993.

Ring-necked pheasant

Fort Riley supports a modest population of ring-necked pheasants. Annual spring auditory surveys indicate that ring-necked pheasants are most abundant north of Vinton School Road. Their preferred habitat is roughly equal proportions of grassland, cropland, and shrubland with less woodland. Spring surveys suggest that the ring-necked pheasant population varies annually, but has remained steady over time, as the number of birds detected in 2014 is equal to the number of birds detected in 1982.

Fort Riley will probably never support high densities of ring-necked pheasants, especially if biologically appropriate prairie management continues. Prescribed burning and mechanical removal of shrublands have produced more homogeneous grassland by removing the brushy cover that pheasants prefer. Also, haying of grasslands and insufficient cropland area are important factors suppressing the number of ring-necked pheasants and, therefore, available for harvest. Additionally, much of the grassland has been invaded by isolated trees that provide roosting sites for avian predators of pheasants and other game birds.

Greater prairie-chicken

Greater prairie-chickens sustain a viable population because of Fort Riley's extensive grasslands. Spring lek surveys indicate that the greatest densities of greater prairie-chickens are in the central area on the largest expanse of high quality grassland. This grassland, relatively free of riparian timber along its creeks, is in the Danger Fan of the Douthit Gunnery Complex (17,000 acres of contiguous native grassland). No leks recently have been found on the installation's east side (Maneuver Areas C, F, and I) or south of Vinton School Road.

Spring lek surveys have been conducted since the mid-1980s. Results indicate that greater prairie-chicken numbers generally increased from 1994-2002, generally decreased from 2003-2012, and increased again from 2013-2015. Overall, results indicate that prairie-chicken populations are remaining stable, as the number of leks and the number of birds on leks in 2015 were stable and higher, respectively, than similar data from 1990.

Spring lek surveys indicate the breeding population's size has been relatively stable, which contrasts to populations in other parts of the Flint Hills. Many parts of the Flint Hills use a popular grazing management system termed Intensive Early Season Grazing, in which landowners annually burn their entire pastures in mid-April, intensely graze cattle on the burned prairie through mid-summer, and then remove the cattle from the grassland to allow it to recover before the onset of winter dormancy. Intensive Early Season Grazing is believed to be detrimental to prairie-chickens. In contrast, Fort Riley range management practices do not manage for livestock, and may be adjusted to favor prairie-chicken production.

Mourning dove

Mourning doves are well distributed because interspersed grassland, "go-back" shrubland, woodland, and weedy, disturbed sites provide excellent spring and summer habitat. Consequently, many doves nest on Fort Riley each year. Most migrate from Fort Riley by late October, but a few individuals do winter at the installation. Mourning doves are found where annual forbs are most abundant, often in disturbed areas.

Cottontail rabbits

Cottontail rabbits inhabit open forests (40–50 percent crown cover), forest edges, brushy areas and uncultivated fields, all of which are abundant and especially common around old building sites and on improved grounds.

Fox Squirrel and Gray Squirrel

Fox squirrels, which are occasionally seen as black-phase individuals, are common in the woodlands, especially in open oak-hickory gallery forests along Wildcat, Timber, and Madison creeks. They are also common throughout the cantonment and improved grounds. Conversely, eastern gray squirrels are rare, as Fort Riley lies on the extreme western edge of their geographical range.

American Woodcock

American woodcock are uncommon fall migrants on Fort Riley and rarely have been found nesting. Kansas is the western most limit of their range and as such are not a high priority management species. They are closely associated with woodland areas, particularly those along the rivers and streams.

2.0 BIG GAME

Of the wildlife found on Fort Riley, those the Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks and Tourism defines as “big game” are white-tailed deer, mule deer, and elk. Fort Riley supports established and huntable populations of white-tailed deer and elk. Few mule deer occur the installation, as

Fort Riley lies along the extreme eastern edge of their distribution range. The most recent recorded harvest of mule deer at Fort Riley was in 1984 when three were taken.

White-tailed Deer

The white-tailed deer in Kansas is a highly adaptable species whose numbers are growing. This species can adapt to many habitats but is most common in forest edges, woodlands, and riparian corridors. On Fort Riley, this species also inhabits mixed shrub and prairie communities as well as prairie/woodland edges.

Fort Riley's deer herd is characterized as productive since most animals have good body condition; males exhibit excellent antler development. Reproductive tract analysis and the fawn-doe ratio of harvested animals indicate that many female fawns of 6-months by early December are bred, and most yearling and adult does give birth to two fawns. Field dressed weights of female and male yearlings average 100 and 115 pounds, respectively. Adult males are occasionally documented exceeding 200 pounds field-dressed.

Competition for deer hunting opportunities has increased dramatically in recent years. That trend is likely to continue as the overall population of Fort Riley and surrounding communities continues to grow. Significant changes in the 2008 Kansas Deer Hunting Regulations greatly increased the number of hunters eligible to hunt on Fort Riley. Thus, adjustments to permit distribution and participation were made in 2008 to preclude a reduction in opportunities for Active Duty Military. Specifically, a three day firearms hunt after Thanksgiving is reserved for DoD ID cardholders. The remaining nine days of firearms deer season is open to the general public. There is no cap on the number of Fort Riley firearms deer hunting permits issued. Fort Riley archery deer hunting permits are unlimited for active duty Soldiers stationed at Fort Riley and Dependents of Soldiers who are newly assigned to Fort Riley and arrive at the installation later than the first day of issuance of archery deer hunting permits to individuals other than Soldiers. The number of archery deer hunters for all others is capped at 200 participants, distributed on a first-come, first-served basis.

A Quality Deer Management Program (QDM) was initiated in 2004 based on hunter survey results that revealed the hunters' desire to increase trophy deer harvest opportunities. The basis of the program of Fort Riley's QDM efforts has been to increase hunter understanding of antler development, harvest selection and effectively aging deer in the field. The results thus far have been impressive, with the mean antler spread increasing from a 12 year average of 14.4 inches to 17.5.inches in 2007.

Elk

Elk (also known as wapiti) are primarily grazing animals that inhabit open prairies and woodlands and woodland edges. They were extirpated from Kansas early during state settlement and were reintroduced to the Fort Riley region in 1986 as a collaborative effort between the installation and the KDWPT. Other Federal agencies, the Kansas State University-Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit, and private, non-profit conservation organizations have supported various aspects associated with the reintroduction.

Initially, twelve elk were reintroduced to Fort Riley in 1986 with five supplemental stockings since then. The total number of elk released on Fort Riley to date is 50. Most came from a captive herd

maintained by the KDWPT near McPherson, Kansas, although a few were trapped from free-ranging herds in Colorado and Montana. The latest stocking was in 1994 when 18 elk were brought from Wind Cave National Park, South Dakota. The purpose of this stocking was not to increase absolute numbers but to increase the genetic diversity of the herd. All elk stocked were certified to be free of disease.

Intermittent aerial surveys of elk were conducted from 1986 until 1997, when systematic, rigorous aerial population surveys began. Surveys indicate that the herd had been increasing at approximately 20% annually. Surveys conducted in February 1998 suggested that the elk population was approximately 152-164 head. However, surveys in August 1998 (after spring calving), estimated the population to be 200-225. Surveys in 1999, 2000 and 2001 indicate that hunting mortality had reduced the herd size substantially.

The antlered to antlerless ratio is estimated to be between 3:1 and 4:1. The 1999 - 2001 surveys determined fewer animals consistently residing on the installation but indicated comparable age and sex ratios. The high bull to cow ratio reflects that the bull harvest is conservative while the cow to calf ratio is approximately 1.6:1.0, which suggests high herd productivity. Aerial surveys completed between 2010 and 2017 have documented between 112 and 232 total elk. The population is considered to be slightly increasing in overall number with an estimated size of 275-300 animals.

3.0 WILD TURKEY

Wild turkeys are another species extirpated during Kansas's early settlement. Fort Riley, in cooperation with the KDWPT, began reintroducing wild turkeys to the installation in 1984. Six (two male, four female) eastern wild turkeys were released along Wildcat Creek in January 1984, with an additional stocking of one male and three female eastern subspecies birds near the original release site in January 1985. At about the same time, the KDWPT released both eastern wild turkeys and Rio Grande wild turkeys in the Timber Creek Drainage on its Milford Lake Public Hunting Area, which lies adjacent to Fort Riley's western boundary. From those and other stockings in the Kansas River drainage, turkeys have spread and are now commonly found throughout the installation.

Wild turkeys prefer oak-hickory gallery forests, but they also like secondary growth woodlands and mixed shrub/woodland habitats. Most wild turkeys on the installation are hybrids of the eastern and Rio Grande subspecies.

4.0 WATERFOWL

Fort Riley's numerous water impoundments provide feeding and loafing areas for waterfowl using the Central Flyway Migration Corridor during their spring and fall migrations. Nineteen species of ducks and five species of geese have been observed on Fort Riley. Ducks observed have been mallard, gadwall, green-winged teal, blue-winged teal, cinnamon teal, northern shoveler, wood duck, American wigeon, northern pintail, common merganser, hooded merganser, red-breasted merganser, bufflehead, ring-necked duck, ruddy duck, lesser scaup, common goldeneye, redhead, and canvasback. Canada, snow, Ross's, cackling and greater white-fronted are the geese that have been observed on Fort Riley. Canada goose, wood duck, mallard, green-winged teal and blue-winged teal have been confirmed nesting on Fort Riley.

5.0 FURBEARERS

Fort Riley's mixture of diverse vegetative communities, impoundments, and streams provides good habitat for several commercially valuable furbearers. Beaver, bobcat, muskrat, raccoon, coyote, red fox, striped skunk and badger are relatively abundant on the installation. Gray fox are less common whereas few mink have been recorded. Long-tailed weasels have been recorded only twice.

The Kansas State University Cooperative Unit conducted research (1996-2000) regarding niche partitioning among mammalian predators on Fort Riley. Data from that study show that Fort Riley has one of the highest densities of bobcats, coyotes, raccoons, and opossums reported in the literature.

Wildcat, Madison, Farnum, Threemile, Rush, and Timber creeks were surveyed for furbearer activity during the summer of 1986 (Robel et al., 1987). Signs of beaver, muskrats, and raccoons were abundant along Madison Creek and the northern portions of Wildcat Creek. Relatively few signs were seen along Rush and Timber creeks. The other streams surveyed had moderate signs along their banks. No detailed population data is available for other furbearers; however, coyotes and striped skunks were considered abundant.

Furbearer populations are underutilized as a recreational resource on Fort Riley. Typically fewer than ten coyotes and raccoons are reported harvested per year. Little effort is, therefore, expended directly to manage their populations except to control nuisance individuals. Nuisance individuals are routinely trapped and euthanized.

6.0 RARE SPECIES – SEE APPENDIX I

7.0 LITERATURE CITED

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APPENDIX K

Surveys Performed on Fort Riley.

1.0 HISTORY OF FLORA AND FAUNA MONITORING AND SURVEYS

Various surveys have been conducted through the years. Conservation Branch, Directorate of Public Works, primarily conduct these surveys, but DPTMS personnel through the RTLA portion of the ITAM program have conducted long-term flora and fauna surveys. Conservation Branch has on file data collected since the early 1980's regarding various populations of wildlife.

Surveying and collecting of harvest information require substantial effort. Until recently, inadequate staffing has been a problem. Beginning in the mid-1990s, added staff began conducting expanded surveys. In particular, surveys of non-game fish populations, threatened and endangered species, and non-game wildlife were greatly expanded.

2.0 THREATENED AND ENDANGERED SPECIES

Federally- and state-listed species have been inventoried, and Federally-listed species are monitored as part of overall compliance with the Endangered Species Act. Population monitoring objectives for Federally-listed threatened and endangered species are specified in the species' management plans.

Surveys are conducted each year to assess abundance, distribution and habitats used on the installation. This information is used for management as well as compliance, specifically, to assess the effects of the Army's actions and to develop Biological Assessments.

Least Tern/Piping Plover

Surveys to locate least terns and piping plovers on Fort Riley were initiated in 1994 as part of an overall Riverine Bird Survey. Survey sites provide a view of the sandbar and beach habitats on the installation. Approximately 40% of Milford Reservoir's shoreline on Fort Riley is surveyed, and more than 76% of riverine sandbar habitat is surveyed. This includes more than 90% of sandbar habitat along the Republican River and approximately 60% of habitat along the Kansas River. Surveys are performed between early April and mid-May, and mid-July and mid-September. Other shorebirds or waterbirds of interest, such as black terns, are recorded as well.

Topeka Shiner

The first systematic, extensive surveys for Topeka shiners occurred in 1991. The USFWS used a minnow seine to survey Wildcat, Little Arkansas, Wind, Four Mile, Threemile, Timber and Rush creeks on Fort Riley during that summer. No Topeka shiners were found, although the USFWS reported the presence of apparently suitable habitat in a number of survey areas.

Annual surveys of all Fort Riley streams by Conservation Branch personnel began in 1995. These surveys followed protocol used by the USFWS and KDWP, which consisted of identifying the fish and recording only the species present. Such a sampling design allowed for personnel to

conduct many surveys and to sample all streams on the installation in a timely manner, but did not provide the means to collect detailed population data. Topeka shiners have been located in six streams as a result of these surveys; Wildcat, Little Arkansas, Sevenmile, Honey, Silver and Wind creeks.

Surveys for Topeka shiners are conducted every other year in streams in which this species has been found. Surveys are conducted a minimum of one out of every five years in streams in which Topeka shiners have not been found. The objectives of these surveys are to determine Topeka shiner presence, fish species assemblages, the density of the various species, water flow values and qualitative information of silt loads. Data will be recorded as needed to meet these objectives. Additional data during surveys may be collected if new information indicates such efforts to be warranted.

Northern Long-Eared Bats

Fort Riley has conducted bat surveys since 2011 using the Anabat SD2 bat detector. Bat echolocation calls are recorded by the detector. Several software programs are used to analyze the calls. These programs automatically analyze each call recorded, identify which species the call most closely resembles, and assign a probability that the classification is correct. After this automated process is complete, the program AnalookW can be used to manually view any calls of interest. AnalookW generates a spectrogram of the call, allowing the user to visually compare the call in question to known spectrograms for the species, and therefore determine if the classification was correct. The presence of the northern long-eared bat has not been confirmed on the installation. The Conservation Branch will continue surveys for northern long-eared bats. If the presence of northern long-eared bats is confirmed on Fort Riley, more intensive surveys for this species will be conducted, both to further delineate where this species occurs on the installation, and to better understand when, where and how this species is using Fort Riley habitats. The surveys may include Anabat technology, drift nets, visual inspections of potential roost sites, or other survey technologies that may come available.

Others

Several species have not been observed on the installation but could potentially occur. Thus, the objective of monitoring is simply to record their presence if it occurs. Whooping crane surveys have been conducted by observing possible roosting sites on the Kansas River. The American burying beetle was systematically surveyed by using pitfall traps from 1995 to 1998. These systematic searches were suspended after 1998 after failure to document any of this species. Other species such as the western prairie fringed orchid and white-faced ibis also are searched for incidentally to other fieldwork.

Future searches for species potentially occurring on the installation will be secondary to monitoring efforts for occurring species.

3.0 NON-GAME MAMMALS

Pitts et al. (1987)

Pitts et al. (1987) conducted mammalian surveys and literature reviews while stationed at Fort Riley. Five of the species reported in that study are not known to have been seen since. From that report, it is sometimes difficult to distinguish animals actually documented from animals that the literature suggested should be present.

RTLA surveys

The RTLA procedure recommends inventorying small mammal populations to help determine health of training lands. Various protocols have been used to perform these surveys. Initially, small mammals were monitored using snap traps distributed in a specified pattern paralleling a vegetation transect line. Sixty transects were sampled for two consecutive nights, once during the spring. The first change to this protocol was to substitute Sherman live traps for the snap traps. Other changes have included altering the time of year for trapping, altering the number of times sampling each transect, and changing the number and locations of transects per year. Training land availability, weather, personnel availability, and improving the protocol have all been reasons for the changes.

The emphasis during the last several years had been to find a rigorous and appropriate methodology and have it become the standard. Small mammal trapping is no longer conducted as part of the RTLA program on Fort Riley.

Bats

Bat surveys were conducted annually from 1996 through 2002. Surveys conducted from 1996 to 1998 were performed primarily in the improved grounds and in historic buildings. The Corps of Engineers Waterway Experiment Station conducted a limited bat survey in 1997 as part of their Conservation Assistance Program and initially identified two bat species using mist-nets: the little brown bat and the big brown bat. The single little brown bat collection was later discredited using forearm length and determined to be a juvenile big brown bat. Surveys were expanded in 1999 to include unimproved grounds. Bat surveys are currently not performed.

Survey methods for bats included use of a bat detector, direct observation, and direct capture. Mist nets were used on the outside of bat roosts and where bats were likely to fly. Mist nets were also put up over creeks, at the edge of timber, and along lakes and ponds. A bat detector was used to first determine the presence of bats in an area. Bats were also hand-captured at roost sites. Bat houses are checked for use.

Fort Riley Pest Managers have documented bats in buildings since 1989. To date, all bats except one that have been removed from buildings have been big brown bats; the exception was an eastern red bat, which was captured during the initial construction phase of Fort Riley's new hospital. Overall, 202 buildings have registered bat complaints. Some buildings had a one-time complaint, while in others bats are a recurring conflict. Buildings that have registered bat complaints are shown in Exhibits K.1-3.

Appendix K, Exhibit K.1. Buildings on Custer Hill from which bats have been removed.

Appendix K, Exhibit K.2. Buildings on Main Post from which bats have been removed.

Appendix K, Exhibit K.3. Buildings on Camps Whitside and Funton from which bats have been removed.

4.0 NON-GAME BIRDS

Bald Eagles

Staff intermittently performed aerial surveys for bald eagles from 1982 to 1990. These surveys consisted of a one-time helicopter fly-over of the Republican and Kansas rivers, from Highway 77 to Marshall Army Airfield. All eagles observed were counted and identified as adult or immature. In 1990-1991, the USFWS conducted bi-weekly ground surveys on the Republican and Kansas rivers and on Milford Reservoir from December to mid-March. All eagles observed were counted and identified as whether adult or immature, and weather conditions at the time of survey were recorded.

Conservation Branch personnel began systematic annual surveys in 1993 using the protocol established by the USFWS in previous surveys. A nocturnal roost was discovered as a result of these surveys in 1994. Two sets of surveys are now conducted annually; a Diurnal Habitat Utilization Survey and a Nocturnal Roost Utilization Survey. Each survey is conducted from mid-October to mid-March annually.

Diurnal surveys are performed weekly. The objectives for the diurnal survey are to determine which areas of Fort Riley are most utilized by bald eagles during daylight hours, whether this utilization changes over time, and how eagle numbers fluctuate throughout the winter.

Roost surveys are performed twice a week. The objectives of the nocturnal roost survey are to determine how many eagles roost on Fort Riley, under what weather conditions roosts are most utilized, and for which winter dates eagles roost on the installation. Data have been rigorously collected and statistically analyzed relative to nocturnal use and have contributed greatly to the understanding of the use of Fort Riley for roosting.

Henslow's sparrow surveys

Henslow's sparrows have been systematically monitored since 1994. Data indicate that Fort Riley supports one of the largest breeding populations in the United States. In addition, data derived from this effort directly contributed to the USFWS decision not to list this species.

Surveys for Henslow's sparrows occur only in high-quality habitats. Native tallgrass prairie is considered high-quality habitat. Grasslands which received a high degree of disturbance due to military-vehicle maneuvering are not considered high-quality habitat, even though they may not have been burned or hayed.

Five-minute point counts are conducted at 500 m intervals along roads that occur through and at the periphery of areas identified to potentially contain Henslow's sparrow habitat. Surveys are performed 100 m from the roads to reduce bias caused by roadside habitat features. Survey routes are driven between 0600-1000 hours on mornings with no precipitation and winds less than 15 mph. Census points along the routes that occur in woodlands are not surveyed. Hayed, burned and vehicle-tracked fields encountered along survey routes are surveyed.

The three most common breeding species found by this are the brown-headed cowbird, dickcissel, and eastern meadowlark. Other common birds identified include Henslow's sparrow, upland sandpiper, Bell's vireo, mourning dove, grasshopper sparrow and eastern kingbird.

Loggerhead Shrike surveys

Systematic monitoring of the loggerhead shrike was conducted by a Kansas State University-Division of Biology graduate student (1995 to 1997) as part of research on shrike habitat use. Loggerhead shrikes also are monitored incidentally to other fieldwork, but are not systematically surveyed.

RTLA Breeding bird surveys

The RTLA procedure recommends inventorying breeding bird populations to help determine health and sustainability of training lands. Sixty transects are designated as wildlife plots. Avian counts are conducted using a modified strip/point count method on all 60 plots.

Avian surveys have been conducted by RTLA since 1990. Surveys begin in late May or early June. Morning surveys are conducted by one observer between sunrise and 1000 hours, on days without rain or strong wind. The survey method currently used involves a surveyor conducting a

3-minute point count during which all birds heard or seen within 100 meters of the point are recorded. The surveyor then walks a 100-m transect in six minutes, recording all birds seen within 100 m of the transect.

Preliminary analysis of trends in bird populations has been performed by Kansas State University (Althoff et al. 2001). The overall trend was that most species remained stable or declined, regardless of habitat or migration assemblages. Declining trends observed for many species are consistent with Kansas, regional and national trends.

The three most common breeding species found by RTLA surveys are the brown-headed cowbird, dickcissel, and grasshopper sparrow. Other common birds identified include blue jay, black-capped chickadee, red-winged blackbird, northern cardinal, eastern wood-pewee, mourning dove, and eastern kingbird.

Conservation Branch Spring Bird Surveys

Initially, spring bird surveys consisted of searching for designated habitat blocks in support of Kansas' Breeding Bird Atlas Project, which was completed in 1997. Thereafter, annual spring bird surveys were initiated on the installation, following Breeding Bird Survey protocol developed as a cooperative effort between the U.S. Geological Survey's Patuxent Wildlife Research Center and the Canadian Wildlife Service's National Wildlife Research Centre to monitor the status and trends of North American bird populations. Five routes that average 13 miles in length are driven in early June, with an average of 25 stops located at 0.5-mile intervals along each route. A 3-minute roadside point count is conducted at each stop, during which the observer records all birds heard or seen within 0.25 mile of the stop.

The three most common breeding species found by spring bird surveys are the brown-headed cowbird, dickcissel, and eastern meadowlark. Other common birds identified include field sparrow, northern bobwhite, red-winged blackbird, and northern cardinal.

Mapping Avian Productivity and Survivorship (MAPS)

The Institute for Bird Populations (IBP) initiated the MAPS project (funded by Army's *Legacy Program*) on Fort Riley in 1993. The purpose of the MAPS project is to provide annual indices and estimates of adult population size, post-fledging productivity, adult survivorship and recruitment for certain terrestrial bird species. The MAPS project uses constant-effort mist-netting to attain long-term demographic data on target bird species. Six MAPS stations were established on Fort Riley. Each station studied a 20-ha area by operating 10 mist nets placed throughout the station. Three of the sites were located on forested areas (TA 2 and 81 and the Funston Landfill area), and three were on prairie locations (TA 24, 39 and 65).

Volunteers began taking over this work from the IBP in the summer of 1999. After that time, the three forested sites were abandoned. In 2005, all sites were abandoned.

The three most abundant breeding bird species captured at MAPS sites were the gray catbird, dickcissel, and grasshopper sparrow. Other common species were the common yellowthroat, Bell's vireo, yellow warbler, brown-headed cowbird, and northern cardinal.

Raptor Surveys

Conservation Branch staff has conducted wintertime raptor surveys since 1983. Winter raptor surveys are conducted along standardized routes each year from early January to mid-February. The surveys are performed in accordance with Raptor Vehicle Census Survey Guidelines (Raptor Vehicle Census Survey Guidelines, Army Technical Manual No. 5-633, Natural Resources, Fish and Wildlife Management). The objectives of the winter survey are (1) to identify concentrations and distributions of winter raptors; (2) to monitor relative abundance of species; (3) to document threatened and/or endangered or rare species; (4) to monitor year-to-year changes in raptor densities and diversities; and (5) to monitor changes in raptor densities and diversities during winter months.

The most common raptor observed is the red-tailed hawk, followed in descending order of frequency by northern harrier, bald eagle, rough-legged hawk, and American kestrel. Other raptors occasionally observed are sharp-shinned hawk, Cooper's hawk, prairie falcon, and merlin.

Shorebird Surveys

Systematic surveys of shorebirds found along the rivers adjacent to Fort Riley have been conducted annually since 1994, in conjunction with least tern and piping plover surveys. During these surveys, thirty-eight species have been observed. Two of these species were county records (sanderling, ruddy turnstone).

Roosting/Nesting Structures

Use of roosting and nesting structures is monitored to determine success of the program. Results show eastern bluebird houses, purple martin houses, and Canada goose platforms are the most frequently used structures, followed by wood duck nesting boxes. Mallard boxes are not used frequently. Bats have not used bat houses extensively.

Christmas Bird Count

Fort Riley's inaugural Christmas Bird Count occurred during the winter of 2008-09. The Fort Riley Count Circle was placed to minimize overlapping areas with the Junction City, Manhattan and Wakefield counts, and is roughly centered on UTM grid 930 370 within the Impact Area.

5.0 REPTILES AND AMPHIBIANS

Calling Amphibian Surveys

Surveys for calling amphibians have been performed intermittently since 1999.

KBS Survey

The Kansas Biological Survey (KBS) systematically documented herpetofauna in 1993 (Busby et al. 1994). Thirty-nine species of reptiles and amphibians (17 species of snakes, 6 lizards, 7 turtles, and 9 amphibians) were captured or observed during the study.

Annual Spring Herpetology Survey

During the month of May, Conservation Branch biologists take one or two days to canvas the installation, specifically searching for all amphibians, reptiles and turtles that can be found. Biologists and amateur herpetologists from across the state are invited to participate in the count.

Ornate Box Turtle Tracking Surveys

In 2006, ten ornate box turtles were fitted with radio transmitters and then tracked for movement locations throughout the year. This was a one year study that was discontinued.

6.0 GAME

Populations of six principle game species on Fort Riley are monitored. Objectives vary from obtaining annual indices of population trends to obtaining specific population parameters such as numbers and age and sex ratios. Some population data are derived from the harvested animals themselves.

Upland Game Bird Surveys

Spring surveys are conducted for greater prairie-chicken, northern bobwhite, and ring-necked pheasant. Greater prairie-chicken surveys count numbers of leks and numbers of birds on each lek to yield population numbers. Auditory surveys of northern bobwhite and ring-necked pheasant yield indices of population trends and do not enumerate population size directly. They are used only for annual comparative information. These surveys have been conducted annually since 1982.

The overall objective for these three surveys is to assess long-term population trends. Data derived from upland game surveys are not used to adapt annual harvest frameworks or bag limits for each subsequent hunting season. However, information is provided to hunters who expect a fall hunting forecast.

6.1.1. Northern Bobwhite

Spring whistle counts, with 3 replications, are conducted in June along four standardized routes. Procedures and data analyses are standardized from year to year. These procedures and analysis methods are on file at the Conservation Branch.

In 2012, Fort Riley completed a research project that tracked monthly survival rates for bobwhites in treated and untreated areas. Treated areas consisted of habitat that had received strip disking and edge feathering of timber edges management actions. Results of this project were published in the Transactions of the Kansas Academy of Science (Smith et al., 2014. 117, no. 1-2: p. 1-14).

6.1.2. Ring-necked Pheasant

Spring crow counts are conducted in May along four standardized routes with 3 replications. Procedures and data analyses are standardized from year to year. These procedures and the analysis method are on file at the Conservation Branch.

6.1.3. Greater Prairie-chicken

Greater prairie-chicken lek counts are conducted from late March to late April. Lek counts are made on each Maneuver Area. Standardized routes are not run. Each Maneuver Area is surveyed twice. Active leks are located by sound and counted. If time is available, flush counts are made on each lek. Lek counts are considered more accurate for assessing populations than are flush counts of leks. Numbers of birds on a lek can vary greatly from day to day, but the numbers of leks remain stable throughout the breeding season.

Big Game Surveys

Elk monitoring is more rigorous because it is a reintroduced species that requires more management.

6.1.4. Elk

Elk have been surveyed since their reintroduction in 1986. Aerial surveys were conducted intermittently until 1997 when a systematic protocol for conducting the surveys twice annually was established. These procedures and the analysis method are on file at the Conservation Branch. Data collected also are on file.

The overall objective for elk surveys is to obtain population information for the establishment of an appropriate harvest framework. These data are used to recommend harvest quotas to KDWPT, and KDWPT uses the data to establish long-term management strategies for this herd.

The specific objectives of the surveys differ somewhat, depending on the season during which the surveys are conducted. The primary objectives of winter surveys are to determine total population size and to determine antlered-to-antlerless ratios. The primary objectives of summer surveys are to obtain cow-to-calf ratios and antlered-to-antlerless ratios. A secondary objective of the survey during both periods is to obtain a breakdown of age classes of bulls. Only winter surveys have been conducted since 2004.

Elk populations also are monitored through harvest. Hunters are encouraged to bring harvested elk to the Conservation Branch Office. Antler measurements are taken based on the Boone and Crockett protocol and pictures are taken of the animals. The age structure of the harvested segment is determined by tooth cementum annuli analysis.

6.1.5. White-tailed Deer

Fort Riley has initiated a Quality Deer Management Strategy. Through this strategy, hunters are educated on how to age live bucks in the field. Hunters are encouraged to not shoot at bucks younger than 2 ½ years of age, but let these deer pass and take either a doe or a more mature buck instead.

Antler measurements (when collected) are compared against age data as a reflection of the herd's condition.

In addition to harvest data collected through iSportsman, Fort Riley conducts Spotlight Deer Counts to monitor population trends and establish harvest quotas. Spotlight Deer Counts, with 3 replications, are conducted in November along four standardized routes. Procedures and data

analyses are standardized from year to year. These procedures and analysis methods are on file at the Conservation Branch.

Wild Turkey

Monitoring of wild turkey populations is limited to data collected during the spring hunting season. Hunters are asked to report the beard size, and spur length of harvested turkeys in iSportsman. These data are compiled and summarized to make year to year comparisons.

Conservation Branch monitors the proportion of jakes (last year's male poults) in the harvest. This indicates reproductive success from the previous year. If the proportion of jakes remains high year after year, this reflects an increasing turkey population.

Furbearers

Furbearer populations are not routinely surveyed. However, their relative abundance has been estimated during two research projects conducted by Kansas State University. The first project involved estimating and assessing quantity of "sign" along major streams bisecting the installation (Robel 1987). The second study estimated small mammalian predator densities (Gipson and Kamler 2006).

7.0 FISH

Sport Fish

Sport fish populations and species assemblages are systematically monitored. Electroshocking and seining are used to sample fish communities in installation ponds and lakes. Currently, electroshocking is used in Moon and Breakneck lakes and Beck and Vinton ponds. Creel surveys are conducted intermittently depending on captor availability.

Non-Game Fish

Numerous inventories have been conducted by personnel of the Conservation Branch, Kansas State University, KDWPT, and USFWS in Fort Riley's streams and rivers (see Section 2.2, above).

Kansas State University conducted a study of fish assemblages in Fort Riley streams (Quist 1996). This study produced a general portrait of fish assemblages on Fort Riley. Fish species in streams in the western portion of the installation show a definite 'lake effect', and are largely represented by centrarchids (sunfish family). Largemouth bass, green sunfish, and bluegill are the major representatives. Cyprinids (minnows) occur in low densities and diversities in these streams, and are primarily represented by central stonerollers, fathead minnows, and red shiners. Streams on the eastern side of the installation that do not drain into Milford Lake are dominated by cyprinids, not centrarchids. Species assemblages are more diverse. Major representatives in these streams include redbfin shiners, bluntnose minnows, common shiners and central stonerollers.

Personnel of the Conservation Branch, the USFWS and Kansas State University have conducted surveys of the Kansas, Smoky Hill, and Republican rivers for the sturgeon chub and other resident fishes. Fish species typically associated with the pool, run, or riffle habitats of these rivers include

shovelnose sturgeon, suckermouth minnow, red shiner, sand shiner, bullhead minnow, bluntnose minnow, central stoneroller, river carpsucker, catfish, stonecat, western mosquitofish, Johnny darter, and orangethroat darter.

8.0 INVERTEBRATES

KDWP

Surveys conducted by the KDWP of Timber Creek in 1996 and Fourmile Creek in 2000 included inventories of aquatic insects and mussels. Altogether, 19 orders/families of aquatic insects and five species of mussels were observed in Madison Creek. Fourteen orders/families of aquatic insects and no mussels were found in Fourmile Creek. Mussels were counted as present whether observed alive or from relic shells.

In House Mussel Survey

During 1998–1999, Conservation Branch staff conducted a systematic survey of the fort's streams for mussels and found evidence of 17 species that have resided on Ft. Riley, of which seven species were found extant. The other ten species have apparently been extirpated from the installation. Two of the ten (black sandshell and hickorynut) have apparently been extirpated from the entire state. The most common species collected alive were the pondhorn, fragile papershell, pink papershell, and mapleleaf. These surveys have not been repeated.

Regal Fritillary and Monarch Surveys

Regal fritillaries have been monitored only incidentally to other fieldwork. Systematic surveys are planned (see INRMP 10.3.2.9).

In 2013, Fort Riley funded the KSU CO-OP Unit to perform a two-year research project to 1) provide spatially explicit estimates of the distribution and abundance of the regal fritillary and its host plant, prairie violet; 2) provide models that identify habitat features and management practices that influence the density of regal fritillary adults; and 3) produce information on the effectiveness of management strategies for the regal fritillary populations on Fort Riley. Results of this project are not yet published.

In 2015, Fort Riley further funded the this project to provide baseline population estimates of adult monarch and population trend estimates of adult regal fritillary. The study also identified environmental attributes such as hay removal and fire land management practices that influence those species, including an analysis of land management implications.

Prairie Mole Cricket surveys

Listening surveys for calling prairie mole crickets have occurred in 1992, 1994 and 1998. Surveys consisted of driving through native prairie habitat in the hour after sunset listening for calling males. USFWS personnel conducted the 1992 surveys. Conservation Branch staff performed the 1994 and 1998 surveys.

Other Invertebrates

Kansas State University collected large arthropods, earthworms and microarthropods from soil samples as part of a research study (Schaeffer et al. 1990). Currently, the RTLA program has

started inventorying soil nematode species richness to help determine health of training lands. RTLA collects two cored soil samples, to a depth of 10 cm, from selected soil quality monitoring plots (approximately 20 plots) and analyzes these for nematode species richness.

9.0 FLORA INVENTORY AND MONITORING

Two Planning Level Surveys have been conducted of the installation's flora. The first was completed in 1985, when the vegetative characteristics of the entire installation, excluding the permanent impact area, were described and mapped. The second was completed in 2003, in which the KBS assessed the current condition of vegetation on the installation, located tracts of native prairie, and determined the locations and severity of noxious weed species infestations. The KBS developed a new vegetation classification for the installation, identifying eight primary habitat types; floodplain forest, ravine woodland, Flint Hills tallgrass prairie, sand prairie, limestone butte vegetation, altered grassland vegetation, woodland-brushy, and planted/cultivated vegetation.

RTLA

The RTLA procedure recommends inventorying vegetation to help determine health and sustainability of training lands. RTLA flora inventory provides long-term assessment of changes in the botanical composition and cover across the installation and estimates associated soil loss under varying levels and kinds of uses. RTLA flora surveys consists of monitoring 162 permanent transects located across the installation. RTLA vegetation surveys began on Fort Riley in 1990, but have been discontinued.

Forest Inventory

Fort Riley's forest conditions were inventoried in 1988-1989 and again in 1998-2000. The most recent inventory was initiated in 2012, and field measurements were completed in 2015.

Savanna Inventory

An inventory of Fort Riley's savannas was conducted in 1999. Sizes, locations, plant associations and characteristics of the savannas were determined. Compilation of this information was not completed. Savanna areas were determined to have at least 5% and less than 15% tree cover, on slopes from zero to nine percent. At least 42 locations were identified as having savanna-like characteristics. At least 11 other locations fell close to the parameters of the classification. Additional data on Fort Riley Savannas are located with the Management Agronomist in the Conservation Branch.

Forest Stand Mapping

Forest inventory plot data were associated with forest stands where data overlapped to provide characterization of those forest stands. Where forest inventory plots were not associated with forest stands, simple stand compartment examinations were made to create the Forest Stand Management Plans. Forest Stand Management Plans are completed for identified stands north of Vinton School Road. Those stands south of Vinton School Road are not all completed but development of remaining stand plans were initiated again during FY10. Maps are created to identify locations and boundaries for these stands and stand treatments. All but the earliest forest

inventory maps are digitized into GIS coverages. The forest maps are on file at the Conservation Branch.

Natural Community Evaluation

The KBS (Lauver 1994) conducted a project to characterize the vegetation communities by analyzing multi-spectral digital LANDSAT data and conduct field surveys of selected natural communities to determine their natural quality. This project produced a general land use/land cover database of Fort Riley. The report concluded that Fort Riley contains a variety of high quality natural communities, with the dominant vegetation type being grassland, and that large areas contain Flint Hills Tallgrass Prairie in good to excellent natural condition. Several examples of high-quality upland forests were located on the southern end of the post, whereas only small patches of high quality wetlands were found. The report is on file at the Conservation Branch.

Invasive Weeds

In addition to the Planning Level Survey completed in 2003 by the KBS that determined the locations and severity of noxious weed species infestations, other noxious weed surveys have been performed. An aerial survey flying predetermined transects north of Vinton School Road had observers marking on maps locations of sericea lespedeza. These surveys were supplemented with driven survey routes conducted south of Vinton School Road. Conservation Branch staff conducted mandatory surveys of vegetation in fields receiving aerial applications of herbicides to control sericea lespedeza. Conservation Branch staff also informally tracks locations of noxious weeds encountered incidentally to other field activities.

Habitat Evaluation

A number of surveys and research projects have evaluated wildlife habitat on Fort Riley. Two recent surveys are described.

The KBS completed a project in 1996 to identify and delineate loggerhead shrike habitat on Fort Riley (Lauver et al., 1996). An existing model for assessing the suitability and availability of shrike breeding habitat in the upper Midwest was modified using remote-sensing to predict shrike habitat. Satellite data was ground-truthed to determine accuracy. A GIS model and map overlays depicting shrike habitat were produced.

The USFWS completed a National Wetlands Inventory in 1994 according to USFWS standard procedures. Remote sensing identified wetlands, and then ground-truthing of a sample of wetlands was completed. This NWI is used for planning but is not accurate enough to use to delineate jurisdictional boundaries for permitting requirements. A GIS data layer was produced.

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APPENDIX L

Shrub Density Determination

1.0 PROCESS USED TO DETERMINE SHRUB DENSITY

A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) in the form of a 32-bit floating point gridded matrix generated by the U.S. Army Topographic Engineering Center (TEC) from Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) data collected at Fort Riley, Kansas during March and April 2006 was obtained. The DEM, resolved to 1 meter, was projected to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system based on the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) G1150 ellipsoid as defined for both the horizontal and vertical datum. Accuracies reflect 0.5 meter absolute horizontal, and 0.3 meter absolute vertical at a 90% confidence level. Separate DEMs were created representing a bare-ground surface and one including all surface structures.

The 32-bit matrices (GEOTIFF format) were added to an ESRI ArcMap document for analysis with ESRI's Raster Calculator. Since corresponding pixels in both DEMs represent the same geographic point, it was possible to subtract pixel values of the bare-ground DEM from those of the full-featured DEM to obtain the height of surface structures in meters. Analysis to locate various vegetation structures was initiated once the grid of surface feature heights had been generated. Shrubs, the main point of interest, were defined as any vegetative structure from 0.9144 m – 6.096 m. Anything above 6.096 m in height was classified as a tree for the purpose of this analysis.

Since the grid of surface structure heights included the heights of buildings, water towers, vehicles, etc., all known man-made structures for which there was geographic data were masked out, leaving a grid of surface feature heights presumably reflecting the height of above ground biomass. In addition to man-made features, harvestable stands of timber were also masked out for the purposes of determining woody encroachment onto valuable grassland areas.

Utilizing mathematical operators and functions in a geoprocessing environment, a single grid of height values was developed for shrubs, and one for trees. The SetNull function in ESRI's raster calculator sets identified cell locations to NoData based on specified criteria. The SetNull function returns NoData if the evaluation on an input conditional raster is true; otherwise, it returns the value identified by the false raster or constant. The cell values of the grid representing above-ground biomass height were set to NoData if they fell outside the 0.9144 m – 6.096 m range, leaving a grid of cell values that represented shrub height. Similarly, a grid of cell values representing tree height was generated.

ESRI's GeoStatistical Analyst toolbox was used to determine density, or "hotspots" of shrub encroachment. Geostatistical Analyst uses sample points taken at different locations in a landscape and creates (interpolates) a continuous surface. The sample points are measurements of some phenomenon, such as radiation leaking from a nuclear power plant, an oil spill, or elevation heights. Geostatistical Analyst derives a surface using the values from the measured locations to predict values for each location in the landscape, relying on the similarity of nearby sample points to create the surface. Deterministic techniques use mathematical functions for interpolation.

Geostatistics rely on both statistical and mathematical methods, which can be used to create surfaces and assess the uncertainty of the predictions.

In addition to providing various interpolation techniques, Geostatistical Analyst also provides many supporting tools. For example, prior to mapping, Exploratory Spatial Data Analysis tools can be used to assess the statistical properties of the data. Having explored the data, the user can then create a variety of output map types (for example, prediction, error of prediction, probability, and quantile) using many variants of kriging and cokriging algorithms (for example, ordinary, simple, universal, indicator, probability, and disjunctive) and associated tools (for example, data transformation, declustering, and detrending). We adopted probability cokriging algorithms, and the resulting map was a series of iso-lines (surface area) indicating a range of predicted shrub densities based on the percentage of land area covered by shrubs on individual 160 acre plots.

2.0 VALIDATING PROCESS

Because the shrub percentage iso-line values created by the GeoStatistical Analyst toolbox seemed lower than expected, a separate analysis occurred to validate the map. The Training Area figures found in Appendix L were compared side by side to subjectively rate the extent of tree cover, shrub cover, and grassland fragmentation within each Training Area. For each category, training areas were given a rating of 0 if it was determined no representative of that category was observed, 1 if that category was present in light quantities, 2 if present in moderate quantities, and 3 if present in heavy quantities. Images depicting the relative amounts of tree and shrub cover, and grassland fragmentation were produced (Exhibits K.1 – K.4).

Further refinement of the training area ratings occurred in order to more readily identify areas with similar scores, resulting in the creation of six new categories. These new categories became:

- Training areas determined to have no shrub cover.
- Training areas determined to have a light shrub cover.
- Training areas determined to have a heavy shrub cover.
- Training areas determined to have a moderate shrub cover, with both a tree cover and fragmentation rating of either none or light.
- Training areas determined to have a moderate shrub cover, with either a tree cover or fragmentation rating of heavy.
- Training areas determined to have a moderate shrub cover, with a tree cover and fragmentation rating other than those listed above.

A new, color-coded image was created based on the six categories that were created (Exhibit K.5). The shrub percentage iso-line values created by the GeoStatistical Analyst toolbox were overlaid onto this image for comparison. Through this comparison, it was concluded that the iso-line values created by the GeoStatistical Analyst toolbox accurately reflect the shrub invasion levels observed in the field.

It was further concluded that in grasslands with an iso-line value ≤ 0.4 , prescribed burning should be sufficient for shrub control. In grasslands with an iso-line value at or greater than 0.41, management beyond prescribed burning will be needed to reduce woody encroachment. In

grasslands with an iso-line value exceeding 0.82, the most aggressive management will be required to combat woody encroachment.

Exhibit L.5. A color-coded image depicting the relative amounts of tree and shrub cover, and grassland fragmentation. A rating of 0 indicates that no representative of that category is present, 1 if that category was present in light quantities, 2 if present in moderate quantities, and 3 if present in heavy quantities.

Appendix M

Soil Erosion and Sediment Control Component (SESCC)

1.0 LANDSCAPE CONDITIONS/GEOGRAPHIC CONTEXT

Soils

The land on Fort Riley is composed of a diverse variety of soils. According to the U.S. Department of Agriculture 1975 *Soil Survey of Riley County and Part of Geary County* there are approximately 58 types of soils found on the installation (Figure 1). Most of these are considered to be in Capability Classes II, III, or IV by the Natural Resource Conservation Service. Class II soils have moderate limitations that reduce the choice of plants or that require moderate conservation practices. These soils are subject to moderate erosion if they are not protected. Class III soils have severe limitations that reduce the choice of plants, require special conservation practices or both. These soils are subject to severe erosion if they are not protected. Class IV soils have very severe limitations that reduce the choice of plants, require very careful management, or both. These soils are subject to very severe erosion if they are not protected.

Figure 1: Fort Riley Soil Types

Simplified Soil Classification

Fort Riley’s Integrated Training Area Management (ITAM) Program regrouped the 58 types of soils found on the installation into 12 simplified Range Site classes (Figure 2) to streamline the decision making process for prioritizing corrective actions for disturbed land. In this reanalysis, Loamy Upland and Clay Upland soils cover approximately 75% of the maneuver areas on Fort Riley. The East side of the installation is primarily a Loamy Upland Soil that is classified as a Type IV soil and subject to very severe erosion if not protected.

Landscape

Fort Riley’s Program has four soil-factors that impact the the

Figure 2 Simplified Soil Types

Conditions

ITAM identified related negatively ability of

installation’s training lands to support training. With comprehensive assessment, mitigation and repair practices will minimize impact to training land sustainability and continue to provide quality lands for training. The factors impacting training lands are listed below.

1.1.1. Maneuver Damage

Maneuver damage occurs in some form during training events. The primary cause of maneuver damage is tactical vehicle traffic; digging (defilades, fox holes), mine plow use and other activities also cause damage. Excessive maneuver damage can create ruts and rills that hinder or restrict training (especially for wheeled vehicles), disturb the native grasses that are useful for preventing erosion, and increase weedy species (less erosion control), which can combine to result in a loss of topsoil. Areas with little native tallgrass prairie vegetation and some amount of rill development are susceptible to increased erosion and gully formation (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3: Aerial image of unusually heavy maneuver damage.

Figure 4: Close up view of maneuver damage.

1.1.2. Gullies

Gullies are actively eroding channels with nearly vertical walls that range from one foot to greater than ten feet in depth (Figure 5). Over time, a rut erodes into a gully. If not repaired, gullies usually continue to enlarge upon each storm runoff event. When large gullies dissect training areas, the areas can become inaccessible or unsafe (for people and vehicles).

Figure 5: Gully that formed after military vehicle traffic.

1.1.3. Damaged Drainage Ditches

Troops often use drainage ditches for maneuver training. The ditches offer some level of concealment but can easily be damaged with repeated use (Figure 6). Damaged ditches can quickly washout and can cut off access to training areas. Blocked ditches also can fill with water which can create obstacles to training and can result in the roads being cut. Once a ditch is damaged, troops will often maneuver along the side of the damaged area creating more damaged land. This trend sometimes continues until a large area on either side of the tank trail is damaged.

Figure 6: Maneuver damage in a drainage ditch that is eroding away to become a gully

1.1.4. Stream Crossing Damage

Low-water stream crossings are sites where tactical vehicles frequently ford intermittent and perennial streams. Repeated traffic at these fording sites can form depressions in the stream channel, increase erosion of the stream bank, and increase turbidity and suspended sediment in the stream. When damage becomes severe, these fording sites become impassable, and tactical vehicles are sometimes stuck.

Fort Riley has 84 hardened crossings to protect the stream channels. As troops cross the streams and high-flow events impact the hardened structure, some damage occurs (Figure 7). Maintaining these hardened fording sites protects water quality in the stream, provides better access to training areas, lessens damage to tactical vehicles, and reduces lost training time.

Figure 7: Stream crossing approach damaged by maneuver traffic.

Troops in mechanized equipment frequently cross low-order stream segments at unhardened locations. Such crossings can be safety hazards with the potential to cause injuries or damage vehicles and equipment. These crossings can also cause damage to the stream's stability. Some of these sites will either need a hardened crossing installed or will need to be blocked off to restrict access.

2.0 ITAM PROGRAM

ITAM Mission

ITAM's mission is to meet the Senior Commander's training needs for accessibility and sustained use of training lands utilized for military maneuver exercises in preparation of real world missions.

ITAM Goal

ITAM's goal is to ensure training lands have availability, accessibility, and capability to safely support 1st Infantry Division, National Guard, and Reserve units' training and maneuver needs at Fort Riley. This is accomplished by 1) Training Land Assessments to identify hazards (safety) and maneuver damage (erosion), 2) Repair and Mitigation of training land concerns, and 3) Post-Project Assessment to monitor land rehabilitation repairs. Past training on the installation has created some areas that are below standards of being safe, causing environmental and training land sustainability concerns.

Training Land Assessments - Safety and Mobility

2.1.1. Monitoring Objective

Training land safety and mobility assessments are conducted for the entire installation on no less than an annual basis. Specific objectives include (1) identifying existing safety hazards (e.g., gullies, improved stream crossing) that require repair, (2) identifying areas with excessive bare soil exposure, and (3) identifying areas susceptible to erosion based on soil type and slope, integrated with vegetation assessments. Assessment results will be used as one information source to identify areas in potential need of land rehabilitation.

2.1.2. Methods

Identify existing safety hazards through periodic field surveys, use of imagery from remote sensing, and from locations provided by units and the Directorate of Public Works Environmental Division (DPW-E), using ancillary data collected during field campaigns for other assessments.

Training Land Repair and Mitigation

Work includes repairing maneuver damage; controlling or filling in gullies; installing ditch linings; repair damaged stream crossings including approaches; and closing unauthorized stream crossings. This objective is a coordinated effort between ITAM (project design / funding) and the DPW-E for NEPA process and any permits required to accomplish training land rehabilitation projects. Project designs and practices will come from prior successful ITAM projects and other governmental agencies, such as the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers and U.S. Department of Agriculture – Natural Resources Conservation Service.

2.1.3. Project Design

The Land Rehabilitation and Management (LRAM) Coordinator develops the project site design. The project site conditions and objectives of the project help determine the best management practices (BMPs) to stabilize and sustain the site over the long-term.

Based upon the site conditions and BMPs selected, the LRAM Coordinator develops a project plan that contains the following information: design, material considerations, construction/installation specifications, required permits, inspection and maintenance criteria, and estimated project cost.

2.1.4. NEPA Process

All ITAM Projects are coordinated with the DPW-E for compliance with National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA), Clean Water Act, endangered species regulations, natural stream flow and cultural resources regulations. When completing a project, the following processes must be completed to ensure regulatory compliance work with DPW-E to write and submit additional environmental regulatory documentation, as required (e.g., wetlands permit application, Stormwater Prevention Plan, Notice of Intent). Once the NEPA review is complete and the REC is signed, work can begin on a project.

LRAM BMPs

LRAM BMPs are commonly modified to meet the installation site conditions. The major BMP categories specified by project group are listed below. Some detailed BMPs can be found in the LRAM Technical Resource Library on the Sustainable Range Program Website.

2.1.5. Maneuver Damage Repair BMP

Maneuver damage is repaired by leveling the disturbed ground to remove ruts and replanting native tallgrass prairie grasses (seeding and mulching is required) to hold the soil and prevent erosion.

2.1.6. Gully Repair BMP

Methods to repair gullies include installing gully checks to provide access across gullies and to prevent further erosion. Sites with small gullies are leveled, regraded, and rock checks are installed to prevent further erosion. The area is then reseeded and mulched as required.

2.1.7. Ditch Lining BMP

The ditches are repaired by lining with rock and finish grading so that vehicles can travel over the rock. This project is only done at locations that are repeatedly damaged during training events and not for every trail on post. No repairs will be made to hardened tank trails that are Real Property.

2.1.8. Repair Damaged Crossings BMP

Work to repair damaged crossings depends on the type and extent of the damage. Work can range from simply clearing out debris that was deposited in the crossing to rebuilding the hardened structure and re-shaping the approaches to direct water away from the crossing and to prevent gullies from forming. Some sites will require hardened diversions to be installed on or before the crossing approaches to redirect stormwater into the riparian areas. Some crossings will be closed off and new crossings will be installed at the proper locations. Some stream restoration is required because of maneuver damage.

2.1.9. Closing off Crossings BMP

Work to close an unhardened crossing includes excavating, hauling and placing rocks in excess of 1 cu meter each across the path. Each site requires a minimum of 6 rocks per side.

Post-Project Assessment

The objective of the Post-Project Assessment is to evaluate completed Projects to determine whether the project was, and continues to be successful, or if more maintenance is needed. Geodatabase layers will be maintained showing locations of completed and future projects.

2.1.10. Methods

The methods used in the assessment will vary depending on the Project that is being monitored. Some projects will be monitored using remote sensing. Other projects will be monitored via simple field surveys and terrestrial photography. Aerial photography (e.g., blimp photographs, digital orthophotographs) can also be used to monitor projects (as appropriate).

2.1.11. Data Management and Analysis

The ITAM program maintains a geospatially-enabled relational database that allows production of maps showing completed and planned LRAM projects. This database is updated as LRAM assessments are completed and again on a periodic basis to help document project success or failure. Occurrence of repeat projects at the same, or nearby, locations may suggest alternative rehabilitation actions are necessary.

2.1.12. Monitoring Schedule

Projects are monitored as needed depending on the type of project that is being monitored. Grass plantings will typically be monitored annually for 3 years following the treatment to determine success. Certain erosion prevention projects will be monitored after large rain events to ensure they are functioning properly.

Appendix N

Borrow Area Management Plan 2016

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Most needs for borrow materials are associated with Military Construction-Army projects, road construction and other contracted projects on Fort Riley. Depending on the size of the project and the original and final grades, the amount of material needed may range from hundreds to tens of thousands of cubic yards.

1.1. Borrow Materials

Soil borrow is used for two major purposes on Fort Riley; as fill material and as topsoil. These uses are greatly different and require different materials. Fill material is used to *fill in* a depression or hole in the ground or otherwise artificially change the grade or elevation of real property to establish or restore a site to suitable grade. Fill dirt is usually compactable subsoil (soil from beneath the top soil and underlying parent material) that has little soil organic matter, since organic matter will decompose and create pockets of empty space within the fill that could result in settling. A clay or clay loam material is typically used to provide for proper compaction. Loam or sand can be used for fill in some situations. Fill is obtained from on-site excavation (cut) activities or excavated and hauled from off-site locations.

Topsoil is used to finish construction sites and fill small holes in improved ground areas. Topsoil provides a medium for plant growth, and therefore must possess good tilth and fertility. Topsoil is usually needed in smaller quantities than fill. Most construction projects require fill to build upon, then use topsoil on top of fill to allow grass lawns and other landscaping to be grown. When feasible, top soil is first stripped from the construction site as the first operation, stockpiled on site, then reapplied.

Rock borrow is used to provide material for tank trails, graveled roads and parking areas. Additionally, certain erosion control projects and hardened stream crossings use rock.

1.2. Borrow Areas

Extraction of soil and rock borrow material from the grounds of Fort Riley can be beneficial as it allows the installation to avoid costs associated with importing materials from the surrounding communities. However, borrow operations also can create negative impacts to the installation, such as loss of training land, unsafe or hazardous slopes, and point source stormwater runoff. Additionally, borrow actions can destroy landscapes and wildlife habitat, disrupt training and cause disturbance such as dust, noise, and traffic. Once vegetative cover is lost, the soils on Fort Riley are susceptible to erosion.

Usually, a borrow area will require access (or haul) roads. Haul roads can present a host of problems themselves, both on and off the actual site. On-site effects are largely noise and dust. Potential off-site effects are:

- Additional vehicles on the roads;
- Damage to roads due to size and number of vehicles using the road;
- Loss of material (particularly rock) from truck beds during hauling;
- Tracking of fill material onto hard surfaced roads;
- Visual intrusion, dust, noise, and vibration;

- Disturbance of habitat; and
- Compaction and settlement.

Borrow activities should occur in locations that are minimally disruptive to the Fort Riley training mission. A satisfactory balance must be sought between the need for borrow material, safeguarding resources, protecting the environment, and the training needs of Soldiers.

1.3. Borrow Area Annual Update

In FY 2015, contractors and government operators conducted borrow activities for fill in TA 6-C and TA 6-D. Borrow activities for rock occurred in TA 90, 91 and 103. Available rock in the TA 91 and TA 103 quarries has been exhausted. These sites have been closed and remediated. New locations for extracting rock borrow are needed for projects that will occur in the northern training areas of the installation. To meet this need, the installation intends to expand the TA 91 rock borrow site to the south, and evaluate historic quarries in TA 47 and TA 51 for re-opening. The installation evaluated and determined to forego the expansion of the TA 1 borrow site at this time.

2.0 PURPOSE

The purpose of this Borrow Area Management Plan is to provide instructions so that borrow-related actions occur in a manner that ensures availability of materials, maintains sustainability of resources, meets environmental compliance, and minimizes conflicts with military day-to-day training operations at Fort Riley.

Soil and rock have been borrowed from Fort Riley lands for many years. Historically, this activity was relatively uncontrolled. Borrow areas were selected with convenience being the primary location criterion, without consideration for the useful life of the site, training and environmental impacts, or closure requirements. Often, a site was used for the duration of a project and then abandoned, without effort to reclaim the area or make it safe or otherwise useful. Some inactive borrow areas have sheer rock or soil embankments, making them unsafe for troops and vehicles. Some are highly visible, making them aesthetically undesirable, or have potential environmental impacts, and many offer little value for military training.

An abandoned rock borrow area with steep rock embankment following completion of borrow.

This plan is intended to be Fort Riley's standard for the planning, operation and rehabilitation of borrow areas on the installation. It provides a detailed framework to control and direct borrow area locations and actions, and addresses applicable local, state, Army, and federal requirements. All borrow area-related actions are to be in accordance with this plan.

This plan has been prepared on the basis of the best information available, some of which is imprecise. For example, there is limited knowledge of the quality and quantity of workable borrow

material at a site. It is also difficult to forecast when certain building projects or construction plans will be funded.

The goal is to make Fort Riley borrow efforts safe and regulatory compliant in a manner that sustains the mission, enhances wildlife habitat, protects the environment and improves the visual appearance of the installation. Adherence to this plan ensures that borrow actions minimally disrupt the training mission, borrow materials are available for construction activities, the environment is protected and appropriate measures are taken to restore a site after borrow actions are complete. The objectives are:

- Provide approximately 60,000 cubic yards (CY) of borrow material per year for Fort Riley's needs over the next 25 years (1.5M CY);
- Minimize disturbance and impact to the training mission;
- Minimize environmental impacts and mitigate those impacts which are unavoidable;
- Protect natural and cultural resources;
- Protect the water environment;
- Ensure borrow areas are safe;
- Restore borrow areas to a beneficial state after use; and
- Provide multiple, concurrent active borrow locations.

3.0 ASSESSMENT

A well-planned project design can reduce the amount of fill material needed. The design of a project should strive for a balanced amount of earthwork so that the amount of cut is equal to the amount of fill required. More often than not this criterion is not met, and projects have excess cut generated, additional fill required, or sometimes both. It is recommended that as soon as the requirement to acquire borrow material or dispose of spoil is identified, coordination with the Environmental Division, Directorate of Public Works (DPW-E) be initiated to determine if existing sites will meet project needs.

If existing sites do not meet project needs, or if currently identified borrow areas become exhausted, unusable, or impractical, then new borrow areas will be necessary. Generally, criteria for selecting a new borrow site will include:

- Proximity to construction sites;
- Type and amount of material needed;
- Longevity of the site to provide needed material; and
- Objectives listed in Section 2 (Purpose).

Fort Riley established a "Soil and Rock Borrow Working Group" in 2009 that identified potential borrow areas that warranted further study. The group was composed of representatives from DPW, Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobility, and Security (DPTMS), Garrison Safety Office and the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers. A synopsis of those studies follows:

3.1. Soil Borrow Report (Professional Engineering Consultants)

Professional Engineering Consultants (PEC) was contracted to conduct a geotechnical drilling program to estimate in-place soil volumes (Appendix I) that could be used as soil borrow material in the future, based upon the potential borrow areas identified by the Working Group. A project goal was to identify approximately 25 years of borrow demand volume. PEC conducted surveys to assess the suitability of proposed borrow areas. The results of their findings are listed below:

- **TA 6:** The potential borrow of the TA 6 Borrow Area was estimated at approximately 800,000 CY of soil. Borrow actions have taken place at this site since that assessment, and the actual quantity of material remaining is unknown. The soil at this site is desirable for fill material and should work well for the installation's soil needs.
- **TAs 14 and 15:** PEC concluded that TAs 14 and 15 have little soil volume and do not offer much potential soil borrow.
- **TA 16:** PEC estimated that TA 16 may yield about 1.5 million CY of borrow material. However, testing performed on samples from the uppermost soil found it to be a heavy clay with limited construction compatibility. Similar testing from deeper soils has not been performed. It is unclear whether deeper materials are more suited for construction needs.

3.2. Rock Borrow Report (Corps of Engineers)

The U.S. Army-Corps of Engineers, Kansas City District (COE) was contracted to assess the suitability and estimate the quantity of potential rock borrow at four sites; Training Areas 6, 37, 80 and 90, based upon the borrow areas identified by the Working Group (Appendix II). A project goal was to identify the general thickness of overburden soils. Consequently, COE conducted soil and rock borings in the designated areas. The results of their findings are listed below:

- **TA 6:** Estimated quantity of limestone=264,851 yd³; Rock Quality Designation (RQD) = 61%, Fair rock quality. Drill and blast may be required for excavation. Considered suitable for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, and rock fill; large, rectangular blocks can be produced in limited quantity. However, it contains significant quantities of chert that may impact its suitability for road gravel with wheeled-vehicle traffic. It is not suitable for riprap or concrete aggregate.
- **TA 37: Poor rock quality.** Fifteen feet of soil and thirteen feet of shale overlay the limestone.
- **TA 80:** Estimated quantity of limestone=339,768 yd³; RQD=75%, Fair rock quality. It is rippable and considered suitable for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, rock fill, road aggregate and riprap.
- **TA 90:** Estimated quantity of limestone=200,367 yd³; RQD=63%, Fair rock quality. It is rippable and considered suitable for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, rock fill, road aggregate and riprap.

4.0 PLANNING

Effective erosion control begins in the planning stages. The first and foremost principle for borrow area activity is to disturb the least amount of ground for the least amount of time.

4.1. NEPA Review

Environmental review and permitting are integral to the planning process. Before opening a new borrow area or establishing a new spoil storage location, review of potential environmental impacts is required by the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA). The process for evaluating an area should begin as soon as the need to establish a new site is identified. If new sites need to be activated, the process will involve consultation and permitting. The environmental review process will involve consultation with government entities outside of Fort Riley, which is the responsibility of DPW-E. Consultation and permitting actions often take 90-120 days, but can sometimes be longer or shorter, depending on the complexity of the negotiations.

Often, the DPW-E NEPA Manager participates in planning or scoping meetings and is in position to participate early in the planning process. In the situation where DPW-E is not included in planning/scoping, the DPW Business Operations (DPW-Ops) or Master Planning (DPW-MP) Divisions will request, either verbally or in writing, evaluation of the potential borrow area through the NEPA Manager.

Based on the NEPA Manager's determination, the proposed site may require evaluation for stormwater concerns, impact on cultural resources, the existence of hazardous waste or contaminated sites, and impact to threatened or endangered species, or migratory birds. The NEPA Manager will coordinate internally with applicable DPW-E media area experts to review potential areas and associated environmental issues. The DPW-E media area experts will review the proposed borrow area with regard to legal and other requirements, and provide the NEPA Manager the results of their review.

If cultural resource issues arise, consultation with the State Historic Preservation Office will be required. If threatened or endangered species, or migratory bird issues arise, consultation with the U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service and Kansas Department of Wildlife, Parks, and Tourism will likely be required. Either situation will likely delay permitting timelines.

Locations proposed for borrow must be evaluated to identify the best suited use for that area. This evaluation does not preclude, but enhances the requirement for NEPA review and documentation. Using a site for borrow may be just one of various competing uses for a location. To achieve a balance, evaluation is helpful to establish importance of the site and the implications of using the area as a borrow area. The degree of importance of a site may be influenced by a number of factors including:

- proximity of the construction project,
- quality and quantity of borrow material present and needed, and
- impedance to the training mission.

The NEPA Manager will compile the results of all environmental analyses and has responsibility for determining the appropriate NEPA documentation for the site. The NEPA Manager will consult with the DPW-E Chief on the outcome. The proposal may require NEPA documentation in the form of an Environmental Assessment, a Record of Environmental Consideration, or the site may be covered by a categorical exclusion. If the proposed location cannot be used because of environmental constraints, DPW-E will coordinate with DPW-Ops and DPW-MP to identify alternative sites with similar characteristics.

4.2. Permitting Under the Clean Water Act

Borrow sites on Fort Riley are controlled under the National Pollutant Discharge Elimination Program (NPDES) permit #F-KS51-PO02, authorized under the Clean Water Act. Kansas Department of Health and Environment (KDHE) has assigned Outfall Number 005A1 to Active Borrow Management Areas and requires updating this plan annually as well as prior to “placing new borrow areas into active use”. Effluent discharge limitations are included on pages 4 and 5 of the NPDES permit.

A Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan (SWP3) will be developed for each new site that will include an examination to determine locations of concentrated runoff, outfalls, and other areas where sediment control structures may be needed to control erosion and sediment for each borrow site. If use of a new borrow site will disturb ground areas of one acre or larger, a Construction Stormwater Permit for the action at that site must be obtained from the KDHE.¹⁴ The permit application, Notice of Intent (NOI) must be submitted to KDHE no later than 60 days prior to ground disturbance. An annual fee of \$60.00 is required. The DPW-E Water Quality Regulations Compliance Manager will work in collaboration with DPW Engineering Services Division (DPW-ESD) to apply for a Construction Stormwater Permit from KDHE, which can occur in conjunction with the SWP3 development. KDHE regulations require that the SWP3 and the application be developed and signed off by a Professional Engineer licensed in the state of Kansas. The plan must be fully implemented for the life of the borrow area.

5.0 OPERATION

Construction projects most often fall under the purview of the Corps of Engineers, the DPW-Ops, the DPW-MP, or the DPTMS Integrated Training Area Management program. During construction planning, the project manager is to coordinate with the DPW-E Division when borrow material is needed, or spoil will be generated. Coordination will include reviewing all aspects of the borrow activities, including haul routes, proximity of construction sites to borrow areas, and the type and amount of borrow material needed. With this information, collaboration between DPW-E and the project manager will occur to identify suitable areas.

The project should be designed to use borrow material from the construction site or previously disturbed locations. If existing sites for borrow and spoils will be used for a project, protocol as outlined in Section 5 (Operation) will be followed. If a new site for borrow or spoil disposal is needed, protocol as described in Sections 4a and 4b will occur prior to following protocol in Section 5.

5.1. Borrow Areas

The list of sites that are approved for borrow activities, or that are in the process of being approved, is at Table 1. Changes from 2014 are that TA 1-B, TA 47, TA 51 and TA 91-B are added, while TA 91 and TA 103 are removed. Site details and maps for the borrow areas are in Appendix III.

¹⁴ A Construction Stormwater Permit from KDHE is required prior to initiation of construction. The Clean Water Act authorizes civil penalties of up to \$37,500 per day per violation in addition to possible criminal sanctions.

The use of a location for borrow other than those in Table 1 requires prior approval from the Director, Public Works, in accordance with the steps laid out in Section 4 (Planning) of this plan.

Borrow Area	Location		Material
Marshall Field (TA 1)	96° 46' 23.08" W 39° 2' 22.5" N	Long Lat	Topsoil
Training Area 1-B	96° 46' 21.56" W 39° 2' 24.4" N	Long Lat	Topsoil
Campbell Hill (TA 6)	96° 41' 14.68" W 39° 7' 30.66" N	Long Lat	Earth Fill
Training Area 47	96° 53' 8.29" W 39° 9' 20.22" N	Long Lat	Rock
Training Area 49	96° 50' 35.36" W 39° 8' 54.78" N	Long Lat	Topsoil
Training Area 51	96° 51' 55.17" W 39° 10' 30.22" N	Long Lat	Rock
Training Areas 79 and 80	96° 56' 31.97" W 39° 16' 1.52" N	Long Lat	Rock
Training Area 82	96° 56' 26.76" W 39° 16' 56.55" N	Long Lat	Rock
Training Area 90	96° 46' 33.26" W 39° 14' 20.263" N	Long Lat	Rock
Training Area 91-B	96° 46' 20.52" W 39° 13' 20.20" N	Long Lat	Rock

Table 1. Names and locations of approved sites for conducting borrow activities on Fort Riley.

5.2. Excess Cut

Government Contract Officer Representatives or government project managers of construction projects with excess cut materials from a site must coordinate with DPW-E Borrow Area Manager to determine locations for stockpiling excess material. Excess clay and topsoil should be stockpiled in separate locations. The DPW likes to keep topsoil stockpiled for small fill and reseeded projects in improved and semi-improved grounds areas. Less suitable material can be used where the quality of the fill material is not critical (e.g., under an unpaved parking area), and should be segregated from clay and topsoil piles.

The list of sites that are currently approved for placement of spoil piles is at Table 2. The use of a location for spoil piles other than those listed in Table 2 requires prior approval from the Director, Public Works, in accordance with the steps laid out in Section 4 (Planning) of this plan.

Spoil Placement Area	Location		Material
Williston Point Rd (TA-13)	96° 46' 59.438" W 39° 5' 59.744" N	Long Lat	Soil, Rock and mixed
Campbell Hill C/D Landfill (TA-8)	96° 44' 23.62" W 39° 7' 15.927" N	Long Lat	Soil, Rock and mixed
CPAC/DPW Spoil Pile	96° 46' 10.72" W	Long	Topsoil

	39° 4' 5.171" N	Lat	
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Table 2. Names and locations of approved sites for placing spoils material on Fort Riley.

5.3. Protocol and Responsibilities

DPW-E will coordinate all users of and access to the borrow areas for borrow-related activity. The current Point of Contact for borrow area use is Mr. Jeff Keating (telephone 239-8022; email jeffrey.f.keating.civ@mail.mil). Contract personnel wishing to use borrow material or dispose of spoils must contact Mr. Keating through their government representative and abide by the stipulations as provided in the memo received that authorizes use of the sites. Government personnel wishing to use borrow material must contact Mr. Keating prior to their occupation of a borrow area. As practical, users will be staggered across the borrow areas to minimize co-occupation of sites. However, complete autonomy of use cannot be guaranteed to any user of borrow areas, so co-occupation should be anticipated. When training areas with active borrow sites are to be closed due to military training, DPTMS staff will inform the DPW-E Borrow Area POC, who in turn is to relay that information to all users active in the borrow areas during that time frame.

One of the main concerns with use of a borrow area from a permitting perspective is the potential for ground disturbance actions to result in sediment loads entering a nearby stream system. Ground disturbance activities include, but are not limited to, clearing and grubbing, establishing haul roads, establishing pads or buildings, and material extraction actions. The site-specific SWP3 will identify proper erosion and sediment control techniques. Erosion and sediment control practices must be properly installed, operated and maintained to be effective. While each borrow area site may differ, the general sequence of activities to control erosion and sediment is as follows:

- Prior to any ground disturbance, the areas where runoff water would leave the site must be determined from the SWP3 and be protected by installing all required sediment control measures, or determining that those measures already installed still are functional. Erosion on the site that results in concentrated sediment-laden runoff must be captured in a sediment detention structure. Structures may include silt fences, hay bale barriers, rock dams, grass filter strips, or sediment basins.
- Clean water that would normally enter the borrow area site from upstream drainage should remain clean. This can be accomplished by DPW-Ops constructing diversions where needed to direct clean runoff water around any disturbed borrow areas, and mulching the diversions.
- The initial establishment of the borrow areas may include construction-type activities such as clearing, grubbing, removal of downed trees and rocks, and stripping of topsoil.
- Cleared and grubbed material will be incorporated into an erosion control structure such as a windrow whenever possible. Otherwise, it will be piled on site or disposed of at the tree disposal area across from the Campbell Hill Construction and Demolition Landfill, as appropriate.
- Topsoil from fill and rock borrow areas will be stockpiled on site to restore vegetation to the site once the borrow activities are complete. Stockpiled topsoil will be fenced or

otherwise surrounded with an engineering technique that will keep sediment from leaving the site.

- Borrow areas should be managed to collect and retain runoff water in an area where borrowing has been completed, rather than allowing sediment-laden water to leave the site. DPW-Ops installs sediment control structures for proper detention of runoff water at the outfall for the borrow area, and installs sediment control barriers (silt fences, hay bales, etc.) where necessary. Borrow areas that allow runoff to bypass an outfall sediment control structure shall have silt fence barriers or other appropriate structures installed to control sediment.
- DPW-E inspects the sites quarterly for compliance with NPDES Permit requirements and the written SWP3. Also, the Division will monitor sediment accumulation in silt fences or sediment basins. DPW-E shall notify DPW-Ops when silt must be removed to provide original design capacity and the silt shall be properly spread in locations to be seeded.
- When Fort Riley is the permittee for construction of a borrow area, the DPW Divisions are responsible for designing, installing, monitoring and maintaining all stormwater control devices.
- The natural drainage pattern of the borrow area is the major consideration for depth to which borrow material may be removed. Excavation should not exceed the low areas that provide natural drainage. Figure 2 depicts the general approach for material removal at a borrow area.

Figure 2. Generalized concept for maximum depth of material removal at borrow locations.

- While a borrow area is in use, extraction activities sometimes leave a steep cut bank that approaches a 90 degree slope angle. To minimize potential safety hazards, whenever borrow actions will cease for a period that exceeds 14 days, the entity performing the borrow action must grade the cut bank to a slope of less than 2:1 at completion of the borrow action prior to the down time. Alternately, the entity performing the borrow may ensure the top side of the cut bank is clearly marked with reflective barrier materials that are visible to operators of vehicles approaching from the topside of the excavation, and warn of the presence of the cut bank.

- Slopes on topsoil stockpiles should be maintained at a 2:1 grade, with silt fences installed around the perimeter.
- In locations where spoil piles are placed and are not intended to be reused, spoil piles are to be leveled and compacted at the end of the project, or whenever stockpile actions will cease for a period that exceeds 14 days.
- Any area that has bare soil exposed to direct rainfall has the potential to erode and move sediment with runoff water. One of the most cost effective methods to stop sediment at the source is to cover the exposed area with mulch. However, the mulch must be removed or recycled when use of the site resumes.
- DPW-E Compliance Inspectors will monitor the borrow areas on at least a quarterly basis and after every rain event of more than one-half inch for the effectiveness of erosion and sediment control structures, to ensure environmental compliance, to identify illegal dumping, and to identify chemical spills. Erosion that does occur should be promptly corrected. DPW-E shall coordinate with DPW-Ops and DPW-ESD regarding additional practices that may be needed if those originally installed are not effective. Any potential safety issues will be reported to the Garrison Safety Office.

6.0 REHABILITATION

6.1. Non-Active Borrow Areas

Fort Riley has former borrow areas that are not currently authorized for use (Figure 3). These sites are ones that were used for borrow activities in the past but were not closed and reclaimed as usable space within the training areas. Actions described in Section 6 (Borrow Area Reclamation) need to be accomplished in these non-active borrow areas.

6.2. Borrow Area Reclamation

Once a borrow area is devoid of useful material, the site needs to be returned to beneficial use for the installation. Exhausted borrow areas have potential for a number of uses. Frequently returning them to suitable use for military training is the most cost effective. Other areas may have use as construction and demolition landfills or disposal for excess compost, biosolids, lime sludge, remediated soil, spoil, or wood chips. Other potential uses are habitat for reptile, amphibian and other wildlife species.

- Slopes must be graded to a trafficable slope of approximately 3:1 or less.
- Adequate drainage must be established to prevent large-scale ponding. When located on a hillside, attention must be given to preventing erosion when reestablishing drainage. Routing outflow to a well vegetated natural drainage path or establishing stormwater diversions will help prevent erosion.
- Once borrow activities cease, evaluation of the site will occur to determine the best suited reclamation plan. When reestablishing vegetation at the site is desired to reclaim the area, topsoil that has been stockpiled will be spread back across the site, followed by reseeding. At other times, maintaining the rocky substrate with scattered loose rocks may be the desired end state to provide reptile habitat. In these instances, once safe slopes are

established and protective erosion measures are enacted, the site will be left to re-vegetate naturally.

- Any windrows should be removed as one of the last tasks prior to reestablishing vegetation on the site.
- When returning an area to native prairie, temporary seeding and or mulching may be required until permanent planting dates can be met. Some cover crops are oats, winter wheat, and western wheatgrass. Cover crops can be seeded along with native seed mixtures. Seed mixture and seeding rate should be selected based on site characteristics.

7.0 POINTS OF CONTACT

For questions or more information about Borrow Sites on Fort Riley contact the DPW Borrow Area Manager. The current Point of Contact for borrow area use is Mr. Jeff Keating (telephone 785-239-8022; email jeffrey.f.keating.civ@mail.mil).

Appendices

Appendix I. Soil Borrow Report (Professional Engineering Consultants)

Borrow Area Management Report for Fort Riley, Kansas Draft Report

INTRODUCTION

On behalf of Ft. Riley, GLMV retained Professional Engineering Consultants, PA (PEC) to prepare a borrow study report of the amount of potential soil volume in certain Training Areas around the Base that could be used for imported fill on construction projects. Two active TA's Nos. 6 and 24 currently serve as borrow sites, the locations are depicted on the enclosed Map No. 1. Base staff identified TAs 14, 15 and 16 as other possible areas in which excavated borrow material could be obtained that is in reasonable close proximity to the Custer Hill Area, also shown on Map No. 1.

PEC conducted a geotechnical drilling program and drilled exploratory holes throughout these areas for the purpose to estimate in-place soil volumes that could be used as borrow material in the future. A project goal was to identify approximately 25 years of borrow demand volume. Annually the Base needs about 100,000 cubic yards (CY) of borrow material for its projects. Consequently finding approximately 2.5 million CY of suitable borrow material was the goal of this study.

FIELD PROGRAM

A field reconnaissance trip was conducted by PEC and BASE Staff on November 2, 2010, to investigate the feasibility for drill rig access into Training Areas 6, 14, 15, 16 and 24. TA 6A-6E was planned to be drilled during the first of two drilling programs such that enough data could be collected to estimate the potential borrow volume from the area. Excavation at TA 6 has only recently begun and there is believed to be a significant volume of suitable borrow material. Training Areas 14, 15 and 16 were considered as potential borrow sites due to their close proximity to the Custer Hill area. A drilling plan was prepared that could preliminarily estimate borrow volume potential. TA 24 was reviewed and would be drilled more relative to confirming little remaining borrow volume potential. All drill holes were planned to terminate at a depth of 20 feet or when a confining rock layer was encountered.

After the field reconnaissance, maps of the Training Areas were prepared that indicated where probable drill holes could be conducted. Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 are included in the Appendix, which includes the approximate boring locations. Additional tree coverage area of TA 16 was considered in the positioning of potential drill holes. These maps were submitted to Base Staff and approved. After staff approval, these maps were submitted to the Fort Riley Dig Safe Office and Kansas One Call to secure drilling permits.

Upon receipt of drilling clearance on November 30, 2010, the first phase drilling program began on December 6, 2010. Forty-four (44) drill holes were accomplished in the five TA's as displayed on Table 1 and Map No. 1. Hole depths and the GPS longitude and latitude location and ground elevations are provided. A complete copy of Allied Laboratories geotechnical report is included in Appendix A and explains the suitability of the soils encountered.

BORROW VOLUME ESTIMATION METHODOLOGY

The drilling hole Global Positioning System (GPS) data was obtained by using a hand-held unit manufactured by Garmin, Model eTrex Vista HCx. The unit has at least a precision of 10 meter horizontal accuracy. The horizontal precision of the GPS unit is satisfactory for this volume estimation study given the large planer area of the borrow sites and the limited number of drill holes that were budgeted and that could be accessed and developed.

GPS longitude/latitude data was converted using the Verscon software into Kansas State Plane Coordinates. The Base's mapping system is based on state plane coordinates and this allowed the plotting of the drill holes on the topographic mapping. PEC had current 2010 aerial photographic mapping of the BASE and this was used with the topography to produce Map No. 1. This map displays the Base's five-foot contour interval topographic mapping; drill holes and the potential borrow areas that were investigated.

The drill hole locations plotted on the topographic mapping provided an approximate ground elevation at each hole. The vertical depth of the drill hole was used as a distance from the ground elevation to determine the elevation of the rock layer. The effective hole depth for recoverable borrow material in open areas was discounted 8" for upper organic material and 12" above the apparent rock layer. The effective hole depth for recoverable borrow material in tree covered areas was discounted 18" for upper organic material and 12" above the apparent rock layer.

For soil volume estimation purposes, the Base's topographic mapping was converted into an irregular shaped computerized surface by the Base's GIS staff. A computerized surface of the underlying rock layer that was encountered by the drill holes was created by PEC from hole locations and the discounted boring depths. This rock surface was extended to the limits of the potential borrow site at a construction slope angle of 3:1. We recommend a resulting maximum slope height along the perimeter of a borrow site to not exceed 20 feet. With a 3:1 slope angle and intermittent terraces of 5 feet in width, the resultant limits of the borrow sites will have adequate slope stability. The drilling depths generally encountered were less than 20 feet. However some depth in TA 6 may exceed 30 feet and the borrow operation in this area may have to plan for the boundary slopes of the borrow site as described above.

These two irregular computerized surfaces were modeled as such and were used to compute the volume between them within a specified horizontal area that would be a practical area to excavate. ArcGIS 3D Analyst version 10 computer program was used. Computerized printouts of determined in-place soil volumes are enclosed in Appendix B. Figures 6 through 9 are included showing the land area used in the volume computation for each of the potential borrow sites.

From this drilling data and the computerized surfaces, estimates of borrow volume from each area were calculated and displayed in Table 2. Data from this study is limited to only a relatively small number of drill holes over a large total area of 505 acres. Consequently the accuracy of the soil volume estimates in this report is based on this limited information. The practical amounts

of excavated acreage in TAs 14, 15 and 16 were reduced to only within the limits of bedrock outcropping along hillsides from the drilling data.

As a verification of the computation of the in-place soil volumes, an estimate was performed using average hole depths over the same borrow site area to cross check the validity of the volume estimated between the two computerized surfaces. Average discounted depths of drill holes were computed within a particular TA. That average discounted depth multiplied by the surface area of the potential borrow area limits computed a theoretical maximum in place overburden that could be used. Table 2 displays these results. The average depth method produces a smaller in-place soil volume than the computerized method since the limits of the borrow site do not address the variability of the existing ground elevation as does the computerized surface method.

These two independent computational methods produced different estimations of in-place volumes, and this check of the computerized theoretical volume indicated similar results. Some limitations of this theoretical volume calculations are in order. It is estimated that only perhaps 90% of this theoretical volume is physically able to be excavated due to variations in the bedrock. Current borrow site TA 6 was investigated with 18 holes and found to have approximately 829,000 CY of in-place material that could be excavated, reference Table 2. So the balance of the desired soil borrow volume would have to be identified in the other training areas.

TA's 14 and 15:

TA's 14 and 15 have little soil volume and are more prairie-like. We estimate a total of 546,719 CY in these areas. Both TAs 14 and 15 have relatively shallow bedrock depths and do not offer much potential borrow volume. They are not recommended to be further evaluated.

TA 16:

This collected data suggests that of the three TAs 14, 15 and 16, TA 16 has the most probable in-place soil volume that could be excavated. Table 2 displays that TAs 14A, 14B, 15 and 16 have approximately 2.1 million CY when applying a 90% recovery factor. TA 16 alone can yield about 1.5 million CY of the desired volume of borrow material over the next 25 years, however the quality of the soil is questionable, being a heavy clay.

TA 16 is a more preferred borrow site in that there is much less native Kansas prairie land to be affected and soil available. However its heavy clay makeup may discount its usefulness to serve as the necessary compliment to TA 6 in order to meet the BASE's construction borrow material volume requirements.

Referring to the preliminary geotechnical report by Allied Laboratories in Appendix A, soils in TA 16 are classified as a heavy clay, whereas TA 6 soils are a lean clay. A second drilling program in TA 16 is recommended to be delayed until the BASE staff has had the opportunity to read this report. More drilling in TA 16 may better estimate in-place borrow volume, but will not change the conclusion that the material at this site is a heavy clay with limited construction applicability.

TA 24:

TA 24 was estimated to have only approximately 12,436 CY of borrow material left. Such a small volume and the fact that recently unsuitable material has been found at the limits of its current excavation, TA 24 should be closed to operation.

TA24 RECLAMATION PLAN

TA 24 has little usable borrow material. Recent excavations have been encountering shale material. It is recommended to be reclaimed as a training area. Photographs of TA24 were taken to display the steep banks at the limits of the borrow area and are enclosed in the Appendix C. These banks should be graded down to a bank slope of 3:1 horizontal to vertical. The bank slopes and flat areas of the former borrow site should be covered with topsoil and seeded. Figure 5 displays this concept.

TA 24 fortunately produces runoff that the BASE has directed to an existing sedimentation pond. No further runoff control improvements are necessary at this borrow site.

Other future borrow site reclamation plans should consider that the overall area be graded to positively drain into a sedimentation pond for control of erosion offsite. Steep side slopes should be regraded as per Figure 5. Suggested seeding specifications are enclosed in Appendix E.

BORROW SITE OPERATION PLAN

Each borrow site should have day to day operational procedures that will allow the BASE management staff to control excavation contractors and the operation of the site. Excavation should start at a predetermined location by Base staff and proceed in a specified direction and width until marked boundary limits of the borrow site are reached. The current operation of site TA 6B is a good example of this concept. Then a subsequent phase of excavation can start from a Base determined location and proceed in a direction and width until another marked boundary limit is reached.

Base staff has marked TA 6B with signage to control its operation. This method is working satisfactorily and should be continued on the other borrow sites in this study.

Once the length and width limits of the borrow site has been fully excavated, BASE staff can determine that excavation operations should cease. At that time the site should be considered to be discontinued and a reclamation plan prepared.

We recommend a resulting maximum slope height along the perimeter of a borrow site to not exceed 20 feet. With a 3:1 slope angle and intermittent terraces of 5 feet in width if the borrow site is deeper than 20 feet, the resultant limits of the borrow sites will have adequate slope stability. Contractors should be directed to leave a borrow site's terminating slopes in such configurations to eliminate the need for final site grading.

It is recommended that the BASE periodically have aerial photography produced of the borrow sites to show the limits of excavation. Annual mapping would be an adequate frequency.

Borrow sites should have a stormwater management plan in which runoff from the facility drains into a sedimentation basin designed to contain and attenuate the 25-year precipitation event. TA 6A has no recognizable stormwater management system in place however TA 6B currently does collect runoff water at the entrance to the borrow site.

A stand-alone portable generator is recommended only to be operated as needed.

Follow the general site good housekeeping requirements of the Kansas Department of Health and Environment (KDHE) under its Notice of Intent (NOI) permitting regulations. Copy of these requirements is included in Appendix D.

BORROW SITE IDENTIFICATION PLAN

Viewing the suggested borrow sites from perimeter roadways is difficult due to the dense tree cover and the distance involved. It is believed that it would be helpful to the BASE staff to know points along the roadways that describe the limits of the borrow sites. Limits of the planned borrow sites were drawn on the aerial mapping (Map No. 1) as straight lines as much as possible over the expected area of soil borrow volume, throughout the drilling hole pattern and in between the known roadways. The direction of these limit lines were extended along an azimuth compass direction to calculate a GPS location on a roadway. Roadway GPS coordinate points and azimuth direction information is included in Table 3. Traversing these azimuth compass direction lines from the roadway GPS points would trace out the borrow site limits.

These GPS roadway points are also shown on Map No. 1 along with a distance in miles from the nearest road intersection. This location analysis is limited to TA 6 since it is the only borrow site well defined at this point in time. These points can be driven to along roadways from a known intersection and then a GPS unit can be used to more accurately find the reference point in the roadway. Viewing in the azimuth direction from the roadway is the location of the boundary of borrow sites. After some initial site clearing is performed to establish access into the borrow sites, site limit signs can be set by BASE staff from the information in Table 3. Setting borrow site limit signs can be performed as necessary when the BASE staff will begin to authorize excavation from any particular borrow site. Borrow site limits signs can be adjusted by BASE staff as necessary after a borrow site becomes active and visible after the tree cover is removed.

CONCLUSION

The borrow volume estimates provided within this study suggest that TA 6 and TA 16 can produce an approximate amount of 2,359,625 CY of fill material. This volume does not meet the 2.5 million CY goal of this study, although this estimated volume is close to the volume goal. The quality of material found in TA 16 is not as good as TA 6 which may limit its construction uses and be more difficult to manipulate. Another environmentally approved site should be suggested for a similar borrow analysis to supplement this volume shortfall. TA 14 and TA 15 are less tree covered and more natural prairie like and should not be considered as borrow areas. TA 24 should be reclaimed as a training area and discontinued for borrow excavation.

Appendix II. Rock Borrow Report (Corps of Engineers, Kansas City District)

CENWK-ED-GG

07 September 2010

ASSESSMENT OF POTENTIAL TRAINING AREA ROCK BORROW SITES, FT. RILEY, KANSAS

Introduction

Environmental Division of the Ft. Riley Directorate of Public Works asked the Geology Section to assess the suitability of potential rock borrow areas at four sites in the Range Training Areas (TA), TA-6, TA-37, TA-80, and TA-90. The request identified the desire for soil and rock borings to confirm rock ledge thickness and extent at each site. Environmental Division, DPW expressed primary interest in estimations of the quantity of suitable limestone rock at each site. The Environmental Division, DPW requirements as understood by the Geology Section are:

- Complete the investigation and report findings within 30 to 90 days
- Identify the thickness and estimate available quantity of limestone beneath each site
- Assess the suitability of limestone at each site for use as aggregate and riprap
- Rippable limestone units that can be excavated with an excavator are desirable
- Limestone ledges that require drill and blast to excavate are less desirable
- Deep excavation to expose and exploit a limestone ledge is not desirable
- Report the general thickness of overburden soils

Environmental Division, DPW provided site maps with designated areas to investigate and the associated acreage for each site from which borrow quantities were calculated.

Methodology

Each site was visited at the on-set of the investigation to assess equipment access and identify the locations of nearby rock outcrops. Aerial photography was used to identify additional potential rock outcrops and their spatial relationship to each site. Two to three borings were completed at each site. Geology Section files were reviewed to assess applicable existing information on file for each site. Field work consisted of geologic reconnaissance and borehole drilling. Ten borings, A-10-21 through AC-10-30, were completed into limestone bedrock by Kansas City District drill crews. Boring depths ranged from 13 ft in AC-10-29 to 51.9' in AC-10-23. Soil overburden was field classified from auger cuttings. Bedrock was drilled and sampled by 4-inch diameter, double-tube, diamond-bit core barrel. The rock core was logged, photographed, placed in wooden core boxes and returned to the Kansas City District office. Detailed examination of outcrops with measured sections was completed at TA-6, TA-80, and TA-90. No outcrops large enough to measure were identified adjacent to TA-37. The closest measureable outcrop to the TA-37 site was a road cut 3,955 feet south of boring AC-10-21 and was considered too far away to compare specific lithologic features but close enough to provide stratigraphic correlation.

Discussion

Boring logs, measured sections of outcrops, limestone unit thicknesses, soil overburden thicknesses, rock quality designation, index strength tests, estimated elevation range of bedrock units were considered in the assessment of each site. The completed drill logs and measured sections were reviewed, entered into the boring log database, and submitted to a series of quality control checks. The rock quality designation (RQD) was determined for bedrock encountered in each boring. The RQD is a measure of the frequency of lithologic discontinuities like bedding planes, joints, and fractures. The RQD was used to assess the relative ease with which the limestone bedrock might be excavated. High RQD values indicate intact or thickly bedded rock whereas low RQD values indicate thinly bedded or extensively broken rock. The thickness of each limestone unit and overlying soil were determined from each boring and correlated to the applicable measured section. Schmidt-type rebound hammer index strength measurements were conducted on selected samples of rock core from each boring except AC-10-21. AC-10-21 did not produce a sufficiently large specimen to conduct the test. Index strength tests are not laboratory tests and are inherently less reliable than lab tests but are useful for quickly establishing the relative strength range of rock. No seismic velocity measurements were made as part of this investigation. Consequently, rippability estimations are therefore qualitative and based on RQD, index strength tests, and professional judgment.

Results

Assessment Criteria:

ETL 1110-2-182 Rock Mass Classification Data Requirements for Rippability
 Tech Report GL-85-3 Geotechnical Descriptions of Rock and Rock Masses
 GL-89-1 Rock Quality Designation after Twenty Years

Several assumptions were made in estimating the quantities for each site: a) One foot of limestone was assumed to be left after excavation to serve as a floor for the quarrying operation; b) Ten percent of the total area of the site was assumed to be unavailable for rock excavation due to overburden soil slope and access road construction; and c) A typical thickness of limestone at each site was intuitively selected to represent the thickness at that site and was used in estimation of quantities.

IA- 6 7.14 acres

Thickness of soil overburden = 1.5ft to 3.5ft of soil remains at active borrow site

Thickness of limestone bedrock = 19.3ft to 28 ft (used 23ft)

Maximum estimated depth of excavation = 31.0ft

Estimated quantity of limestone = 264,851 cubic yards (assumes 7.14 acres)

Quantity of limestone per acre = 37,094 cubic yards

Estimated quantity of soil overburden = 46,061 cubic yards

Controlling limestone discontinuity spacing = Thin to thick bedded = 0.2ft to 2ft

RQD Average = 61% Fair rock quality

Index strength (correlated to unconfined compressive strength) = 6,250 psi to 2,700psi correlates to hard/very hard rock based on ETL 1110-2-282 Figure 2.

Assessment of suitability of limestone at TA-6 for mechanical excavation: Based on bedding thickness up to 2 ft, fracture spacing up to 10 ft, RQD, and index strength tests, the Florence Limestone is qualitatively considered not rippable. Drill and blast is likely to be the only cost effective means of rock excavation as mechanical production is anticipated to be extremely slow.

Assessment of suitability of limestone for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, and rock fill: Large rectangular blocks of Florence Limestone can be produced in limited quantity mechanically and to a lesser extent through blasting. The Florence LS generally has poor freeze-thaw durability and is not suitable for riprap. Blasting may produce a wide range of particle sizes. Standard quarry methods can be employed to produce a variety of smaller rock products such as road aggregate and ditch check. The Florence LS contains a significant percentage of chert making it unsuitable for concrete aggregate. The chert may produce very sharp and abrasive aggregate.

TA-37 two sites, 35 acres and 8 acres = 43 acres

Thickness of soil overburden = 14.4ft to 28.6ft

Thickness of limestone bedrock = 11.6ft to 17.2ft, average = 14.9ft (used 14ft)

Maximum estimate depth of excavation = 44.5ft

Estimated quantity of limestone = 874,104 cubic yards

Quantity of limestone per acre = 20,328 cubic yards

Estimated quantity of soil overburden = 1,373,592 cubic yards

Controlling limestone discontinuity spacing = Thin to thick bedded = 0.2ft to 2ft, predominantly thin bedded

RQD Average = 34% Poor rock quality

Index strength (correlated to unconfined compressive strength) = 2,800psi to 3,900psi correlates to hard/very hard rock based on ETL 1110-2-282 Figure 2.

Assessment of suitability of limestone at TA-37 for mechanical excavation: The Ft. Riley Limestone underlies TA-37. Based on bedding thickness predominantly 0.5 ft, RQD, and index strength tests the upper Ft. Riley Limestone is qualitatively considered to be rippable. The extent of weathering, the spacing of vertical joints and fractures, and local bedding thickness will control the relative ease the upper Ft. Riley can be excavated by mechanical means. Large areas may be excavated mechanically after ripping by a dozer equipped with a single shank ripper tooth. Some areas may resist ripping by dozer and locally require employment of a hydraulic-hammer attached to an excavator arm to loosen. Locally, where bedding is thin, and joints and fractures are closely spaced, mechanical excavation with a large excavator may be possible on a limited basis.

Assessment of suitability of limestone for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, and rock fill: The upper Ft. Riley Limestone varies from thin to thick bedded. Thin and medium

bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of road aggregate and small ditch check rock. The thick bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of large ditch check rock, riprap, and rock fill. Some zones may contain shale partings and beds that may only be useful as rock fill. The overburden at this site may exceed 22.5' over much of the southern site. Fifteen feet of soil and about 13 feet of shale may overlie limestone beneath the northern site. The excavation of thick overburden at TA-37 solely to access the underlying limestone may be cost prohibitive. However, if the TA-37 sites were used as soil and random backfill borrow sites for construction projects at Ft. Riley, eventually the limestone could be accessed economically.

TA-80 18 acres

Thickness of soil overburden = 3.5ft to 20ft

Thickness of limestone bedrock = 13 to 14.4ft (used 13ft)

Maximum estimated depth of excavation = 33ft

Estimated quantity of limestone = 339,768 cubic yards

Quantity of limestone per acre = 18,876 cubic yards

Estimated quantity of soil overburden = 287,496 cubic yards

Controlling limestone discontinuity spacing = vertical fractures 0.75ft apart

thin to thick bedded = 0.2ft to 2ft, predominantly thin bedded

RQD Average = 75% Fair rock quality

Index strength (correlated to unconfined compressive strength) = 2,500psi to 4,700psi
correlates to hard/very hard rock based on ETL 1110-2-282 Figure 2.

Assessment of suitability of limestone at TA-80 for mechanical excavation: The Towanda Limestone is currently being mechanically excavated along the western boundary of the TA-80 investigation site. Based on vertical fracture spacing of 0.75ft, bedding thickness predominantly 0.5 ft, RQD, and index strength tests; the Towanda Limestone beneath the investigation site is qualitatively considered to be rippable. The extent of weathering, the spacing of vertical joints and fractures, and local bedding thickness will control the relative ease the Towanda Limestone can be excavated by mechanical means. Large areas may be excavated mechanically after ripping by a dozer equipped with a single shank ripper tooth. Locally, where bedding is thin, and joints and fractures are closely spaced, mechanical excavation with a large excavator may be possible.

Assessment of suitability of limestone for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, and rock fill: The Towanda Limestone varies from thin to thick bedded with vertical fractures spaced 0.75ft to 1.0ft apart. Thin and medium bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of road aggregate and small ditch check rock. The thick bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of large ditch check rock, riprap, and rock fill, however the closely spaced vertical fractures may limit the maximum rock size that can be consistently produced.

TA-90 23 acres

Thickness of soil overburden = 2.8ft to 12.0ft
Thickness of limestone bedrock = 6.0ft to 8.3ft (used 7ft)
Maximum estimated depth of excavation = 20ft
Estimated quantity of limestone = 200,367 cubic yards
Quantity of limestone per acre = 8,712 cubic yards
Estimated quantity of soil overburden = 83,490 cubic yards
Controlling limestone discontinuity spacing = vertical fractures 0.75ft apart
thin to medium bedded = 0.2ft to 1.0ft
RQD Average = 63% Fair rock quality
Index strength (correlated to unconfined compressive strength) = 3,700psi to 5,200psi
correlates to hard/very hard rock based on ETL 1110-2-282 Figure 2.

Assessment of suitability of limestone at TA-90 for mechanical excavation: The Towanda Limestone is currently being mechanically excavated along the eastern boundary of the TA-90 investigation site. Based on vertical fracture spacing of 0.75ft, bedding thickness predominantly 0.2 ft to 1.0ft, RQD, and index strength tests; the Towanda Limestone beneath the investigation site is qualitatively considered to be rippable. The extent of weathering, the spacing of vertical joints and fractures, and local bedding thickness will control the relative ease the Towanda Limestone can be excavated by mechanical means. Large areas may be excavated mechanically after ripping by a dozer equipped with a single shank ripper tooth. Locally, where bedding is thin, and joints and fractures are closely spaced, mechanical excavation with a large excavator may be possible.

Assessment of suitability of limestone for production of road gravel, ditch check stone, and rock fill: The Towanda Limestone varies from thin to thick bedded with vertical fractures spaced 0.75ft to 1.0ft apart. Thin and medium bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of road aggregate and small ditch check rock. The thick bedded zones may be conducive to the mechanical production of large ditch check rock, riprap, and rock fill, however the closely spaced vertical fractures may limit the maximum rock size that can be consistently produced.

Conclusions

Proposed borrow areas TA-80 and TA-90 are the best candidate sites for development of rock borrow material. The soil overburden thickness at these sites is not excessive and Towanda Limestone is present in sufficient quantity to be economically feasible to exploit. Numerous sites at Ft. Riley have demonstrated the Towanda Limestone can be excavated mechanically with large excavators and the rock material produced from those sites is adequate for use in range road maintenance.

Proposed borrow area TA-37 is underlain by the Ft. Riley Limestone rather than the Towanda Limestone. Although the properties of the upper Ft. Riley Limestone appear to be similar to those of the Towanda LS, the Ft. Riley Limestone does not have the history of excavation by track-hoe that the Towanda LS has and the Ft. Riley LS at TA-37 is overlain by a relatively thick mantle of soil overburden that reduces the desirability of TA-37 for rock borrow

development. If the proposed TA-37 sites were first used as soil and random borrow material, the underlying limestone could subsequently be economically exploited.

Proposed borrow area TA-6 is an active soil borrow site within the construction/demolition landfill. Most of the overburden soil has already been removed from the area designated on the site plan provided by Environmental Division, DPW for drilling. The northern portion of the area designated TA-6A has not been stripped or borrowed and was not investigated for this report. Although a large quantity of limestone (Florence Limestone) is present beneath the TA-6 site, the fact that the rock will likely require drill and blast excavation methods reduces the site desirability solely for rock production. The high chert content in the Florence Limestone reduces the suitability of the rock for aggregate and riprap applications. However, the extra effort and expense required to exploit the limestone at TA-6 may be acceptable if additional landfill space is needed.

Based on a geologic section of the proposed TA-6 site, it appears as though the Florence Limestone dips gently to the southwest. Consequently, it is anticipated to occur at progressively higher elevations in a northeasterly direction. The topography of the northern extension of the TA-6A site decreases to the north. As a result, the Florence Limestone present beneath that portion of TA-6 is anticipated to be thinner due erosion.

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Appendix III. Site details and maps for the active borrow areas.

Appendix III, Map 1. General locations of Borrow Areas on Fort Riley.

Appendix III, Map 2. Henry Drive Borrow Area (TA-1)

The Henry Drive Borrow Area (TA-1) was used to obtain topsoil material during construction projects at Marshall Air Field. How much useable material remains is not known. Much of the site is overgrown with grass and trees, including an agro-forestry planting established in the mid-1990's.

The soils in this area are represented by the Muir Series. Muir soils consist of very deep, nearly level, well drained material that formed in silty alluvium and colluvium. These soils occur on terraces of major rivers and creeks. The Muir soils are silt loam to silty clay loam, have a very high water retention capacity, and are moderately permeable. Flooding is a hazard. The site is relatively flat.

This location is outside of the perimeter access gate for Fort Riley. There is a gate in the perimeter fence that may be used; however, access through that gate must be coordinated with the Provost Marshall Office.

No borrow action will occur within the potential expansion area until the NEPA and SWP3 coordination as described in Section 4 of this plan are completed.

Appendix III, Map 3. Campbell Hill Borrow Area (TA-6)

The Campbell Hill Borrow Area (TA-6) is used to mine clay material. Borrow material should be removed from the active portion of the site until reaching the depth limits at the site.

The soils in this area are represented by the Smolan-Geary soil association that consists of deep, gently sloping and sloping soils on high terraces and uplands. These soils formed in loess. The soils are silt loam to silty clay loam and are moderately well drained to well-drained. Soil management of this soil association is concerned mainly with controlling water erosion. The drainage at the site is generally to the north and east to Dry Branch Creek.

Permanent storm-water structures include diversions to channel any stormwater coming off the site to a sedimentation pond. The sedimentation pond acts as a basin to collect sediment laden runoff. Silt fencing will be used around soil storage pile that are placed outside the confines of the borrow area.

Appendix III, Map 4. Custer Hill Borrow Area (TA-24)

The Custer Hill Borrow Area (TA-24) was used to mine clay fill borrow. A survey conducted in 2011 by Professional Engineering Consultants (PEC) found that TA 24 has little usable borrow material remaining. Recent excavations have been encountering shale material. The site is closed for borrow and has been reshaped to remove hazardous slopes.

Soil management of this soil series is concerned mainly with controlling water erosion. The drainage at the site is generally to the south and southwest to Fourmile Creek. This site has sedimentation ponds to capture stormwater runoff leaving the site. The sedimentation ponds act as basins to collect sediment from the runoff and allow the water to percolate into the ground.

Appendix III, Map 5. Training Area 49 Borrow Area

The Training Area 49 Borrow Area is used to mine top soil. Borrow material will be removed from the active portion of the site until there is no longer any useable material remaining. No borrow action will occur within the potential expansion area until the NEPA and SWP3 coordination as described in Section 4 of this plan are completed.

The soils in this area are represented by the Crete soil series. The Crete series consists of deep, nearly level to undulating soils that developed in loess. Crete soils are silty clay loam, have slow runoff and are slowly permeable in the subsoil; wetness can be a problem during excess moisture. However, in hot, dry summers the soils tend to be droughty. Soil management of this soil series is concerned mainly with controlling water erosion. The drainage at the site is generally to the west to Rush Creek.

This location is relatively level, and has remnant terraces from prior crop production that provide an existing mechanism to slow runoff. The terraces divert runoff to either the natural drainage that is densely vegetated, or a road side ditch, which also is vegetated. Preservation of the outermost terraces precludes installation of new diversion structures. In the event terraces are leveled, permanent stormwater structures, including diversions and sedimentation ponds, will be installed. Silt fencing will be used around soil storage piles that are placed outside the confines of the borrow area.

Appendix III, Map 6. Training Areas 79 and 80 Borrow Areas

The areas in TAs 79 and 80 are used for rock borrow. The soils in this area are primarily in the Clime-Sogn and the Dwight-Irwin Complexes. Both soil types are susceptible to erosion when the surface is unprotected. Most of the soil in this area has been removed to expose the limestone layers beneath and is stockpiled in TA 80.

Drainage in the area is generally towards the south and west, to an unnamed tributary of Timber Creek. Stormwater protection is provided by graded berms surrounding the site. The TA 79 site has a sharply cut face ranging from 4-9 ft that may pose a safety hazard to vehicles and foot traffic, especially at night and because of the proximity to the road.

Appendix III, Map 7. Training Area 82 Borrow Area

The area in TA 82 is primarily being used for rock borrow for construction projects at the Douthit Gunnery Complex. The soils in this area are primarily in the Clime-Sogn and the Dwight-Irwin Complexes. Both soil types are susceptible to erosion when the surface is un-protected. Most of the soil in this area has been removed to expose the limestone layers beneath and does not appear stockpiled on-site.

Drainage in the area is primarily towards the west of the site. Stormwater protection is provided by graded diversions surrounding the site and check dams as necessary within the active borrow area.

Appendix III, Map 8. Training Area 90 Borrow Area

The site in TA 90 is an old rock quarry site that was re-activated in 2010 when ITAM began borrowing rock from the site. Most of the soil had been removed by previous quarrying efforts, with some or most of it stockpiled on-site. The soils in this area are primarily in the Clime-Sogn and Complex which are susceptible to erosion when the surface is un-protected.

Drainage at the site primarily is to the southeast corner towards Wind Creek, a stream with the **endangered Topeka shiner**. Stormwater protection is provided by graded diversions surrounding the site and a small sedimentation pond in the southeast corner of the site.

Appendix III, Map 9. Training Area 91 Borrow Area

The site in TA 91 is currently being used for rock borrow by the DPW for road work and construction projects. The soils in this area are primarily in the Clime-Sogn Complex and Wymore Silty Clay Loam. Both soil types are susceptible to erosion when the surface is un-protected. Most of the soil in this area has been removed to expose the limestone layers, but remains stockpiled at the site.

Drainage at the site primarily is to the northwest side towards Wind Creek, a stream with the **endangered Topeka shiner**. Stormwater protection is provided by graded diversions surrounding the site.

Appendix III, Map 10. Training Area 103 Borrow Area

The site in TA 103 has been used for rock borrow by the DPW and ITAM for tank trail repairs, range construction projects, and LRAM projects. The soils in this area are primarily in the Clime-Sogn Complex and Irwin Silty Clay Loam. Both soil types are susceptible to erosion. Most of the soil in this area has been removed to expose the limestone layers beneath. Little usable borrow material remains.

Drainage at the site is primarily towards the west towards Threemile Creek. Stormwater protection is provided by graded diversions surrounding the site.

APPENDIX O.

TRAINING AREA SPECIFIC MANAGEMENT PLANS

